

A MANAGERIAL ROADMAP DEVELOPMENT FOR INDUSTRY 4.0-BASED
SMART MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISE: CROSS-SECTOR STUDY IN
TURKEY

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ABSTRACT

A managerial roadmap development for industry 4.0-based smart manufacturing enterprise: a cross-sector study in Turkey.

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Digitalization and smartness surround us, ICT becomes an integral part of enterprises and human lifestyle and penetrates all aspects of life. Thus, the fourth industrial revolution dramatically reshapes technologies, business models, systems, structures, strategies, procedures, culture, industries, and competition conditions. In this context, enterprises face with a new set of requirements and are in need of conceptual frameworks, business models, assessment tools for measuring their maturity and readiness in multiple aspects, and roadmaps to guide them towards the smart factory.

To fill these literature gaps, this study first provides a comprehensive clustering of enabling technologies, design principles, features, key capabilities and requirements to cover knowledge availability, technological, managerial, organizational and human-related dimensions, based on a comprehensive literature review. Then, a business model and a multi-perspective conceptual framework for smart manufacturing organizations are developed. Afterwards, a multi-dimensional and weighted smart factory requirements maturity index is proposed and a practical assessment survey tool is developed, which are in compatibility with the requirements, business model and framework.

The field study is conducted via case study approach, and the assessment survey tool and the maturity index system developed is applied to investigate the current SF readiness and maturity in 8 case study companies operating in the Turkish automotive industry. The field study has shown the applicability and practicality of the survey tool and the scoring system developed to investigate the readiness and maturity levels of the enterprises.

Findings show that 50% of surveyed companies suffer from immaturity and inability to meet the proposed SF's requirements, partially or completely, and positioned at the experienced-learner and intermediate levels. Remaining 50% of the surveyed companies demonstrated a significant maturity towards smart factories in particular individual dimensions, although they do not have full implementations and still expect to face with many hurdles in their smartness journey. When different dimensions are considered, it has been found that: a) knowledge availability regarding smart factories and industry 4.0 acceptably exists in the automotive sector, b) technological dimension showed lower readiness, and c) managerial, organizational and human-related dimensions appear sufficient for implementing and operating smart factories.

Based on the maturity analysis for the case companies, specific and individual suggestions are made to surveyed companies towards developing an integrated set of smart capabilities and meeting SF requirements. A generic roadmap to guide the enterprises in their smartness efforts is also provided.

Combined use of integrated and compatible set of requirements, business model, conceptual framework, maturity assessment and measurement tool, and the roadmap developed in this study facilitates a multidimensional and comprehensive view of the enterprises towards smooth transition to smart manufacturing organizations. Thus, the study offered an in-depth academic overview as a theoretical contribution and a practical systematic for enterprises seeking to adopt the smart factory.

Keywords: Industry 4.0, Smart factory (SF), SF-technologies SF-capabilities, SF-Requirements, SF-business model, Framework, Maturity model, SF-roadmap.

ÖZ

Endüstri 4.0 tabanlı akıllı üretim işletmesi için bir yönetimsel yol haritasının geliştirilmesi: Türkiye'de sektörler arası çalışma

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Dijitalleşme ve akıllık kavramı etrafımızı sarmakta, bilgi ve iletişim teknolojileri işletmelerin ve insan yaşam tarzının ayrılmaz bir parçası haline gelmekte ve hayatın her alanına nüfuz etmektedir. Böylece, dördüncü sanayi devrimi teknolojileri, iş modelleri, sistemleri, yapıları, stratejileri, prosedürleri, kültürü, endüstriler ve rekabet koşullarını önemli ölçüde yeniden şekillendirmektedir. Bu bağlamda, işletmeler yeni gereksinimlerle yüzyüzedir ve kavramsal çerçevelere, iş modellerine, olgunluklarını ve hazırlıklarını birden fazla açıdan ölçmek için değerlendirme araçlarına, ve kendilerini akıllı fabrikaya geçiş için yol haritalarına ihtiyaç duymaktadır.

Literatürdeki bu boşlukları doldurmak üzere, bu çalışma öncelikle kapsamlı bir literatür incelemesine dayanarak etkinleştirici teknolojiler, tasarım prensipleri, özellikler, temel yetkinlik ve gereksinimlerin bilgi mevcudiyeti, teknolojik, yönetsel, organizasyonel ve insanla ilgili boyutları kapsayacak şekilde kapsamlı bir kümelenmesini sunar. Daha sonra, akıllı üretim organizasyonları için bir iş modeli ve çok yönlü bir kavramsal çerçeve geliştirilmiştir. Ardından, gereksinimlere, iş modeline ve çerçeveye uyumlu bir şekilde çok boyutlu ve ağırlıklandırılmış bir akıllı fabrika gereksinimleri olgunluk indeksi önerilmiş ve pratik bir değerlendirme aracı geliştirilmiştir.

Saha çalışması, vaka çalışması yaklaşımı ile gerçekleştirilmiş ve geliştirilen değerlendirme aracı ile olgunluk endeksi sistemi, mevcut akıllı fabrika hazırlık ve olgunluklarını araştırmak üzere Türk otomotiv endüstrisinde faaliyet gösteren sekiz şirkete uygulanmıştır. Vaka çalışması, işletmelerin hazırlık ve olgunluk seviyelerini araştırmak için geliştirilen değerlendirme aracının ve puanlama sisteminin uygulanabilirliğini ve pratikliğini göstermiştir.

Bulgular, arařtırmaya katılan řirketlerin % 50'sinin olgunlařmamıřlıktan ve önerilen akıllı fabrika gereksinimlerini kısmen veya tamamen karřılayamamaktan muzdarip olduđunu göstermektedir; ve deneyimli-öđrenen ve orta seviyelerde konumlandırılmıřtır. Arařtırmaya katılan řirketlerin geri kalan %50'si, tam uygulamaları olmamasına ve akıllılık yolculuklarında hala birçok engelle karřılařmayı beklmelerine rađmen, belli boyutlarda akıllı fabrika yolunda önemli bir olgunluk göstermiřlerdir. Farklı boyutlar göz önüne alındıđında, řunlar bulunmuřtur: a) Otomotiv sektöründe akıllı fabrikalar ve endüstri 4.0 ile ilgili kabul edilebilir bir bilgi mevcudiyedi vardır, b) teknolojik boyut daha düřük bir hazır olma göstermiřtir, ve c) yönetimsel, organizasyonel ve insanla ilgili boyutlar akıllı fabrikaların uygulanması ve iřletmeleri için yeterli görünmektedir.

Vaka řirketlerinde yapılan olgunluk analizine dayanarak, arařtırmaya katılan řirketlere entegre akıllı yetenekler kümesi geliřtirme ve akıllık fabrika gereksinimlerini karřılama konusunda özel ve bireysel önerilerde bulunulmuřtur. İřletmelere akıllı sistem çalıřmalarında rehberlik edecek genel bir yol haritası da sađlanmıřtır.

Entegre ve uyumlu olan gereksinimler kümesi, iř modeli, kavramsal çerçeve ve olgunluk deđerlendirme ve ölçüm aracının birlikte kullanılması, ve bu çalıřmada geliřtirilen yol haritası, iřletmelerin akıllı üretim kuruluřlarına sorunsuz geçiř yolunda çok boyutlu ve kapsamlı bir bakıř sađlamaktadır. Bu nedenle, çalıřma teorik katkı olarak derinlemesine bir akademik genel bakıř ve akıllı fabrikayı benimsemek isteyen iřletmeler için pratik bir sistematik sunmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Endüstri 4.0, Akıllı fabrika (SF), SF-teknolojileri, SF-yetenekleri, SF-Gereksinimleri, SF-iř modeli, Çerçeve, Olgunluk modeli, SF-yol haritası.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Endüstri 4.0, Akıllı fabrika (SF), SF-teknolojileri, SF-yetenekleri, SF-Gereksinimleri, SF-iř modeli, Çerçeve, Olgunluk modeli, SF-yol haritası.

DEDICATION

“After thanking God for everything He has given me in this Life.”

I dedicate my study

“To whom lit my life with hope and taught me, and the eyes that removed all my worries.”

To my wonderful parents.

“To whom are tougher my synergy, and the hands that extend to me in every ordeal to help and support me in difficulties,

To my parents-in-law.

“To whom are my haven, my comfort and the ambition of my life who was with me in each and every step, for her patience and support,

To my beloved wife

To those who have endured the journey of my studies for long days, and they preferred me to themselves, (They are in the eye a delight, in the heart happiness, in mind a comfort, and in the life a smile)”

To My children

To whom reach me to safety and extended the hand of help and tenderness, and lit the path of my life and endured the trouble of my journey.”

My dear brothers, sisters and friends

“To all those who are happy with my success, I dedicate my humble efforts with all love, respect and appreciation.”

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviations	Term
AAS	Administration Shell
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial intelligence
AM	Additive Manufacturing
AR	Augmented Reality
BD	Big data analytics
BI	Business Intelligence
CAD	Computer Aided Design
CAGR:	Compound Annual Growth Rate
CAM	Computer Aided Manufacturing
CC	cloud computing,
CIM	Computer Integrated Manufacturing
CMM	coordinate measuring machine (CMM)
CNC	Computer Numerical Control
CPPSs	cyber-physical production systems
CPS	Cyber-physical system
CRM	Customer Relationship Management
CSaaS	the control system as a service
EIU	Economist Intelligence Unit
EMSs	Energy Management Systems
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
GVCs	Global Value Chains
HMI	Human machine Interface
I4.0	Industry 4.0
ICT	Information Communication Technologies
IEC ----	International Electro-technical commission
IIOT	Industrial internet of thing
IIRA	Industrial Internet Reference Architecture
IMSA	Intelligent Manufacturing System Architecture
IOD	Internet of Data
IOP	Internet of People
IOT	Internet Of Thing
IT	Information Technology
IVRA	Industrial Value Chain Reference Architecture
LANs	Local Area Network
LGV	Laser Guided Vehicles
M2H	Machine to Human
M2M	Machine to Machine
MaaS	Manufacturing-as-a-Service
MES	Manufacturing execution systems
MES	Manufacturing execution system.
MOS	Manufacturing Operating System
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
PAAS	Process as a service
PHM	Prognostics and health management
PLC	Programmable Logic Controllers

PLM	Product Lifecycle Management
QR codes	Quick Response Codes
R&D	Research and Development
RAMI 4.0	Reference Architecture Model Industry 4.0
RCS	Resilience control system
RFID	Radio Frequency IDentification
SCM	Supply chain management
SGAM	Smart Grid Architecture Model
SKU	Stock Keeping Unit
SMO	Smart manufacturing organization
UX	User experience
VR	Virtual Reality
WSN	wireless sensor networks
XML	Extensible Markup Language

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

This dissertation concentrates on the problem domain of knowledge and experience about implementing industry 4.0-based smart factory and related technologies for embracing digitalization. This chapter introduces the general background, the study's significance, the study's objectives, the study's problem and questions, the study's model and methodology, limitations and delimitations of the study, and terminologies.

1.1. General background

Today, digitalization surrounds us, penetrates all aspects of life, and becomes an integral part of human lifestyle and enterprises. In smart environments, the various digitalization forms compel manufacturing enterprises to embrace advanced technology and rely on high Information communication Technology (ICT) to remain in the competition and growth mode. However, are the traditional models, structures, strategies, and practices still valid?

The manufacturing industry occupies a significant position in Turkey's national economy and is one of Turkey's pillar industries. The next three sections give a brief background in the area of research.

1.1.1. Industry 4.0

The first three industrial revolutions represented by mechanization, electricity, and information technology (IT) merged and overlapped with human effort in manufacturing (Sachdeva, et al., 2017). Technological advances have significantly impacted manufacturing, especially with the recent employment of digitalization, which allowed for the automation of production processes (Ennis, et al., 2018). The merge of technologies and ICTs is an establishing pillar of new ways of doing businesses (Saucedo-Martínez, et al., 2018; Moica, et al., 2018). Thus, the Industry 4.0 was founded by German during the Hannover Fair event in 2011, which refer to start the 4th industrial revolution (Lee, et al., 2015; Qin , et al., 2016), to face substantial economic and social challenges (Ganzarain, et al., 2016). Many manufacturing enterprises look upon industry 4.0 as a way by which to sustain competitive advantage. During the last years, the interest and industrial use of industry 4.0 technology and related systems and tools have grown considerably.

Davies et al. (2017) point out that Industry 4.0 appears as a set of devices, production centers, machines, and products that consist of embedded systems and programs in order to allow autonomously communicate with each other, exchange information, and invoke actions and control each other independently (Davies , et al., 2017).

Kamble et al. (2018) point out industry 4.0 as an essential contributor in the digital manufacturing and automation environment, including various technologies to enable value chain development, reduce lead-time-out, and enhance quality performance (Kamble , et al., 2018). Thus industry 4.0 is a mix of advanced and homogeneous technologies allowing manufacturing enterprises to be smart and conscious. Therefore, I4.0 is a smart, interactive, and conscious ecosystem configured through equipping all entities (machines, systems, products) with embedded technologies, actuators, AI algorithms, and sensors which allow a set of capabilities such as integrating, interconnecting, interacting among all entities, including stakeholder, under the networked environment of Cyber-Physical system and Internet of Things (IoT). Based on all of the above, establishing the digital value network under a creative business model are available and realizable.

1.1.2. Business model (BM)

Today, a smart environment compels its inhabitants to continuously respond and adapt with its dynamism, complexity, and digitalization, especially industrial enterprises, rather than vanishing.

Nowadays, the increased digitalization and innovative technologies facilitate the embracing of Industry 4.0, which influences the organizations' life (Trotta, et al., 2018). Consequently, manufacturing enterprises initiate to practice and embrace a set of high-advanced technologies such as 3D printing, smart logistics, networked production, Big Data Analytics, Cloud Services, etc., and they begin to develop new organizational structures and establish business models to utilize the opportunities that these novel technologies offer (Prause, 2015). The traditional barriers of manufacturing enterprises are broken down by business digitalization, thus rethinking and reengineering existing business models are inevitable.

The context and content of the business model became critical for sustaining harmony with the smart environment. Therefore, the business model is a linking framework among strategies, technologies, processes, and ICT (Veit, et al., 2014).

Accordingly, Baden-Fuller & Haefliger, 2013 point out the BM as a solving system of problems such as recognizing who is (or are) the customer(s), interacting with their needs, realizing satisfaction, and monetizing and profiting the value (Baden-Fuller, et al., 2013). A business model is a logical and rational description of how enterprises create, deliver, and capture value. In simple words, the business model is a way of creating and delivering desired value.

1.1.3. Smart Manufacturing Enterprises

The inevitability of ICT interaction and advanced technologies promote intensive discussion and pervasive using smart factory approaches in recent years.

The smart machines and products act in integration with everything in the factory, including the human, upon continuous internet connectivity to secure the high degree of sharing of real-time data with each other. Smart factory brings fundamental changes in inventing, manufacturing, and shipping products, ultimately enhancing worker safety and protecting the environment (Hozdić, 2015). The adaptability and flexibility in the production process facilitate handling the short life-cycle challenges and high-customization needs (Syberfeldt, et al., 2016), due to the convergence of virtual and physical worlds in a future factory (Hozdić, 2015). Based on the utilization of destructive and heterogeneous technologies, the new generation of factory tends to be more cognitive, automated, autonomous, and flexible; these technologies; IoT, CPS, big data analytics, and cloud computing, to name a few, adds new capabilities to cope with the latest emerged challenges in the business environment (Yang, et al., 2019; Mabkhot, et al., 2018). Thus, the smart factory is a networked production system characterized by self-optimization, flexibility, self-adaptation, consciousness, information exchangeability in real-time or semi-real time, and autonomously manage entire production processes (Burke, et al., 2017). Besides that, Hozdić, 2015; Kang et al., 2016 stressed that smart factory is an industrial solution in charge of adaptability of the production process to sustain harmony with the dynamic, smart, and complex environment and to solve related problems (Hozdić, 2015; Kang, et al., 2016).

1.2. Significance of the Study

Generally, industrial sectors significantly impact the global and local economies, which contribute by 80%, 90% of an export ratio for EU and Turkey. The environmental megatrends such as changing demographics, globalization, scarcity of resources, climate change, massive development in technological sectors, dynamic innovations,

shortened life-cycles, and mass customization shape the future of manufacturing. Therefore, an expected and inevitable increase in the role of industry 4.0 stems from the sophisticated business environment reflections and impacts. Added to that, the demanded, smart and diverse customers who pursue to fulfill their needs smartly and economically. Furthermore, all manufacturing systems, entities, and objects became increasingly complex, dynamic, intelligent, interoperable, and interdependent.

All the above is for establishing an integrated and comprehensive vision to facilitate digital transformation. However, the desired digitalization transformation faces many challenges, even though its digital transformation's feasibility has existed. The term "industry 4.0" and related technologies are not widely known. The term "smart manufacturing enterprises" is a broad concept, and it has many interpretations. Thus, the term appears ambiguous, and the transformation steps are not well identified. The Cost-effectiveness of the short-term implementation is not clear, and well-defined industry 4.0 performance criteria are still missing (under developing), leading to the avoidance and/or ignorance of this technology. All of the above is amplified by environmental challenges which industrial enterprises can face.

To cope with and face these challenges, the industrial organization should be perfect in flexibility, faster, adaptability, responsiveness, profitability, and proactive behavior to survive, grow and realize a sustainable competitive advantage. Therefore, the manufacturing organization should ride the change wave to avoid retrogression and vanishing ultimately.

Traditional manufacturing enterprises lose their opportunities for future-oriented success unless embracing the industry 4.0 concept and adopting a smart manufacturing philosophy.

Accordingly, Industry 4.0 is a creative and smart solution to face external challenges, and industry 4.0 based smart manufacturing systems have a vital contribution to the sustainability of success and growth. Hence, the enterprises which refuse to address these new developments cannot remain competitive in the long-term in the face of competitive pressures.

1.3. Objectives of the Study

Smart manufacturing enterprises are differentiated from the traditional manufacturing enterprises in their high-ability to utilize future opportunities because of innovative and

destructive technologies and strategies that are involved. The study will attempt to provide a business framework and suggest a proper business model for applying industry 4.0 based smart factory and related technologies by proposing a roadmap to adopt the fourth revolution's factory.

Therefore, the study's aims are as follows:

- Putting forward the key capabilities and their enabling technologies to industry 4.0 based smart manufacturing systems.
- Establishing a comprehensive review and determining Industry 4.0 based smart manufacturing enterprise requirements.
- Realizing the integration and interdependence between the industry 4.0 framework and the proposed business model.
- Determining the existing progressive level of smart factory's implementation concerning technologies, knowledge, and managerial and organizational sides in Turkish industry in the selected manufacturing sector.
- Providing a comparative analysis for selected cases concerning knowledge, technological, managerial, organizational, and human-related dimensions.
- Providing improvement suggestions for surveyed Turkish cases.
- Proposing an applicable roadmap to transform traditional enterprises into smart enterprises.

1.4. Study's Problem and Research Questions

The deficiency of knowledge and experience around implementing industry 4.0, smart factory and related technologies leads manufacturing enterprises to avoid or ignore innovative technologies. This deficiency is the primary source of a set of problems, and the impact and significance of this study will be to provide a proper solution for:

- No predefined or well-known structure for applying industry 4.0 based smart manufacturing enterprises.
- The absence of a dynamic and creative business model consistent with the dynamism and complexity of this technology.
- Lack of organization's awareness about benefits, requirements, characteristics, or reflections of industry 4.0 in Turkish manufacturing enterprises.

- The absence of reliable and clear roadmaps and proper steps to adopting and embracing industry 4.0 makes traditional manufacturing enterprises suffer.
- The absence of explicit and shared experiences of industry 4.0 implementations and required know-how lead to avoid similar investments.

Consistent with and motivated by study's aims, the resultant work aims to integrate organizational, managerial, human-related, and technological aspects.

According to this planned chapter structure, proposed research questions that are planned to be answered in each chapter are shown in the following table.

Table 1.1: Research questions

Chapters	Subsections	Research questions
<p>Chapter 2 "Theoretical background and Literature Review"</p>	<p>2.1. Industry 4.0 2.1.1 I4.0 philosophy and its importance 2.1.1.1 Industry 4.0 Philosophy 2.1.1.2 Importance of industry 4.0 2.1.2 Existing architectural design and components 2.1.2.1 Industry 4.0's Architectures 2.1.2.2 Industry 4.0's components 2.1.2.2.1 State-of-the-art enabling technologies of I4.0 2.1.2.2.2 Core components of Industry 4.0 2. 2. Smart manufacturing 2.2.1. Smart Factory Philosophy (SF) 2.2.2. Smart Factory Operating Mechanism 2.2.3. Building Smart Factory Capabilities 2.2.3.1 Smart factory features 2.2.3.2 Enabling technologies for building SF's 2.2.4 Mapping of SF Capabilities: Features, Design Principles, and Enabling Technologies 2.2.5 A comparison of SF and I4.0 enabling technologies 2.3. Business Model 2.3.1 Business Model Conceptualization 2.3.2 Philosophy and its importance 2.3.3 Benefits and challenges of IT-Based business models 2.3.4 Existing Business Model Framework designs and components 2.4. Various countries perspective 2.4.1 Turkish perspective 2.4.2 Digitization programs in various countries</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is industry 4.0 a philosophy or just technology? What is the philosophy behind industry 4.0? • What are manufacturing enterprises' reasons for embracing the industry 4.0 and transforming into smart manufacturing enterprises? • How does industry 4.0 based smart concepts help enterprises to obtain and retain a sustainable competitive advantage? • Does Industry 4.0 enable increased individualization of products, shorter time to market and boosts in terms of productivity, and flexibility? • Does industry 4.0 assist the organizations to be lean? • Does industry 4.0 based smart enterprise support sustainability? • Does the industrial organization have proper awareness and knowledge to apply industry 4.0? • Are industrial organization and others aware of industry 4.0 benefits? • Are the novel terminologies theoretically discussed in extensively and sufficiently manner? Are there any ambiguities about industry 4.0 and smart system terminologies? • What characteristics should a smart factory have? Is there a known and accepted Industry 4.0 architecture? • What are well-known components of industry 4.0 based smart factory? What is the typical mix of SF components? Does industry 4.0 components work individually or integrated manner? • What are the main capabilities for SF? • What are the main enabling technologies in relation to smart factories? How can these technologies be grouped? • What are the main design principles in relation to smart factories? How can these design principles be grouped? • What are the main features in relation to smart factories? How can these features be grouped? • How do features, Design Principles, and Enabling Technologies interact to build the desired capabilities? • Are there any accepted business models to support Industry 4.0? How does business model support industry 4.0 implementation? • What are the components and properties of existing industry 4.0's business model? • What is the relationship between the business model and industry 4.0 technologies? • Is digitized business model suitable to industry 4.0 based smart manufacturing enterprises? • What is the existing Industry 4.0 and smart systems in Turkey? • Are there any proven roadmaps to industry 4.0 implementations?

Chapters	Subsections	Research questions
Chapter 3 Smart factories requirements	3.1 Technological requirements 3.2 Managerial requirements 3.3 Organizational requirements 3.4 Human-related requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the requirements to adopt smart factories? How can the smart factory requirements be grouped? • What are the technological requirements for SF? What are the best managerial practices for SF? What management practices facilitate business model innovations and industry 4.0 implementation? • What effect does strategic planning have on the digital transformation journey? How does a leadership characteristic facilitate SF implementation? • What is the role of organizational infrastructures in enabling the transition to a smart factory? What are the requirements in terms of organizational structure? • Which new organizational forms facilitate business model innovations and implementing of industry 4.0 technology? • What effect do digitalization have on the manufacturing enterprise structure? • What are the requirements of smart manufacturing enterprises in terms of human-related issues? • How does the digitalization culture of the manufacturing enterprises impact acceptance of industry 4.0? • What kind of knowledge should employees have? What kind of training should be provided by enterprises? Is effective learning and innovation environment critical for successful applying of industry 4.0?

Chapters	Subsections	Research questions
Chapter 4 Conceptual Framework Development	4.1 Proposed Smart-Capabilities Business Mode 4.2 The unique characteristics of proposed business model 4.3 Proposed multi- perspective framework for SMO 4.4 The unique characteristics of proposed multi- perspective framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does collaborative and comprehensive business model serve digital transformation? • Does a data-driven and networked business model facilitate smart factory implementation? • What is an appropriate business model for applying smart factory? • Is it possible to realize networked integration by applying SF-business model? • What is the role of the business network partners in the smart factory application? • How smart capabilities form SF-business model? • What are the best components of SF-business model? • How does a SF-business model ensures full collaborative performance? • What are the main dimensions of the SF framework? • How does the smart capabilities form within smart factory framework? • What are the main characteristics of the SF framework?
Chapter 5 Survey and Index development	5.1. Survey Development 5.2. Validity and Reliability 5.3. Smart Factory Requirements Maturity Index (SFRMI) 5.3.1. Requirements Maturity index 5.3.1.1. Maturity index for Technological Requirements (MT) 5.3.1.2. Maturity index for Managerial Requirements 5.3.1.3. Maturity index of Organizational Requirements (MO) 5.3.1.4. Maturity of Human-related Requirements (MHh) 5.3.1.5. Maturity of Knowledge Requirements (MK)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can the requirement dimensions identified can be converted to a practical, multi-dimensional maturity measurement survey tool? • How can different dimensions measured and aggregated in an overall maturity level assessment? • How can different weighting criteria can be included in the assessment?

Chapters	Subsections	Research questions
Chapter 6 Field Application	<p>6.1. Selection of the case-study companies and survey approach</p> <p>6.2. Calculation of the SF's maturity levels for 8 case companies</p> <p>6.3. Further Findings</p> <p>6.3.1 Digital transformation hurdles</p> <p>6.3.2 Needed initiatives towards smart-factory preparation</p> <p>6.3.3 Cases' organizational features</p> <p>6.3.4 Research questions revisited</p> <p>6.3.4.1 A roadmap to the future</p> <p>6.3.4.2 The manufacturing enterprises' reasons for embracing the industry 4.0</p> <p>6.3.4.3 Turkish manufacturing enterprises effort toward I.40</p> <p>6.3.4.4 Turkish manufacturing enterprises' awareness and knowledge</p> <p>6.3.4.5 Current digitalization, smartness, and automation level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do Turkish automotive manufacturing enterprises have proper awareness and knowledge to apply SF? What is the current knowledge level availability among the case companies? • What is the current level of technology utilization in the considered companies? • What is the current level of digitalization, smartness, and automation among surveyed manufacturing companies? • What is the current level of managerial maturity towards smart factories for the considered companies? Are the managerial infrastructures in the surveyed companies adequate for the SF implementation? • What is the current level of organizational maturity towards smart factories for the considered companies? Are the organizational infrastructures in the surveyed companies adequate for the SF implementation? • What is the current level of human resource readiness towards smart factories for the considered companies? • What is the overall level of fulfillment of SF requirements in the Turkish automotive sector? • What is the degree of maturity of the surveyed enterprises? Are there mature companies in Turkish automotive enterprises for smart factory? Which hurdles do case companies expect to face for switching to the smart factory? • What are the main reasons for embracing the smart factory among the surveyed companies? <p>Do Turkish automotive manufacturing enterprises have any tendency toward industry 4.0 implementation?</p>
Chapter 7 Case-Based Discussion and Roadmap Development	<p>7.1. Case-based discussion</p> <p>7.2 Suggesting the roadmap for smart factory implementation.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are specific suggestions to be offered to case companies to improve the maturity towards smart factories? • What can be a generic roadmap to be suggested for SF implementations?

1.5. Study's Model and Methodology

The study's systematic system relates to a comprehensive and coherent search followed by a reasonable and predefined approach. Accordingly, our methodology and generic structure consist of many essential steps represented in the following figure:

Figure 1.1: Steps followed for the study

According to the nature of the thesis, tools and methods that are used as part of the study are as follows:

- A structured taxonomic approach for a literature review.
- Conceptual modeling (model, framework).
- Different diagramming and mapping tools (business process flowcharts, value stream mapping. etc.) are used to provide visualization and interpretation purposes.

- Qualitative approaches are used (structured assessment survey) to determine the current technological, managerial, organizational, and human-related field for digitization transformation implementation.
- AHP method is used to estimate the study's dimensions weights, besides using the expert rating to scale each maturity item.
- A set of statistical tools are used to analyse the survey results for maturity.
- Accordingly, a generic and applicable roadmap to transform traditional enterprises into smart enterprises will be determined.

CHAPTER 2:

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND AND LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Industry 4.0

The environmental megatrends such as changing demographics, globalization, scarcity of resources, climate change, huge development in technological sectors, dynamic innovations, shortened life-cycles, and mass customization shape the future of manufacturing. Added to that, more demanding, smart, and diverse customers are pursuing to fulfill their needs in a smart and economical way. Also, the increasing complexities of manufacturing systems such as dynamism, intelligence, interoperability, and interdependence among entities and objects are characterizing this era. In the context of smart and dynamic environments and derived challenges, destructive technologies and innovative scenarios pave the way to embrace and use industry 4.0. A confluence of the environmental pressures, available infrastructures, and expected benefits leads to accelerated industry 4.0 adoption in the next decade.

The contributions of the first three industrial revolutions are represented by mechanization, electricity, and information technology (IT), which merged and overlapped with human effort in manufacturing (Sachdeva, et al., 2017; Salkin, et al., 2018; Qin, et al., 2016; Ennis, et al., 2018; Kagermann, et al., 2013). The interactive integration of digital, physical, and biological entities shifts the environment to become smart and aware, representing the fourth Industrial Revolutions' contributions. Figure 2.1 demonstrates the main stages and features of the industrial revolutions.

The continued volatility of market demand, scarcity of natural resources, high-costly energy, aging, globalization, shortened product life-cycles, high complexity, and fast innovation are prevalent challenges in the current business environment which can be faced by embracing industry 4.0, which include a set of developed technologies, and innovative methods (Moica, et al., 2018; Ganzarain, et al., 2016; Francalanza, et al., 2018; Qin, et al., 2016). To cope with the smart environment and global challenges, the novel industrialization concept called industry 4.0 has emerged and became imperative for enterprises. (Lee, 2015; Mabkhot, et al., 2018; Saucedo-Martínez, et al., 2018; Zhong, et al., 2017).

Figure 2.1: Industrial revolution
(Produced by the author)

The first appearance of industry 4.0 by German, as a public-private sectors initiative, during the Hannover Fair event in 2011 pointing out the high-technology based strategy to safeguarding competitiveness and create smart factories, refers to start of the 4th industrial revolution (Strange, et al., 2017; Sirkin, et al., 2015; Lee, 2015; BCG, et al., 2016; Brettel, et al., 2014; Qin, et al., 2016; Müller, et al., 2018) to face substantial economic and social challenges (Ganzarain, et al., 2016). The significant impacts of industry 4.0 are expected to emerge within 15 years on the German economy (BCG, et al., 2016). Most industrialized countries followed Germany's suit to establish and embrace the fourth industrial revolution and related technologies and concepts; different countries initiated similar programs under different titles, as shown in table 2.1. Ghobakhloo (2018) stressed that manufacturing enterprises still consider industry 4.0 a top priority despite the vague and complex understanding of this phenomenon and the absence of a transformation roadmap to industry 4.0 (Ghobakhloo, 2018). Bahrin et al., 2016 refer that I4.0 is an emerging structure relying on the Cyber-Physical Production System (CPPS), which extensively utilizes local, global networks for real-time and automated exchange of data, information, and business processes are steered and coordinated (Bahrin, et al., 2016).

Table 2.1: Industry 4.0 program title

Country	Program title
United States	Advanced Manufacturing Partnership
German	High-tech Strategy 2020
French	La Nouvelle France Industrielle
United Kingdom	Future of Manufacturing
The European Commission	Factories of the Future
South Korea	Innovation in Manufacturing 3.0
Chinese	Made in China 2025
Japanese	Super Smart Society
Singapore	Research, Innovation and Enterprise 2020 plan (RIE2020)
Russian	The development of the digital economy until 2024

The industry 4.0 concept emerged from the collaboration of key actors from business, academia, politics (Reischauer, 2018), and interdisciplinary interaction. The increased interaction of entities, including technologies, humans, ICT, nanotechnology, biomechanics, and similar advanced techs, contributed to the emergence of destructive and dynamic systems that form smart operating environments and new working ways.

The German Federal Ministry of Education and Research stressed that Industry 4.0 would include "processes will be controlled and coordinated in real-time over large distances" based on the capacity of "equipment, machines, and single components to exchange information continuously" (Fuchs, 2018), through physical and virtual worlds' convergence, that are increasingly merging together a growing number of networked physical objects which owns an intelligent sensor and actuator technology (Bitkom e.V., et al., 2016). Increased digitalization overlap in production and communication technology could be considered paving a way to integrate many different business dimensions and ultimately embrace industry 4.0 (Dalenogare et al., 2018) and construct smart factories and smart products.

The diversity in definitions of industry 4.0 does not prevent the integration and similarity in the authors' perspective but reflects the diversity of authors' scientific background and viewpoint. Summarizing industry 4.0 definitions are shown in table 2.2. Each definition consists of two main aspects, which are technological and organizational.

Table 2.2: Industry 4.0 concept's dimensions

Dimensions	Focus	Description	Authors
Technology	Integration	Integration of Process, components, and technologies.	Sanders et al, 2016; Schmidt et al.,2015; Oesterreich, et al, 2016; Kolberg et al., 2017; Kagermann et al,2013; Shafiq, et al.,2015; Rüßmann, et al.,2015; Dalenogare, et al.,2018; Ghobakhloo,2018; Posada et al, 2015; Hermann et al.,2015; Fuchs,2018;
	Networking	Networked components, objects, products, systems.	Schmidt et al.,2015; Kolberg et al.2017; Kagermann, et al.2013; Pfohl et al,2015; Davies , et al.,2017; Shafiq, et al.2015; Francalanza, et al., 2018; Reischauer, 2018; Hermann et al.2015; Bahrin et al, 2016.
	Smartness	Smart products, part, machines, objects.	Brettel,, et al.,2014; BCG, et al. , 2016; Davies et al., 2017; Schmidt et al,2015; Francalanza et al,2018; Schwab, 2016; Hermann et al., 2015;
Organizational & Managerial	Value chain	Innovative and digital value chain.	Oesterreich, et al, 2016; Kagermann, et al.2013; Pfohl et al,2015; Vaidya et al,2018; BCG, et al.,2016; Reischauer, 2018; Ghobakhloo, 2018; Schwab,2016; Hermann et al.2015;
	Business model	Digital and innovative business model	Kagermann, et al.2013; Rüßmann, et al.,2015; Reischauer, 2018; Hermann et al.2015; Bahrin et al ,2016;

The first aspect is the technological dimension, which clarifies and describes industry 4.0's components and general mechanisms and technologies. Most authors focus on the integration side of components, technologies, systems, and products of industry 4.0 concept (Sanders et al., 2016; Schmidt et al.,2015; Oesterreich, et al., 2016; Kolberg et al., 2017; Kagermann et al.,2013; Shafiq et al.,2015; Rüßmann et al.,2015; Dalenogare et al.,2018; Ghobakhloo,2018; Posada et al., 2015; Hermann et al.,2015; Fuchs,2018). For instance, Dalenogare et al. (2018) refer to I4.0 as a “new industrial stage in which vertical and horizontal manufacturing processes integration and product connectivity can help companies to achieve higher industrial performance” (Dalenogare, et al., 2018). Furthermore, the smartness of products, machines, objects, and components has a critical role in establishing the industry 4.0 concept, which is stressed by many authors such as (Brettel et al.,2014; BCG et al.,2016; Davies et al.,2017; Schmidt et al.,2015; Francalanza et al.,2018; Schwab, 2016; Hermann et al., 2015). For example, Shafiq et al., 2015 consider I4.0 as “combining of intelligent machines, production systems and processes to form a sophisticated network” (Shafiq, et al., 2015), and (Schmidt et

al.,2015; Kolberg et al.2017; Kagermann et al.2013; Pfohl et al.,2015; Davies et al.,2017; Shafiq et al.2015; Francalanza et al.,2018; Reischauer, 2018; Hermann et al. 2015; Bahrin et al., 2016) point out that networking of components, objects, products is considered a fundamental aspect of the industry 4.0 concept.

Therefore, according to the technology's perspective, I4.0 refers to "the structure emerging from the interactive integration among advanced and innovative technologies like CPS, IoT, AI, Big data analytics and cloud computing, which are combined in devices, production centers, machines and products supported by a network of embedded sensors and systems in order to allow autonomous communication with each other, exchange information, autonomous decision making, and invoke actions and controlling each other independently and consciously manners.

The second dimension consists of organizational aspects like the value chain and business model of the concept of Industry 4.0; several authors present industry 4.0 as a creative value chain within the innovative business model based on a suitable and sufficient organizational structure for operating in a smart environment. This aspect cannot be ignored in industry 4.0 because value creation is considered a trigger and navigator for industry 4.0, and their implementation requires an innovative business model and creative organizing methods and vice versa. Several authors touched upon the organizational aspect of industry 4.0 in their definitions, such as (Oesterreich et al., 2016; Kagermann et al. 2013; Pfohl et al., 2015; Vaidya et al., 2018; BCG et al.,2016; Reischauer, 2018; Ghobakhloo, 2018; Schwab, 2016; Hermann et al. 2015). For instance, Vaidya et al. define I4.0 as "a new level of organization and control over the entire value chain of the life cycle of products; it is geared toward increasingly individualized customer requirements" (Vaidya, et al., 2018). The business ecosystem in the context of industry 4.0 requires a deep understanding of value creation mechanisms under these cooperative networks of smart entities, objects, partners (Ennis, et al., 2018).

Accordingly, a comprehensive review of the industry 4.0 concept should be touched upon two inextricable dimensions derived from the authors' perspective. These dimensions form a coherent understanding of the industry 4.0 concept. As a result of this, industry 4.0 a set of enabling technologies to ensure interconnectivity, integrative,

interactivity, and autonomous decision making of all entities under an IoT environment to configure smart-interactive value creation networks that including most stakeholders.

Also, I4.0 is a smart, interactive, and conscious ecosystem configured through equipping all entities (machines, systems, products) with embedded technologies, actuators, AI algorithms, and sensors which enable integrating, interconnecting, interacting among all entities, including all stakeholders in the networked environment of Cyber-Physical system and Internet of Things. Based on all of the above, establishing digital value networks under a creative business model are available and realizable.

2.1.1 I4.0 Philosophy and Its Importance

2.1.1.1 Industry 4.0 philosophy

Traditional manufacturing philosophy is exposed to radical changes as an inevitable result of deploying digitalization in manufacturing sectors (Mabkhot, et al., 2018; Rübél, et al., 2018). The merger of technologies and (ICTs) is establishing new pillars of doing businesses and form a new industrial era (Saucedo-Martínez, et al., 2018; Moica, et al., 2018; Stock, et al., 2016; Kang, et al., 2016; Mabkhot, et al., 2018; Shafiq, et al., 2015). Therefore, competition rules and customers' demands are being reframed base on IoT concepts and digitization of manufacturing (Dalenogare, et al., 2018). Furthermore, Industry 4.0 imposes a new style of partnerships via service-based relationships and improving core business capabilities (Ennis, et al., 2018). Besides that, I4.0 is an innovative style of organizing and controlling the entire value chain, which exceeds a single enterprise (BCG, et al., 2016), and increases products' customization (Vaidya, et al., 2018). The practical and efficient managing and utilizing of real-time data and cumulative knowledge from an integrated object and partner networks have essential contributions for value creation via raising derived data value, enabling novel business models, offering a range of features for all partners (Bitkom e.V., et al., 2016; Ennis, et al., 2018; Dalenogare, et al., 2018), optimizing entire value networks, developing intelligent monitoring systems and enabling autonomous decision's making (Rübél, et al., 2018). Thus, in the light of embracing industry 4.0, business models and practices are reformulated and renewed the relationships among partners based on collaborative networks (Ennis, et al., 2018; Salkin, et al., 2018).

The distributed heterogeneous networks of stakeholders in industry 4.0's context (Davies , et al., 2017) and real-time communication among objects, systems, and humans

lead to establishing a dynamic, self-organized, self-adapting, and real-time optimized value networks enabling horizontal and vertical integration (Bitkom e.V., et al., 2016; Müller, et al., 2018; BCG, et al., 2016), Industry 4.0 facilitates the perpetual exchange of information and communication among manufacturing elements (C2C), (C2M) and (M2M) by using standard Internet-based protocols, to ensure that knowledge management 4.0, autonomous machine learning, and decision-making are constructed by adopting this interaction (Müller, et al., 2018; Roblek, et al., 2016; BCG, et al., 2016). Furthermore, developed cyber-physical systems (CPS) and a massive set of exchanged data manage data-driven processes, which utilize big data analysis to steer smart machines (Strange, et al., 2017; Sirkin, et al., 2015) and determine competition style and collaboration ways of enterprises (Ennis, et al., 2018).

The smart and connected systems under the industry 4.0 context impose new machine-to-machine and human-machine relations. As a result of systems' connectivity, an enormous amount of data is flowing and exchanging. Thus, effective data flow management must manage acquired and accessed data from smart and distributed systems under an industry 4.0 environment (Salkin, et al., 2018; Davies, et al., 2017). Continuous acquisition and analysis of data enable self-control abilities of systems and objects, which allow forecasts and take precautions to prevent systems, machines break down and optimizing production (Salkin, et al., 2018; Roblek, et al., 2016). The digital solutions are provided to customers in industry 4.0 content, such as Internet-based services accompanying smart products, the connectivity platforms used in the industry, which are considered a real-time data source. (Dalenogare, et al., 2018; Kagermann, 2015; Reischauer, 2018). Establishing a smart, open manufacturing platform for industrial-networked information applications allows data monitoring, tracking products' position and status, and keeping instruction to control production processes (Vaidya, et al., 2018). Thus industry 4.0 is an assembled and accumulated force of configured-technologies and concepts based on four essential disruptions: enormous generated data; raised computational power; high-connectivity, and CPS, which impose a set of required-modifications in ways of doing things (Baur, et al., 2015).

The embedded transmitters and sensors impose an innovative and distinctive vision of environment entities to ensure enhanced connectivity and interactivity into integrated networks; Increased usage of transmitters and sensors, regeneration, and

reconfiguration is required in all aspects of life, including manufacturing enterprises to match them with the smart environment. Therefore, innovative ways of thinking based on the information and the connected and networked business model are required to establish an innovation economy and digital value-added based on accessed online services.

Reischauer, 2018 considers industry 4.0 as policy-driven innovation discourse in manufacturing sectors that aim to make innovation systems more institutionalized. Based on the Triple-Helix mode of innovation, which encompasses business, academia, and political dimensions, industry 4.0 is wide-communicative action that crowds actors to work and innovate collaboratively (Reischauer, 2018). Industry 4.0 considers a watershed in manufacturing enterprises' abilities and instrumental competencies while reformulating the conceptual and content of whole processes, jobs, and relationships.

Emerging CPS due to integrated interaction among IoT, ICT, and machines enable high connectivity in the manufacturing system upon industry 4.0 context. This profound change characterizes the fourth industrial revolution (Dalenogare, et al., 2018; Kagermann, et al., 2013; Sony, 2018). The communication and coordination among internal entities of manufacturing enterprise are allowed by the cyber-physical system (CPS) and the internet of things (IoT) (Qin, et al., 2016; Kagermann, et al., 2013) supported by networks of embedded sensors, systems, and smart algorithms (Salkin, et al., 2018). The increased usage of embedded transmitters in all entities, which are developed to be smaller, lighter, less power consumption, and cheaper (Roblek, et al., 2016), is the kernel of I4.0 technology, contributing to a new paradigm shift. This paradigm shift enables products to be controlled along an entire manufacturing process, and ensures that production units and system are able to self-aware, self-configure, self-organize and self-optimize autonomously and independently, initiate actions, self-control, and mutually control each other (interactive control) (Kagermann, et al., 2013; Müller, et al., 2018; Sachdeva, et al., 2017; Davies , et al., 2017; Lasi, et al., 2014; Qin, et al., 2016).

The novel technological period enables the convergence of the physical and virtual world and high interconnectivity of economic and social activities, which are allowed by technology platforms such as the internet, mobility, and sensor systems (Roblek, et al., 2016). Therefore, all entities have their own identities in the network, and they are

able to interconnect, interact, and negotiate with each other to facilitate sharing knowledge via an integrated, tested, and optimized system (Shafiq, et al., 2015).

Therefore, the manufacturing landscape has been changed when information and knowledge technologies, such as IoT, CPS, cloud computing, BDAs, Data Mining, AI, Smart Objects, adaptive robotics, additive manufacturing are widely used in an integrated and coordinated manner with hardware components which enable digitalization transformation (Ennis, et al., 2018; Salkin, et al., 2018). Using industry 4.0 allows manufacturing systems to observe physical objects and processes by virtual replication via digital-twins technology, to configure comprehensive dataset, which is fundamental to establish a collaborative and communicative network and smart decision making (Zhong, et al., 2017; Davies , et al., 2017; Bitkom e.V., et al., 2016). Depending on the integrated network and objects integration, including products within the internet environment, allow the extended and remote sources of information, besides the collected and resulted data from embedded systems, sensors, and RFID saved in the cloud to be shared with the operating environment entities, all objects, machines, and systems that are networked and integrated with cloud computing. Proactive maintenance is based on collected data that provides information about production's optimization opportunities (Roblek, et al., 2016).

Qin et al. (2016) point out that the philosophy of Industry 4.0 revolves around two main concepts: interoperability and consciousness. These intended foundations cover numerous sub-concepts, technologies, applications, and so forth that incorporated into a manufacturing framework. Interoperability implies digitalization, standardization, communication, real-time responsiveness, flexibility, and customizability, whereas consciousness includes predictive maintenance, self-configuration, self-awareness, intelligent presentation, self-optimization, and decision making (Qin, et al., 2016). In the context of these concepts' content, each concept has a unique formation that operates in interacted integration with others by achieving interoperability and consciousness, including related sub-concepts that ultimately allow applying and operating industry 4.0.

Integration considers the core idea of interoperability, and it is the crucial point of IoT and CPS. Three main types of integration are pointed in the industry 4.0 network: horizontal integration consisting of the collaboration among partners networks to share

resources and information (collaborative value network). End-to-end integration is engineering integration of the whole value chain for product's chain, and vertical integration is ICT integration over manufacturing enterprises including all hierarchical levels (Kagermann, et al., 2013; Qin, et al., 2016; Dalenogare, et al., 2018; Brettel, et al., 2014). According to horizontal and vertical integration under the industry 4.0 context, a new generation of interrelationships and interdependencies has emerged within entire manufacturing enterprises (Rübel, et al., 2018).

Salkin et al., 2018 add three ideas to approach of industry 4.0 philosophy. Firstly, the networking of distributed-entities is enabled through IIOT and alternative connections to link a set of dispersed- technologies and systems to each other, such as wireless sensor networks, embedded systems, cloud systems, additive manufacturing, and autonomous robots. Secondly, the integrated, computer-based environment is formed by the interaction of cyber-physical systems and adaptive robots in the presence of disruptive technologies like three-dimensional (3D) visualization, printing, and simulation. Thirdly, the widespread usage of coordinating tools and big data analysis in the whole system allows autonomous processes conducting and real-time decision making (Salkin, et al., 2018).

The industry 4.0 philosophy concentrates on the integration between production and servitization concepts to create a unique business model, creative value network, improve internal processes, better integrate with partners, and establishes a collaborative network with partners by using advanced technologies in production and depending on a product service-system and related technologies (Ennis, et al., 2018). Industry 4.0's networks are formed by the integration of (a) RFID, (b) wireless sensor networks (WSN), (c) middleware, (d) cloud computing, and (e) IoT application software, which establish exchanging structure of data, information and knowledge supported by both human efforts and artificial intelligence (Roblek, et al., 2016). Thus, converting traditional machines to self-aware, smart, and self-learning machines is possible by embracing industry 4.0 technologies to enhance overall performance, including the maintenance sector (Vaidya, et al., 2018).

2.1.1.2 Importance of industry 4.0

The implementation of industry 4.0 is accompanied by a range of changes in managerial, organizational, and technological domains, which are imposed by

advanced technologies, and the innovative value chain of industry 4.0, due to interventional impacts of industry 4.0; therefore, I4.0's impacts exceed the potential cost and efficiency gains from the implementation of industry 4.0 to optimizing internal and core capabilities and renew behavior patterns.

The managerial importance of industry 4.0 stems from the impacts and changes that I4.0 imposes. Moreover, industry 4.0's requirements impose new business processes and digitalize most processes, which significantly impact. Therefore, I4.0 configured and re-engineered the whole management process, which required new preparation, long-term supporting, and operating practices. Besides, embracing industry 4.0 redraws and redefines traditional concepts like customers, job design, performance criteria, and work mechanism.

Industry 4.0 involves a range of reflections in enterprises' performance like an opportunity to grow revenue and thrive (Rübel, et al., 2018), combine resources, quickly adapt to changes and divide risks (Brettel, et al., 2014; Dalenogare, et al., 2018). Therefore, I4.0 pursues to make proactive behavior one of the organizational features, and their business model (Rübel, et al., 2018; Dalenogare, et al., 2018) and CPS supports accurate decisions making (Dalenogare, et al., 2018). Complementary and installed services with manufactured products are the base of customer satisfaction and effective competition in the production environment of industry 4.0 (Ennis, et al., 2018; Rübel, et al., 2018). Furthermore, the smart, effective, efficient, customized, and individualized production at the right cost is realized through industry 4.0, which supported by advanced technologies such as smarter machines, faster computers, cheaper data storage, smaller sensors, and transmission to form and provide a smart and awareness machines and products with connecting and learning abilities (Vaidya, et al., 2018), to increase flexibility, adaptation, and customization (Ennis, et al., 2018) and enhancing decision-making accuracy in the operational and strategic domain (Dalenogare, et al., 2018; Kagermann, et al., 2013). Also, the increased productivity through utilizing smart and advanced technologies under industry 4.0 context could secure skilled and cognitive jobs and raise employee income, but also could disappear some traditional job (Roblek, et al., 2016).

Industry 4.0's impacts extend to reach the strategic level. Industry 4.0 implementation requires embracing innovative strategies to harmony with industry 4.0's required

infrastructure, such as encouraging self-learning, self-optimizing, initiatives, cognitive thinking, and data-driven behaviors, which improve employees' skills qualifications. Industry 4.0 urges enterprises to adopt strategies to deploy change culture and accept digitalization like continuous learning programs and training programs, supporting by conferences, workshops, and social learning groups that promote employee performance and productivity. Besides, embracing industry 4.0 forms a proper infrastructure of the comprehensive business-intelligence system, which is considered a decision support system, sharing-knowledge tools, could be extended to provide knowledge for all workers and, in extreme tech level, for all entities.

High customized products are one of the main aims of embracing industry 4.0; the I4.0 reflections extend to enhance order management, manufacturing commissioning, delivery to the utilization, and enhancing research and development (Vaidya, et al., 2018; Dalenogare, et al., 2018). Therefore, in the logistics aspect, optimizing transport processes, eliminating unnecessary material flows, removing wrong delivery, optimizing lead-time, reducing inventory, and decreasing damaged goods is possible by data transparency throughout the entire supply chain within industry 4.0 (Müller, et al., 2018; Rübel, et al., 2018).

A high level of communication with partners, including customers, and emerging collaborative relationships in the industry 4.0 context contribute to establishing customer-orientation systems, high-satisfaction, customized, smart, individualized, and obtainable products are delivered. In the digitization era, classical processes are updated, and a radical change is applied, including the managerial process, to form data-driven processes or smart processes, which enable enhancing accurate decision making, accelerating process, high response, and improving predictive behavior. Realizing a vertical, horizontal, and end-to-end integration in industry 4.0 optimizes the system's intercommunication and interoperability.

Depending on the transparency of demand, process, and data accompanying with industry 4.0 implementation, the load balancing and optimized utilization are realized, which also allows intelligent scheduling, low energy consumption (Müller et al., 2018), reducing waste and recycling of products (Vaidya, et al., 2018; Dalenogare, et al., 2018). Smart systems' energy consumption is predictable (Müller, et al., 2018) and

manageable, leading to cost optimization and high performance via simulation technology.

From the organizational aspects, the collaborative networks under industry 4.0's context enable manufacturing enterprises to establish a smart, interconnected and self-regulating value creation network, and they provide value for all the members of value networks, including customers via smart products and platforms (Dalenogare, et al., 2018; Müller, et al., 2018; Liao, et al., 2017; BCG, et al., 2016), which ultimately improve the quality, efficiency, and service level (Zhong, et al., 2017). Industry 4.0 encourages utilizing methodology and architecture as a crucial part of an organization's culture via proper training programs and familiarization with the cooperative relationship among partners (stakeholders) and the core capabilities of partners (Davies , et al., 2017), So the new generated relationships impose new levels of integration and coordination, which pave to the interactive alliances, mutual interests, shared data, shared resources and shared responsibilities and risks among partners in the context of the industry 4.0.

Sirkin et al. (2015) point out that industry 4.0 and related technologies enable high flexibility, small batches for specific customers, and fast-adjustment to design changes (low setup time, high-responsively), shortening time to market.

The real-time communication among objects, partners, and systems in industry 4.0 network leads to establishing dynamic, self-organized, and real-time optimized value networks (Bitkom e.V., et al., 2016) and, accurate decisions in a swift manner are available in industry 4.0's environment (Müller, et al., 2018; Kang, et al., 2016), Additionally, reconfiguring and modifying are allowed by industry 4.0 to transfer a traditional business model to an innovative business model and to establish collaborative interrelationships.

Davies et al. (2017) stressed that the high responsiveness of industry 4.0 to customers' needs relies on the interconnected world via smart factories (Davies , et al., 2017). By utilizing the new generation of CRM within IoT context provide a perfect understanding of customers and allow proactive support by utilizing IoT data, also considering IoT as an integrationist environment of ERP under smart factory content that involves smart equipment, which allows exchanging data with the operating environment (Roblek, et al., 2016).

The technological aspects. The interconnectivity and availability of data from product usage back to design in real-time assist in concurrent design. As a result, life cycle management, including recycling and product utilization, is improved (Müller, et al., 2018). Moreover, improving resource utilization and energy savings via integration of production with smart grids are possible (Dalenogare, et al., 2018). Thus, the reduction of produced wastes, resource consumption, pollution, CO2 emissions, and costs in the industry 4.0-based smart factory are realized (Kagermann, 2015; Müller, et al., 2018). Hence industry 4.0 paves the way to complex-automated -sustained manufacturing processes (Qin , et al., 2016). Furthermore, real-time information availability of products and production systems ensures smooth inter-company operations, unites their core competencies, and eliminates companies' boundaries (Brettel, et al., 2014). Achieving flexible, smart, more productive, and reconfigurable manufacturing processes are allowed by the integration among ICT and manufacturing technologies to face the challenge of a dynamic and smart environment (Brettel, et al., 2014; Dalenogare, et al., 2018; Reischauer, 2018; Zhong, et al., 2017).

The innovative purchasing mechanisms, the optional product functions and features, and unrestricted demand quantity are offered to customers by industry 4.0 technology, enabling customers to change or/and add new options during production (Qin , et al., 2016). The high customization in industry 4.0 philosophy stems from widespread usage of additive manufacturing (3D printer) and high-autonomy, which provide users high-selectability of options and customize parts.

Regarding social aspects of Industry 4.0, the integrated communication network of industry 4.0 implies real-time connection among all partners, and each one is in charge of optimizing their configuration, which maximizes the profit for all cooperative partners with limited shared resources (Qin, et al., 2016; Kagermann, et al., 2013; Davies , et al., 2017). Labor productivity should rise, and labor costs should fall in the medium-term, and firms will base their production location decisions less on production costs and more on proximity to customers (Strange, et al., 2017). Industry 4.0 has promoted and required high human-learning abilities and intelligent training programs through smart assistance systems and Human-Machine interactions, through smart human-machine interfaces, enhance worker satisfaction level. Furthermore, industry 4.0 has promoted cognitive-orientated jobs more than those with muscular orientation and has imposed innovative jobs (Müller, et al., 2018). Therefore the required muscular

and manual efforts are mitigated and maximize the IT-skills utilization thus, jobs design has developed, and the new job has emerged and in parallel with vanishing some classic jobs (Müller, et al., 2018; Davies , et al., 2017), besides that industry 4.0 pave the way to operate machines in easily, simply, stable and efficient manner, and providing a new generation of products with advanced-abilities like conscious, state-diagnoses, and interoperability (Qin , et al., 2016).

2.1.2 Existing Architectural Design and Components

2.1.2.1 Industry 4.0's architectures

The complexity of configured systems and increased use of embedded sensor networks allow emerging embedded and connected systems besides an integrated set of smart entities, a fundamental pillar of industry 4.0 implementation. These disruptive and complex configurations require a clear and understandable architecture to be applicable and available.

Generally, architecture is considered to assist and develop tools, knowledge transformers, organizing quality, tools to connect system functionality, instructing design, and tools for the easy and fast understanding of a system (Sharpe, et al., 2019). Therefore, the existence of an understandable and applicable architecture facilitates digital transformation planning and enables implementing industry 4.0 and managing the digitalization efforts.

Many publications discuss the industry 4.0 architecture concerning IIOT, CPPS, Enterprise Architectures, Enterprise Integration, and Cloud Manufacturing. Thus, many architectures are proposed but without consensus in opinions about an accepted or common architecture. The proposed architectures reflect an individual's perspective or a small research group's perspective (Yli-Ojanperä, et al., 2018). A unified architecture was increasing and became inevitable due to the risky and expensive digitalization programs needed to realize full automation and smartness in end-to-end business processes, production and to cover all the products.

Therefore, conducting a theoretical survey that shows existing architectures of industry 4.0 are indispensable, Table 2.3 below shows the most relevant architectures related to industry 4.0.

Table 2.3: Architectures of industry 4.0

Architecture	Developed by	Root	Usage	Components / layers
Reference Architecture Model industry 4.0 (RAMI 4.0)	BITCOM, VDMA and ZWEI	Smart Grid Architecture Model (SGAM)	I4.0	Hierarchy Levels, Layers, Lifecycle and Value Stream
Industrial Internet Reference Architecture (IIRA)	IIC	(ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010) Systems and software engineering Architecture description.	IIOT / I4.0	Viewpoints, Lifecycle Process and Industrial Sectors
Intelligent manufacturing System Architecture (IMSA)	MIT and SAC		I4.0	Life Cycle, System Level, and Smart Functioning.
Industrial Value Chain Reference Architecture (IVRA)	IVI		IIOT / I4.0	Management view Activity view, Asset View
3C CPS (3C)	AHMADI et al. (2018)	(Anthropocentric Cyber-Physical System) (ACPS)	CPS/I4.0	The physical component (PC), the computational/cyber component (CC), human component (HC) and related interactions (interface)
5C CPS (5C)	Lee et al. (2015)	3C CPS Architecture	CPS/I4.0	connection, conversion, cyber, cognition, and configuration levels

1. The 3C CPS Architecture for Industry 4.0

The 3C architecture is considered as an advanced-version of ACPS (Anthropocentric Cyber-Physical System), which is an essential element for the future industries based on high connectivity of all the components PC, CC, and HC on every individual level of operations, including all interactive relations (interfaces) (HC-CC; HC-PC; CC-PC). The connectors and protocols of ACPS architecture are used to configure a stable and connected environment for 3C architecture, representing industry 4.0 architecture and their validity to guide a manufacturing organization's digitalization efforts.

In these architectures, all physical entities are equipped with embedded sensors, systems, and actuators to produce smart entities consisting of three main elements physical components, smart components, and connectivity components (Ahmadi, et al., 2018).

The 3C architecture is built on the integration and interaction among Human Components, Physical components, and Cyber components to establish industry 4.0's environment besides the constructed interface of components interactions and connectors, as is shown in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2: The 3C CPS Architecture
Source: (Ahmadi, et al., 2018)

2. Reference Architecture Model industry 4.0 (RAMI4.0)

RAMI4.0 is a developed version of the Smart Grid Architecture Model (SGAM) to meet I4.0 requirements (Sharpe, et al., 2019; Pessoa, et al., 2018), by using the 3D representation to depict industry 4.0's architecture. It is proposed by the German's Association (BITCOM, VDMA, and ZWEI) as the foundation for the development of products and business models (Pisching, et al., 2018; Zezulka, et al., 2016). Using RAMI4.0 enables establishing coherent architecture and preparing to I4.0's ecosystem, involving non-proprietary systems solutions (Pessoa, et al., 2018).

RAMI 4.0 is strived to coordinate three main aspects (axes): Hierarchy Levels (horizontal axis), Layers (vertical axis), and Life Cycle and Value Stream (the left axis) based on three fundamental types of integrations (vertical, horizontal, end-to-end engineering) (Pisching, et al., 2018; Pessoa, et al., 2018) as it is shown in Figure 2.3.

- Hierarchy Level: Based on IEC 62264, 2013 and IEC 61512-1:1997, the basis of Hierarchy Levels of RAMI 4.0 is identified (international standard of Enterprise-control system integration). RAMI 4.0 consists of seven layers called 'Enterprise,' 'Work

Centers,' 'Station,' 'Control Device,' 'Field Device,' and 'Product.' The last two elements are newly added to extend individual factory boundaries at the top, by modifying SGAM. This dimension presents per component functional descriptions appearing how interacted with life cycle and value stream dimensions (Bitkom e.V., et al., 2016; Pisching, et al., 2018; Sharpe, et al., 2019). This level shows the information about configuration scenarios and functions for development processes, production lines, manufacturing machinery, field devices, and the products (Bitkom e.V., et al., 2016), to realize the integration of enterprise-control systems (Pessoa, et al., 2018).

- Layers are the structure of the digital/ virtual representation of an industry 4.0 component (the composition of physical assets and where they are resided) (Bitkom e.V., et al., 2016; Pessoa, et al., 2018; Pisching, et al., 2018; Zezulka, et al., 2016), which also includes the passive technology usage (embedded technologies) such as Quick Response Codes (QR codes), operators, reality and barcodes in asset level. While in integration level consist of a set of technologies to hold information of different assets and ensure connecting hardware such as sensors, human interfaces, and RFID readers, the standardization of communication are used in the communication layer to apply a uniform format to data and information exchanged through it, as well as, providing a set of services used to control the Integration layer. Information layer presents run time preprocessing of events and apply context to events passed to it, executes the events with respect to rules, provide a formal description of the rules and events to initiate the functional layer, ensuring high-quality data, data integrity, symmetric integration of various data, and using service interface to provide structured data. Functional Layer provides a formal description of functions and establishes a platform for horizontal integration of different functions where services are operated and described based on run time and modeling environment of services. The layer also boosts the run-time environment for applications and technical functionality to support business processes. Creating rules and decision-making logic also happens in this layer. Business layer ensures the integrity and orchestrates the functions and services in the value stream. Modeling, simulating and applying of rules according to legal and regulatory framework conditions to map business models and related processes happen at this layer (Zezulka, et al., 2016; Pessoa, et al., 2018; Bitkom e.V., et al., 2016; Pisching, et al., 2018; Sharpe, et al., 2019).

- Life Cycle and Value Stream:

The life cycle and value stream axis consist of two main parts “Development (Type)” and instance (Bitkom e.V., et al., 2016). The development (Type) stage commences when the product design and process model are developed (Zezulka, et al., 2016). The initial idea of design is continually negotiated to gain a serial production basis; instance stage is commenced after passing all tests and validation; by creating a basis for the serial production in this stage, an acceptable design (instance) is manufactured having unique identifiers, to be sold and delivered to customers ultimately (Pessoa, et al., 2018; Sharpe, et al., 2019). Fig 2.4 shows the philosophy of the life cycle & and value stream axis.

Figure 2. 3:RAMI 4.0 architecture

Figure 2. 4:The philosophy of life cycle & and value stream in RAMI4.0

3. Industrial Internet Reference Architecture (IIRA)

The Industrial Internet Reference Architecture was published by Industrial Internet Consortium (IIC) in June 2015 (Li, et al., 2018). Based on ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010:2011, the IIRA was created to describe the conventions, principles, and practices of a system that facilitates the assessment and systematic resolution of stakeholders' concerns in an effective manner (Kemppainen, 2016). IIRA is a standards-based open architecture for IIOT system for improving the interoperability, mapping applicable technologies, and providing guidance technology and standard development, as well as enhancing documentation and communication of the system, solution, and application architectures (Lin, et al., 2017; VDI/VDE-GMA Technical Committee, 2017). The Industrial Internet Reference Architectures (IIRA) provides a generic description and representation of entities in a high level of abstraction to promote broad applicability in industry sectors to maximize value (Lin, et al., 2017b; VDI/VDE-GMA Technical Committee, 2017). The IIRA describes and summarizes the popular features, characteristics, and patterns from the specific case defined in the manufacturing environment, updated and revised continually according to feedback (Lin, et al., 2017b).

Generally, a reference architecture is considered as an initiating point for the extended and detailed framework and discussions to enable subsequent designs, with a high level of abstraction which enables IIRA to identify and comprehend the critical issues and patterns over its applications in various use cases and sectors (IIC, 2015). The IIRA includes three fundamental aspects: Viewpoints, Lifecycle Process, and Industrial Sectors, as shown in Fig 2.5 (Li, et al., 2018). The IIRA viewpoints are identified by the relevant stakeholders of IIoT systems and determined the proper framing of concerns. These four viewpoints are:

Business viewpoint: in this viewpoint, the stakeholders and their concerns are identified, including their vision, values, and objectives in establishing IISs system and mapping to essential system capabilities (IIC, 2015; Li, et al., 2018; VDI/VDE-GMA Technical Committee, 2017).

The usage viewpoint: tackling and identifying the main concerns of expected system usage (the expected use) to deliver and enable the core capabilities of the system by a sequence of activities and interactions of all entities, including human and logic users,

product managers, system engineers, end-user, and all individuals who are related system under consideration are possible human-users of IIRA (IIC, 2015; Li, et al., 2018).

Functional viewpoint: The functional perspective of IRA's viewpoint emphasizes the functional components, which consist of a set of provided functions to realize system objectives and ensure intended use, desired interactions, and activities of its actors. The functional viewpoint provides fundamental building-blocks of the system's functions such as their structure, interrelation, interfaces, and interactions with their environment (systems, elements). The IIRA goes further in this viewpoint than in the others by providing a concrete functional model consisting of five distinct functional domains that are intended to be widely applicable in IIoT systems (Kemppainen, 2016; IIC, 2015; VDI/VDE-GMA Technical Committee, 2017).

Figure 2.5: Idea of IIRA
(Li, et al., 2018)

The implementation viewpoint deals with the technologies needed to implement functional components (functional viewpoint), communication schemes, and lifecycle procedures. These elements are coordinated by activities (usage viewpoint) and supportive of the system capabilities (business viewpoint) (Lin, et al., 2017b).

4. The Industrial Value Chain Reference Architecture (IVRA)

In 2016 the Industrial Value Chain Initiative published a reference architecture called the Industrial Value Chain Reference Architecture to enable connecting technology from a bottom-up approach, usually used Smart Manufacturing Units (SMUs) as

synonyms of IVRA (Takahashi, et al., 2017). Also, IVRA relies on layers technology, which is clustered in three primary layers (perspective):

- **Management Layer:** This layer reflects the management's perspectives and targets. The manufacturing structure, organization structure, the philosophy and concept of value, and essential and critical issues are discussed. Customers' views and feedback are debated concerning quality, delivery accuracy, and values of all products or/and services that manufacturers provided. The environmental perspective and a view of positioning for business strategies and intellectual property are discussed to overview the comprehensive picture.
- **Asset layer:** Humans, processes, products, and plants are detailed discussed in this layer with respect to activities, items, relations, and characteristics. All assets valuable to manufacturing enterprises are shown, including virtual (Data) and physical entities.
- **Activities layer:** different activities of individuals, machines, and their interactions are discussed in this layer, all human and/or machine activities are discussed and describe to execute, evaluate and update, which based on the Deming circle philosophy (PDCA-circle) to improve targeted issues proactively continuously, which consist of “Plan,” “Do,” “Check” and “Action.”

Figure 2. 6:Industrial value chain reference architecture (Takahashi, et al., 2017)

5. Intelligent Manufacturing System Architecture (IMSA)

In 2015 the IMSA was published to tackle the new generation of challenges and deliver a proper understanding of smart manufacturing in China, to seek the integration and

fusion of ICT and manufacturing technologies (life digitalization). The philosophy of IMSA is based on three aspects: lifecycle, system hierarchy, and intelligent functions (Wei, et al., 2017).

- In the lifecycle aspect of IMSA, the connected value chain is discussed concerning design, production, logistics, sales, and service to establish an integrated chain. The sequential activities of value creation are associated and influenced mutually; each industry has a designated lifecycle (VDE, et al., 2015; Wei, et al., 2017).
- The organizational structure is discussed concerning the hierarchical division of enterprises' manufacturing activities, which consists of five hierarchies: equipment hierarchy, control hierarchy, workshop hierarchy, enterprise hierarchy, and cooperation hierarchy.
- As a result of digitalization, the new generation of manufacturing activities consists of smart functions that enable reaching the goal of self-sensing, self-learning, self-adaptation, self-decision, and self-execution. The intelligent functions encompass five layers: resource elements, system integration, interconnection, information fusion, and new business pattern, as shown in Figure 2.7.

Figure 2. 7: Intelligent manufacturing system architecture

6. 5C architecture

The first appearance of the 5C architecture is in 2015 by Lee, Bagheri, and Kao as vertical integration architecture of CPS to provide a step-by-step guide for developing and deploying a CPS in manufacturing sectors (Lee, et al., 2015). The logical properties acquired by adopting CPS technology under the industry 4.0 context will enable and enhance maintenance functions and better physical entities' controllability (Rødseth, et al., 2017).

Figure 2. 8: 5C architecture
Source: (Ahmadi, et al., 2018)

Based on CPS attributes, the five levels of the 5C architecture are identified, which designate as “Connection Level,” “Conversion Level,” “Cyber Level,” “Cognition Level,” and “Configuration Level” (Lin, et al., 2018; Lee, et al., 2015) as it is shown in Figure 2.8.

Lin et al. (2018) emphasizes the impact of 5C architecture on assessing current manufacturing capabilities to embrace industry 4.0 by describing the main functions starting from hardware connection, information discovery, automated system, predictive maintenance, and smart production (Lin, et al., 2018).

Lee 2015 stresses real-time data acquisition, ensuring high connectivity among physical entities and data management and analysis via a clearly defined the needed know-how to establish CPS starting from gathering data to value creation (Lee, et al., 2015). The 5C architecture levels, as it is shown in Figure 2.8, are described below:

1. Smart connection level is focused on gathering various data from dispersed sources, including networked sensors, controllers, and subsystems like ERP, MES, SCM, and CMM. Real-time, reliable, and accurate gathering processes from physical entities are the first construction step of CPS implementation. This stage consists of description and identification of required networks and tools, including sensors-types and protocols, to ensure the acquisition of data (connecting, capturing, recording, sharing) in the seamless and tether-free manner (Lin, et al., 2018; Plessis, 2017; Qin , et al., 2016).
2. Data-to-information conversion level: extracting the useful and meaningful information is the core of the second stage to convert extracted data from connected entities to usable and meaningful information (Lee, et al., 2015; Rødseth, et al., 2017; Plessis, 2017; Lin, et al., 2018), In the prognostics and health management context, the created information deals with a set of Indicators such as power consumption, levels of vibration, RIFD data, usage data, so on to estimate and create health value, current state, and estimated remaining useful life of connected entities. This stage enables self-awareness in networked physical entities (Lee, et al., 2015; Plessis, 2017; Rødseth, et al., 2017).
3. Cyber level: Cyber stage is considered a central hub where the networked machines continually send information to save and analyze the gathered information. The extracted information is used to produce better insight and knowledge of the individual status of all connected physical entities (historical information). The availability of analyzing information allows self-comparison ability among connected entities, where the individual performance of machines is measured and rated, thus the assessing-comparison are allowed to predict the future behavior of physical entities and facilitate prognostic and health management (PHM) (Jiang, 2017; Lee, et al., 2015; Plessis, 2017).
4. Cognition Level: The cumulative generation of monitored system knowledge in the current stage supports the decision-making and drives the human interaction and evaluations by providing a proper presentation (a visual packaging and display) of analytics and acquired knowledge. Therefore, transferring and sharing acquired knowledge is a core objective of this stage (Lee, et al., 2015; Plessis, 2017).

5. Configuration level: The cyber level feedback streams (digital advice) to physical space enable the self-configuration and self-adaptive abilities of physical entities by acting as supervisory control. The corrective and preventive decisions taken in the last stage have been applied to the configuration stage, which acts as a resilience control system (RCS) of the monitored systems. These reconfigurations ensure high flexibility and adaptability of systems (physical and cyber) (Lee, et al., 2015; Rødseth, et al., 2017; Lin, et al., 2018). The following table provides a comparative summary of these six main architectures:

Table 2. 4:A comparative table for six architectures

Architectures	Scope	Context	Human aspect	Functions aspect	Business aspect	Integration		
						Vertical	Horizontal	End-to-end
RAMI 4.0	I4.0 / Smart factory	Framework, concepts, methods, templates, technologies, and standards	The arrangement and orchestrating efforts of the value stream	Functional layer: describing required functions, services, applications, and circumstances to configure intended systems, which are run and integrated to support business processes	Business layer: “orchestrating and managing the whole business life cycle and Value stream.”	Hierarchy Level	Value networks	Value stream
IMSA	I4.0 / Smart factory	Proposes suitable scenarios to cope with the new generation of challenges by providing the standard framework, systems characteristics, standardization, and all dimensions' logistic relations: general standards and key industrial standards.	The human efforts fall within complementary requirements for all layers and dimensions.	The functional aspect of IMSA is based on merging IT and the classical concept of function to create the IT-based functions, which is a smartness tool of IMSA.	The system hierarchy's cooperation level reflects the business aspects of IMSA architecture by managing the cooperation among their value chains and cross-region enterprises.	system hierarchy	the cooperation level of the system hierarchy and lifecycle	Lifecycle and intelligent functions
IIRA	IoT/ I4.0	Framework, principles, concepts, methods, and templates	The human's concerns (stakeholders) are building blocks of IIRA	Functional viewpoint: the functional components (a set of crosscutting functions) to realize desired interactions, use, and objectives of systems	Business viewpoint: Using stakeholders' concerns to establish, maintain and modify the IIOT systems.	usage viewpoint	Business Viewpoint, lifecycle	Lifecycle, Functional viewpoint , implementation viewpoint

IVRA	IIOT / I4.0	provides configuration scenarios through interaction of knowledge/engineering flow, the demand/supply flow and hierarchical levels .Establishes connected environment for all entities (hardware, software ,and humans)	The human's interactions, relations, actions, performance, roles, perspectives and decisions are the core blocks of IVRA.	The Functional aspect of IVRA are created and configured by the three layers interactions and theirs related aspects.	Management layer reflects the management's philosophy, perspectives, strategies and targets, along with customers perspectives	Management Layer	Not supported	Asset layer & Activities layer
3C CPS	CPS/I4.0	Providing a guideline, stable and connected environment, main interfacing elements (connectors, protocols), sub-element (human, cyber and physical parts), improving the standardization level, and general description of possible interaction scenarios.	The human is considered as interactive components with high adaptability to the smart and changeable environment, also work-based learning and broader skills are an inevitable requirement thus Human Component considers the inevitable components for the newly coined Industry 4.0.	Not mentioned	The 3C-CPS lacks of horizontal integration efforts and the networking and communication with business environment are not included.	HC-PC HC-CC PC-CC interactions	Not supported	HC-PC HC-CC PC-CC interactions
5C CPS	CPS/I4.0	The 5C architecture provides a detailed guideline for developing and deploying industrial applications based on CPS and self-evaluation tool of capabilities, besides providing a hierarchy representation of CPS.	In 5C architecture, Human considered as a user of CPS, especially, in cognition layer (supporting decision making).	The five level represented the main functional aspect of 5C architecture, the logical properties of applying CPS enable and enhance functional performance, and the vertical integration of 5C architecture supports and converts essential functions to be smarter through high-connectivity and intelligent data management.	The horizontal integration and business environment are Ignored by 5C architecture in directly manner but with adopting ERP as one of information sources which include outside data,	All 5C layers support vertical integration	Not supported	All 5C-layers support end to end integration efforts, especially in Smart connection and Data-to-information conversion

2.1.2.2 Industry 4.0's components

2.1.2.2.1 State-of-the-art enabling technologies of I4.0

Kagermann considered the convergence among virtual and physical entities as a core inspirational source of innovation and change in all sectors of our lives (Kagermann, 2015). This convergence has an exponential impact of reconfiguring all ecosystems, especially in the manufacturing sectors, based on the high-velocity technologies which are utilized to ensure the highly harmonic, integrative, and intraoperative operating of all components.

Industry 4.0 impacts stem from their key components and related interactions among these components, and the major challenge is identifying the best mixture of components to embrace and implement industry 4.0's system (Resman, et al., 2019). The interactive integration of industry 4.0's components and related implications, such as transparency, autonomous and interconnection of the entire-processes and components, allow optimizing their efficiency, quality, flexibility, customization (Qin, et al., 2016; Oesterreich, et al., 2016; Müller, et al., 2018) and the efficiency and effective utilization of resources and energy to shape ultimately smart, networked and agile value chain (Ganzarain, et al., 2016; Resman, et al., 2019). Thus, the configurative and composite nature of industry 4.0 imposes combining a wide variety and range of heterogeneous technological domains which interact and integrate to establish smart systems to realize their desired characteristics.

Besides, in consciousness context, the intelligent behavior of machines, objects, and systems within industry 4.0, that are driven by consciousness abilities, which able to find information, create knowledge, do analysis, decide and deliver the action independently, autonomously, and intelligently (Qin, et al., 2016). In this regard, the increased usage of embedded sensors leads to emerging embedded and related systems, which are a central pillar of industry 4.0 implementation. The embedded sensor-based systems provide a massive number of data as ongoing feedback on monitoring and controlling activities within the entire manufacturing processes, including products, besides modifying virtual models of equipment, conveyors, and machines by this information (Dalenogare, et al., 2018).

The upshot of all this is that advanced technologies' possession does not ensure industry 4.0's implementation. Having a novel layout, structure, and integrated architecture to

enable targeted characteristics as well as knowledge of how to utilize these technologies are required.

After reviewing the different papers, it has been observed that each author discusses the I4.0's key technologies according to the study's scope and industry's needs in their papers. Consequently, different identifications and approaches emerged for I4.0 technologies. Highly-diverse and heterogeneous technologies of I4.0 are still continuously developing based on rapid development in all sciences domains. Most advanced and has been developed technologies have a high possibility to be used as a component of industry 4.0.

The conducted review revealed that 46 authors surveyed mention 40 different technologies as enabling technologies to I4.0. This number is still increasable. Figure 2.10 shows this great diversity of enabling technologies. The variation of consensus degrees, as presented in Figure 2.9, reflects the extended range of I4.0's applications and the required multidisciplinary technologies to form I4.0. It seems to be a significant consensus on the description the main technologies of I4.0 represented by Cyber-physical System, Internet of Thing, Big Data, Additive Manufacturing, Robots, and Cloud computing based on their appearance's frequency percent in discussed papers which are: 85%, 72%, 67%, 52%, 46%, 78% respectively, as it is shown in Figures (2.11) and (2.12). Undoubtedly, that does not erase or decrease the importance of other technologies.

Figure 2. 9: The consensus degree of proposed I4.0's technologies (Created by author)

Figure 2. 10: The available enabling technologies of I4.0.
(Created by author)

In particular, Figure 2.11 represents the top six technologies ranked by the number of publications identified as enabling technologies. Figure 2.13 presents a glance at the dramatic increase in the number of publications from 2012 to 2019 associate with the top six technologies of I4.0.

Figure 2. 11: The most prevalent I4.0's technologies.

(Created by author)

* The number next to reference indicates how many technologies have been mentioned in that resource.

The convergence of the top six acceptance technologies' adoption trends, as shown in Figure 2.11, refers to their criticality in the I4.0 configuration and reflects their interactive role.

Figure 2.12: Temporal trends of the common I4.0's technologies (Created by author)

Figure 2.14 shows the contributions per author regarding the number of proposed I4.0 technologies. The disparity of each researcher's view about the enabling technologies stems from their perspective to realize and configure I4.0. Each author proposed their I4.0 technologies to achieve desired characteristics of the system such as integrability, interoperability, autonomous and smartness...etc. Figure 2.12 and 2.13 displays the temporal distribution of surveyed documents to identify enabling technologies. The proposed technologies range from 3 to 15, classified as high consensus, partial consensus, and high diversity.

Figure 2.13: Time distribution (Created by author)

Figure 2- 14: The contributions per authors*.
(Created by author)

* The number next to reference indicates how many technologies have been mentioned in that resource.

For instance, all of Vaidya et al., 2018; Bahrain et al., 2016; BCG and TÜSIAD, 2016; and Alcácer et al., 2019, agreed that core enabling technologies are CPS, IoT, Big Data, AM, Robotic, CC, Simulation, System Integration, and AR, while Rüßmann et al. 2015; Ennis, at el., 2018 added CAD/CAM, and Rüßmann et al. 2015 consider social product development also as enabling technologies. Many authors have uniquely determined I4.0's technologies, such as Santos et al. (2017), Tarassov (2019), and Rajput & Singh (2019). The content analysis of these selected documents (46 papers) is presented in Tables 2.6 & 2.7 which provide a brief explanation of the 40 technologies proposed by all authors. Tables also display the consensus degree of authors concerning I4.0 enabling technologies.

The literature survey of 46 papers that were published between (2012-2019), in an attempt to define Industry 4.0's technologies, provided quantitative evidence for the proposed technologies of Industry 4.0 as summarized in Tables 2.5 & 2.6 and Figures 2.9,2.10,2.11,2.12,2.13 and 2.14. In the same regard, Table 2.5 reflects the differentiation among the authors' perspectives and represents their roadmap components to applied industry 4.0.

Most of these enabling technologies work under clusters or embedded technologies or within major technologies besides many supporting technologies to realize desired features. Similarly, industry 4.0's configuration established smart interaction and integration among heterogeneous entities similar to the Lego-style concerning high reconfigurability, flexibility, and interoperability, while standardization is still under development.

Table 2.5: Analysis of surveyed references with respect to enabling technologies

(Created by author)

<i>authors</i>	<i>year</i>	<i>CPS</i>	<i>IoT</i>	<i>Big Data</i>	<i>AM</i>	<i>Robotic</i>	<i>CC</i>	<i>Simulation</i>	<i>System Integration</i>	<i>AR</i>	<i>Automation</i>	<i>AI</i>	<i>CAD/CAM</i>	<i>FLEXIBLE</i>	<i>[MES/SCADA]</i>	<i>DIGITAL_SERV</i>	<i>Smart factory</i>	<i>ICT</i>	<i>RFID</i>	<i>ERP</i>	<i>Social product development</i>	<i>Semantic Technologies</i>	<i>IoS</i>
<i>Ghobakhloo</i>	2018	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓									✓	✓
<i>Rißmann, et al.</i>	2015	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓									✓	
<i>Lu</i>	2017	✓	✓	✓			✓					✓						✓	✓	✓	✓		
<i>Ermis, et al.</i>	2018	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓										
<i>Saucedo-Martínez, et al</i>	2017	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓										
<i>Kang et al</i>	2016	✓	✓	✓			✓			✓													
<i>Toro et al</i>	2018	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓			✓	✓											✓	
<i>Dalenogare</i>	2018			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓								
<i>Salkin et al</i>	2018	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓													
<i>Vaidya et al</i>	2018	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓													
<i>Bahrin et al</i>	2016	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓													
<i>BCG and TÜSİAD</i>	2016	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓													
<i>Oesterreich & Teuteberg</i>	2016	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓			✓								✓					✓
<i>Alcácer et al</i>	2019	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓													
<i>AKBEN & AVŞAR</i>	2018	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓											✓
<i>wang et al</i>	2016			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓						✓					
<i>Moeuf et al</i>	2018	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓												✓	
<i>Ardito</i>	2018	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓													
<i>Santos et al</i>	2017	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓													
<i>Kamble et al</i>	2018	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓													
<i>Mohamed et al</i>	2019	✓		✓			✓	✓	✓	✓		✓											✓
<i>Sony</i>	2018	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓									✓	✓	✓		✓
<i>Kagermann</i>	2015	✓	✓	✓			✓																✓

<i>authors</i>	<i>year</i>	<i>IoP</i>	<i>IoD</i>	<i>Blockchain</i>	<i>Embedded systems</i>	<i>IIOT</i>	<i>ICME</i>	<i>Modeling</i>	<i>Sensors</i>	<i>Smart energy</i>	<i>HCI</i>	<i>PLC</i>	<i>IoE</i>	<i>Fog.c</i>	<i>M.C</i>	<i>GIS</i>	<i>Drones</i>	<i>Cognitive C.</i>	<i>Advanced. M</i>	<i>Agent-Based Systems</i>	<i>Total</i>	
<i>Ghobakhloo</i>	2018	✓	✓	✓																		15
<i>Rüßmann, et al.</i>	2015																					11
<i>Lu</i>	2017														✓	✓						11
<i>Ennis, at el.</i>	2018																					10
<i>Saucedo-Martínez, et al</i>	2017																					10
<i>Kang et al</i>	2016								✓	✓												6
<i>Toro et al</i>	2018					✓						✓										10
<i>Dalenogare</i>	2018																					9
<i>Salkin et al</i>	2018					✓																9
<i>Vaidya et al</i>	2018																					9
<i>Bahrin et al</i>	2016																					9
<i>BCG and TÜSİAD</i>	2016																					9
<i>Oesterreich & Teuteberg</i>	2016										✓											9
<i>Alcácer et al</i>	2019																					9
<i>AKBEN &AVŞAR</i>	2018																					9
<i>wang et al</i>	2016				✓																	8
<i>Moelf et al</i>	2018							✓														8
<i>Ardito</i>	2018					✓														✓		8
<i>Santos et al</i>	2017				✓				✓												✓	8
<i>Kamble et al</i>	2018																					7
<i>Mohamed et al</i>	2019					✓								✓								7
<i>Sony</i>	2018																					6
<i>Kagermann</i>	2015		✓	✓																		6

<i>authors</i>	<i>year</i>	<i>CPS</i>	<i>IoT</i>	<i>Big Data</i>	<i>AM</i>	<i>Robotic</i>	<i>CC</i>	<i>Simulation</i>	<i>System Integration</i>	<i>AR</i>	<i>Automation</i>	<i>AI</i>	<i>CAD/CAM</i>	<i>FLEXIBLE</i>	<i>[MES/SCADA]</i>	<i>DIGITAL_SERV</i>	<i>Smart factory</i>	<i>ICT</i>	<i>RFID</i>	<i>ERP</i>	<i>Social product development</i>	<i>Semantic Technologies</i>	<i>IoS</i>
<i>Wan et al</i>	2016	✓			✓	✓				✓													
<i>Lom et al</i>	2016	✓	✓																				✓
<i>Tang et al</i>	2019		✓		✓	✓						✓											
<i>Tarassov</i>	2019	✓	✓				✓					✓											
<i>Mabkhot, et al.</i>	2018	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓										✓						
<i>Zhong et al.</i>	2017	✓	✓	✓			✓											✓					
<i>Plessis</i>	2017	✓	✓	✓													✓	✓					✓
<i>Qin, et al.</i>	2016	✓	✓	✓								✓					✓						✓
<i>Sirkin et al</i>	2012				✓	✓											✓						
<i>Cheng et al.</i>	2015	✓	✓	✓			✓											✓					
<i>Lee et al</i>	2015	✓		✓		✓	✓															✓	
<i>Vogel-Heuser & Hess</i>	2016	✓		✓			✓																
<i>Devezas & Sarygulov</i>	2017	✓			✓		✓																
<i>Wollschlaeger et al</i>	2017	✓		✓		✓	✓			✓													
<i>Rajput & Singh</i>	2019	✓	✓				✓				✓												
<i>Hidayatno et al</i>	2018			✓	✓		✓			✓		✓											
<i>Thames & Schaefer</i>	2017		✓		✓		✓												✓				
<i>Erol et al</i>	2016	✓	✓				✓										✓						
<i>Strange et al</i>	2017		✓	✓	✓	✓																	
<i>Roblek et al</i>	2016	✓	✓														✓						✓
<i>Xu et al</i>	2018	✓	✓				✓		✓														
<i>Davies et al</i>	2017	✓	✓																				✓
<i>Hermann</i>	2016	✓	✓														✓						✓

<i>authors</i>	<i>year</i>	<i>IoP</i>	<i>IoD</i>	<i>Blockchain</i>	<i>Embedded systems</i>	<i>IIOT</i>	<i>ICME</i>	<i>Modeling</i>	<i>Sensors</i>	<i>Smart energy</i>	<i>HCI</i>	<i>PLC</i>	<i>IoE</i>	<i>Fog.c</i>	<i>M.C</i>	<i>GIS</i>	<i>Drones</i>	<i>Cognitive C.</i>	<i>Advanced. M</i>	<i>Agent-Based Systems</i>	<i>Total</i>
<i>Wan et al</i>	2016	✓						✓													6
<i>Lom et al</i>	2016	✓											✓	✓							6
<i>Tang et al</i>	2019			✓													✓				6
<i>Tarassov</i>	2019																	✓			6
<i>Mabkhot, et al.</i>	2018																				5
<i>Zhong et al.</i>	2017																				5
<i>Plessis</i>	2017																				5
<i>Qin, et al.</i>	2016																				5
<i>Sirkin et al</i>	2012					✓	✓														5
<i>Cheng et al.</i>	2015																				5
<i>Lee et al</i>	2015																				5
<i>Vogel-Heuser & Hess</i>	2016	✓	✓																		5
<i>Devezas & Sarygulov</i>	2017			✓				✓													5
<i>Wollschlaeger et al</i>	2017																				5
<i>Rajput & Singh</i>	2019																	✓			5
<i>Hidayatno et al</i>	2018																				5
<i>Thames & Schaefer</i>	2017					✓															5
<i>Erol et al</i>	2016					✓															5
<i>Strange et al</i>	2017																				4
<i>Roblek et al</i>	2016																				4
<i>Xu et al</i>	2018																				4
<i>Davies et al</i>	2017																				3
<i>Hermann</i>	2016																				3

Table 2.6: State-of-the-art I4.0 technologies

Key Technology	Description	Authors' consensus degree
<p>Cyber-physical System</p>	<p>CPS is an integrational environment for physical and virtual entities that ensure the real representation of physical objects in cyberspace and deploy high interconnectivity, interoperability, and knowledgeability level.</p>	<p>Rüßmann, et al., 2015; Ennis, at el.2018; Saucedo-Martínez, et al,2017; Mabkhot, et al., 2018; Zhong et al., 2017; Sony,2018; Ghobakhloo,2018; Salkin et al,2018; Plessis , 2017; Vaidya et al,2018; Roblek et al,2016; Qin, et al., 2016; Bahrin et al,2016; Davies et al,2017; BCG and TÜSIAD,2016; Kagermann, 2015; Kamble et al,2018; Kang et al ,2016; Oesterreich & Teuteberg,2016; Hermann,2016;Cheng et al.,2016; Lee et al ,2015; Vogel-Heuser & Hess,2016; Wan et al,2016; Devezas & Leitão,2017; Lu,2017; Wollschlaeger et al,2017; Moeuf et al,2018; Toro et al, 2018;Xu et al,2018; Alcácer et al,2019; Lom et al, 2016; Tarassov,2019; Ardito, 2018; Mohamed et al,2019;Rajput & Singh, 2019; Santos et al, 2017;AKBEN &AVŞAR, 2018;Erol et al,2016.</p>
<p>Internet Of Thing</p>	<p>IoT is all enabling technologies (software, hardware) to facilitate the communicability of physical objects and their interactivities to Cyberspace.</p>	<p>Rüßmann, et al.,2015;Ennis, at el.,2018;Strange et al,2017;Saucedo-Martínez, et al,2018;Mabkhot, et al.,2018;Zhong et al.,2017;Sony,2018;Ghobakhloo, 2018 ; Plessis,2017;Vaidya et al,2018; Roblek et al,2016; Qin, et al,2016;Bahrin et al, 2016 ;Davies et al,2017;BCG and TÜSIAD,2016;Kagermann,2015;Kamble et al, 2018 ;Kang et al , 2016;Oesterreich & Teuteberg,2016;Hermann,2016;Cheng et al., 2016 ;Lu,2017;Toro et al,2018;Xu et al,2018;Alcácer et al,2019;Lom et al, 2016 ;Tang et al, 2019;Tarassov,2019;Rajput & Singh, 2019;Santos et al ,2017;Thames & Schaefer, 2017;AKBEN &AVŞAR,2018;Erol et al,2016;</p>
<p>Big Data</p>	<p>In simple words, finding the valuable and realistic meaning hidden behind extracted raw data to reconfigure systems to smart systems.</p>	<p>Rüßmann, et al.,2015;Ennis, at el.,2018;Dalenogare et al,2018;Strange et al,2017; Saucedo-Martínez et al,2018; Mabkhot, et al,2018;Zhong et al.,2017; Ghobakhloo ,2018;wang et al,2016;Salkin et al,2018; Plessis,2017;Vaidya et al,2018; Qin, et al.,2016;Bahrin et al,2016;BCG and TÜSIAD, 2016;Kagermann,2015;Kamble et al,2018;Kang et al, 2016;Oesterreich & Teuteberg,2016; Cheng et al.,2016;Lee et al,2015;Vogel-Heuser and Hess, 2016; Lu,2017 ;Wollschlaeger et al,2017; Moeuf et al,2018;Toro et al, 2018;Alcácer et al,2019; Ardito,2018; Mohamed et al,2019; Hidayatno et al ,2018; AKBEN &AVŞAR,2018;</p>
<p>Additive Manufacturing</p>	<p>Using depositing layers technologies to gradually embody the product's 3D design through 3d printers.</p>	<p>Rüßmann, et al.,2015;Ennis, at el.,2018;Dalenogare et al,2018;Strange et al,2017; Saucedo-Martínez, et al,2018; Ghobakhloo, 2018;wang et al,2016;Salkin et al,2018;Vaidya et al,2018;Bahrin et al,2016;Sirkin et al,2012;BCG and TÜSIAD, 2016;Kamble et al,2018;Oesterreich & Teuteberg,2016;Wan et al,2016;Devezas & Leitão, 2017; Moeuf et al,2018;Alcácer et</p>

		al,2019;Tang et al,2019;Ardito, 2018;Santos et al ,2017;Hidayatno et al, 2018;Thames & Schaefer,2017;AKBEN &AVŞAR,2018.
Robots	Is a smart, interactive, reconfigurable, and adaptable technology to deal with product's case individually within batch size one in collaborative workspace.	Rüßmann, et al., 2015; Ennis, at el.,2018; Strange et al,2017; Ghobakhloo,2018;wang et al,2016; Salkin et al,2018;Vaidya et al,2018;Bahrin et al,2016;Sirkin et al,2012; BCG and TÜSİAD,2016;Kamble et al,2018;Lee et al,2015;Wan et al, 2016; Wollschlaeger et al,2017;Moeuf et al,2018;Toro et al,2018;Alcácer et al,2019;Tang et al,2019; Tarassov, 2019; Santos et al ,2017;AKBEN &AVŞAR,2018.
Cloud Computing	Is enabling the technology of sharing and remotely-usage of distributed resources.	Rüßmann, et al., 2015;Ennis, at el.,2018;Dalenogare et al,2018; Saucedo-Martínez, et al,2017; Mabkhot, et al.,2018;Zhong et al, 2017; Sony, 2018;Ghobakhloo,2018;wang et al,2016;Salkin et al,2018;Vaidya et al,2018; Bahrin et al,2016;BCG and TÜSİAD ,2016;Kagermann,2015;Kamble et al,2018;Kang et al,2016;Oesterreich & Teuteberg ,2016;Cheng et al,2015; Lee et al,2015;Vogel-Heuser and Hess,2016;Devezas & Leitão,2017;Lu, 2017;Wollschlaeger et al,2017; Moeuf et al,2018;Toro et al,2018;Xu et al,2018;Alcácer et al,2019;Tarassov,2019;Ardito,2018;Mohamed et al,2019;Rajput & Singh,2019;Santos et al,2017;Hidayatno et al, 2018;Thames & Schaefer, 2017; AKBEN &AVŞAR, 2018;Erol et al, 2016;
Simulation	Using the real-time 3D representation of the whole ecosystems including components, processes, products, entities and humans to mirror the real world in a virtual model, where synthesized models simulate properties of the considered physical model, to reflect system's performance in macro and micro level.	Rüßmann, et al.,2015;Ennis, at el.,2018;Dalenogare et al,2018; Saucedo-Martínez, et al,2017; Ghobakhloo,2018;wang et al,2016;Salkin et al, 2018;Vaidya et al,2018;Bahrin et al, 2016;BCG and TÜSİAD , 2016;Kamble et al, 2018;Alcácer et al,2019;Ardito,2018.
System Integration	Is establishing an integrative framework to create a harmonic and cooperative environment of heterogeneous entities including technologies, human and systems.	Rüßmann, et al.,2015; Ennis, at el.,2018; Dalenogare et al, 2018; Saucedo-Martínez, et al,2017; Salkin et al, 2018; Vaidya et al,2018; Bahrin et al,2016; BCG and TÜSİAD ,2016; Xu et al,2018;Alcácer et al,2019.
Augmented Reality	Is 3D representation technologies of digital or computerized graphics which reflects the real environment provides user more insight and interaction with designs and production processes including designing, training, fault diagnostic, monitoring, planning, maintenance tasks etc.	Rüßmann, et al.2015;Ennis, at el.,2018; Saucedo-Martínez, et al,2017; Ghobakhloo, 2018; Salkin et al,2018; Vaidya et al,2018; Bahrin et al,2016; BCG and TÜSİAD, 2016; Oesterreich & Teuteberg, 2016; Wan et al,2016; Wollschlaeger et al,2017; Moeuf et al,2018; Toro et al,2018; Alcácer et al,2019;Ardito,2018;Hidayatno et al,2018;AKBEN &AVŞAR,2018.
Automation	Is a set of technologies to remove human interventions or a direct control from the machine, a process, or a system to be work autonomously and automatically.	Dalenogare,2018;Saucedo-Martínez, et al,2017;Ghobakhloo,2018;Toro et al,2018;Rajput & Singh,2019.
Artificial intelligence	A set of technologies to mimic human's intelligence by exploiting computers abilities to extract, interpret, analyses, learn, and make a decision, which is an essential pillar for smartness ecosystem. Using AI technologies such as machine	Wang et al,2016; Qin, et al.,2016;Lu ,2017;Tang et l,2019; Tarassov,2019;Mohamed et al, 2019; Hidayatno et al,2018; AKBEN &AVŞAR,2018.

	learning and deep learning algorithms to configure smart production system are a core of I4.0.	
CAD/CAM	One of the enabling technologies for digitalizing design-to-manufacturing process, so it still adopted in Industry 4.0, by a digital representation of the desired design to produce prototypes and to facilitate the production process.	Rüßmann, et al.,2015; Ennis, at el.,2018; Dalenogare et al, 2018; Saucedo-Martínez, et al,2017; Ghobakhloo, 2018.
“FLEXIBLE” Flexible manufacturing lines	Combining the digital automation with embedded sensor networks to optimize reconfigurability of manufacturing systems.	Dalenogare et al,2018
[MES/SCADA] Manufacturing Execution Systems (MES) and Supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA)	Enabling a real time data acquisition through SCADA in MES context	Dalenogare et al,2018
Smart factory	Is combined system that assists people and machines to interact and execute their tasks.	Mabkhot, et al.,2018; Plessis,2017; Roblek et al,2016; Qin, et al.,2016;Sirkin et al,2012; Hermann,2016; Erol et al,2016.
ICT	A group of technologies that provide access to information and exchanging it through telecommunications.	Zhong et al. ,2017; wang et al,2016; Oesterreich & Teuteberg,2016; Cheng et al.,2015; Lu,2017.
RFID	Is identification technologies accompanying of all entities, the entities' detailed information is been written to the RFID card, which is readable through a working environment to collect real time data	Sony,2018;Lu,2017;Thames & Schaefer,2017.
ERP	Is a set of various informational subsystems within the organization to manage and integrate all business processes and resources.	Sony,2018;Lu,2017.
Social product development	Using a set of technologies to enable an interactive development of products (interactive design), the crowdsourcing, mass collaboration, open innovation, and cloud-based design and manufacturing considered as core technologies of Social Product Development.	Rüßmann, et al.,2015;Sony,2018;Lu,2017.
Semantic Technologies	A set of protocols, unified languages, and common standards to establish connected and interoperated environments, and to formulate communication manner and interaction among heterogeneous entities.	Ghobakhloo,2018; Lee et al ,2015; Moeuf et al,2018; Toro et al,2018.
IoS	IOS considered as an operating environment of Product-as-a-Service (PaaS) business model, the systematic utilize of the IOS is a core base in value creation network.	Ghobakhloo,2018; Plessis,2017; Roblek et al,2016; Davies et al ,2017; Kagermann, 2015; Oesterreich & Teuteberg,2016. Lom et al,2016; Mohamed et al,2019;Akben &Avşar,2018.
IoP (Internet Of People)	Is a socio-technical system which considers the interaction and interrelationship between humans and their personal devices as active elements of the internet	Ghobakhloo,2018; Vogel-euser and Hess, 2016; Wan et al,2016. Lom et al,2016.
IoD (Internet Of DATA)	Data arrangement technologies to organize the interaction of data entities by using embed virtual tags, which record and trace data's activities since they are created, to facilitate data interaction and integration for more useful information.	Ghobakhloo,2018; Kagermann,2015; Vogel-Heuser and Hess,2016.
Blockchain	An innovative digital technology enables secure, fast, transparent, immutable transaction processes as well as redefines trust in a fully autonomous and automated manner that leads to dramatic changes in businesses networks.	Ghobakhloo,2018; Devezas & Leitão,2017; Tang et al,2019.

Embedded systems	is semi-independent system consist a set of technologies (hardware and software) to performs specific functions for processing, controlling and monitoring within a larger mechanical or electrical system.	wang et al,2016; Santos et al ,2017.
IIOT(Industrial Internet Of Thing)	The extended utilization of IoT in the industry context is mostly called IIoT.	Salkin et al,2018; Sirkin et al,2012; Toro et al,2018; Ardito, 2018; Mohamed et al,2019; Thames & Schaefer,2017;Erol et al,2016.
ICME(Integrated Computational Materials Engineering)	Creating computer models of products and simulating their properties before they are fabricated	Sirkin et al, 2012.
Modeling	Is a digital representation of processes, functions, objects and components in real-world.	Wan et al,2016; Devezas & Leitão, 2017; Moeuf et al 2018
Sensors	Data gathering technologies which embedded in physical entities to detect or measure certain indicators in real time,	Kang et al,2016;Santos et al,2017.
Smart energy	Using smart technologies to optimize consumption of energy	Kang et al,2016.
Human-Computer-Interaction	Is a multidisciplinary field to design interaction point between humans (the users) and devices.	Oesterreich & Teuteberg,2016.
Product lifecycle management	Is a kit of the processes to manage product lifecycle. This information presents a better understanding of the product situation.	Toro et al,2018.
Internet of Energy(IoE)	“is integrated dynamic network infrastructure based on standard and interoperable communication protocols that interconnect the energy network with the Internet, which includes a variety of operational and energy measures including smart meters, smart appliances, renewable energy resources, and energy efficiency resources. Electronic power conditioning and control of the production and distribution of electricity are important aspects of the smart grid.”	Lom et al,2016.
FOG computing	“Is architecture and a distributed computing infrastructure that uses one or a collaborative multitude of enduser clients or edge devices to accomplish a substantial amount of storage.”	Lom et al,2016; Mohamed et al,2019
Mobile computing	“Is an enabling technology that allows exchanging of data, voice and video via a computer or any other wireless enabled device without having to be connected to a fixed physical link”.	Lu,2017.
Geographic Information Science	Using Geographic Information Science (GIS) visualized methods to improve the performance of smart manufacturing processes.	Lu,2017.
Drones	using drones in carrying sensors to record data and to facilitate logistic processes,	Tang et al,2019.
cognitive computing	Is a set of enabling technologies which based on AI philosophy and their scientific principles and signal processing.	Tarassov,2019;Rajput & Singh,2019.
Advanced manufacturing	Using a contemporary manufacturing technologies to optimize enterprises' performance and products.	Ardito,2018.
Agent-Based Systems	“Is a form of distributed artificial intelligence, this computational entities capable of perceiving their environments and taking action regarding them”. The agent technology is an appropriate tool to deal with complexity and planning of manufacturing of Industry 4.0.	Santos et al,2017.

2.1.2.2.2 Core components of industry 4.0

Lu 2017 stressed that a long and broad list of enabling technologies is used to configure industry 4.0 systems due to the collective nature of I4.0 is often used as an umbrella term for a set of heterogeneous technologies (Lu, 2017). To reply to the research questions "What are well-known components of industry 4.0?" and "What is the individual effect of industry 4.0 components," which are early defined. The author makes use of a literature-based analysis to redefine 4.0's enabling technologies. In the same regard, the author agrees with the majority in determining the core technologies, with a high possibility of improving the technological composition of 4.0 using supporting techniques.

1. Cyber-physical systems

The first appearance of the CPS term in 2006 at NFS workshop held in Texas-USA is as "a system composed of collaborative entities, equipped with calculation capabilities and actors of an intensive connection with the surrounding physical world and phenomena, using and providing all together services of treatment and communication of data available on the network." Thus, CPS is considered a fundamental interconnecting element to establish a connected environment for physical entities (Ahmadi, et al., 2018). In this regard, the CPS enables embracing destructive applications and innovative business models in enterprises (Reischauer, 2018). The core concerns of CPS are the integration of computing with the physical world and creating an integrated harmonic system of physical systems and cyber systems. Thus, CPS is a system of systems, and the new interactions among all subsystems (control, communication, and computation) of CPS require integrable-design to ensure the realization of the automated, autonomous processes (Lin, et al., 2018; Toro, et al., 2015).

The CPS refers to an embedded technical system in which devices, machines, buildings, infrastructures, and production facilities are equipped (Reischauer, 2018; Fuchs, 2018), to establish global networks for business, based on enabling autonomous exchanged data, triggering actions, and controlling each other independently (Shafiq, et al., 2015). These networks include chips and sensors embedded into products to connect with the network (Fuchs, 2018; Lee, 2015). In turn, CPS is in charge of capturing, recording, and interpreting data generated and gathered by sensors' networks and the manual inputs for digital twins. Accordingly, the gathered data are processed by a set of smart

algorithms and artificial intelligence technologies to determine their behavior and interaction for environmental signals and indicators (Reischauer, 2018; Shafiq, et al., 2015; Lee, 2015). In this regard, the produced information is calculated and synchronized concerning health, performance, and risk-indicators (conditions, current state) of physical components and machines in real-time (Lee, 2015). Thus, the virtual representations allow manipulating, managing, monitoring, controlling, and actuating all physical entities (manufacturing facilities, production cells, production lines, and individual machines) in Cyberspace (Sharpe, et al., 2019). CPS allows all entities to become searchable, explorable, and analyzable in the network with high-accessibility from anywhere (Shafiq, et al., 2015). CPS enables identifying all smart entities (recognizability), continuously determining the entities' location and their own history, providing information about the current state, and proposes alternative ways to attain the desired state. The produced pieces and products carry information about the required processes to complete it (how it should be processed). Therefore, all entities that control and configure themselves independently according to current situation requirements negotiate to coordinate available, spare capacity of entities and trigger actions. CPS is considered the backbone of horizontal, vertical, and end-to-end engineering integrations (Kagermann, 2015; Kagermann, et al., 2013). Ultimately, the self-organizing characteristic of CPS is enabled based on communicability with local and global environment entities, including humans. Self-regulating systems enable the disappearing of boundaries among ICT, medicine, nanotechnologies, biotechnologies (Reischauer, 2018), and other advanced technologies, which allow the emergence of new interactive ecosystems smart-life style. Furthermore, many innovative and creative technologies characterized by smart, cognition, and awareness characters result in a changed economic and social life.

CPS is an engineered system to promote physical entities' abilities to enable features like stability, high performance, robustness, efficiency, and reliability via tight integration of ICT and control technologies and is considered the novel generation of operating systems (Shafiq, et al., 2015). CPS is a complementary concept for industry 4.0 philosophy (Lee, 2015; Mabkhot, et al., 2018; Saucedo-Martínez, et al., 2018; Zhong, et al., 2017). The integration of smart machines, warehouse systems, and production facilities generates a Cyber Physical production System (CPPS) that incorporates inbound and outbound of all activities and functions besides allowing end-

end entities-coordination in all aspects (Kagermann, 2015; Lee, 2015). Therefore, CPPS is considered the next generation of manufacturing systems and industrial versions of CPS, with the same philosophy and architecture but in different roles. CPS relates to sensors/actuators with localized knowledge, but CPPS is associated with the process level (Shafiq, et al., 2015; Lin, et al., 2018).

The digital real-time representation system (virtually representation) of physical entities in cyberspace allows tight monitoring, controlling, and interacting with their environments based on real-time physical-entities data (Lee, 2015; Sharpe, et al., 2019). CPS technologies exist in machines, objects, products to ensure proper harmony and interaction with environments, but CPPS is assigned to coordinate environment's entities like manufacturing center, manufacturing cells, and factory (Shafiq, et al., 2015). Therefore, CPS is considered a destructive system that imposes fundamental changes and modifies human, machines, and systems interactions, based on exchanging information and analyzing it.

CPS integrates physical and virtual entities that ensure real representation of physical objects in Cyberspace, deploying high interconnectivity, interoperability, and knowledgeability.

2.Cloud Computing

Cloud computing content is continually developed due to developments in related technologies and ingredients such as hardware, distributed computing, virtualization technology, service delivery, etc.

From the strategic viewpoint, Cloud Computing is one of the outsourcing strategies via the purchased acquisition of the shareable infrastructures, software, knowledge, applications, systems, and intelligence kits considered high customization services or on-demand services. The availability of CC services decreases the required investment in IT assets, which are the sources of competitive advantage and organizational innovation (Alcácer, et al., 2019). Cloud computing applications provide a cloud of software, and a cloud of the web-based dashboards and collaboration tools for management of manufacturing enterprises, facilitating resource integration and establishing flexible and collaborative infrastructures (Plessis, 2017). Cloud design allows users to upload, share, and use resources (data, information, knowledge, software, and smartness tools) by clients (Xu, et al., 2018). In this context, cloud

computing technologies enable secure and convenient storage of the exponentially rising volume of data produced by connected and smart systems, objects, and subjects (Plessis, 2017; Kagermann, 2015). Also, Cloud computing provides a base for providing functional-services (service-orientation) in production systems. The cloud warehouse configures new service infrastructures that serve all production system entities (Kagermann, 2015). Hence, Manufacturing-as-a-Service (MaaS) enables using a network of resources (Xu, et al., 2018). In the same regard, embracing the service-oriented strategy, where functions are provided as services, allows users to request desired services at any level; the service-oriented approach is the core of Cloud Manufacturing (Alcácer, et al., 2019). Cloud computing, mobile computing, and big data are considered fundamental pillars for a new industry generation. Cloud computing and mobile computing are services-provider in the smart factory, which can be accessed globally via the internet. Provided services are integrated and utilized easily (Roblek, et al., 2016; Alcácer, et al., 2019).

For instance, an American motor vehicle-manufacturing company uses a co-created strategy to design and minimize an open-source motor vehicle designs cost based on cloud computing technology by a group of designers, engineers, fabricators, and enthusiasts in its virtual community (Xu, et al., 2018).

Servitization of classical functions based on cloud computing provides an opportunity to reduce cost, continuously update and simplify and innovate their business model, besides technological benefits.

3. Big Data

The data-driven technologies enable enterprises to extract value economically and smartly. Big data technology interferes with most of today's technologies and devices. Therefore, tremendous and miscellaneous data is produced by interconnected heterogeneous objects. This structured, semi-structured, and unstructured data needs to be discovered, captured, managed, and analyzed. This, in turn, allows contemporary manufacturing enterprises to utilize gathered information to reshape and enhance value chain and decision making (Ghobakhloo, 2018; Alcácer, et al., 2019), and generating valuable data provides profit opportunities for manufacturing enterprises in the knowledge era (Alcácer, et al., 2019).

Multi-source data such as networked sensors, search engines, and social media sites provide analyzable raw data where big-data techniques are utilized (Strange, et al., 2017). The accumulated knowledge is used to optimize asset efficiency, enhance performance, improve product customization, boost predictive maintenance programs, eliminate asset breakdowns, enhance supply chain effectiveness, simplify production processes (Strange, et al., 2017; Ghobakhloo, 2018), realize the fault-free process, provide a good solving-base of problems, obtain effective real-time decision-making, enhance cost-efficient (Alcácer, et al., 2019; Vaidya, et al., 2018), and enhance monitoring of emerging trends and opportunities (Strange, et al., 2017). Indeed, possession of BD's technologies increases smartness abilities, logical proactive behaviors, data-driven behaviors, high-transparency, realistic planning, reliability, controllability, and rationality of decisions.

Recent improvements in ICT, especially in computing power and a lower cost of hardware, including data warehouses and servers, enable rapid growth in Big Data Management (BDM) (Strange, et al., 2017). Besides, the virtual representation of physical entities allows making a realistic analysis (information processing) in innovative forms at effective-cost and without passive impacts in real production (high seamlessness, fewer downtimes, reduce lead-time) (Pessoa, et al., 2018; Alcácer, et al., 2019). They help manufacturing enterprises establish a comprehensive, smart, and real-time vision based on instant-big data analysis to sustain and enhance competitiveness and decision-making (Ghobakhloo, 2018).

In Industry 4.0 context, the Big Data extensions and related technologies contribute to establish and add many smart applications, characteristics, and abilities, such as self-organization, self-awareness, self-maintenance, business intelligence, self-control, self-optimization, self-learning, and so on, for all virtual and physical entities and their consisting ecosystems.

4. Internet of Things (IoT)

The rapid development and increasing impact of this novel technological era enable the convergence of the physical and virtual world that encourages the high interconnectivity of economic and social activities, which are allowed by technology platforms such as the internet, mobility, and sensors systems (Roblek, et al., 2016; Herrmann, 2018). The first appearance of IoT was in 1999 by Kevin Ashton, described as “a highly and widely connected world where connectable-physical entities are hosted

and enabled constant connectivity among entities.” Consequently, the unique identifiable interoperable entities are able to exchange valuable information to optimize their decisions, processes, and performance, especially in production sectors (Fatorachian, et al., 2018; Xu, et al., 2018). Unique identifiers and tags equip all physical entities, including products, to allow tracing in real-time and exchange required information about their provenance, utilize, and destination. Therefore, self-coordination and auto-synchronization are allowed by IoT technologies (Strange, et al., 2017; Xu, et al., 2018). Thus, remote management of distributed systems and entities is enabled by the IoT (Fatorachian, et al., 2018).

IoT refers to structured networks that include radio-frequency identification (RFID), sensors, software, connectivity enabling kits, and physical objects that exchange, store, process, and analyze information and manage interaction with each other coordinate with intelligent entities. (Roblek, et al., 2016; Kang, et al., 2016). Hence, the IoT’s networks establish a proper operating environment for monitoring activities, simultaneous control, and coordinating for the whole manufacturing processes concerning production quality and maintenance (Roblek, et al., 2016; Kagermann, 2015). The digitization of current proven concepts imposes a quantum leap in performance, productivity, flexibility, high quality, and connected manufacturing areas via the utilization of IoT and CPS (Kagermann, 2015). Thus, the IoT is a novel industrial ecosystem that enhances productivity, efficiency, and reliability of manufacturing by combining intelligent and autonomous machines, data analysis, and coherent collaboration of machine-human (Kamble , et al., 2018). Various and extensive definitions of IoT stems from multidisciplinary scholars and their various interests. Furthermore, the wide-use of IoT serves to formulate a broad concept of IoT. Generally, the communicability of physical objects and their interactivity are based on IoT technology. (Ghobakhloo, 2018).

- The Industrial Internet of Thing (IIoT)

The extended utilization of IoT in the industry context is mostly called IIoT. Its utilization enables the digital representation of objects, processes, products, and all manufacturing infrastructure under established communication networks on IoT (Ghobakhloo, 2018).

IIOT enables the digitized connection within a completed and integrated network of sensors, middleware, embedded systems, healthcare equipment, transportation

equipment, cloud computing and repository systems. Consequently, the systems' characteristics are enhanced, such as optimizing the visibility, observation, and insight for entire operations and assets of manufacturing enterprises at the operational level (Jeschke, et al., 2017), and full digitalization, high-connectivity, autonomous and intelligent action at the factory level. Besides that, the organizational structure and performance are optimized too (Arnold, et al., 2016). Thus, efficiency and effectiveness are being realized in predictive maintenance, product quality, greening the manufacturing, and design optimization by IIOT utilization (Ghobakhloo, 2018). In the same regard, realizing a perfect understanding of customers, offering proactive supports and real-time feedback are enabled by CRM under IoT context; thereby, customer support systems are activated, such as innovative customer service, on-demand pricing, in-store experiences, and individually marketing (Roblek, et al., 2016).

The IIoT is established on smart machines' high-superiority in capturing data and communicating in an accurate and ongoing manner (Ghobakhloo, 2018; Fatorachian, et al., 2018; Arnold, et al., 2016). The interactive environment formed by IoT enables networking the smart devices with decisions making (strategically and operationally), including manufacturing execution systems (MESs), energy management systems (EMSs), and Enterprises Resources Planning system (Roblek, et al., 2016), which ultimately create a novel manufacturing model (Arnold, et al., 2016).

- Internet of service

IoS is considered an operating environment of the Product-as-a-Service (PaaS) business model; the IOS's systematic utilization is a core base in the value creation network. The open and direct link with customers has been possible and available due to IoS technologies which enable manufacturing enterprises to establish communication channels with clients and optimize competitive advantages by providing supplementary services and innovative value creation networks (Ghobakhloo, 2018).

- Internet of People (IoP)

Internet of People (IoP) is a socio-technical system that considers the interaction and interrelationship between humans and their personal devices as active elements of the internet (Ghobakhloo, 2018). The social connectivity of smart devices and the People as a Service (PaaS) concept and resulted interactions represent the core of IOP, which coordinates the interaction with other devices (social communication, for example) by

linking with IoT. The consequences of social interaction are huge data about the users' tendency, needs, intentions, sentiment, and sociological profile, which extrapolates from people's social media posts and internet activities (Ghobakhloo, 2018).

Gathering, computing, and simulating data that stem from the IOP environment enables manufacturing enterprises to forecast consumption and purchase patterns, purchase motivation, and real-time reaction and actionable results (Ghobakhloo, 2018).

- Internet of Data

IoD is an IoT extension related to data in digital environments and data sources. Data-transformation methods, storing, managing, and processing in the IoT environment where countless digital entities provide a tremendous amount of data. Virtual tags represent data activities and data vitalization results from a tagging technic that enables enterprises to utilize gathered data thanks to big data analytics (Ghobakhloo, 2018; Anderl, et al., 2016).

5. Additive-manufacturing

The core idea of Additive manufacturing is based on depositing layers technologies to embody the product's 3D design gradually. The 3D design is prepared by computer-aided design (CAD) software. Then, the design is embodying by using a 3D printer that utilizes materials in liquid or particle form such as plastic, synthetic resin, ceramics, glass, stainless steel, etc. The produced objects' attributes rely on materials features or bonding methods (Strange, et al., 2017; Tang, et al., 2019; Kang, et al., 2016). The embracing of AM assists manufacturing enterprises to enhance their performance, especially in:

- Providing a faster, cheaper, and better development of prototypes and high personalized products to meet customer's needs.
- Enhancing the created value by simplified production of complex products, increased parts, and enhanced part flexibility.
- Increase production efficiency and production flexibility by optimizing lead-times, reducing logistical cost, fostering material efficiency, decreasing produced waste, and enhancing resource efficiency.
- Providing a competing opportunity through the product's variety and using CAD software output standardization enables remotely producing by compatible 3-D

printers, enhancing the cost. (Tang, et al., 2019; Strange, et al., 2017; Huang, et al., 2013).

Embracing AM assists manufacturing enterprises to provide highly customized products in small batches. On-demand production enables reducing cost and obtaining time efficiencies (Plessis, 2017). Besides, AM supports environmental friendly product design, eliminating waste and saving energy (Huang, et al., 2013). Furthermore, AM provides opportunities to enhance the competitive edge (Tang, et al., 2019), and to reduce transport distances and stock on hand (Bahrin et al, 2016).

AM is considered as an innovation source because of its ability to produce complex geometry parts which are difficult to obtain using traditional processes (Huang, et al., 2013), to reduce logistical costs and lead-times (Tang, et al., 2019), and ultimately achieving high- performance and more valuable products (Plessis, 2017).

General Electric is considered as an entrepreneur in additive-manufacturing utilization, represented by building fuel nozzles for LEAP-turbofan engines via 3D-printer for single-aisle aircraft, using layer-building technology by the computer-guided laser of material powder, the new generation of nozzles is lighter than the classic one by 25% and five-time longer-life (durable) from the manufactured version of nozzles (Sirkin, et al., 2015).

6. Autonomous Robots

The first appearance of industrial robots was in 1960 (Sirkin, et al., 2015). The dynamic development and utilization of high-tech robotics (Akaev, et al., 2017) create an interactive and collaborative workspace with a human because of the increased abilities, technological performance, and decreased costs (software & Hardware) (Strange, et al., 2017; Bayram, et al., 2018), to realize high quality, precision in production processes (Rajput, et al., 2019) to mitigate waste ratio (Tamas, et al., 2019), and to tackle complex assignments in less-structured environments (Rüßmann, et al., 2015; Strange, et al., 2017) and performing the dangerous tasks for humans (Bayram, et al., 2018).

In difficult, complex, dirty, hazardous, and dull activities (Alcácer, et al., 2019), replacing the humans' effort with industrial robots are crucial to ensure safety and quality besides their impact on work's environment (the number of employees, nature of work, performance, required capabilities) (Szalavetz, 2019). The robots are currently

used to operate autonomously, precisely, flexibly, reliably, versatility, and cooperatively with smart entities and humans (Vaidya, et al., 2018; Salkin, et al., 2018). Consequently, robots are considered a valuable economical alternative to human's efforts which became more intelligent, interconnected, and available for most manufacturing enterprises (Strange, et al., 2017) to ramp up performance and efficiency (Halevi, 2017). To enable the interactions of physical entities with the environment, the equipped computer, the network of sensors, and learning ability are required to ensure robots' cooperation (Tarassov, 2018; Rajput, et al., 2019) and autonomous decisions making to perform their tasks. Therefore, robots are one of AI applications (Alcácer, et al., 2019). The networked robots interact with their environment based on their integration with ambient intelligence and web service technologies. Interactive and smart robots are an essential pillar of I4.0. I4.0 provides a proper smart robotic environment to integrate cooperative robots (Zhang, et al., 2019).

7. Augmented Reality (AR)

AR is a digital 3D representation by reconfiguring digital information to represent the real-world, enabling users to sight, interact, and manifest in a virtual environment; AR mirrors the real world with additional information and options. Thus, AR is a supplement to reality and not a substitute for it (Liberato, et al., 2018; Alcácer, et al., 2019).

AR technologies tended to increase human performances (Vaidya, et al., 2018), improve decision making and optimize work procedures (Alcácer, et al., 2019), and enhance a human's perception of the environment (Esengün, et al., 2018) by providing accurate real-time information. The attached information could be texts, symbols, images, three-dimensional animations, audio or video..etc (Alcácer, et al., 2019; Esengün, et al., 2018; Vaidya, et al., 2018). AR is characterized by the ability to show the real and virtual world, enabling entities' interaction in both worlds, and aligning and twinning virtual objects with real objects (Alcácer, et al., 2019; Esengün, et al., 2018).

8. Simulation

The simulation model is a proper solution to configure the object's digital prototype to reflect real and designed features, abilities, and performance (Biles, et al., 2006). Simulation technologies are used to test alternatives and feasibility of projects or ideas, also utilized real-time data to build a network simulation, provide smart virtual

assistance through human thought processes simulation (Ennis, et al., 2018; Plessis, 2017), and simulate the behavior of the system or its equipment (Mabkhot, et al., 2018). Besides, overcoming obstacles such as reducing trial and error costs, identifying efficient labour distribution, recognizing a bottleneck point, isolate other costly design errors, and evaluating various operating conditions (Biles, et al., 2006; Plessis, 2017).

Recently, the rapid development of computing abilities enables the enhancement of accuracy and validity of the simulations' results and enhances the performance of simulation applications. The spread of smart things and computerized life contribute to real-time data-stream which reflect the real environment. Thus, "the 3D representations are no longer just simulations, but live stream representations of the company" (Plessis, 2017), thus it enables experimenting the effectiveness of the alteration without them being implemented (Saucedo-Martínez, et al., 2018).

9. Systems integration

In the I4.0 context, the cooperative perform are required from all entities within value creation network, including engineering, production, marketing, suppliers, and supply chain operations, customers, and all connected entities (Alcácer, et al., 2019) to enable self-decision making and possess integrated functions (Salkin, et al., 2018). The high performance and harmony of miscellaneous-heterogeneous technologies, systems, and humans require a cooperating system or scenarios to seamless real-time data exchanging in a meaningful and understandable manner. The embracing of I4.0 leads the companies, departments, functions, and capabilities to be more cohesive by real-time exchangeability of data a cross-company, partners' networks, and universal networks (Rüßmann, et al., 2015). Most authors are agreed that the entities (software & hardware) integrate into three main directions, horizontal, vertical, and end-to-end engineering integration.

- Horizontal integration

The required collaboration by I4.0 imposes high integrated data exchangeability among value creation network entities (business partners, departments, functions, business models). The horizontal integration's impacts represent many alterations and adaptations throughout its entire value creation network, including sourcing, design, manufacture, and delivery effort. An interconnected ecosystem is necessary to establish an interactive system used in industrial standards and protocols (Manogaran, et al., 2017; Plessis, 2017; Türkes, et al., 2019; Sony, 2018; Alcácer, et al., 2019). Today, the

independent platform is considered as the suitable technology for exchanging data or information among distributed partners (Alcácer, et al., 2019; Türkes, et al., 2019; Rüßmann, et al., 2015).

- Vertical Integration

Each smart enterprise consists of entities, operations, systems, functions, departments, logistics networks, services, products, and embedded systems interacting in a smart, connected and integrated manner. The smoothly exchanging of data, information, and knowledge among all hierarchical levels requires a smart-interconnecting of digital business units (CPS, IoT) to attain a flexible and reconfigurable production system and create a self-organized system, and provide customized products. Many systems play a fundamental role in this integration, such as ERP, CAPP, MES, and Business intelligence ..etc. (Alcácer, et al., 2019; Manogaran, et al., 2017; Rüßmann, et al., 2015; Türkes, et al., 2019).

- End –to-end integration

End-to-end engineering is configured by the interaction of vertical and horizontal integrations. This digital integration creates links among all processes in the whole value-chain like design, customer requirements, planning, production engineering, manufacturing activities, maintenance, invention, services, preservation, disposal, and recycling. The configured digital model for integrating these entities enables exchanging real-time data, enhancing data's accessibility of entities, optimizing control abilities, and bridging gaps between designing and manufacturing and the customer (Alcácer, et al., 2019; Manogaran, et al., 2017; Salkin, et al., 2018; Dalenogare, et al., 2018; Sader, et al., 2017).

The increased use of embedded sensors allows to emerge embedded and connected systems, a fundamental pillar of industry 4.0 implementation. The embedded sensor-based systems provide a massive number of data as ongoing feedback on monitoring and controlling activities within the entire manufacturing processes, including products, and modifying virtual models of equipment, conveyors, and machines by this information (Dalenogare, et al., 2018).

Also, in consciousness context, the behavior of machines, objects, and systems within industry 4.0 is directed by consciousness abilities that concern information, knowledge, analyzing, decision-making, and autonomously and intelligently delivering the action independently (Qin, et al., 2016). The interactive integration of industry 4.0's

components and related implications, such as transparency, autonomous and interconnection of entire-processes and components, allow optimizing their efficiency, quality, flexibility, customization (Qin, et al., 2016; Oesterreich, et al., 2016; Müller, et al., 2018) and the efficiency and effectiveness utilization of resources and energy to shape ultimately a smart, networked and agile value chain (Ganzarain, et al., 2016).

The existence of embedded sensors ensures connectivity and interactivity among smart products, devices, and partners by using IoT technology. Thus, gathering real-time data enhances quality, accurate decision-making, optimizes productivity and cost by using big data analysis, supported by greater autonomous and flexible robotic technologies and additive manufacturing (3D-printing). Moreover, touch-interfaces and augmented-reality technologies improve human-machine interaction (Strange, et al., 2017; Baur, et al., 2015; Oesterreich, et al., 2016) that generate meaningful data and enhance the abilities and knowledge.

Figure 2.15: I4.0 proposed components

2. 2. Smart Manufacturing

2.2.1. Smart Factory Philosophy (SF)

One of the causes of turbulent environments is demanding and smart customers who have high expectations, where intensive competition and increased globalization. Besides rapid technological development and short product life-cycle that imposes manufacturing enterprises to increase financial outlays in research and development sectors, stress on innovation to ensure the flexibility, responsiveness and become eco-friendly (Odważny, et al., 2018b; Burke, et al., 2017). The new generation of factory tends to be more cognitive, automated, autonomous, and flexible, based on the

utilization of destructive and heterogeneous technologies, to name a few, IoT, CPS, big data analytics, and cloud computing, which added new capabilities to cope with the latest emerged challenges in the business environment (Yang, et al., 2019; Mabkhot, et al., 2018). All these technologies and characteristics meet in smart factory configuration.

Scholars' special attention reflects the increased impact and importance of smart factories for academia and business, whose impetus is to configure an acceptable smart factory concept and demystify being a multidisciplinary concept for practitioners. Multiple conceptualizations have appeared, demonstrating symmetric trends and a unified basis in the concept's forming, as shown in table 8. Interestingly, the smart factory concept's predefining was in 2008 by Lucke's description of the smart factory concept, matching with many contemporary perspectives, maybe extrapolating to the reality of future factories.

Researchers have previously identified a variety of smart factory concepts with lots of convergence and different points. Authors such as Lucke et al.,2008; Radziwon,2014; MacDougall,2014; Hozdić, 2015; Chien,2017; Burke,2017 point out that smart factories are innovative solutions to cope with smart environment challenges, smarter customers, and activist competitors, see Table 2.7. Many authors focus on the gained features and required merits to conceptualize a smart factory (to form a concept), as shown in Table 2.8. To mention a few, the needed features are decentralization, adaptivity, connectivity, integrity, agility, and autonomous, authors assuming critical importance to establish the smart factories (Lucke et al.,2008; Radziwon,2014; MacDougall, 2014; Verzijl et al.,2014; Hozdić,2015; BITKOM, 2015; Möller, 2016, Wang, 2016; Zhang, 2016; Strozzi,2017; Chien, 2017; Burke, 2017; Gubán et al., 2017; Odważny,2018a).

In the same regard, Table 2.8 shows that the connected and interactive (collaborative) environment is an important foundation for conceptualizing a smart factory for many researchers (Lucke et al., 2008; Radziwon, 2014; MacDougall, 2014; BITKOM, 2015; BCG, 2016; Möller,2016; Zhang,2016; Strozzi, 2017; Chien,2017; Burke,2017; Kaihara et al.,2017; Odważny, 2018a). This cooperative environment consists of smart entities (cyber and physical), where entities interact to increase performance and quality.

In this respect, Lucke et al., 2008; Radziwon, 2014; MacDougall, 2014; Hozdić, 2015; BITKOM, 2015; Möller, 2016; Wang, 2016; Chien, 2017; and Burke, 2017 stressed that production system's flexibility is an essential pillar to form and explain smart factory concept.

Lasi et al. (2014) depict the SF as a future factory that consists of connected and automated entities, where human's efforts are eliminated or decreased by real-time exchangeability of data and managing it to ensure a smooth flow of production (Lasi, et al., 2014). Newer sources of BCG 2016; Zakoldaev et al. 2019; Benotsmane et al. 2019 believe that the smart factory is an applied version of industry 4.0 and related technologies, as it is shown in Table 2.9. I4.0 creates a world in which virtual and physical production systems' entities flexibly interact with each other within a smart environment (Karabegović, et al., 2020).

In the same regard, the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) considers smart manufacturing as integrable and interoperable systems with high adaptability and real-time responsiveness to variable demand and conditions of the business environment, with stress on customer needs (Odważny, et al., 2018a). Doubtlessly, a smart factory is a set of smart entities that form integrated, interconnected, and interoperated systems supported by a network of sensors to ensure real-time responding to environmental challenges (Odważny, et al., 2018b; Herrmann, 2018).

The previous sections have shown that smart factories are a set of physical and cyber entities working and interacting smartly to ensure configuring an integrated production system characterized by a dynamic configuration, self-optimization, and self-diagnosis, self-adaption, self-control, and self-learning.

Table 2.7: Smart factory definitions

Authors	Year	Definitions
Lucke et al	2008	"A context-sensitive manufacturing environment that can handle turbulences in real-time production using decentralized information and communication structures for optimum management of production processes."
Radziwon	2014	"Is a manufacturing solution that provides flexible and adaptive production processes that will solve problems that arise in a productive environment with changing conditions in a world of increasing complexity."
MacDougall	2014	"A connected and flexible manufacturing system that uses a continuous stream of data from connected operations and production systems to learn and adapt to new demands."
Verzija et al	2014	"SF denotes a highly productive manufacturing environment of connected and intelligent machines and materials where waste, defect, and downtime is minimized."
Lasi et al	2014	"Depicts a future state of a fully connected manufacturing system, mainly operating without human force by generating, transferring, receiving and processing the necessary data to conduct all required tasks for producing all kinds of goods."
Hozdić	2015	"Is a production solution flexibly and efficiently should be to meet the needs of today's market, and achieves integration between the various industrial and non-industrial partners who build dynamic, and very often and virtual organizations."
BITKOM	2015	"Refers to the integration of information and communication technology which enables machines, equipment, vehicles, products, and humans to connected to each other and to exchange information in real-time."
BCG	2016	"SF is a production plant where the pillars of Industrie 4.0 are implemented."
Möller	2016	"Is a new level of socio-technical interaction of all stakeholders and resources involved in the manufacturing process which allows individual manufacturing, resilient manufacturing, and augmented operators".
Wang	2016	"A cyber-physical system that implements flexible and agile production and integrates physical objects such as machines, conveyors, and products with information systems."
Zhang	2016	"Is indeed a dynamic integrated cyber-physical-human manufacturing system in which the physical resources are implemented as smart things that communicate with each other and with human resources via IIoT and IoP and WoT infrastructure."

Strozzi	2017	"Dramatically and pervasive application of networked information-based technologies throughout the manufacturing and supply chain enterprise."
Chien	2017	"As a collection of systems which are fully integrated and interoperable and can work in real-time in response to varying demand, circumstances in the supply chain and "customer requirements
Burke	2017	"The SF is a flexible system that can self-optimize performance across a broader network, self-adapt to and learn from new conditions in real or near-real time, and autonomously run entire production processes."
Kaihara et al	2017	"Is a new concept in which the powerful infrastructure is currently capable of digitizing data and consolidation accurately and integrating vertical and horizontal value chains in complex business processes such as tradeoff decision customization and fulfilling orders".
Gubán et al	2017	"Is a complex system that integrates the main elements (e.g., autonomous robots, Internet of Things, Big data, Cloud Computing, Simulation, etc.) of the Industry 4.0 production philosophy."
Odważny	2018	"As a smart, independent factory equipped with sensors and orientated towards support for people and machines in carrying out their tasks."
Zakoldaev et al	2019	"Is an Industry 4.0 company to manufacture an item designing component and prepare the technological documentation".
Benotsmane et al	2019	"Is a complex system that integrates the main elements of the Industry 4.0 concept (e.g., autonomous robots, Internet of Things, and Big data)".
Deloitte	2017	"Is a flexible system that can self-optimize performance across a broader network, self-adapt to and learn from new conditions in real or near-real time, and autonomously run entire production processes".

(Created by author)

Table 2.8: Anchors of definitions

Definition's aspects	Smart Factory	Authors
Manufacturing solution	An innovative solution to cope with a changing environment and dynamic and complex challenges	Lucke et al, 2008; Radziwon, 2014; MacDougall,2014; Hozdić, 2015; Chien,2017; Burke , 2017.
Set of Features	Designing a system whose entities and processes are characterized by a set of features such as connectivity, interoperability, flexibility, smart, integrability, and awareness to shape and provide a set of targeted features, to name a few, self-organized, self-optimised, self-control, productivity, and adaptability.	Lucke,et al,2008; Radziwon ,2014; MacDougall , 2014; Verzij et al,2014; Hozdić,2015; BITKOM , 2015; Möller, 2016, Wang, 2016 ; Zhang, 2016; Strozzi ,2017; Chien, 2017 ; Burke , 2017; Gubán et al, 2017; Odważny ,2018a, Burke ,2017.
Collaborative environment	To configure a harmonic system of heterogeneous entities requires a container-environment to ensure high interoperability, connectivity, interactivity, and integrability among all entities. These environments consist of sensors, actuators, embedded programs, communication tools, advanced algorithms, big data tools etc., to enable collaboration and interactive environments.	Lucke et al, 2008; Radziwon,2014; MacDougall , 2014;BITKOM ,2015;BCG, 2016; Möller ,2016; Zhang, 2016; Strozzi, 2017; Chien, 2017; Burke ,2017; Kaihara et al,2017; Odważny, 2018a.
Flexible operation	A set of flexible and adaptable entities (software, physical, and process) should be interacting and integrated to establish a smart factory.	Lucke et al, 2008; Radziwon ,2014; MacDougall,2014;Hozdić , 2015; BITKOM , 2015; Möller, 2016; Wang, 2016; Chien, 2017; Burke , 2017.

2.2.2. Smart Factory Operating Mechanism

The next decade is possible to witness a considerable rise in the new wave of factory infrastructure, a transformation that has already started. Today, it is becoming increasingly tough to ignore the foundations and motivations of the 4th revolution embracement.

Klaus Leukert, one of the SAP managers, said: "Anything that can be digitized will be digitized." Thus, digitalization life is harnessed to simplify and optimize the human lifestyle, affecting people, systems, machines, and products alike. At the end of the twentieth century, the digitalization and smartness associated with manufacturing and factory have appeared (Odważny, et al., 2018a). The time has come for a bold and novel competitiveness strategy that will benefit from intelligent manufacturing as a strategic asset for growth and facing business environment challenges. The utilization of smart factories' intelligence encourages product innovation rate enhancement (Rubio, et al., 2018) which will enable having superior competitiveness (Burke, et al., 2017).

Smart factories have been identified as major contributing factors for increasing a new industrial revolution implementation, which is considered a serious challenge facing manufacturing enterprises. Thus, embracing and adapting to these technologies became inevitable and critical to surviving in the smart business environment (Sjödin, et al., 2018). Many manufacturing enterprises are already leveraging SF's technologies in such areas as smart planning, smart scheduling, and AR in maintenance. SF is not only a technical side or shop-floor system but is a more holistic endeavor going beyond the shop floor toward reshaping the enterprise business model and influencing a broader ecosystem. SF is an integral component in a vast digital supply network and has multiple impacts on manufactures' abilities to effectively meet and adapt to a changeable marketplace (Burke, et al., 2017).

In the literature, it is frequently seen that the CPS factory, CPPS, industrial internet factory, cloud manufacturing, smart industries, advanced manufacturing, digital manufacturing, smart production, ubiquitous manufacturing, and smart factory are used as interchangeable synonyms (Mabkhot, et al., 2018; Radziwon, et al., 2014; Mittal, et al., 2017).

The rigid automation and low flexibility in the traditional manufacturing process (3rd industrial revolution) impose slow resetting, retooling, and reorganization of machines and entities (Karabegović, et al., 2020), whereas the industrial development,

production, and entire business value chains expose manufacturing enterprises to disruptive change in the industry 4.0 context (CRO Forum, 2015; Karabegović, et al., 2020). For instance, the inevitable fusion of information technology (IT) and operations technology (OT) and high connectivity among entities transfer traditional supply chains from linear, sequential process to digital, interconnected, and interacted process, called digital supply networks (Burke, et al., 2017). Emerging smart technologies and embedding them in factories' entities with high connectivity and integrability are motivators for this 4.0 wave (CRO Forum, 2015), which establish an integrated value creation network including all partners and related business processes in the smart factory context, characterized by adaptability and resource efficiency (Shafiq, et al., 2015).

The philosophy of “design anywhere, manufacture anywhere” relies on internet-based technologies in general, which pave the way to arise and configure innovative manufacturing philosophies based on connected and integrated environment to enable data-exchanging (sharing) across multiple platforms and infrastructures. The configured enterprises will be mostly information-oriented and knowledge-driven. All entities (physical, cyber, process) need to be interacted and integrated into a networked system to work in “distributed environments,” to perform tasks integrally regardless of the physical location of entities (Caputo, et al., 2016; Rubio, et al., 2018). In the same regard, enabling machines to make decisions is an initial step of automation which is based on combining a set of rules, algorithms, and recently artificial intelligence (AI) technologies besides the existence of CPS to allow physical entities to self-optimization, self-control, and self-decisions which humans typically take (Burke, et al., 2017). Thus, I4.0's wave brings an innovative change in production, management, business model, supply chain, and value network when applied (Rubio, et al., 2018).

SF is a manufacturing solution to enable innovative capabilities to cope with dynamic and complex environmental challenges. This innovative solution involves increased automation and a combination of cyber and physical entities, which allow high automation of all processes and optimizes the whole performance, enabling a dynamic enterprise that ensures effective collaboration of industrial and non-industrial partners (Radziwon, et al., 2014). Via the interaction of smart factory technologies to present efficient digital and real manufacturing systems, contextual-knowledge is enhanced to help humans and physical entities execute their tasks smartly and precisely. The

configured knowledge represented entities' performance (historical and ongoing) information and predicted performance (Mabkhot, et al., 2018).

The fourth industrial revolution is considered a real establishment of a smart factory due to the noticeable and dynamic growth in sensors, automation, wireless technologies, and artificial intelligence (Odważny, et al., 2018a). Based on I4.0, the smart factory is configured by components such as AM, AR, IoT, BD analytics, autonomous robot, simulation, cyber-security, vertical and horizontal integration, and cloud (Strozzi, et al., 2017; Herrmann, 2018), which leads to the fusion of virtual and physical worlds, the overlapping of artificial intelligence, machine learning, M2M communication and automation of knowledge with manufacturing operations. This convergence motivates the emergence of smart factories (CRO Forum, 2015).

The smart factory's ongoing evolution nature stems from its alignment with the latest technologies (the possibility of embracing new technologies) to build and maintain flexible learning systems (Burke, et al., 2017). Data-driven innovation (based on the availability and visibility of data) coupled with smart entities based on CPS's utilization form a new generation of production system towards the smart factory. (Yang, et al., 2019). The operational mechanism of the smart factory is based on CPPS and IoT to create connected and integrated environments of heterogeneous physical objects (machines, conveyers, products...etc.) besides a set of information systems like ERP, MES, and CAPP to optimize performance primarily operational performance (Wang, et al., 2016).

The dynamic configuration and open infrastructure of smart manufacturing rely on interaction and integration among networked machines to enhance the adaptation and flexibility of the process, customized tasks, valid, applicable, and faster solutions for emerged problems, increasing created value and optimize system's performance (Yang, et al., 2019; Odważny, et al., 2018a). The utilization of assistance (embedded) systems enables networking, automation, self-independence, and integrated decision-making in the smart factory and allow self-controlled processes (Feldmann, et al., 2018). The smart factories' entities are data-driven units capable of gathering and using data and information in all management processes. Thus, a smart factory is characterized by smooth flow, ease of adaptability, advanced data security, and providing a close relationship with customers and suppliers (Odważny, et al., 2018a).

The CPS enables communication among physical and virtual worlds' entities, especially in manufacturing environments, when physical objects and their digital twins are connected to communicate and interact within networks (Karabegović, et al., 2020). The interaction between CPS and IoT is the backbone of a smart factory, facilitating decentralized decision-making and enhancing remote control abilities by establishing a digital twin of physical entities and processes. Similarly, the smart factory's participation in collaborative networks allows consulting-based decision-making and has a mutual effect among networks' participants (Odważny, et al., 2018b).

The decomposition of units to subunits that are interchanged and matched to reconfigure various units and systems refer to the modular components (units) that interact, connect, and exchange resources via standardized interfaces. The reconfigurable and reusable entities (physical, cyber, process) form the basis of modularization, and the re-composition of value-adding is based on the (re-)combining entities with other modules (Mittal, et al., 2017; Kühnle, et al., 2015). Consequently, the configuration of a networked manufacturing model is possible, based on on-demand access to sets of shareable resources to shape temporary and reconfigurable manufacturing lines that foster efficiency, reduce product lifecycle costs, enable on-demand tasks to be performed, and enhance the allocation of resource (Caputo, et al., 2016).

The existence of embedded and powerful computers enables CPS to make decisions within the smart factory context. Self-decision making lets decentralized processes remove central planning and monitoring. Self-decision making and decentralization are supported via networks of smart sensors, continually providing and exchanging monitored data. These networks allow real-time analysis of performance for all entities (physical, cyber, process), which enable automatically redirecting the production process to other available machines if there are any predicted failures, low performance and/or expected stoppage in particular machines. All these interactions are conducted in the internet environment (Karabegović, et al., 2020).

One of the smart factory common examples is Tesla's smart factory which is an integrated and connected environment of devices, sensors, and robots interacting together to produce cars and batteries in an efficient manner (Sjödín, et al., 2018). In smart factories, many technologies and philosophies interact to create an integrated and connected environment that enables decentrally controlling, digitally utilizing

connected machines, products, systems, components, and employees (Feldmann, et al., 2018). Thus, the innovative production process was created in a smart factory environment which is characterized by context-aware, autonomous, and individualized small-lot orders.

2.2.3. Building Smart Factory Capabilities

Today, the challenges faced by manufacturing enterprises go beyond finding new and abundant sources and enhancing productivity towards meeting smart competitors and customers, dynamic and smart environment, rapid technological developments, and finding and establishing proper capabilities. The manufacturing enterprises are under intensified pressure on how to face these challenges and which capabilities are required to cope with them. Thus, many capabilities are needed to be built via a set of features, design principles, and destructive enabling technologies, which should be embraced and implemented under smart factory context.

In many resources, a smart factory is considered a set of interactive, smart, and dynamic capabilities to cope with today's business environment. The manufacturers scramble for desired capabilities possession in manufacturing that has primarily revolved around how to integrate the features, design principles, and enabling technologies toward the smart factories.

The following section defines and logically clusters the individual characteristics, design principles, and enabling technologies—this section concerns building an interactive environment to have the desired capabilities via discussing the fundamental capabilities.

2.2.3.1 Smart factory features

The industry 4.0 based smart factory consists of flexible, independent, and smart entities were integrating and interacting to possess desired features that stem from utilized I4.0's. The smart factory integration and flexibility rely on the connected and interacted entities upon the network, which ultimately enables remote control and management of the systems (Odważny, et al., 2018a).

A set of interlaced and integrated features should be acquired and/or produced via establishing a smart and integrated system of systems to survive. A survey of the recent literature shows that some of the features identified are used synonymously and may be integrated to present a more focused result. Some of these features can be merged, integrated, and clustered together as certain items are relatively closely related.

Hence, different terminologies used in the considered literature are presented in Table 2.9, regarding the capabilities and related features along with the supporting authors. Table 2.9 presents a list of 52 features that are associated with SF. These features are effectively clustered under five capability groups. Logical relations are used in marking the most suitable clusters. Synonymous use and confusion in the terminology are eliminated. As such, Table 2.9 proposes a clustering of capabilities and related features. Such classification provides a vital opportunity to improve the understanding of smart factories' contents and characteristics and can act as guidelines that an organization should follow to build and embrace SF. The clustering of closely related to design principles based on their integration is addressed in the subsequent sections (Cimini, et al., 2019).

Table 2.9: Smart factories features

Capabilities	SF's features	Authors
Autonomous Capability (entities, process)	Self-controlled	Feldmann et al,2018; Cimini, et al ,2019; Karabegović et al,2020;
	Self-organized	Herrmann,2012; Lee et al,2015; Wang, 2016;Rojko,2017; Benotsmane et al, 2019;
	Self-configuration	Herrmann,2012; Lee et al,2015; Karabegović et al,2020;
	Self-coordination	Herrmann,2012;
	Self-diagnostic	Herrmann,2012; Lee et al,2015; Karabegović et al,2020;
	Self-decision	Wang,2016;
	Self-compare	Lee et al.,2015;
	Self-optimization	Herrmann,2012; Wang,2016; Rojko,2017; Burke et al,2017;
	Self-adapt	Cimini, et al,2019; Burke et al,2017; Benotsmane et al, 2019;
	Self-predict	Lee et al.,2015; Burke et al.,2017;
	Self-aware	Herrmann,2012; Lee et al,2015; CRO Forum,2015; Rojko,2017; Burke et al,2017; Mittal et al,2017; Kibira et al, 2015;
	Automation	Cimini, et al,2019; Li,2015; Karabegović et al,2020;
	Autonomous	Feldmann et al,2018; Wang, 2016; Cimini, et al,2019; Kühnle and Bitsch, 2015; Mittal et al,2017; Rüb & Bahemia,2019;
Dynamic Interaction Capability	Connectivity	Burke et al,2017; Mittal et al, 2017; Rubio and Andina, 2018; Rüb & Bahemia, 2019; Karabegović et al,2020; Rojko,2017;
	Interoperability	Odważny,2018a; Kühnle and Bitsch,2015; Mittal et al.,2017; Rojko,2017; Benotsmane et al., 2019;

	Integrability	Caputo, et al,2016; Li,2015; Odważny,2018a; Cimini, et al,2019; Mittal et al,2017; Rüb & Bahemia,2019;
	Decentralization	Odważny,2018a; Feldmann et al,2018; Park and Tran, 2014; Mittal et al,2017; Lasi et al,2014; Benotsmene et al, 2019;
	Real-time enterprises	Herrmann,2012; Cimini, et al,2019; Thoben et al, 2016; Benotsmene et al, 2019;
	Accessibility	Cimini, et al,2019; Lee et al, 2015; Rüb & Bahemia,2019; Karabegović et al,2020;
	Transparency	Burke et al,2017; Lee et al, 2015;
	Traceability	Rubio and Andina, 2018;
	Digitization	Caputo, et al,2016; Li,2015; CRO Forum,2015; Kühnle and Bitsch; Mittal et al,2017;
	Cyber Security	Odważny,2018a; Mittal et al,2017; Rubio and Andina, 2018; Rüb & Bahemia,2019;
	Information appropriateness	Cimini, et al,2019; Mittal et al,2017;
	Socio-technical interaction	Cimini, et al,2019; Rüb & Bahemia,2019;
	Smooth data flow	Odważny,2018a; Cimini, et al,2019; Karabegović et al,2020;
Customizing Capability	Need-oriented	Herrmann,2012; Rubio and Andina, 2018; Rojko,2017; Benotsmene et al, 2019;
	Small-lot order	Odważny,2018a;Wang,2016; Strozzi, et al., 2017; Rüb & Bahemia,2019; Thoben et al, 2016;
	Customization	Rubio and Andina, 2018; Rüb & Bahemia,2019;Karabegović et al, 2020 ; Rojko,2017; Thoben et al, 2016; Benotsmene et al, 2019;
	Individualized product	Wang,2016; CRO Forum,2015; Cimini, et al,2019; Rüb & Bahemia ,2019; Thoben et al, 2016; Lasi et al,2014; Benotsmene et al, 2019;
Intelligence Capability	Reconfiguration	Radziwon et al,2014; Rojko ,2017; Lee et al
	Virtualization	Benotsmene et al, 2019;
	Modeling	Li,2015; Caputo, et al,2016; ; Rubio and Andina, 2018
	Visualization	Li,2015; Caputo, et al,2016; Odważny,2018a;
	Modularity	Kühnle and Bitsch,2015; Mittal et al,2017; Benotsmene et al, 2019;
	Optimal resource allocation	Caputo et al.,2016; Rubio and Andina, 2018;

	Intelligent sensing “data availability”	Rubio and Andina, 2018; Karabegović et al,2020; Thoben et al, 2016;
	Information’s integration	Rubio and Andina, 2018; Rüb & Bahemia,2019; Karabegović et al,2020; Rojko,2017;
	Advanced analysis	Rubio and Andina, 2018; Li,2015; Rüb & Bahemia,2019; Karabegović et al,2020; Karabegović et al,2020; Rojko,2017;
	Prediction	Mittal et al,2017; Karabegović et al,2020; Benotsmane et al, 2019;
	Learn	Burke et al,2017; Benotsmane et al, 2019;
	Proactivity	Rojko,2017;
	Awareness	Rüb & Bahemia,2019; Karabegović et al,2020;
Competitive Capability	Responsive	Caputo, et al,2016; Cimini, et al,2019;
	Agility	Radziwon et al,2014; Resman et al,2019; Burke et al,2017; Mittal et al,2017; Kibira et al, 2015; Rubio and Andina, 2018; Karabegović et al,2020;
	Efficiency	Prist et al,2019; Caputo, et al,2016; Sjödin et al, 2018; Rubio and Andina , 2018; Rüb & Bahemia,2019; Karabegović et al,2020; Lasi et al,2014;
	Lean	Radziwon et al,2014; Lee et al,2015;
	Adaptability	Herrmann,2012; Radziwon et al,2014; Odważny,2018a; Rojko, 2017; Cimini, et al,2019; Sjödin et al, 2018; Burke et al,2017; Strozzi, et al., 2017; Park and Tran, 2014; Mittal et al,2017; Rüb & Bahemia,2019; Karabegović et al,2020;
	Flexibility	Herrmann,2012; Radziwon et al,2014; Resman et al,2019; Prist et al,2019; Park and Tran, 2014; Mittal et al,2017; Lee et al,2015; Karabegović et al,2020; Thoben et al, 2016; Lasi et al,2014; Benotsmane et al, 2019;
	Sustainability	Sjödin et al.,2018; Burke et al.,2017; CRO Forum, 2015; Mittal et al.,2017; Kibira et al., 2015b; Rubio and Andina, 2018; Benotsmane et al., 2019;
	Optimization	Odważny,2018a; Cimini, et al, 2019 ; Rubio and Andina, 2018; Benotsmane et al., 2019;
	Predictive	Burke et al.,2017

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Based on Table 2.9, Figures 2-16 to 2-20 indicate each capability cluster's desired features followed by its discussion. It is significant to bear in mind that these features continuously interact to build advanced capabilities.

Autonomous Capability: As shown in Figure 2-16, a wide range of features could lie under this capability to enable autonomous interaction, triggering actions, reacting, create services, and awareness...etc, for all entities. The compositenature of autonomous capability requests a wide arrange of integrated and overlapped characteristics. To name a few, these are self-controlled, self-aware, self-organized, self-configuration, self-predict, self-coordination, self-diagnostic, self-decision

(reasonability), self-compare, self-optimization (make the best solution), self-adapt (contextual behaviour), automation, and autonomous.

Figure 2- 16: The Autonomous capability- building features

The Dynamic Interaction Capability: The required features to build this capability, as depicted in Figure 2.17, ensure the operation of each entity and the whole system in an integrated and coordinated manner. They allow smooth exchanging of data among entities (physical, cyber, process, and human), ensure interoperability and collaboration among distributed objects.

Real-time, automated communication among smart equipment with users and other entities encourages generating dynamic process innovations (Sjödin, et al., 2018). A fully connected and flexible system is the essential pillar for SF. Utilization of a constant stream of data leads to shape on-demand and data-driven processes, and integrating these enormous sets of data stemming from smart and distributed physical, operational, and human assets result in an entirely different ecosystem. It totally reconfigures the processes related to production, maintenance, inventory tracking. Digitization of processes via building digital twins and smart relationships among entities are enabled within the manufacturing network, ultimately reshaping an agile, integrated and intelligent system (Burke, et al., 2017).

Figure 2. 17: The dynamic interaction capability building features

Customized Production Capability: demand-driven (need-oriented) production, small-lot order, and individualized product feature, as given in Figure 2.18, deliver efficiency gains and effective customer participation in businesses which undoubtedly enhances the competitive capability, resource-efficient manufacturing, profit opportunity.

Figure 2.18: Customized production building features

Intelligence Capability: is the source of smartness for all entities and enterprises. This capability starts in acquiring data to produce knowledge, and it enables knowledge dissemination by sharing to enable predictions. To establish a smart system, we need smart entities and intelligent infrastructure with many required features. As it is shown in Figure 2.19, the compositive nature of smartness imposes having a set of features like intelligent sensing, data availability, information integration, advanced analysis, prediction, heterogeneity, learning, proactivity, and awareness to configure the smartness base of all entities (physical, cyber, process). Besides, all required features to anticipate the future lies under this capability. These features help entities eliminate failures before they occur via efficiency, reconfigurability, optimal resource allocation, consciousness, and visualization. All entities drive their actions based on real-time situation-awareness. This capability is considered as the infrastructure of many competitive capabilities, to be discussed next.

Figure 2.19: Intelligence capability building features

Competitive Capability: As shown in Figure 2.20, competitive capability describes the system's ability to cope with challenges and changes in the business environment regardless of dynamism and complexity of challenges. The competitive capability includes a list of characteristics like flexibility, sustainability (Martínez-Olvera , et al., 2019; Kusiak, 2017), agility (Kang, et al., 2016), lean, adaptability, predictive, socio-technical interaction (Davies , et al., 2017), optimization, and responsiveness. Via these lists of features interacting and integrating, this capability group forms the basis of development and growth. Consequently, competitive capabilities go beyond the traditional boundaries of the shop-floor as well as the organization toward strategic, social, and economic dimensions. Hence, they affect the overall performance and facilitate the exploitation of the existing and new markets.

Figure 2.20: Competitive capability building features

2.2.3.2 Smart Factory's Design Principles

Design principles refer to the necessary core foundations to configure a smart environment containing smart factory entities. They assist designers in building new smart factories or providing ways to modify existing traditional factories to be smart (

Mabkhot, et al., 2018). They are considered fundamental pieces of the smart factory for easy and systematic implementation to provide “systemization of knowledge,” and these design principles are widely applicable within the smart factory (Hermann, et al., 2016).

Since design principles result from researchers' and practitioners' accumulated wisdom, this subsection tries to identify the core aspects of smart factory design principles based on 36 research papers. Despite differing views of authors and their multiple identifications of principles, Table 2.10 displays the 54 principles that the survey proposed. The table contains the agreement percentages and the supporting authors for each design principle. Figure 2.21 present the frequency of the design principles.

Table 2.10: SF-design principles

Design Principles	Agreement Percentages	Authors
Service Orientation	8.4%	Ghobakhloo,2018;Gilchrist, 2016;Wang et al,2016; Plessis,2017; Hermann,2015; Shafiq et al, 2015; Hermann et al,2016;Posada et al, 2015;Vogel-Heuser and Hess, 2016;Theorin et al, 2017 ; Lu ,2017; Thames & Schaefer,2017;Perales et al ,2018 ;Mohamed et al,2018; Lom et al,2016;Salkin et al,2018; Mohamed et al ,2019; Mittal et al,2017;
Decentralization	8.4%	Ghobakhloo,2018;Zhong et al. ,2017;Gilchrist,2016;Wang et al,2016;Plessis,2017; Hermann,2015; Shafiq et al ,2015;Hermann et al,2016;Lasi et al,2014;zhang et al,2017;Lu ,2017;Li,2018;Liao et al, 2017; Mohamed et al,2018;Lom et al,2016;Salkin et al, 2018;Mohamed et al, 2019; Mittal et al,2017;
Virtualization	8.4%	Ghobakhloo,2018;Gilchrist,2016;Wang et al,2016; Plessis,2017;Hermann,2015; Shafiq et al ,2015; Almada-Lobo,2015;Hermann et al,2016;Posada et al, 2015;Vogel-Heuser and Hess,2016; Lu ,2017; Li,2018;Perales et al ,2018;Mohamed et al,2018;Lom et al,2016;Salkin et al,2018; Mohamed et al ,2019; Mittal et al,2017;
Real-Time Capability	8.0%	Ghobakhloo,2018;Gilchrist,2016;Plessis, 2017;Hermann, 2015;Shafiq et al ,2015; Hermann et al,2016; Vogel-Heuser and Hess,2016;zhang et al,2017;Lu, 2017;strange & Zucchella,2017;Liao et al,2017; Perales et al ,2018;Mohamed et al,2018;Lom et al,2016;Salkin et al,2018;Mohamed et al ,2019; Mittal et al,2017;
Interoperability	7.6%	Ghobakhloo,2018;Gilchrist,2016;Wang et al,2016; Plessis,2017; Hermann,2015; Shafiq et al ,2015; Hermann et al,2016;Vogel-Heuser and Hess, 2016;Lu ,2017; Li,2018;Perales et al ,2018 ;Mohamed et al,2018;Lom et al,2016;Salkin et al,2018; Mohamed et al ,2019; Mittal et al,2017;
Internet Of Things	6.8%	Ghobakhloo,2018;Zhong et al ,2017;Gilchrist,2016; Roblek et al,2016; Davies et al, 2017;Erol et al, 2016; Theorin et al,2017;zhang et al,2017;Lu, 2017;Wollschlaeger et al,2017;Thames & Schaefer, 2017;strange & Zucchella,2017;Li,2018;Liao et al,2017; Devezas & Sarygulov, 2017 ;Perales et al, 2018;
Modularity	6.3%	Ghobakhloo, 2018; Gilchrist, 2016; Plessis, 2017; Hermann, 2015; Shafiq et al ,2015; Hermann et al, 2016; Vogel-Heuser and Hess,2016;Lu,2017;Perales et al ,2018; Mohamed et al,2018;Lom et al,2016; Mohamed et al ,2019; Mittal et al,2017;
Smart Product	5.9%	Ghobakhloo,2018;Zhong et al.,2017;Gilchrist,2016; Roblek et al,2016; Davies et al, 2017;Lasi et al, 2014;zhang et al,2017;Lu, 2017;Wollschlaeger et al,2017;Thames & Schaefer,2017;Liao et al,2017; Devezas & Sarygulov,2017;Perales et al ,2018;Santos et al,2017;

Smart Factory	4.6%	Ghobakhloo,2018;Gilchrist,2016; Roblek et al,2016; Davies et al. ,2017;Lasi et al,2014;Lu ,2017; Wollschlaeger et al,2017;Thames & Schaefer,2017;Li,2018; Devezas & Sarygulov,2017;Perales et al ,2018;
Horizontal Integration	4.2%	Ghobakhloo,2018;Gilchrist,2016; Roblek et al,2016; Daviesa et al.,2017;zhang et al, 2017;Lu, 2017; strange & Zucchella,2017;Liao et al,2017;Devezas & Sarygulov,2017; Salkin et al,2018;
Internet Of Services	4.2%	Ghobakhloo,2018;Gilchrist,2016; Roblek et al,2016; Daviesa et al.,2017;zhang et al, 2017;Lu, 2017; Li,2018Liao et al, 2017; Devezas & Sarygulov,2017; Perales et al,2018
Vertical Integration	3.8%	Ghobakhloo,2018;Gilchrist,2016; Daviesa et al,2017;Almada-Lobo,2015;Lasi et al, 2014; Posada et al,2015;Lu, 2017;Devezas & Sarygulov, 2017;Salkin et al,2018;
Standardization	2.1%	Plessis,2017; Hermann, 2015; Qin et al, 2016; Kagermann et al, 2013; Kang et al, 2016;
Product Personalization	1.7%	Ghobakhloo,2018; Roblek et al,2016;Hermann,2015;Liao et al,2017;
Reference Architecture	1.3%	Qin et al.,2016; Kagermann et al,2013;Kang et al,2016
Delivering A Comprehensive Broadband Infrastructure	1.3%	Qin et al.,2016; Kagermann et al.,2013; Kang et al.,2016
Safety And Security	1.3%	Qin et al.,2016; Kagermann et al.,2013; Kang et al.,2016
Work Organisation And Design:	1.3%	Qin et al.,2016; Kagermann et al,2013;Kang et al,2016
Training And Continuing Professional Development (CPD):	1.3%	Qin et al.,2016; Kagermann et al., 2013; Kang et al.,2016
Regulatory Framework	1.3%	Qin et al.,2016; Kagermann et al,2013;Kang et al,2016
Resource Productivity And Efficiency	1.3%	Qin et al.,2016; Kagermann et al,2013;Kang et al,2016

Corporate Social Responsibility	1.3%	Kagermann et al,2013;Kang et al,2016
Agility	0.8%	Wang et al,2016;Salkin et al,2018
Managing Complex Systems	0.8%	Kagermann et al,2013;Kang et al,2016
Interconnection	0.8%	Hermann,2015;Hermann et al,2016;
Real Time Data Management	0.8%	Wang et al,2016 (Wang, et al., 2016)
Integrated Business Processes	0.8%	Wang et al.,2016
Iiot	0.4%	Erol et al,2016;
Cloud Based Manufacturing	0.4%	Erol et al,2016;
Smart Manufacturing	0.4%	Erol et al,2016;
Connectivity And Mobile	0.4%	Almada-Lobo,2015
Cloud Computing And Advanced Analysis	0.4%	Almada-Lobo,2015
information Transparency	0.4%	Hermann et al,2016
technical Assistance	0.4%	Hermann et al,2016
flexibility	0.4%	Hermann et al,2015
Consciousness	0.4%	Hermann et al,2015
Smart Solutions	0.4%	Santos et al,2017
Smart Innovations	0.4%	Santos et al,2017
Smart Supply Chain	0.4%	Santos et al,2017

Figure 2.21: The frequent design principles

As shown in Table 2.10 and Figure 2.21, varying degrees of agreement and various terminologies are used to clarify that clear identification of the design principles is hard in the smart factory context. Today, many discussions are held about the design principles and their SF's roles, and there seems to be only a certain degree of consensus. Hence, providing a set of design principles to be adopted and disseminated within manufacturing enterprises is vital for SF. to enable successful transform Figure 2.22 displays nine design principles to guide researchers and practitioners towards SF.

Figure 2.22: SF's design principles

Based on the references mentioned in Table 2.10, these main principles can be summarized as below:

Digitalization is a digital form for the analog or physical entities (objects and processes) that a computer can process; **Virtualization** creates a paired digital version of entities (physical and process). It is the virtual instance of the physical environment and its related interactions. **Interoperability** creates a cooperative and integrative interaction and understandable behaviors of various entities (physical, cyber, process). **Integrated system**: unifying efforts to realize goals. **Standardization** is using fully accepted interacting and performing methods and rules by most parties. Thus, it is creating standards to guide and facilitate the operating, managing, controlling, evaluating, and maintaining the system and related components and products in a multi-partner environment. **Flexibility** is the entities' ability to respond to changeable-demand and produce various products. **Modularity** is the degree of reconfigurability of entities to compose different systems, operations, functions, and products. **Decentralization** is the ability to autonomously decision-making (self or local) and manage each entity's own behavior. **Service-orientation** is making everything pairs to service, is called servitization by some authors, such as Product-Services System and process as a service (PAAS), and it is considered one of outsourcing strategies kinds.

Safety and security are the connected and networked nature of the smart factory system relies on the existence of advanced security systems (technologies) to protect systems, networks, and data from cyber threats.

2.2.3.2 Enabling technologies for building SF's

The smart factory comprises a set of technologies and tools used to enrich and enhance manufacturing processes to provide a premium competitive advantage. The enhancement methodology is centered on utilizing ICT with advanced production technologies to ensure the high flexibility, connectivity, and integrability in the physical processes to cope with dynamically changing the environment (Odważny, et al., 2018a). Smart Factory is about networking smart entities and systems via a set of software so that smart intercommunication with each other has been possible and the automatically organized tasks can easily be coordinated (Herrmann, 2018).

Many manufacturing enterprises try to embrace a set of smart factory components partially or gradually. For instance, Scania, the Swedish truck manufacturer, continually pursues innovation in its manufacturing processes, such as integrating industrial robotics, CAD/CAM, programmable logic controllers [PLCs], and Lean management techniques in production system operations to move to the next generation of the factories (Sjödín, et al., 2018).

Automation, computerization, optimization, and robotics, are the main technologies to cope with a highly dynamic environment supported by agile and lean management practices. Acquisition of such advanced technologies integrates and configures smart factory infrastructures to enhance quality and performance (Odważny, et al., 2018b). All devices are connected via IoT philosophy, requiring entities to automatically acquire, process, and exchange data with other entities. Smart entities (physical, cyber, process) are equipped with proper capacities to accomplish desired processes independently based on the goal and circumstance. They interact and integrate via semantic services in the context of the smart factory. In the same regard, self-organization enables entities to achieve specific goals (Caputo, et al., 2016; Li, et al., 2015). This connected and interactive environment created by IoT enables the cyber and physical world to increasingly fusion together in an integral manner. The IoT technologies contribute to uniquely identifiable physical entities, enable connectable entities and receive a digital representation (Herrmann, 2018).

Figure 2. 23:SF's technologies
(Created by author)

The smart factory components presented in Table 2.11 and Figure 2.23 are derived from current SF literature. Similar to the confusion in terminology mentioned while discussing capabilities and features, some of these components are somewhat similar, and they can be clustered. Many researchers around the world proposed a list of 28 technologies that are associated with SF. Some of these technologies can be considered as umbrella terms consisting of a set of subcomponents, and the differentiated technological requirements among manufacturing sectors require that a variety of fundamental technologies which form smart factories are to be embraced.

The agreement degree shown in Figure 2.23 highlights that the IoT and CPS are considered the smart factory's backbone. It operates with cloud computing technologies in a connected environment to enable entities to be smarter and to behave autonomously. Big data support this integrated environment, and various other technologies such as augmented reality, additive manufacturing, and robotics stand out as supporting technologies.

Table 2.11: Smart factory's components

Components	Authors
IoT	Strozzi et al, 2017; Kagermann et al, 2013; Herrmann, 2018; Feldmann ,2018; CRO Forum,2015; Rojko ,2017; Karabegović et al, 2020;Liao et al,2014; Resman et al,2019;Prist et al, 2019 ;Sjödin et al,2018;park &Lee ,2015;Kang et al,2016; Mittal et al,2017;Benotsmane et al,2019;
CPS	Strozzi et al,2017; Herrmann,2018;Feldmann, 2018;Rojko, 2017; Karabegović et al,2020; Liao et al, 2014;Resman et al,2019;Prist et al,2019;Sjödin et al, 2018;park &Lee,2015; Kang et al,2016; Mittal et al,2017;Benotsmane et al,2019;
CC	Strozzi et al,2017;Kagermann et al,2013;Herrmann,2018; Rojko ,2017;Karabegović et al,2020;Liao et al,2014;Resman et al,2019;Prist et al,2019;Kang et al,2016; Mittal et al,2017; Benotsmane et al,2019;
Autonomous	Strozzi et al, 2017;Herrmann,2018;Feldmann,2018; CRO Forum ,2015;Rojko, 2017;Resman et al,2019;Prist et al,2019; Sjödin et al,2018; Mittal et al,2017; Benotsmane et al,2019;
AM	Strozzi et al,2017;Herrmann,2018;CRO Forum,2015; Karabegović et al, 2020 ;park &Lee ,2015;Kang et al,2016; Mittal et al,2017;Benotsmane et al,2019;
BD	Strozzi et al,2017;Herrmann,2018;CRO Forum,2015; Rojko, 2017; Resman et al,2019; park &Lee, 2015; Mittal et al,2017; Benotsmane et al,2019;
Robotics	Strozzi et al,2017;Herrmann,2018;CRO Forum,2015; Rojko,2017; Karabegović et al ,2020;Benotsmane et al,2019;
AR	Strozzi et al,2017;Herrmann,2018; CRO Forum,2015; Kang et al,2016; Mittal et al,2017;Benotsmane et al,2019;
Embedded syatem	Feldmann,2018;Rojko,2017;Karabegović et al,2020;park &Lee ,2015; Mittal et al,2017;
Simulation	Strozzi et al,2017;Herrmann,2018; Mittal et al,2017; Benotsmane et al,2019;
Integration	Strozzi et al,2017;Herrmann,2018; Mittal et al,2017; Benotsmane et al,2019
Real-time capabilities	Herrmann,2018; Rojko,2017;park &Lee ,2015; Mittal et al,2017;
CPPS	Herrmann, 2018;Kang et al,2016; Mittal et al,2017;
Energy saving	park &Lee , 2015;Benotsmane et al,2019; Kang et al,2016
Holograms	park &Lee , 2015;Benotsmane et al,2019; Kang et al,2016
Digital product memory	Herrmann,2018;Feldmann,2018;

Artificial intelligence	Liao et al,2014; Sjödin et al,2018;
Smart product	Park &Lee , 2015;Benotsmane et al,2019;
"IT-based production management"	Park &Lee , 2015;Benotsmane et al,2019;
Tracking and tracing	Park &Lee , 2015;Benotsmane et al,2019;
Intelligent control	Park &Lee , 2015;Benotsmane et al,2019;
human factor	Kagermann et al,2013;
Accepted standards	Herrmann,2018;
Optimized processes	CRO Forum,2015
RFID	Karabegović et al,2020
Digital twins	Liao et al,2014;
Algorithms	Liao et al,2014;

Prepared by author

The utilization of I4.0's enabling technologies as the main component of the smart factory leads to an increase in the efficiency of all entities and production processes, enhances production entities' availability, boosts the value per employee, and optimizes performance. Enhancing lead-times, setup times, and delivery times and reducing cost are achieved when the smart factory was embraced (Resman, et al., 2019). These technologies enable a distributed production process, encouraging a small-scale production, high customization, and high participation of a user in the whole process (Li, et al., 2015). Consequently, smart factories utilize industry 4.0 technologies to configure a fully connected and integrated production system for the future via autonomously generating, transferring, receiving, and processing heterogeneous data to conduct and drive all entities' actions and related tasks.

The cooperative and interactive use of various available modern systems and technologies (such as CPS, BD, IoT, CC, AM, Robotics, CIM, ERP, Simulation, and AR) together with business intelligence and their related technologies, support the organization's efforts to become smart manufacturing systems and to obtain superior performance and competitive advantage. Furthermore, the establishment of systems with an increasing capability to instantly report deviations, make predictions/ forecasts are made available within the smart factory, facilitating proactive behavior to set up countermeasures. Naturally, all these should happen in the big data context (increased data volume, the increased velocity at which data is produced, captured in a wide variety of formats, and exchanged automatically and autonomously). Therefore, it is foreseen that providing a comprehensive and coherent review of the possible smart factory's enabling technologies will facilitate designing and configuring the smart factory. Based on extant literature, the proposed core enabling technologies are revealed in Figure 2.24.

The smart entities (smart objects and software) communicate and interact via CPS, IoT, and cloud technologies which consider as the main pillars of SF (Prist, et al., 2019; Feldmann, et al., 2018; Herrmann, 2018), which allow entities to have communication, computing, precise control, remote coordination and autonomous-decision-making abilities (Caputo, et al., 2016). A digital factory under IoT philosophy, CPS produces tremendous sets of data stored in local or cloud repositories that require novel technologies and methodologies to be converted into business intelligence. (Yang, et al., 2019). Data gathered via sensors' networks are processed and evaluated by big data

technologies (Herrmann, 2018; Feldmann, et al., 2018). In this context, CPS is digital representation technologies of physical entities and processes based on embedded sensors networks, connected to other digitalized, virtual objects and processes to form digital twins (Feldmann, et al., 2018). CPS includes various objects, machines, products, devices, production facilities, buildings, and logistics components that all contain embedded systems. CPS entities are connected independently with other entities via Machine-to-machine (M2M) communication, (Herrmann, 2018; Mittal, et al., 2017).

Figure 2.24: SF enabling technologies

The physical entities and processes are equipped by embedded minicomputers or microprocessors to facilitate controlling, regulating, monitoring, and gathering information of the corresponding system (Herrmann, 2018). Sensors and actuators accompany the embedded systems networks, which work independently, allow tracking and recording environmental changes data. The gathered data contribute to executing autonomous, decentralized control and regulation processes (Feldmann, et al., 2018), whereas actuators are the implementational arm of CPS to affect their environment physically (Herrmann, 2018). Real-time data availability enables peer-to-peer communication, comparison, and the fusion of related data from all smart entities and systems to form a healthy prediction base for all objects at all levels. A healthy configured diagnostic system enables factory management to optimize maintenance programs, achieve just-in-time production, and support downtime reductions

(Herrmann, 2018). In this context, the digital product memory is production information (requirement, progressing, etc.) that accompanies the workpiece in the producing process. Each workpiece carries automatically readable and sufficient information for resetting, controlling, retooling and operating the machines autonomously to conduct the required production tasks, which helps achieve a fully decentralized production environment. Automatically and independently circulating (exchanging) the relevant information between the machines and under-operation element leads to real-time and on-going documentation of the product life cycle, allowing fast identification of faults and defects in the production system (Feldmann, et al., 2018; Herrmann, 2018).

The real-time exchange of enormous amounts of data among smart entities provides the foundations to ensure integration, and advanced processing of a varied set of data is a core prerequisite to create an intelligent and flexible system. Thus, the core mission of gathering and analyzing data is to identify patterns and causalities while providing predictive models and building knowledge (Herrmann, 2018; Odważny, et al., 2018b). The interconnectivity of smart factory's entities stems from IoT, "a global information network composed of large numbers of interconnected Things," to form a digitally integrated manufacturing enterprise including physical entities, services, and software such as ERP, MES, SCM, to name a few (Yang, et al., 2019).

The usage of ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) and CIM (Computer Integrated Manufacturing) support I4.0 in configuring SF to provide prolific databases for Business Intelligence (BI) tools. Within such a structure, the integration of ERP, BI, and CIM and the other I4.0 enabling technologies that come together enrich and optimize integration efforts (horizontal, vertical, and end-to-end), knowledge, and smartness for all levels. Thus, ERP, CIM, and BI technologies are considered as the managerial and organizational weapons at strategic levels.

Within such a context, human interface, usability, and simplicity concepts are exposed to significant changes resulting from digitalization. However, all scenarios still consider humans as the center of attention. In this context, human activities tended to be controlled rather than operating activities under I4.0 via advanced Human Machine Interface (HMI) (Herrmann, 2018). Today advanced technologies overlap to configure HMI like VR, AR, and real-time simulation, which became more sensitive to control

via gesture, voice, or touch displays. Thus, mobile devices integrate humans directly into the communication network of the SF (Herrmann, 2018; Karabegović, et al., 2020). The utilization of unified and accepted standards and interfaces facilitate creating active networks and fluent communication among objects, entities, and environments. As an example, using the IPv6 protocol created in 2012 to create a commensurate with broad networks of the distributed entities in the context of smart factories (Herrmann, 2018; Mittal, et al., 2017; Mabkhot, et al., 2018), and to secure high connectivity and interactivity among smart factory entities is highly preferable for manufacturing enterprises to have a robust network to guarantee the desired performance of entities. High availability of wired or wireless internet ensures a connected CPS environment and the ongoing exchange and abundance of data. Wireless LANs (Local Area Network) play an essential role in ensuring entities' connection (Herrmann, 2018). Using cloud computing solutions enables the smart factory to implement of service-orientation philosophy across all enterprise functions effectively. This enables outsourcing required IT solutions, allowing a flexible and needs-oriented model and decreasing the investment in IT infrastructure. Keeping up with the latest technologies that are provided by the external or internal provider of cloud computing services falls into three core classes: Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS), The Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS), and Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) (Herrmann, 2018; Sjödin, et al., 2018).

In the smart factory context, automation is a core pillar to optimize and accelerate production processes. Combining digitalization and artificial intelligence makes the production process function more intelligent and systematic, where preplanned processes are executed autonomously or automatically. The automation degree ranges from partial to semiautomatic to full automation (Herrmann, 2018). Full automation is required for smart factory operations where the advanced control system executes required tasks to accomplish the workpiece. The most suitable type of automation for the smart factory is flexible automation, an advanced version of programmable automation. It decreases setup time to near zero, including retooling and reprogramming through the smart machines' self-organizing (Groover, 2010; Burke, et al., 2017). Robots' essential role stems from a required automation degree in smart manufacturing, high overlapping with CPS and M2M. Along with a wide range of abilities, innovative features of robots, such as smartness and interaction, encourage

increasing embracement of the robots (Herrmann, 2018; Benotsmane, et al., 2019; Rüb, et al., 2019).

The additive manufacturing (AM) (3D printer) has a vital role in configuring and enhancing smart factory efficiency and effectiveness (Herrmann, 2018; Groover, 2010; Mittal, et al., 2017). For additional details, see section 2.2.2.4.

2.2.4 Mapping of SF Capabilities: Features, Design Principles, and Enabling Technologies

This section presents a perspective on how the different characteristics, design principles, and enabling technologies can be clustered and related to create a consolidated and compact mapping. Table 2.12 below shows the mapping.

Table 2.12: Capability building features, design principles, and enabling technologies

Capabilities	Proposed Smart factory's features	Proposed Design principles	Core enabling technologies
Autonomous Capability (entities, process)	Self-controlled	Virtualisation Digitalisation Interoperability Integrated system Standardisation Flexibility Modularity Decentralisation	CPS
	Self-organization		BD
	Self-configuration		IoT
	Self-coordination		CC
	Self-diagnostic		AM
	Self-decision		Robotics
	Self-compare		CIM
	Self-optimization		ERP
	Self-adapt		Simulation
	Self-predict		AR
Dynamic Interaction Capability	Connectivity	Virtualization Digitalization Interoperability Integrated system Standardisation Flexibility Service Orientation Decentralisation Safety and Security	CPS
	Integrability		BD
	Networked		IoT
	Real-time Skills		CC
	Accessibility		AM
	Transparency		Robotics
	Traceability		CIM
	Automation		ERP
	Smooth data flow		Simulation
Customising Capability	Need-oriented	Virtualisation Digitalisation Service Orientation Modularity Standardisation integration system Safety and Security	IoT
	Small-lot order		CC
	Customisation		BD
	Individualised product		ERP
Intelligence Capability	Info-integration from heterogeneous sources	Virtualization Digitalization Interoperability Integration	Simulation
	Intelligent visualization		AR
Intelligence Capability	Info-integration from heterogeneous sources	Virtualization Digitalization Interoperability Integration	CPS
	Intelligent visualization		IoT
Intelligence Capability	Info-integration from heterogeneous sources	Virtualization Digitalization Interoperability Integration	BD
	Intelligent visualization		CC

	Real-time data availability from heterogeneous sources	Service Orientation Safety and Security Decentralization	AM CIM ERP BI AR Robotics Simulation
	Intelligent analysis		
	Intelligent Learning		
	Intelligent sensing		
	Intelligent reconfiguration		
	Intelligent proactive behavior		
	Intelligent awareness		
	Intelligent predictability		
Competitive Capability	Agility	Virtualisation Digitalisation Interoperability Integrated system Standardization Flexibility Service Orientation Modularity Safety and Security Decentralization	CPS IoT BD CC AM CIM ERP BI AR Robotics Simulation
	Lean		
	Adaptability		
	Sustainability		
	Optimization		
	Responsive		
	Scalability		
	Efficiency		

In this table (13), capability clusters are related to the desired SF features, design principles, and supporting technologies. This table provides a compact classification and clustering based on extant literature, and this mapping can be utilized as a guide for drawing the implementation's roadmap. Each capability cluster is discussed below:

Autonomous Capability is the ability of SF's entities to smartly, autonomously, and speedily behave according to the situation (contextual behave) and current circumstances, including all self-abilities. Each self-feature cannot be discussed in isolation from other self-features because they are highly correlated and intertwined in their creation-techniques and their outputs and tend to be more integrated with each other to establish auto-capabilities. Another critical aspect to remember is that building a set of self-features for entities via interaction and integration of other features, technologies, and design principles are required for building autonomous capabilities.

Naturally, design principles are fundamental bases for many enabling technologies to produce desired features and their operational objects which cooperate in obtaining these principles. CPS, IoT, BD, and CC technologies cannot assure interoperability between entities unless applying integrated system, standardization, and modularity

principles. These coherently integrated relations impose the compulsory presence of these principles and technologies together, as is exposed in Table 2.12.

Dynamic Interaction Capability includes the properties of products, parts, materials, and processes in which they can dynamically interact within the system. Many of these properties share the formation of these abilities via the individual or collective effort of many enabling technologies: CPS, BD, IoT, CC, AM, AR, Robots, Simulation, as well as other supporting technologies. The existence of design principles forms a proper environment to achieve interacting-features such as connectivity, integrability, networked, real-time skills, accessibility, transparency, traceability, and smooth data flow. For instance, CPS, IoT, big data, and all related sub-technologies cooperate to create connectivity. A set of design principles like Virtualization, Digitalization, Interoperability, Integrated system, Standardization, flexibility, Service Orientation, and Safety and Security are considered as core-basis for these features. Hence, collaboration scenarios among the design principles and enabling technologies are unlimited since the scenarios are situational-driven and contextual-behaviors.

Customizing Capability includes all requirements to satisfy customers' needs individually. The individualization of the required efforts imposes that multiple configuration scenarios, various technologies, principles, and features cooperate in its formation. This significant overlapping creates individual satisfaction for smart customers.

Different techniques and design principles are involved in forming desired features. For instance, IoT ensures connection; CC provides functional services. BD builds intelligence. BI enables managerial decision-making, AR and simulation represent scenarios and designs. Together, these technologies operate under various design principles such as virtualization, digitalization, service orientation, modularity, standardization, integration, and safety and security.

Intelligence Capability, the individual and dynamic nature of smartness, and distinctive building requirements for each entity enforce full cooperation and interaction of all features, principles, and technologies to build it as it is exposed in Table 2.12. For example, each object requests individual info-integration and unique information. Thus, all entities are involved in compositing this ability. In the same regard, the existence of the core enabling technologies that shape the proper infrastructures to achieve desired features, like info-integration from heterogeneous sources, intelligent visualization,

real-time data availability from varied sources, intelligent analysis, smart learning, intelligent sensing, etc., will become useless unless all underlying design principles. In this context, extracting value from this capability depends on the degree of cooperation, harmonization, and integration which are offered by the volume and variety of data generated by the networked entities to draw the behavior of individualized objects (physical, process, cyber), leading to the consciousness of entities.

Competitive Capability is a set of interacting capabilities oriented to satisfy the business environment's needs and face their challenges. This external-looking capability differs from previously proposed capabilities because it is cumulative results of the interactions of many capabilities, features, principles, and techniques. Therefore, possessing features like agility, lean, adaptability, sustainability, optimization responsiveness, scalability, and efficiency will be a serious reserve for developing competitive advantages to meet the smart consumer's needs and face the smart competitors. Thus, their impacts go beyond the industrial impact to social impact.

This capability is the tangible result side of the smart factory as perceived by multiple stakeholders. It has a direct relationship with the business environment and strategy development. Undoubtedly, achieving each trait requires comprehensive cooperation and integration. Multiple technologies, a family of features, and capabilities come together to provide strategic advantages. Hence, the harmonization of multiple technologies has become a powerful strategic management tool.

All of these capabilities, features, and enabling technologies are shown in the summary diagram given in Figure 2.25.

Figure 2. 25: Smart capabilities map

2.2.5 A Comparison of SF and I4.0 Enabling Technologies

The conducted surveys revealed that all the identified technologies for SF and I4.0 show significant commonality, and this character is emphasized in several literature items. Smart factories are recently showing a tendency to merge with industry 4.0 technologies. It is observed that the emerging concept of the smart factory is generally defined by the introduction of industry 4.0 technologies which promote rapid and widespread information flow, integration, and smartness within a manufacturing system. Literature survey up to this point and technologies identified in Figure 2.23 illustrates that the common capabilities and features of the smart factory and I4.0 lie in the technological field, which is mostly built on Industry 4.0's enabling technologies. The topics of standardization, information security, interoperability, integration, customization, interdependence, modularization, similar infrastructures, and so on are common concepts in smart factory, and Industry 4.0 stresses that the utilization of industry 4.0's enabling technologies assists in handling the smart factory transformation challenges, and form the base of smart or future manufacturing systems.

Many authors agreed that Industry 4.0 enabling technologies and smart factory components are alike since SF is based on I4.0 philosophy, such as Strozzi et al.,2017; Kagermann et al., 2013; Herrmann,2018; Feldmann,2018; CRO Forum, 2015; Rojko, 2017; Karabegović et al., 2020; Liao et al.,2014; Resman et al.,2019; Prist et al., 2019; Sjödin et al.,2018; park &Lee,2015; Kang et al.,2016; Mittal et al.,2017; Benotsmane et al.,2019. Figure 2.26 exhibit a sample comparison between smart factory components and industry 4.0 components.

Figure 2. 26: The comparison of the common enabling technologies of SF and I4.0

It is clearly indicated that there is a high degree of similarity and consensus in the determined main components and a significant degree of symmetry in describing the core technologies of smart factories and industry 4.0. Thus, it is impossible to discuss the smart factory in isolation of I4.0. Figure 2.26 presents the shared technologies between I4.0 and SF and the frequency of appearance for each one.

2.3. Business Model

2.3.1 Business Model Conceptualization

A business model explains the concept of how a company does business and makes money. A business model ultimately ties the organization's practical and financial aspects, turning the power and capability of the enterprise into economic value. This demonstrates how business works, facilitates market planning, and promotes execution. The word 'business model' is described as explaining how things are to be achieved to provide value to consumers, how money is spent for sustainability, how an organization is to be run, or how competition for clients in a competitive market is generated and obtained. Business Model, in turn, represents an organization producing, developing, and receiving interest (Duarte, et al., 2020; Gieriej, 2017).

Scholars have sought to provide different definitions and a wide range of terminology to understand the business model (BM), which represents projects and entrepreneurial practices that aim to improve economic, social, and ecological sustainability.

In literature, principles of the business model concept varied, and in various resources, the business model is considered as “an understanding tool”; “description the interactions logics”; “interacted systems description”; “conceptual tool”; “concise description tool”; “description of the monetization mechanism”; “organizational description”; “features and capabilities' description”; “scenarios description”; or “measurement tool (see Table 2.13). All these perspectives are to formalize a business model's essential components that focus on describing the elements, logics, relationships, architectures, and semantics to create desired value.

Therefore, to explain how BM generates and collects value through its activities, many viewpoints have been put forward on business models, which basically illustrate the role of a collection of assets, activities, and alliances that support a cost structure and revenue model in line with the value proposition for a particular customer segment (Bogers, et al., 2015). This perspective lies under “Description of the monetization mechanism,” which received a consensus of 20% of the surveyed authors, such as

Aversa et al. (2015); Brea-Solís et al., (2014); Casadesus-Masanell & Ricart, (2010); Chesbrough & Rosenbloom (2002); Elbers., (2010); Johnson et al., (2008); Seelos and Mair, (2007); Teece, (2010); Trimi et al., (2012), that consider business models as a value creation mechanism (given in Table 2.13).

Amit and Zott, 2001; Brea-Solís et al., 2015; Johnson et al., 2008; Marin et al., 2015; Michelini and Fiorentino, 2012; Morris et al., 2005; Onar & Ustundag, 2018; Osterwalder et al., 2005; Slywotzky & Wise, 2003; Teece, 2010; and Trimi et al., 2012 stressed on the description business model as a representation of the interactions logic, the logical characteristic of enterprise relations and interactions. Others go beyond to consider it as a representation of possible scenarios to realize the required value (such as Slywotzky & Wise, 2003), or as a conceptual tool to represent enterprise activities and how the businesses are done to create desired value (like Elbers, et al. 2010; Michelini and Fiorentino, 2012; Osterwalder et al., 2005).

In the same regard, BM is an essential representation tool of the activity system covering inbound logistics, deliveries, operations, outbound logistics, marketing and sales, and service, besides support tasks. Such activities create value because every activity is successively added to certain material goods and when the activities are improved (Casadesus-Masanell, et al., 2015). Moreover, Table 2.14 shows different BM definitions and summarizes authors' perspectives and their tendencies; thus, the deduced notion from “Table 2.14” considers business models as a representation tool providing a comprehensive understanding of the required models, architectures, interactions, and functional relationships in respect to logics, scenarios, and potential ways to create desired value.

A comprehensive business model should present and consist of proper information about the interaction of managerial, organizational, technological, and human infrastructure to create desired value.

The variety of the conceptualization pillars variety of the business model (as shown in Table 2.14) could be an excellent identifying-base for presenting and configuring a comprehensive business models (BM) review. Therefore, BM is a comprehensive tool, which describes the interactions' logics (organizational relationships) among key entities to configure a conceptual view of monetization mechanism (value creation network), features and capabilities, and potential scenarios.

To summarize, the BM is a representation of required and potential entities' interactions to create the desired value, including humans, physical, and cyber entities.

Table 2.13: Different conceptualization pillars of BM

<i>Conceptualization's pillars</i>	% of appearance	Authors
Description of the interactions logics “Business logic.”	25%	Amit and Zott, 2001; Amit and Zott, 2015; Brea-Solís et al.,2015; Casadesus-Masanell& Ricart, 2010;Elbers, et al.,2010; Marin et al., 2015; Michelini and Fiorentino, 2012; Morris et al.,2005; Onar & Ustundag,2018; Osterwalder et al.,2005;; Stoilkovska et al.,2015; Teece, 2010; Trimi et al.,2012; Wirtz. et al.,2016.
Description of monetization mechanism	20%	Amit and Zott,2015; Aversa et al.,2015; Brea-Solís et al.,2015; Casadesus-Masanell & Ricart,2010; Chesbrough & Rosenbloom ,2002; Elbers.,2010; Johnson et al., 2008; Seelos and Mair,2007; Stoilkovska et al.,2015; Teece,2010; Trimi et al., 2012;
Interacted systems description	15%	Amit and Zott,2001; Amit and Zott, 2015; Aversa et al.,2015; Jerman et al., 2019; Johnson et al.,2008; Marin et al., 2015; Michelini and Fiorentino,2012; Osterwalder et al.,2005; Slywotzky & Wise,2003.
Overall understanding tool	10%	Amit and Zott,2015; Chesbrough & Rosenbloom, 2002; Morris et al., 2005; Onar & Ustundag, 2018; Teece, 2010; Wirtz et al., 2016.
Conceptual tool	7%	Elbers.,2010; Michelini and Fiorentino,2012; Osterwalder et al.,2005; Stoilkovska et al.,2015.
strategic tool	7%	Amit and Zott,2015; Osterwalder et al.,2005; Seelos and Mair,2007; Slywotzky & Wise, 2003.
Features and capabilities' description	7%	Amit and Zott,2001; Chesbrough &Rosenbloom,2002; Jerman et al.,2019; Seelos and Mair,2007.
Concise description tool	5%	Marin et al., 2015; Morris et al.,2005; Wirtz. et al.,2016.
Analysis tool	3%	Onar & Ustundag,2018; Teece,2010
Organizational structure description	2%	Slywotzky & Wise,2003

Table 2. 14: Business model definitions

<i>Authors</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i>Concept</i>
Jerman et al.	2019	"Is a category of organization models, which describes business features."
Onar & Ustundag	2018	"Is a comprehensive tool to understand the way of doing the business of the firms and to analyze their performance and competitive strategies through the design of their products or services offered to the market."
Marin et al.	2015	"A living organism" influenced by different factors, such as leadership and top management orientation."
Brea-Solís et al.	2015	"As the logic of the enterprise, the way it operates, and how it creates and captures value for its stakeholders."
Aversa et al.	2015	"A modular design composed of three basic elements: value creation, delivery and capture."
Stoilkovska et al.	2015	"Is a conceptual frame for identifying how a company creates, fulfils and extracts values."
Michelini and Fiorentino	2012	"Is also defined as a conceptual tool, which is which elements are a set of concepts, objects and their relationships, which expresses the business logic of a specific organisation."
Trimi et al.	2012	"Describes how things have to be done to deliver value to customers, where to put the money for the sustainability of the firm, and how to manage the organization."
Casadesus-Masanell & Ricart	2010	"Description of how it operates, creates and captures value for stakeholders in a competitive marketplace." (Casadesus-Masanell, et al., 2010)
Elbers.	2010	"Is considered as a conceptual tool that represents the company's underlying mechanism how a business creates, delivers, and captures customer value".
Ricart	2010	"Reflection of the firm's realized strategy."
Teece	2010	"Articulates the logic, the data and other evidence that support a value proposition for the customer, and a viable structure of revenues and costs for the enterprise delivering that value."
Johnson et al.	2008	"Consist of four interlocking elements, that taken together, create and deliver value."
Seelos and Mair	2007	"A set of capabilities that is configured to enable value creation consistent with either economic or social strategic objectives."
Osterwalder et al.	2005	"A conceptual tool that contains a set of elements and their relationships and allows expressing the business logic of a specific firm."
Morris et al.	2005	"Is a concise representation of how an interrelated set of decision variables in the areas of venture strategy, architecture, and economics are addressed to create sustainable competitive advantage in defined markets."
Slywotzky & Wise	2003	"A set of recipes for firm activities that incorporate organizational design and strategy."
Chesbrough & Rosenbloom	2002	"The business model provides a coherent framework that takes technological characteristics and potentials as inputs and converts them through customers and markets into economic outputs."
Amit and Zott	2001	"A business model is a system of interdependent activities that enlarge the boundaries of an organization."

2.3.2 Philosophy and Its Importance

The interaction between digital platforms, industries, and cultures is becoming more and more volatile and interlinked as the world is increasingly digital, the market is increasingly more competitive, and the environment becomes more chaotic and complicated. The rapid penetration and broad deployment of digitalization create opportunities as well as threats for a whole ecosystem and related companies, especially traditional businesses. The emergence of digital platforms, smart and digital economy, high connectivity, increased integrability, intelligent, agile, and lean processes lay the groundwork of novel and innovative business models, bringing radical changes and having significant effects that eventually promote smart organizations.

This exponential rise in environmental volatility and cultural transition and the increasing pace of transformation in the enterprise, and the increased use of digital technologies create a rapidly changing and different global business landscape. In this regard, El Sawy and Pereira (2013) indicate numerous digitalization's implications: temporary competitive advantage, perishability of the strategies, the requirement for dynamic capabilities; technologies and services are becoming outdated rapidly; and constant innovation becoming vital.

Today's ecosystems operate predicated on cooperation and integration of all participants. Thus the "coopetition" (is a combination of the words "competition" and "cooperation") is relentless. Stakeholders' fate is linked to each other's and the community's destiny. Business models and new technologies coevolve, and if we study them in an isolation manner, we cannot really grasp their trajectories (El Sawy , et al., 2013). Furthermore, businesses have to operate in more complex environments in response to time, innovation, socio-economic progress, and downturns (Tomlins, 2014; Akyuz, et al., 2019). The reflection of ICT fusion with manufacturing technologies (I4.0) opens up new incredible capabilities for both individual and collective (business, groups). As an example, these capabilities include fast communication, objects interaction, cognitive skill, social networks, e-commercial, accessibility to a massive amount of information, computerizing capabilities, and reengineering humans relationships (Digilina, et al., 2020; Duarte, et al., 2020), which work together to reconfigure practices, behaviors, activities, processes, businesses, and entire ecosystems.

Even though business models have been central to trade and economic activity since ancient times, the business model definition has become popular and has since gained momentum with the Internet's advent in the mid-nineties (Zott, et al., 2011; Kim, 2015). Digitalization leads to a higher speed of business activities in addition to connectivity. Finally, the value creation sources are expanded by digital technologies, which enable new business models to be developed, digitizing business functions and emerging digital supply and delivery chains. The generated data can optimize each entity and the entire value chain (Kahre, et al., 2017; El Sawy , et al., 2013; Aagaard, 2019; Akyuz, et al., 2019). Changes imposed by digitalization extended to include all aspects of life (political, social, economic, and technological), thereby, compel enterprises to cope with the new challenges via emerging novel business models (BM) based on customer-oriented and advanced technologies (Digilina, et al., 2020; Pólkowski, et al., 2017; Aagaard, 2019). This trend is a global paradigm shift in understanding strategic management through innovative technologies in the age of digital economy, accounting for the transformation of goods, services, systems, organizational structures and business models (Kahre, et al., 2017). Furthermore, digitalization fundamentally transformed the management of the supply chain's information flows to reshape the conditions under which businesses communicate. The value chains are reconfigured to facilitate new Internet-based organizational structures (Rossignoli, et al., 2015). In the same regard, BM creates an unavoidable value proposition for consumers, obtains a favourable cost and risk structure, and considers the vital resources to be used and the key relationships to be formed. This allows companies to guarantee that their strategic or operational management adopts essential elements (Duarte, et al., 2020) to keep pace with the new digital world (Ziyadin, et al., 2020). Aagaard (2019) emphasized the digital business model's role in the measurable enhancement of business performance by examining how businesses implement and execute digital technologies and business models. Innovation, as a growth engine for the vertical and horizontal industry, is therefore, seen as inevitable in the digital business.

I4.0 provides an appropriate environment for modern, creative, and evolving business models to reach a more sustainable level via the models are powered by intelligent data generated from supporting systems and infrastructures (Gu, et al., 2019). I4.0 encompasses the entire supply network (including the design and development of products as well as organizational and functional management) and thus involves the

introduction of new business models and systems (Prause, 2015). Thus, I4.0 comes to set a unique path of generating customer value, creating innovative business models, imposing socially and environmental sustainability, and enhancing flexibility and robustness via a set of integrated entities that change practice/behaviors (Duarte, et al., 2020; Bradley, et al., 2020). In this respect, Duarte et al. (2020) underlined that I4.0 automatically configures many facets of business processes, including product, product quality, production time, risk, and eco-friendly activity, which go with the lean and green understanding characteristics. Lean management calls for each operation and task to be evaluated to eliminate any worthless actions (wastes), diminish useless resources, and minimize expenses and time. Waste reduction and avoiding non-value stages within the value-network, and delivering standard and stable products at low cost are required. In the same regard, green management seeks to reduce the environmental risks and impacts by reducing environmental waste in businesses and partners to achieve benefit and market goals.

It is worth mentioning that the business model outlines an enterprise's framework to serve its clients and market growth factors. Varied actors, resources, and business activities are included in a good business model. It is considered as an approach to produce and sale the product, bringing value to the product and company, sustaining the relations with the customer, and determining the mechanisms for sale, costing, and revenue collection (Pólkowski, et al., 2017). Today, the outsourced support of the business model (cloud services) adds complementary organizational skills and capabilities, such as the capacity of human resources to develop quickly in response to demand growth, process management capabilities, and the ability to manage global operations (Kirchmer, 2015).

Most researchers agreed that e-business, strategic management and innovation, and technology management are key concerns linked to the business model configuration (Zott, et al., 2011). They also agreed that the enterprises' master core competencies and ability has been a core success factor for business models (Brenner, et al., 2015). Indeed, disruptive technological changes and strategic aspects have opened up new horizons for the new business models by encouraging companies to radically change their way of organizing and participating in economic interactions, both within and across company and market borders, including how firms communicate both suppliers and consumers.

The increasing emphasis on the e-business models arises from creating value, optimizing performance, and sustaining companies' competitive advantage, especially with the growing digitalization rate (Zott, et al., 2011). The introduction of Web 2.0 technologies has also altered the essence of digital co-operation and intellectual skills and thus created environmental chaos, supported by an open-innovation and worldly shareable-sources (El Sawy , et al., 2013). More digital networking platforms such as social networks, mobile telephone applications, and web 2.0 apps are coming on the market, and buyers are empowered to communicate with each other and with sellers. These Internet-based technologies often accelerate the obsolescence of classic business models and give consumers more significant power (Rossignoli, et al., 2015). These examples highlight the new and evolving complexity of modern business environment dynamics.

Tepeş et al. (2015) indicate the possibility of creating additional consumer value by using a particular new organizational, strategic and technological approach in an innovative BM. Via the management of the product life cycle and Product-Service System (PSS) strategy, added value can be generated in the customer's mind, along with the presence of contemporary enterprise philosophies (virtual organization, technology networks, new business models, etc.) and advanced technological approaches (ICT, sensors, smart entities, new materials, etc.) (Tepes, et al., 2015).

Teece (2010) points out the essential nature of a business model in the way the company provides consumers with value, entices customers to pay money for the value, and turns those transactions into income. In other words, businesses will figure out what customers are looking for, their anticipations, and paying for it. The way a company organizes this is at the heart of its business model. A business model is a term that describes how companies operate and build stakeholder values. Business models' main concern areas are IT implementation, technology management, strategic issues, and product-service innovation. Besides, business model functions are to classify market segments, formulate strategies, express values, determine value chain structure, explain the enterprise's position, and evaluate cost structure and profitability (Jerman, et al., 2019; El Sawy , et al., 2013).

Gassmann et al. (2014) and Pólkowski, et al. (2017) emphasized that a business model would tackle all four elements: what, how, who and value, specified in the circle is shown in Figure 2.27. "What" means the critical promotions of the organization, the

"who" implies targets the intended clients, "how" means the way to satisfy customer requirements. The business model also represents the source of "income" for the company.

Figure 2. 27: The sequential logic of entity relationships in BM

Source: (Pólkowski, et al., 2017)

PWC's report (2016) stressed that pioneer industrial companies offer their customers disruptive digital solutions, i.e., platforms and data-driven services via disruptive digital business models that reconfigure value networks to increase value sources such as digital revenue and optimize customer participation and accessibility. In smart ecosystems, digital outputs and complete solutions are provided to customers, leading to disruptive business models.

Classic business models are designed based on a firm-centric approach. However, it's easy to see why traditional BMs are insufficient due to the nature of the IoT ecosystem in that companies need to work with competitors and industries. Moreover, fast changes in technology industry market conditions mean that firms need to adapt quickly to consumer and market demands to thrive and remain competitive (Aagaard, 2019).

El Sawy and Pereira (2013) and Aagaard (2019) both underline that the functions and role of IT in organizations have changed over the years from the viewpoint of interactions (IT as communications channel), via an immersion perspective considered IT as a business environment, to the view of convergence that considered IT as the fabric of organizations. Recently, it is well-proven and well-supported that IT is an enabler for most capabilities of smart environments, products, and enterprises. Modular

platforms can be modified and interacted in various ways, and digital business ecosystems require these innovative new technologies and strategies for value creation and for capturing and integrating capabilities across borders. This is shown in Figure 2.28.

Figure 2.28: IT interactional evolution

Source: Created by the author based on (Aagaard, 2019; El Sawy , et al., 2013) perspectives

2.3.3 Benefits and Challenges of IT-Based Business Models

At the organizational and industrial level, the manifestation and penetration of the complexities and dynamism of emerging business environments around us are imposing destructive changes, which systemically distorts ecosystem boundaries by means of new digital technologies, platforms, diverse and smart capabilities, and environmental opportunities (El Sawy , et al., 2013). Therefore, embracing a novel, BM is accompanied by complex challenges in cultural, strategic, operational, organizational, and financial aspects, with significant and interlaced impact on enterprises' capability (Copani, et al., 2014). BM innovation involves the proposal for

a new or amended value, new business processes (especially in the supply chain), new target clients and markets (Kirchmer, 2015). Kahre et al. (2017) stressed that digital technologies increasingly influence our everyday life, and emphasize that IT and innovative technologies can provide sustainable competitive advantages. In the same regard, encouraging business-IT alignment to create value, support business strategy, and driving innovation.

Digital business ecosystems, unlike other business environments, cannot be expected to return in any kind of "equilibrium" after disturbance changes. Instability ensures that cause and effect can ripple or completely destroy the ecosystem's function or survival in an unpredictable manner. Preparing these unknowns calls for a new form of management sensitivities: a capacity to develop new structures and insights and a pragmatic vision for 'black swan' risk. Due to the interconnectedness of the fates of all participants and that of the environment, rivals also collaborate together for "coopetition," for example in developing technical standards or shared channels (El Sawy , et al., 2013).

The traditional business-centric business model view focuses on a firm's viewpoint and value creation for its clients. Conversely, in the ecosystems model, the participants are autonomous and loosely connected in business environments, interdependent for their development and survival. The firm's ecosystems extended to contain all cross-boundaries partners. Thus, it is not easy to draw a border surrounding ecosystems (Leminen, et al., 2019).

The significant aspect of I4.0 is value creation, which involves increasing efficiency and developing contemporary business models by presenting new opportunities that are likely to disturb conventional business models. An increase in productivity created by I4.0 technologies can lead to further employment and increased consumer demand. However, the use of advanced technologies and processes can also have a redundancy impact on jobs, accompanied by technological changes that can positively and negatively affect employment (create, reconstructions, and demise) (Jerman, et al., 2019). In the same regard, I4.0 sets a new course to consumer value creation via a clear understanding of the customer requirements and high exchangeability of that data all over the value network (Duarte, et al., 2020).

ICT enables enterprises to adopt sustainable business models to manage upstream and downstream relations of the production chain so as to increase the efficiency of the value chain as a whole (Rossignoli, et al., 2015; Gu, et al., 2019), i.e., the IoT-based business model requires cooperation between our fellow businesses, communication with customers and others, and all IT applications are a vital resource in the IoT business model, while in traditional business applications are the auxiliary components (Pólkowski, et al., 2017). Thus, novel business logic and knowledge are the leading and primary competitive advantage for an organization (Jerman, et al., 2019), through utilizing IoT to produce more data that helps them to interact with their customers effectively, and reduce operating costs or increasing organizational performance (Pólkowski, et al., 2017).

A single company is often struggling to manage the variety of resources and practices it needs, and the business model is likely to influence and organize collective actions rather than merely focusing on individual opinions and the environment. A networked business model facilitates collective value creation by providing shared insights on their incentives, activities, and resources (Leminen, et al., 2019). While Hansen (2014) claims that a prerequisite for any business model's effectiveness is that both the consumer and the organization delivering the product or service will gain tangible benefits. A premium business model is successful only if it provides both vendor and consumer measurable-advantages (Hansen, 2014). Therefore, BM provides a primary value proposition for consumers, provides a beneficial structure of cost-risk, and considers key resources and key relationships that need to be formed. This helps companies to ensure that crucial elements for their strategic or operational management are implemented (Duarte, et al., 2020).

Ahmad-Kahn et al. (2019) stressed that upgradable products have a promising potential to extend product life and satisfy the changing customers' desires by incorporating practical and efficient changes over several successive life cycles. An upgradable product concept's potential benefits include resource efficiency, new business prospects, and lower overall cost to the customer over the life cycles (Ahmad-Khan, et al., 2019).

2.3.4 Existing Business Model Framework Designs and Components

In the literature, there exists a number of business model framework designs and components. Several authors take into account considerable impacts of innovation

level, product development, consumers' behavior, economic pressures, a threat to competition, state's policies, suppliers, investors as well as many other environmental factors on the company in their business model (Duarte, et al., 2020; Gu, et al., 2019). Recently, it appears that the accelerated influence of ICT and artificial intelligence began to reconfigure the BM concept, a theoretical paradigm that explains the elements and fundamental processes of value-creation and capture in an enterprise.

In this section, the author attempted to review six main frameworks in literature used for business modeling with detailed discussions of their ontologies and component structures. Ontology is a formalization of a framework, vocabulary, and their semantics of the essential components of a business model. Thereby, clearness in terminology for the frameworks and components helps to construct the company's core logic, desired interactions, and interrelationships to understand the business model.

The literature on the business model studied identifies the aspects and interactions explaining how an organization produces revenue and the market value of a wide range of BMs. The number of components mentioned by scholars varies in their proposed framework, reflecting their perspective for BM's configuration (see the summary Table 2.16).

1. BM Canvas framework

Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010) suggested the BM canvas as a blueprint that encompasses nine components: main stakeholders, key operations, key sources, value proposition, groups of consumers, networks, customer relations, cost structure, and revenue streams, to represent the organization's philosophy, as described in Figure 2.29.

The concept series starts with a "value proposition" connected to "consumers segments," accompanied by channels" and "customer relationships." A question asked in "revenue streams" is what customers are ready to pay and should be considered as "key resources," "key activities" and "key partners" to finalize with "cost structure."

Figure 2.29: BM Canvas

Overall, this model structure contributes to the development of a brilliant business with profits and sustainability techniques. The value creation includes the core operations, capital, and alliances. Value delivery covers the goods and provided-services, the distribution, dissemination, and sales networks, the customer segments, and the established relationships. Expenses and revenues generated by a business are represented by value capture (Duarte, et al., 2020).

2. Product-Service System (PSS) BM framework

The transition from products to solutions is not only relevant to the transformation of the product-oriented to a PSS but can include the restructuring of the business model, as it is described in Figure 2.30. The core components are drawn from the Business Model Canvas (BMC). Thus, it is a modified version of BMC.

Figure 2.30: PSS framework

Due to the lack of required infrastructure, many production processes are still unable to cope with big data. The new ways of designing, delivering, and running Product-Service Systems (PSS) become feasible through the sensor, cloud, and internet technology and evolving approaches such as business analysis and mobile computing. Thus, the significant influence of industry 4.0 is represented by the transition from the manufacturer to the manufacturing service provider. The impact of PSS goes beyond physical products to encompass the creative processes, services, and innovative ways of communication and collaboration, which ultimately provide novel forms of value creation and create an innovative business model. (Kölsch, et al., 2017).

3. The RCOV framework

The company's success relies on the relationship and interaction nature between its finances, organization, and ability to propose a novel market-value. There are three core components of BM in the context of RCOV: tools and skills (RC) to support or complement; business organization (O) inside or within a value network; and value

proposals (V) by delivery of goods and services. These components describe business expenditures structure, amount, and sales, therefore, its profit and its sustainability in the long-run. The competencies refer to the know-how, skills, and abilities that can be combined, leveraged, enhanced, and changed. The 'organization' refers to the variety of activities carried out by a company as part of the value chain and its partnerships with third parties (including vendors, rivals, regulators and supplementaries) to leverage its resources and competencies. Finally, the "value propositions" are eventually delivered in the form of products and services to consumers. Value propositions concern three aspects: 'What?' "Will be offered (products and services)," how?' it be proposed (access conditions), and "to whom be suggested?" "(clients). (Demil, et al., 2010; Moyon, et al., 2013).

Figure 2.31: RCOV framework
Source: (Demil, et al., 2010)

4. Value-Information-Process (VIP) framework

One of the theoretical BM models that focus specifically on the networked operating processes and interdependencies is the value-for-information process (VIP) framework suggested by Solaimani and Bouwman (2012), as given in Figure 2.32. The framework aims at (a) providing a description of the inter-organization relationships and interdependencies underlying Business Models, (b) promoting a thorough review of the related relationships of intra-organizational interactions and interdependency, and (3) suggesting multiple review stages.

In this model, 'V' represents the formation and sharing of values between participants, from tangible streams (e.g., monetary flows) to intangible currents (e.g., cooperative partnership). 'I' means information and knowledge sharing and development amongst stakeholders, from unprocessed data to information and knowledge. The "P" represents the fundamental processes underlying the networking business. In the same regards,

four essential elements of networked enterprise partnerships are included on the horizontal axis of the framework, i.e.: (1) business network delineation; (2) network resources and capabilities; and (3) networked entities interactions; and (4) relationships and connections between partnering actors (Solaimani, et al., 2017).

Figure 2.32: VIP framework

Source: Based on Solaimani& Bouwman, 2012 (Solaimani, et al., 2017)

5. The Solution business model framework

The four stages of the solution BM (develop solutions, create demand, sell a solution, and deliver solution) and three interplay classes (commercialization, industrialization, and innovation platform) are vital aspects of the system. Eight types of skills and management practices (as it is shown in Figure 2.33) reflect the interactions of solution process phases with commercialization and industrialization. The framework consists of: (1) developing solutions: development of values and solutions; (2) creating demand: value proposition and solutions availability; (3) selling solution: quantification value and solution composition; and (4) deliver the solution: value testing and distribution of solutions. The framework also includes four external capabilities: Strategic Planning, Management Systems, Support for Infrastructures, and Human Resources Management (Storbacka, 2011).

The business model approach system has three distinguishing characteristics. First, commercialization and industrialization and operate in a synchronized manner. Under the solutions business model approach, the consumers become a deeply inter-dependent entity into the solution-development process, and industrialization and commercialization are getting to be interdependent and inter-functional operation (Ibid). Secondly, standardization and systematic improvements of components and solutions to ensure scalability, repetitiveness, and delivery efficiency. Third, supporting capabilities that are not visible to customers is the base of building a solution business platform.

Figure 2.33: The solution business model framework
Source: (Storbacka, 2011)

6. Beacon Business model framework

The interaction of Enterprise Financial Model, Internal Operating Model, and Network Partner Model configure this model, which ultimately forms the business model characteristics and enterprise, as depicted in Figure 2.34. The author has deliberately portrayed each of the secondary components (which are described in Tables 2.15) at the same level of consideration regardless of any apparent hierarchy since their relative importance is not generalizable and differs by the company preferences.

Figure 2.34: Business model 'Beacon' framework

Table 2.15: Secondary components of 'Beacon' framework description

Internal Operating Model	
Component	Description
Product Portfolio	Product variety, quality, design, features, packaging, sizing, service, warranties
Brand Management	Price, Promotion, Placement; Including R&D, brand development, activation
Sales Management	Customer acquisition, retention, relationships, assessment, deletion
Supply Chain Management	Plan, Source, Make, Deliver
Coordination	Framework for information exchange, decision-making, transacting within and outside the business
Organization	Strategic capabilities, people, rewards, structure, and process
Enterprise Financial Model	
Revenue	The revenue-generating mechanism from value creation
Cost	The costs associated with value creation, delivery, and capture
Cash	The working capital model and the mechanism by which free cash is generated and used
Asset & Investment	Fixed, tangible, and intangible assets; Investments in innovation and adjacent spaces
Ownership	Stakeholder mapping; decision rights
Risk	A mechanism to cope with / leverage different types of risks and market uncertainty
Network Partner Model	
Consumer	Model for value creation, delivery and capture with end-user
Customer	Model for value creation, delivery and capture with the first-order intermediary
Supplier	Strategic sourcing considerations for secure, reliable, quality, flexibility in supply
Complement	Appropriateness, complementarity regime, co-specialization
Society	Corporate social responsibility and ethical behaviour
Environment	Sustainable ecological and environmental practices

Source: (Parekh, 2016)

Table 2.16: Summary table for existing business model frameworks

BUSINESS MODEL FRAMEWORK	ATTRIBUTES	COMPONENTS	CORE PHILOSOPHY
BM CANVAS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conceptual instrument • Comprehensive • Simplified • Useful and flexible tool • Long-term planning tool. • Possesses key categories. • Development tool • Modifiable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customers segment • Value proposition • Channels • Customers' relationship • Revenue stream • Key resources • Key activities • Key partners • Cost structures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer-centric • Comprehensive view • Co-operation centric • Multi-level Integration centric • Network interdependencies
THE RCOV FRAMEWORK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic approach • Ongoing interactions snapshot • For enterprise or a set of enterprises. • Focus on capabilities and knowledge. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resources & competences • Value propositions • The internal and external organization • Volume & structure of revenues • Volume & structure of costs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to leverage resources and competencies. • What is the internal and external organization of the business. • How to supply products and services to markets. • Interaction of finances, organization and ability to create value.
PRODUCT-SERVICE SYSTEM BMS FRAMEWORK (PSS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fulfil client needs • Enhancing customer loyalty. • Faster innovation. • useful and flexible tools • describe the operational environment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Value proposition • Key resources • Key activities • Partnerships • Customers • Revenues and costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customized production • Integrated production • Building unique relationships with clients. • Product-Service oriented

Continued...

Business Model framework	Attributes	Components		Core Philosophy
Value-Information-Process (VIP) framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networked environment • Interdependencies entities. • Interconnected map • Harmonized intents tool • Effective stakeholder's participation. • Operation-oriented. 	Horizontal axis <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business network • Resources and capabilities. • Networked interactions. • Relationships and accountability 	Vertical axis <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Value • Information • Process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing a comprehensive view of BMs' interactions and interdependencies. • Facilitating a systematic analysis of elements interactions and interdependencies. • Networked operational processes • Multiple levels of analysis
Solution business model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration • Customization • Integrated solutions • Servitization • Oriented product/ service systems. • Cross-functional integration. • Standardization and systematic development. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solution process. • Commercialization. • Industrialization, • Solution platform 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individualized offers • Complex customer problems • Interactively designed solutions • Integrative added value • Combining knowledge, products and/or services. • Collaborative solution • Collaborative innovation
Beacon Business model framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Components-centric. • Operation-oriented • Holistic view • Flexible • Cross-functional integration. • Customer-centric 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enterprise financial model. • The internal operating model. • The network partner model. <p>Each one has subcomponents as it shows in Table (2.15)</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What will you sell? • What is the winning aspiration • What is the market? • Who is the customer? • What is the value proposition? • How will you win?

The application of each framework allows management to develop a clear understanding of the business model concept and the transformation needed to implement it. Table 2.16 summarizes the considered frameworks in this study regarding attributes, components, and core philosophy. It appears that the BMC and Beacon are more overarching frameworks, which combine existing elements and their intended interactions holistically to configure an enterprise's business.

PSS framework allows technological innovation and collaboration under the operational approach; thus, it would correspond with smart factories' requirements. While RCOV framework focuses on relationships and interactions to create value, thus is compatible with the business network principles. Also, VIP framework concentrates on networked operating processes and knowledgeable-interdependencies, which are suitable to be a base of networked creation of value. While the solution framework relies on unifying multiple stakeholders' conflicting requirements via integrating capabilities and management practices, this collaborative is coped with smart factories' requirements.

Generally, business models explain how companies produce, provide and catch value (Kölsch, et al., 2017; Digilina, et al., 2020) via building absorptive and dynamic capabilities which are strictly related to systematically generate value innovation initiatives and value creation innovatively (Matthyssens, 2019). The BM framework or representations are commonly used instruments for evaluating and improving emerged or future business enterprises. The selected framework substantiates or operationalizes the business model concept, and the functional business model framework depicts the convergence and interaction of key decision variables, including the requirement of individual elements that are internally consistent. In fact, "*the BM structure reveals the core of how the market system is integrated more than the sum of its parts (interaction logic).*" It should be simple, transparent, measurable, logical, comprehensive, and operationally applicable, and meaningful (Pfeiffer, et al., 2017). Therefore, scholars and practitioners stress the need to shift the emphasis from conceptualization to BM implementation. It can be considered a comprehensive set of practices that will help companies to execute their strategies.

Accordingly, creating a comprehensive visualization of smart enterprises and their interactions request an overall representation of its business model via a conceptual presenting tool that covers most actions, objects, concepts, and relationships in a

simplified scheme, which expresses the logic behind the business. The unique abilities of the smart factory imposed a sophisticated requirement and connected and complex conditions to operate. In addition to this, they need an advanced intelligent business model to satisfy the environment's need and face business challenges. Thus, BM is a comprehensive representation of intended interactions among heterogeneous entities aiming at developing approaches to goals.

2.4. Various Countries Perspective

2.4.1 Turkish Perspective

Turkey is the 17th largest economy in the world, and its industrial output accounts for 28% of GDP. The GDP growth is projected to slow but to stay around 5% in 2018 (OECD, 2018). The industrial sectors have a significant impact on the global and local economy, which contribute by 80%, 90% of an export ratio for EU and Turkey respectively, but only 30% of Turkey's manufacturing output and 37% of its exports consist of medium- and high-tech products, while these make up 63% of EU exports (Turkstat, 2017).

Turkey positions itself in the global value chain by leveraging its logistical advantage, lower labor costs, and flexible production capabilities; therefore, advanced manufacturing technologies are increasingly being implemented across Turkey, with international companies leading the way. Therefore, Turkey needs to take concrete steps in digitalization and advanced manufacturing to move from growth dependent on cheap labor to that based on high productivity and innovation

Through advanced manufacturing technologies, Turkey can move up the global value chain, ensure its future global competitiveness, and boost the economy. Based on the economy's size, over the next decade, Turkey is expected to invest about 10 to 15 billion TL (about 1 to 1.5 percent of manufacturing revenues) must be invested per year to integrate Industry 4.0 technologies into the manufacturing process over the next ten years (BCG, et al., 2016).

If Turkey fully adapts the industry 4.0 concept, it could save \$15 billion/year in current manufacturing costs. This analysis is based on a 4-7% estimated increase in productivity, considering total production costs (BCG, et al., 2016). According to Turkstat 2019 data, the High-Technology products represent only 3.5% of total sales, and medium-high technology products are 26%. The rest is described as a Low-technology product, and the medium is 70.6, which refers to clear motivation to develop

and embrace destructive technologies. Therefore, utilizing advanced technology and industry 4.0 allows increasing the high technology of Turkish sales. The next table shows the shares of sales from production by technology level – Turkey.

Table 2. 17: Shares of sales from production by technology level

Technology level	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Low technology	39%	37%	37.8%	38.8%	39.1%	38.9%	38.8%	36.4%	35%	36.6%
Medium-low technology	33.6%	35.8%	36.2%	34.8%	34.4%	33.4%	32.9%	34.6%	36%	34%
Medium-high technology	23.8%	24.2%	23%	23.7%	23.5%	24.6%	25%	25.9%	26.1%	26%
High technology	3.6%	3%	3%	2.7%	3%	3.2%	3.3%	3.1%	2.9%	3.5%

Source; TURKSTAT, based on 2020 data,

The increased value added by manufacturing sectors in Turkey reflects the importance and impact of industrial sectors in the Turkish economy, thus developing manufacturing sectors reflected on Turkish GDP at the end. The efforts should exert to raise the productivity and quality of output. The figure below shows the value-add from 2005 to 2017.

Figure 2.35: Value added by manufacturing sectors

Source: TURKSTAT, based on 2017 data

TÜBİTAK study (2017) pointed out that Turkish manufacturing enterprises vary in their awareness and knowledge about industry 4.0 and related technology. Only 22% of manufacturing enterprises have a deep awareness and practical knowledge, and 59% of manufacturing enterprises have general information and knowledge, but 19% do not have any awareness or knowledge. The unfilled knowledge-gap among Turkish manufacturing enterprises leads to avoiding digitalization transformation; therefore, the

effort should be made to fill this gap, facilitating industry 4.0 implementation. The figure below shows a knowledge level related to industry 4.0 technology.

Figure 2.36: Knowledge level
Source: Tubitake, 2016

Figure 2.37 gives a comparative graph of the years 2017, 2018, and 2019 for multiple sectors and shows the importance of the sectors concerning total sales; accordingly, supporting these sectors directly influences the Turkish economy. Base on Turkstat data in 2020, the food manufacturing sector has a remarkable effect on exports by approximately 13.5%, manufacture of basic metals has 12.5%, motor vehicles and trailers are the next effective sectors by 10%. These indicators interpret the reasons for selecting these sectors and giving them a priority in this study.

Figure 2.37: The role of industry sectors
Source: TURKSTAT, based on 2019 data

Consistent with Turkish government trends, which stressed increase digitalization in industrial sectors, many associations conducted a set of studies. Such as TUBITAK has developed in 2017 a roadmap that should prepare the Turkish industry for adoption and development of Industry 4.0 concepts. This roadmap identifies three technology groups, which are digitalization, connectivity, and future factories. Under these groups, eight critical technologies, ten strategic targets, and 29 critical products have been identified to which the Turkish industry should devote its attention (TÜBİTAK, 2017). Also, Boston Consulting Group and TUSIAD in 2017 present the roadmap in cooperation with all stakeholders, which emphasizes the industrial organizations and suppliers need to stay abreast of the technologies that triggered Industry 4.0. Preparing a roadmap for utilizing future opportunities and determining their mutual effects with their business models, more importantly, they need to outline a clear roadmap of their workforce and equipment requirements and act accordingly (BCG, et al., 2016). As such, providing a forward roadmap for selected sectors promote the exerting efforts to embrace digitalization.

2.4.2 Digitization Programs in Various Countries

Manufacturing digitization, smart manufacturing, and smart factory are hot topics. Many governments supported technology advancement through numerous programs to improve countries' productivity. Governments are seeking to create strategies and policies to promote smart manufacturing adoption, from the US Advanced Manufacturing Partnership to Germany's High-Tech 2020 plan, like these programs shown in table 19. Most primary industrial countries believe and act accordingly that digital, interrelated, and interoperable economies are inevitable and encourage having research and innovation efforts related to embracing manufacturing's digitalization. Table 2.18 tackles the various policies and viewpoints in a variety of primary industrial countries.

Table 2.18: Industry 4.0 programs

Country	Program
United States (US)	"Advanced Manufacturing Partnership"
German	"High-Tech Strategy 2020"
French	La Nouvelle France Industrielle (Alliance pour l' Industrie du Futur) (l'usine du Futur)
United Kingdom (UK)	Future of Manufacturing
European Union	"Industry 4.0: Powering Europe" & Factories of the Future
South Korea	Innovation in Manufacturing 3.0 and smart manufacturing
Chinese	Made in China 2025 strategy

Japanese	Super Smart Society 5.0
Singapore	Research, Innovation and Enterprise 2020 plan (RIE2020)
India	Made in India
Australia	Industry 4.0 Testlabs
Finland	Industrial Internet Program
Italy	Fabbrica del Futuro
Netherlands	Smart Factory
Russia	National Technology Initiative
Belgium	Made Different
Sweden	Produktion 2030
Spain	Connected Industry 4.0

CHAPTER 3

SMART FACTORIES REQUIREMENTS

In the context of smart factories (comprehensive digitalization, intercommunication, integration. etc.), all stages of the supply network, starting from the customer, extending to, production system and after-sell product-services (entire value network), are usually accompanied by significant impacts and interrelated requirements. Therefore, combination of smart technologies form the backbone for the entire system. From the onset of industrialization, technological leaps contributed to conceptual and operational shifts that directly influenced the organizational and functional areas of individual and collective work and upstream systems.

I4.0 faces a crucial range of challenges, including lack of skilled labor, aging population, resource-efficient, sustainable industrial growth, mass customization, increased demand volatility, shorter life cycle, competitive supply chain, unpredictable markets, and cost-reduction pressures (Shamim, et al., 2016). Thus, highlighting the requirements are preconditions for embracing smart factories, i.e., qualifications, training, sufficient resources, and flexible and innovative processes (Rüb, et al., 2019).

To envisage all organization elements' integrated performance under smart manufacturing organizations and build an integrated picture of the requirements of digital transformation for traditional factories, and consistent with the outcome of the literature review. The researcher used five integrated aspects of the requirements, including knowledge, managerial, organizational, and technological, and the last thing related to people to build an integrated vision of the essential requirements for setting up smart factories or switching to SF.

3.1 Technological Requirements

Digitalization wave imposes embracing innovative technologies, adopting emerging technology or/ and reusing existed technologies to cope with dynamic challenges and create coherent and integrated systems (Glatzel, et al., 2018; Shamim, et al., 2016). In this regard, Herrmann (2018) underlines the need to acquire new abilities and skills of physical entities like self-optimization, self-diagnosis, self-configuration, smartness, and cognition-enhancing automation level. While Li et al., 2015 point out the gradual changes in traditional equipment enable new levels of capacities like state acquisition,

self-perception and smart-predictions, self-optimizations and self-decisions, self-control, self-organize, and smart-learning to form SF characteristics.

Sjödin et al. (2018) and Karabegović et al. (2020) stressed that embracing a smart factory requires large-scale and systemic transformation for all aspects, building integration and communication among all cyber-physical systems. Also, Martínez et al., 2017 pointed out the reorganization of operations is not intended to mark a radical change in the organization's functioning, but rather adapt the technology and management to the new level of operating systems, automation, and tools which create the potential value of activities. The smart factory based on I4.0 technology involves integrative components (actuators, machines, sensors, robots, conveyors, etc.), ensuring real-time information flow automatically. It becomes a conscious and intelligent factory (Qin et al., 2016). This exchange of data gathered through sensors' networks in a real-time synchronization with their digital twins and simulation production's models enables the CPS role of physical entities (Karabegović, et al., 2020).

In smart factories, technologies blur the boundaries between the physical and digital entities and impose profound changes on human life and work style. Numerous identifications and approaches have emerging to classify the diverse and heterogeneous SF technologies. Businesses and managers find it difficult to keep track of more than 60 different enabling-technologies of both I4.0 and SF (see Tables 2.6 & 2.11). The technologies in the context of smart factory take not only into account the technologies but also the broad spectrum of design principles and characteristics that serve innovative value creation, just to name a few: Virtualization; Digitalization; Interoperability; Self-controlled; Self-organization; Customization; Optimization; and Responsive...so on (see Figure 3.1). SF technological configuration goes beyond identified technologies to an interactive configuring of the desired-features, design-principles, and core technologies. Identifying smart factories' technological requirements (SF) requires a full understanding of the relations of features, principles, and technologies (for more details, see Figure 3.2 and sections 2.2.3-2.2.5).

Figure 3.1: Technological requirements

3.2 Managerial Requirements

3.2.1 Direction-Setting

A) Clear vision and mission

PwC organization stressed on "Evaluate your digital maturity now and set clear targets for the next five years" Therefore, organizations will take the time to identify their vision and draw their strategies in any additional move they take to become truly digital organization (Geissbauer, et al., 2016). Building desired awareness, clear vision, and understanding of smart factory content (concept, technologies, implementation, mechanisms) facilitates the smart factory's implementation (Sjödín, et al., 2018; Glatzel, et al., 2018).

B) Overall-Strategy

Experiences indicate that general advice is needed to build an appropriate strategy to cope with Industry 4.0 challenges (Erol, et al., 2016) and 77 percent of businesses say that Digital Transformation is their top business strategy, according to the Economist Intelligence Unit (EIU) (Pereira, et al., 2019). Thus, identifying the related concepts and priorities to coin an overall-strategy (short-, medium- and long-term), addressing the technological, managerial, organizational, and human issues requires a roadmap for SMO, covering technologies acquisition strategy, collaboration strategy, innovation strategy, alliance, acquisitions, and mergers strategy. Accordingly, no one-size strategy suits for all businesses or industries, due to an enterprise is a set of unique entities, interactions, and features; thus, Smart Manufacturing Organization (SMO) journey starts with gaining a full understanding and clear vision based on pre-known targets and real technological maturity level assessment

C) SMART Goals: Having SMART goals ensures that manufacturers can articulate their proposals, clarify their ideas, focus their efforts, coordinate their energies, make efficient use of their time, money, and resources productively, and improve their chances of achieving them. Thus, SMART is a term for the goal-setting that manufacturing enterprises should use. To ensure the targets are straightforward and realistic, each should be: Specific (simple, sensible, meaningful); Measurable (significant, motivating); Achievable (accepted, attainable); Relevant (reasonable, realistic, resource-based); Time-bound (time-based, time-limited, time / cost-sensitive, timely).

D) Ongoing commitment and support: to implement smart factory strategically planning and to move toward digital transformation, which enhances their competitiveness in the market; this is not an easy task and requires a long-term commitment and support (essential facilitators) to ensure the smooth-shifting from traditional to digital.

3.2.2 Leadership

A. Innovation-driven: Leaders need skills that empower them to introduce an innovative idea to the market, assuming there is often a better way to address a dilemma. Thus, innovative leadership seeks new opportunities for developing current and futures market processes.

B. Networked cooperation: Lone geniuses do not necessarily make inventions. Creative perspectives from a thoughtful exchange of ideas may give rise to continuous creativity that propels the company to higher heights. A networked chief promotes mutual inquiry and enables transparent communication with individuals interested in the scenario or situation.

C. Coaching-style: Leaders act as coaches encouraging informal relations, leaner hierarchy, command, and control gives way to collaboration and innovation. Blaming gives way to encouragement, more understanding, and learning.

D. Openness to change: If team members come up with a creative idea, openness leaders are open to pursuing innovative concepts. This openness to new, even radical, ideas contributes significantly to a highly innovative organizational climate.

E. Digital skills: An effective digital leader recognizes the meaning and processes of data and all related technologies and how it is utilized to produce smartness and knowledge to sustain business development.

F. Tech-savvy: A successful digital leader should know how new emerging technologies can serve value creation innovatively and how digital assets can maintain a competitive edge.

3.2.3 Managerial Practices

The organizations wishing to adopt I4.0 are taking measures and practices to achieve compatibility with SF requirements. These heterogeneous and integrative practices encompass all organization's entities and their business network-partners. The author

clusters these practices in a category to help manufacturers and academics identify, understand, and satisfy these requirements.

A. Lean-maximization practices: Manufacturing companies are dealing with the required precision and efficiency in today's smart era by following a range of management practices that are compatible with reducing all forms of losses and avoiding waste (for instance, removing traditional jobs; merging jobs; expanding jobs, diversifying tasks, changing job content, enhancing job quality and performance...etc,) which improve job efficiency and organization efficiency ultimately help the organization to encounter the heavy competition. Qin et al. (2016) indicate that transforming classic processes into digital, simulated processes that manage and control by a decentralized and interdependent system to increase efficiency and effectiveness (Qin et al., 2016). In the same regard, Sjödin et al. (2018) point out that spreading and ensuring a unified language among personnel in the context of digital transformation scope is crucial to erase any non-valuable action or misunderstanding and to collaborate.

B. Agility-maximization practices: initiating concrete steps toward agile processes and behaviors via various sets of practices covering the whole-organization and extending to business partners is vital for enabling responsiveness, flexibility, and effectiveness, which are the basis of agility. In this regard, Martínez et al., 2017 and Rüb et al., 2019 stressed on building an effective integration and coordination of all organization's areas, entities, and their partners with computer systems and information management systems. Therefore, digitalizing most processes, enabling smooth info-flow, leading to knowledge-driven behaviors towards greater efficiency and faster reaction and enhanced productivity, thus making entities and factories more intelligent, more flexible, and highly reconfigurable, leading to maximizing agility of all operations (Strozzi, et al., 2017).

C. Dynamic abilities building practices: Building dynamic capabilities are vital to handle business strategies, business model, and product portfolio effectively, to reach new markets and clients, to improve supply chain processes and structures, to optimize risk management and compliance problems, and to handle cultural management issues arising as a result of globalization (Shamim, et al., 2016). The current environment and new demand patterns lead to the fast adoption of adaptive manufacturing systems relying on dynamic capabilities to provide a responsive and adaptable system. They are

constructed by ongoing and synchronous development of skills, technologies, quality, and performance. A set of practices laying under this category are training programs, workshops, augmented-reality applications, and online-practices.

D. Learning practices: Providing effective learning programs adopted on having the appropriate infrastructure (physical, software, experience, and knowledge) to facilitate learning processes (for groups or persons), SMO needs efficient practices to keep the organization's cognitive inventory up-to-date. Having continuous learning practices are required to cope with the significant digital transformation of jobs' content and observed prevalence of cognitive-oriented jobs. The transformation of labor-intensive and muscular-jobs towards cognitive-jobs is due to the widespread use of the data-driven process, decision, and behavior for all entities. The new challenges need different skills and knowledge. The Singapore Economic Development Board (SEDB) (2019) refers to the professional leadership team, and the workers will be unmotivated from rigid hierarchical frameworks, erratic procedures, and soloed systems. However, when workers learn and are motivated to use open channels for collaboration and innovation, their process's effectiveness and efficiency are ensured.

E. Engagement-practices: worker participation is essential to gain lean and agile structures and processes. It is also critical for change acceptance (reducing resistance) and increasing job satisfaction. Enhancing collaborations and engagement are still the cornerstones for establishing an integrated and innovative environment.

F. Innovation practices: Shamim et al. (2016) stressed that smart enterprises need to encourage workers to operate according to the needs and the pace of I4.0 via providing an environment of innovation & development is highly critical, as it is a vital facilitator for development and innovative activities. Maintaining innovation stems from management's effective practices, which includes providing an encouraging, rewarding, and infrastructure and effective management of acquiring talent, pioneers, and inventors.

G. Culture enrichment practices: These include the initiating of a chain of practices to enhance organizational culture matching with smartness requirements, such as supporting the motivation for learning and innovation motivation for employees and promoting learning and innovation across the enterprise (Shamim, et al., 2016).

H. Rewards, Motivation and Compensation practices: require redesign and implementation of appropriate and effective programs of rewards, motivation, and compensation to ensure that the goals of these practices are met and job satisfaction is increased.

3.3. Organizational requirements

Over the last century, whenever digitalization rates have risen, there have always need to change; thus, the enterprise's reorganization is obviously in vogue and taking multiple sides like:

3.3.1 Business Model

The author meets various frameworks and business modeling approaches for creating business models by reviewing the literature available. Multiple ideas are based on previous publications, and they influence the inadequacy of the current versions. Simultaneously, each author gives a different perspective on different aspects. Hence, there is a semi-consensus that the best business model creation approach is not available as yet.

The dynamic nature of the market environment requires immediate coping of the organization with technology changes (Pólkowski, et al., 2017), which leads to a creative redefinition of value. Management researchers have taken into account the business model principle in their efforts to understand the development of value in the networked markets. (Zott, et al., 2011). In designing new business models, technological innovation and digitization are becoming increasingly essential engines due to the innovations in business models are starting to cross multi-industries, and the fourth industrial revolution encourages environments that enable smart objects to provide progressively or fundamentally new business models (Leminen, et al., 2019)

Therefore, new business models will offer new options and opportunities, for example, to introduce automation equipment for manufacturing companies and whom less developed sectors. Besides that, contemporary business models have contributed to rapid growth in cross-industry in logistics, production, delivery, and so on, open new business opportunities and generate many more workers than are lost by outsourcing or digitalization (Landscheidt, et al., 2018). The novel business models also allow companies to achieve success via the development of positive or negative external effects for the enterprise (Jerman, et al., 2019).

The digital economy has given companies the opportunity, in conjunction with a company and many partners, to experiment on new forms of value-creation mechanisms that are networked to create value for multiple users (Zott, et al., 2011). In the IoT business model context, the traditional actions have undergone dramatic operational changes (Pólkowski, et al., 2017) to provide customers and employees with unique and distinctive values and compete more effectively in a digital economy. Therefore, framework identification allows management to develop a clear understanding, comprehensive review, and potential value creation philosophy of the business model concept and the transformation needed.

The unique capabilities of the smart factory have imposed sophisticated requirements and complex operating conditions. Consequently, SMOs need an intelligent and capable business model to meet the environmental needs and face business challenges. Qin (2016) points out that building an integrated network among partners. Each partner has a real-time contribution to add a positive value to the network (modifying, reconfiguration) in an integrated and cooperative manner. SMO should support several BM characteristics, such as lean, agile, sensitive, networked, dynamic, and connective, to enrich their business model and modify it to cope with smart operating environments, as discussed in previous section 2.3.

Many postulates are meant to exist for smooth and efficient operating in order to ensure the efficacy and efficiency of the smart business model; thus, the author suggests a business model operation principle that meets the needs and features of smart plants:

- **Virtualization:** The process and supply chain virtualization ensure seamless inter-company processes, providing all participating companies with real-time access to the related product and output information (Brettel, et al., 2014). Visualization techniques allow employees to design, schedule, and coordinate production work easily and remotely. Allow cloud-based applications to conduct processes and functions as well (Chromjakova, 2018). On the other hand, ERP and BI implementation require the virtualization of an enterprise's processes and activities.
- **Digitalisation:** Digital technology offers opportunities to optimize and increase value creation and capture. Such opportunities must be translated into the ecosystem sense to increase the resource efficiency of the actors. Digitalization is described by Tilson et al. (2010) as "a sociotechnical process for applying digital technologies to

wider social and institutional contexts which make digital technologies infrastructural" (Pfeiffer, et al., 2017). The advancement of wireless and Internet technology created a new approach of the structuring of organizations and market boundaries, including a multi-faceted platform, which concentrated on customer experiences and their interactions to build manufacturing platforms for developing a community of effective stakeholders (Zhaoa, et al., 2019)

- **Interoperability:** The business model often facilitates the unification of the goals and objectives of all entities, including partners, through embracing interoperability and communication among entities, also orchestrating heterogeneous entities performance and effectively operating business model could be possible via interoperability of process, concepts, and outcomes in digital forms and virtual environment.
- **Integrated system:** Connected and integrated entities enable businesses to make new strategic choices in terms of value generation and value-capture, information utilization and management, coherent partnerships, and imposing novel interactions in ecosystems (Leminen, et al., 2019).
- **Standardization:** A common understanding of business models is a precondition for the long-term use of cross-company networking potential. Unified and integrated procedures should be developed, best practices, knowledge, and experiences – especially from every department–should be regularly reported. Besides that, various functions within networks of values must be considered (BITKOM e.V., et al., 2016).
- **Flexibility:** Prause (2015) stressed that fractal organizations or modular organizations are a set of flexible and adaptable systems that have the potential to organize themselves and adapt themselves rapidly for changing business environments. For most businesses, greater flexibility and adaptability are required to face the demands of today's competitive climate (Daft, 2010).
- **Service Orientation:** In order to optimize performance, agility, and responsiveness to evolving customer demands and market challenges, most companies are now based on Service-Oriented Architecture (SOA) concepts (Kajan, 2018; Adrodegari, et al., 2016). Thus BI, ERP, CRM, and SRM are service-oriented systems. Besides that, Functions as a service, Software as service, Process as a service are the operational side of service-orientation via cloud computing.

- **Modularity:** Establishing the modularized architectures and reconfigurable-business model increases possibilities for changes and enhances innovation. Furthermore, such possibilities rely on the system's decomposability, in other terms, divided into loosely coupled modules if it can be and to what degree (Aversa, et al., 2015). The modular business model's architecture refers to a concept that illustrates how compatible product components are combined (Leminen, et al., 2019; Bask , et al., 2014). Thus, the business model modular approach can enhance the flexibility of business models that require experimentation in creative configurations and provide innovative ways to meet clients' diverse needs and services (Aversa, et al., 2015; Leminen, et al., 2019).
- **Safety and Security:** As digitization, connectivity, and networking increases of heterogeneous entities interior the supply network, business network, and ecosystem, the safety and security challenges are maximized, therefore, is needed to embed safety and security-orientation in the organization's culture and make it as one of its business model implementation pillars.

A Smart Factory is a system distinguished by the ideal flow of information steaming from a virtual copy of the physical world that gathers the actual data obtained from the simulation models to ensure a high degree of data security (Odważny, et al., 2018b). As the skilled human operator is an integral part of the manufacturing chain, human-robot co-operation's working environments are enhanced, which may reduce health risks in the workplace and eliminate unsafe job practices (Sjödin, et al., 2018).

- **Decentralization:** Besides enabling the decentralized decision making of entities at the shop-floor level, the automation of enterprises' processes and activities lead to simplify structure (the smallest possible number of basic organizational units), as well as decreasing the intensity of direct supervision (Tworek, et al., 2017). Likewise, smart factory sensitivity and adaptability require strong decentralization.

3.3.2 Structural Requirements:

Organizational structure is a set of clear and implicates rules and policies that identify, assign, control, and coordinate roles and responsibilities. This affects how employees behave, communicate and perform, and how efforts are achieved to realize organizational targets. Much as process design determines how successful a project will be, an organization's structure determines how successful the business is in meeting its objectives (SEDB, 2019). Thus, in order to address today's challenges, companies

reinvent their operating environment, job practices and activities, and – finally – whole plant's operations (Cagliano, et al., 2019). Daft, 2010 stressed reengineering organizational structures and business processes to ensure a perfect utilization of advanced technologies.

Evidence indicates that organizational structures are continually evolving and organizations (and their forms) in the 21st century would be different from those we currently experience, where the newly emerging structural dynamics of modern organizations are explicitly at odds with static structures (Mandal, 2008). Cagliano, et al, 2019 stressed the crucial impacts of smart factories' technological complexity in reshaping the operation environment, working activities, organization structure, and – ultimately – organization design dimensions that collectively construct different organizational models (Cagliano, et al., 2019).

Smart manufacturing structures tend to be more flexible, without departmentalization or hierarchical corporate hierarchy, which can hinder decision-making or taking action. Robbins et al (2012) also found that many of today's most effective companies would perform more efficiently while staying fluid and unstructured: the optimal framework for them is not static, constrained, and predefined. In the same direction, Shamim et al. (2016) claim that smart factories need to develop adaptive structures to their requirements and conditions; no particular correct solution is suitable for every enterprise; the resultant organizational structure is subject to contingency theory and depends on a variety of factors

The smart manufacturing organization (SMO) based on I4.0 increases the decentralization level, maximizes data-transparency and encourages collaboration internally and with external stakeholders to help companies make agile decisions and adapt to changes (SEDB, 2019). In various organizational areas and sometimes at different levels, employees in an organization must exchange knowledge and work together. Such an environment needs minimal structural, systemic and physical barriers to permit employees to work together in the best way possible and learn from one another (Robbins, et al., 2012).

The need of 360-degree integration of smart factory's characteristics and capabilities in both levels (enterprise, production) imposes imperative interventions of requirements; therefore, we will depend on the organization structure characteristics approach to

summarize the main requirements that compatible with a pre-viewed system features in the context of organizational structure and organization's design.

Initially, Table 3.1 demonstrated the possible characteristics of the main structures and designs of the organizations. Accordingly, it is impossible to configure a smart organization depending on a certain structure or design (see Table 3.1). Therefore, a unique configuration is needed combining the useful and proper characteristics and effectively overcoming the conflicts of interests among partners. Consequently, the author draws on these five broad categories of requirements and demonstrates their applicability regarding smart factories' topic via multi-structure configuration.

These requirements may involve many conflicts. For instance, the dynamic and innovative nature of a smart factory with modularity and standardized nature of SF, is a creative stage that charts the organization's success and structure. Therefore, these specifications are not accessible in the context of a concrete structure, design, or specification, and organizations that wish to change digitally must create a thoroughbred organizational structure (unique structure). The table below can help to provide a brief image of the integration and convergence points between the organizational framework and designs that are familiar with the specifications and requirements of smart manufacturing organizations.

a. **Lean:** the smart organization struggles to create a compatible mixture of the span of control, need-orientation, flat hierarchy, job-breadth, job contents, and required qualifications as the base of the lean structure to enhance efficiency. Generally, significant modifications occurred to occupations over SF emergence stages. These can be summarized as newly emerging or disappearing tasks; combination, digitization, modelization, and automation (that imposed by smartness era) which collectively reengineering jobs and their operating structure; redefining the needed skills and qualifications to match the smart entities (devices, processes, software, concepts) and knowledge-orientation. Establishing a lean structure improves the pace of decision-making, responsiveness, flexibility and promotes digital transformation and adaptability by purifying the system from non-value elements.

Table 3. 1: Organization's characteristics that meet with SF requirements

		Organization Structures			Organization Designs				
		Mechanistic	Organic	Matrix	Project Teams	Flat hierarchy	Boundaryless	Learning	Network
Requirements	Lean	No matching	- Jobs-breadth - Wide spans of control - Skilled jobs	- Need-oriented - Jobs-breadth- Wide spans of control- Skilled jobs	- Slim hierarchy - Skilled jobs - Need-oriented - Jobs-breadth	- Slim hierarchy - Skilled jobs - Need-oriented- Jobs-breadth - High span of control	- Slim hierarchy - Skilled jobs - Need-oriented- Jobs- breadth- High span of control - Novel job's contents	- Skilled jobs - Need-oriented- Jobs- breadth- High span of control - Novel job's contents	- Slim hierarchy - Skilled jobs - Need-oriented- Jobs- breadth- Novel job's contents
	Agility	No matching	- Flexible - Decentralized - Responsive	- Flexible - Responsive - Decentralized	- Autonomous decision - Flexible - Responsive - Decentralized	- Autonomy - Flexible	- Flexible- Decentralized - Responsive - Adaptable - Autonomous decision	- Flexible- Decentralized - Responsive - Adaptable	- Flexible- Decentralized - Responsive - Adaptable - Autonomous decision
	Integration	Integration	- Interconnected - Collaboration - Interrelated	- Interconnected - Collaboration - Interrelated -Harmonic	- Interconnected - Collaboration - Interrelated -Harmonic - Interoperability,	- Interconnected - Collaboration - Interrelated -Harmonic - Interoperability	- Interconnected - Collaboration - Interrelated -Harmonic - Interoperability,	- Interconnected - Collaboration - Interrelated -Harmonic - Interoperability,	- Interconnected - Collaboration - Interrelated -Harmonic - Interoperability,
	Smartness	No matching	- Transparency - Free flow of information - Support innovativeness	- Transparency- Free flow of information- Support innovativeness	- Knowledge-driven - Interconnectedness - continues learning and innovating	- Support learning and innovation efforts - Interconnectedness	- knowledge-driven- Interconnectedness, - Continues learning and innovating - Transparency	- knowledge-driven- Interconnectedness, - Continues learning and innovating - Transparency	- knowledge-driven- Interconnectedness, - Continues learning and innovating - Transparency
	Modularity	- Formalization - Standardization - Automation	No matching	- Formalization- Standardization - Automation	No matching	No matching	No matching	No matching	Standardization

Source: Author prepared

b. **Agility:** This robust backbone becomes a springboard for smart manufacturing organizations and an effective approach for managing digital transformation. The agility is enabled by dynamic capabilities of structures such as flexibility, responsiveness, adaptability, and autonomous-decisions toward reshaping strategy, processes, employees, and technologies in line with the characteristics of smart factories and business environment challenges. Moreover, developing and reinforcing decentralization, knowledge-driven orientation, and service-orientation are crucial for agility.

c. **Integration:** the industrial organizations operating synergistically as part of efficient value-chains are imperative to start the change and transformation towards digitalization (Martínez et al, 2017). Furthermore, the configurable nature of smart factories is based on integrated entities, including the organizational aspects. Via establishing interconnective, interrelated, and interoperable structures lead to a harmonic environment and effective networked collaboration along with fast decision circles, reduced risk of conflict, interactive relations, rational-decisions, and enhanced job satisfaction.

d. **Smartness:** Data-transparency and the existence of effective data-flow enable interconnectivity of integrated entities (humans, jobs, processes, devices, and decisions). The digital, data-driven, and logical-relations replaced traditional relations in the organizational structure. Besides, building the learning-oriented structure became the foundation for both innovation and digitalization. Knowledge-driven interactions have also become cornerstones of smart structures.

e. **Modularity:** this approach involves encouraging formalization and increasing the modularization of processes based on high-standardization, which automate attitudes and interactions among the workforce and entities, configuring a modular structure.

3.3.3 Cultural Contents and Related Requirements

An organization's culture is described as a diverse collection of principles, opinions, values, beliefs, and symbols that form the way a group works, and can be a source of sustainable competition, thereby constituting an effective strategic tool (SEDB, 2019). Thus, the cultural contents are a fundamental part of implementing Industry 4.0 and smart factories due to their value, impact, and power within organizations. In order to prepare the smart factory organizational climate, the digital transformation demands a set of reinforced values, ideals, and ethics.

Any culture enhancement requires efficient and progressive programs and policies to anchor desired values, principles, and ethics via enriching and/or replacing existing contents and imposing others that take root in the digital transformation. The following can be highlighted as the vital culture contents for configuring a smart factory:

- a. **Knowledge-orientation:** enhancing knowledge utilization and individual obligations of data transparency are essential to ensure that corporate leaders and members utilize sufficient and suitable knowledge (SEDB, 2019).
- b. **Quality-orientation:** anchoring quality values and enhancing employee's passion for achieving quality.
- c. **Learning-orientation:** encouraging continuous seeking to develop the knowledge, capability, skills, and competencies.
- d. **Collaboration-orientation:** consolidating the concepts of cooperation, joint action, networked work, and joint performance in their culture, e.g., co-tasks, joint-goals, collaborative processes, and partners' interdependency.
- e. **Innovation orientation:** becoming increasingly innovation-oriented and triggering creativity within the company and across borders via a set of programs and policies.
- f. **Initiatives & participation:** encouraging innovation, ongoing improvement, participation, involvement, and change acceptance while increasing job satisfaction.
- g. **Digitalization-values: encouraging** data-driven behavior, enhancing digital awareness to avoid change resistance, and introducing a culture utilizing digital technologies to facilitate smart manufacturing technologies.

3.4 Human-Related Requirements

A. **Innovative-thinking:** Many creative ideas for developing systems come from the employee, who is the system's top expert (Mabkhot et al., 2018). Thus, SMO must retain creative entrepreneurs and skilled workers.

B. **Data-related skills:** Increasing data accessibility will help integrate the workforce with the system, and providing workers with adequate programming and mechatronics skills is essential in the new smart context (Mabkhot et al., 2018). Employees should realize that exchanging information is vital in their personal and organizational interests (SEDB, 2019). Therefore, employees must have data-sharing, data manipulation, and analysis skills.

C. **Interactivity:** Enabling human-technology collaboration, human-environment interaction, and improved HMI paradigms, including coexistence with robotics (cobots) or completely different ways of communicating and working in factories, where people control activities intelligent devices and systems (SEDB, 2019; Shafiq, et al., 2015).

D. **Dynamic-Skills:** Emerging technology and methods will radically change the nature of jobs and the types of skills needed (SEDB, 2019), as well as existing and expected human resources expertise (Ghobakhloo , 2018). Organizations must carefully assess the expertise, skill inventory, and technical capabilities of existing staff and further define the abilities that the company does not actually have. The increased preference for cognitive over muscular skills leads to new digital skills exceeding beyond conventional capabilities. In this regard, major skills are data processing, data mining, system integration, software development, problem-solving, data analysis, decision making, use of digital technology, innovation, and automation management.

E. **Real-time Capability:** Enabling the workforce to instantaneously respond and promptly make decisions based on the real-time exchange of information between individuals, manufacturing systems, and other related entities of the cyber-physical systems.

In this section, technological, managerial, organizational, and human-related requirements have been gathered for SF. Requirements House for SF given in Figure 3.2 provides a compact summary representation of these requirements. That does not negate the value of other conventional criteria that are proper for SF.

Figure 3.2: Smart Factory Requirements House
Created by author

CHAPTER 4

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK DEVELOPMENT

Literature review in the previous chapters put forward a variety of frameworks. An original mapping of technology, design principles, features, and capabilities are performed. Business model canvas concept is elaborated; and requirements are gathered. Based on these ideas, this chapter offers a proposed business model for a smart factory compatible with a multi-perspective capabilities framework and the multi-perspective framework. In this section, detailed explanations are provided for both the framework and the model, and then advantages and originality of them are defended.

4.1 Proposed Smart-Capabilities Business Model

Based on the business canvas logic and multi-perspective capabilities framework, we offer the following model as the big picture smart business model.

The proposed model given in Figure 4.1 manifests itself at the process, organizational, and network levels. Hence, it is compatible with the system hierarchy of the multi-perspective framework given in Figures 4.3 & 4.4 Key resources, key processes, and key resources engage in key interactions to provide capabilities extending from the shop floor to the ecosystem. Systems and processes integration is considered to be contingent upon stakeholders' consensus on value creation and result in a set of created capabilities from all resources and related interactions. The main elements of the business model proposed in Figure 4.1 are discussed below:

Figure 4.1: Smart-capabilities business model

1. **Key technologies:** Industries currently face multiple challenges exacerbated by rapid technological shifts, e.g. shorter product life cycles, unpredictable demands and highly personalized goods (Mabkhot, et al., 2018; BCG, et al., 2016; Jerman, et al., 2019; Onar , et al., 2018), and technological innovation and disruptive technologies have often shown that market structure and value creation are evolving systematically. Thus, the value-added interprets and reflects the efficiency and effectiveness of the innovative use of technologies and other resources. The individual and networked interactions and influences of proposed smart factory enabling technologies (CPS, IoT, BD, CC, AM, CIM, ERP, BI, AR, Robotics, Simulation) are a core component of value creation network (see Figure 4.2).

The technologies in the context of smart factory take not only into account the technologies but also the broad spectrum of design principles, and characteristics that serve innovative value creation, therefore, identifying technological requirements of smart factories (SF) requires a full understanding of the relations of features, principles and technologies. See section 2.2.3 (Building Smart Factory Capabilities) for more detail.

Figure 4.2: Value added network mapping by smart factory enabling technologies

2. **Key resources** are the vital assets required to run a business model. Human, ICT, knowledge, physical and finance are the most critical resources categories for any business models (Adrodegari, et al., 2016; Charamba, 2017) with differentiated responsibility, logical-relations, and roles. What are the essential key resources concerning quality, cost, features, etc.? To individually provide the desired value for

partners including customers, what are the new competencies and skills?; what are helpful financial resources adequate to substantial capital investment needs; what is the required distribution channel (Adrodegari, et al., 2016)?

3. **Key Processes:** Charamba (2017) point out that the main functions created by multi-processes and are essential tasks performed by a company to ensure business survival. Key processes are all the required procedures or practices that the business undertakes with the primary objective of generating profit across the network of value creation. Thus, it is embodying of how the technologies and resources are utilized to create the desired value across the processes, including design, operations, sales and marketing, product development and design, production. Smooth and integrated processes within and across the partners sit at the centre of success. Hence, the identification of the key processes involved in our value creation network is critical. Ensuring inter-company connectivity, integrated and collaborative processes, joint planning, execution and control as well as joint problem-solving across partners is the fundamental idea.

4. **Key interactions** are the dynamic interactions needed to integrate the performance of all entities and to achieve the interrelated objectives of the business network participants. The relations logic, the nature of the interactions, the communication channels, and the parties characteristics and their related objectives make it possible for relationships and inter-relationships to describe and control the logical-creation of value (business logic), just to name a few, data exchange, self-coordination, interdependence and interoperability.

As a result of the effective and efficient integration of the essential elements of the model (key technologies, key resources, key processes, key interactions), smart enabling capabilities emerge, allowing intelligent manufacturing enterprises to survive and grow and enabling a set of crucial features to sustain competitive advantage and optimizing the environmental enterprise-fingerprint.

5. **Main capabilities** enable organizations to be agile, lean, rapid response and adaptable with high scalability. Besides, a wide range of entities' features (machines, operation, systems, functions...) will be enabled, to name a few: connectivity, integrability, networked, accessibility, transparency, traceability, automation, and smooth data flow (for further details, see 2.2.4). The proposed categories of capabilities encompass autonomous Capability, Dynamic Interaction Capability, Customizing

Capability, Intelligence Capability and Competitive Capability which required a set of design principles (such as virtualization, digitalization, interoperability, integration, standardization, flexibility, service orientation, modularity, safety and security, decentralization, to achieve them.

6. **Business Network** is a diverse, integrated and interconnected network of companies, groups, and individuals to achieve joint-objectives, and the joint-interests brought them together. Each business network participant has unique relations, impact, channels, technologies, joint-development and value-added. The following are the main participants within the network:

6.1. **Customer:** As a consequence of building intended capabilities, customers' participation is optimized and extended via joint-design, co-operate, and joint decision. A clear understanding of needs, motivations, tendencies, expectations, purchasing power (Onar , et al., 2018; Aversa, et al., 2015; Bradley, et al., 2020) are necessary along with proper identification of demand channels, technologies, and relations to provide proposed individualized value and customized products. In this regard, the following questions need to be answered:

"What kind of relationship does each of our customer segments expect us to have with them (Adrodegari, et al., 2016)? Which ones have we established? What are undertaken to motivate and impress customers? (Charamba, 2017) For whom our value is made (Onar , et al., 2018)? What are our consumers ' benefits? What problem will we help to solve for our customer? What needs do we meet for our customers? How are we providing each consumer segment with packages of goods and services? (Osterwalder , et al., 2011) How do they fit into the rest of our business model? How costly are they? For whom are we creating value? Who are our most important customers? How customized our service and product for each customer? What are the required channels to reach and interact with customers?"

6.2. **Supplier:** Efficient supply network will be needed to ensure inter-company connectivity, transparency of information, integrated and collaborative processes, joint-decisions, responsive engineering processes and joint-solutions. These require close relationships, active networks, integration, collaborative innovation, strategic alignment and synchronization. Key questions that require to be answered are: Who are our vendors? What are the joint resources? What are the joint-ventures?

6.3. **Provider:** Along with main suppliers, close relationships and collaboration have to be maintained with the providers in the network. They include any provider, such as IT provider, 3PL and 4PL logistics provider, that the central company is interacting. These providers are becoming more and more integral parts of today's supply networks, and they are assuming a critical role in networked relations. In this regard, defining the scope of the relationships and responsibilities with these providers with well-defined contractual agreements assume critical importance for the long-term relationships. Determining the extent of reliability and interdependency and ensuring service level guarantees become critical strategic issues within the network.

6.4. **Workers:** businesses should use different types of HMI to enhance work safety and allow ergonomic workplaces to be built, social aspects of technology, i.e. human contact and connectivity, play a significant role in maintaining a sense of belonging (Schneider, 2018; Bouwman, et al., 2008). A clear understanding of needs, motivations, skills, qualifications, and catalysts, enables organizations for cultivating digital and security culture, supporting employees' physical and mental abilities, eliminating human defects, optimizing effective training programs, fair payroll system, high wages for skilled jobs, encouraging "communities of practice", and remotely maintenance and online assistance. Besides that, providing BI services, effective human-machine-interfaces, digitalizing tasks, high accessibility of knowledge, and enhancing safety conditions add significant direct value and facilitate value creation in each network entities.

6.5. **Competitors:** Who are our rivals? What are their unique abilities and features? Who are the nearest competitors? What is collaboration feasible with them? How much collaboration is feasible between us? What are their pricing mechanisms? Moreover, how useful it is for the consumer? Answering such questions and continuously monitoring the rivals and their performance is vital to compete effectively, and exchange of information could facilitate adopting joint-venture, and/or outsourcing strategies.

6.6. **Shareholders:** Owners often are concerned for profits and capitals and look for clear financial bottom-lines. Hence, they are concerned for the optimization of production efficiency and effectiveness. To cope with this interest, a set of innovative capabilities are built such as competitive, intelligence, customizing, dynamic interaction and autonomous capabilities and a broad range of embedded features that

enable smart manufacturing enterprises for answering the central questions of: "What are shareholders' interests? Do shareholders support innovative investment? How could we satisfy shareholders goals? What is our investing motivating? What are the fundamentals of our investment success? Which are the attracting features for shareholders?"

6.7. **Others:** the high connectivity, smartness, and integration facilitate manufacturing enterprises to cope with other partners such as government, unions, financial institutions, Legal and legislative organizations.

7. Ecosystem

7.1. **Community:** Generally, heterogeneous groups, different cultures, dynamic needs, diverse motivations, various affiliations, and differentiated lifestyles are sources of social challenges for the organizations. In this regard, the dynamic interaction and intelligence capabilities enable tracing the changes in the ecosystem, gathering data, and analyzing this data to reconfigure our strategies, processes, and products and services, for enhancing the value provided for the community (such as positive footprints, knowledge, and value).

7.2. **Economy:** the economical parameters (such as economic performance indicators, expectations) (Piscicelli, et al., 2019; Wirtz, et al., 2017) are remarkable data-sources of BI services, advanced analytics and then data-driven decision-making (Schneider, 2018). At the same time, increased responsiveness and flexibility reduce the impacts of economic risk, and the interaction of capabilities lead to superior performance which reflect positively on economic performance also.

7.3. **Environment:** The critical problems facing humanity are global warming, greenhouse gasses, deforestation and depletion of resources (Piscicelli, et al., 2019; Charamba, 2017; Mabkhot, et al., 2018). Consumption and industrial practices have a significant effect on rising or decreasing these environmental challenges. Hence, environmental concerns represent a critical issue to which organizations as well as the networks should respond to. Via agile and lean processes and systems and the use of high technologies enable smart manufacturing enterprises to enhance their effort for the green production system. Reducing energy consumption, decreasing pollution levels, strengthening cooperation among environment entities, green manufacturing

initiatives, cost-efficient manufacturing processes, minimizing waste, and optimal raw-material utilization are core issues that have to be handled.

8. Value creation and knowledge

The primary task of every company is to build (and maintain) value and creating profits (Martínez-Olvera , et al., 2019; Kusiak, 2017).

8.1. Value Propositions are integrated processes by which a company can satisfy the customer needs (Onar , et al., 2018) Thus, they define the packages that generates value (Osterwalder , et al., 2011) via products, software, services, or a mix of them and they are the cumulative performance of all the entities (humans, machines, systems, products, processes, and services). Enterprises are establishing a full understanding of what the client or community needs to come up with a clean description of the value proposition for each or all of these categories, and to manage the consumer loyalty issues (Onar , et al., 2018; Charamba, 2017). Undoubtedly, a business model should create an unavoidable value proposition for consumers, obtain a favorable cost and risk structure and consider the vital resources to be used and the key relationships to be formed.

8.2. Value creation: Boos et al., 2014; Martínez-Olvera et al., (2019) point out four aspects that generate demand for a product, service or mix of both: product (what should be created/offered?), operation (how should it be made?), machinery (what should it be generated by?), and individuals and organizations (when / where will it be manufactured and who will manufacture, supervise and handle it?) (Martínez-Olvera , et al., 2019). Value creation also has to be based on the business logic of highly personalized product-service combinations that are well-synchronized with partners needs (Schneider, 2018) via technological innovations (Onar , et al., 2018). A proposed business model focuses on the integration of technological innovations, integration of heterogeneous data and related advanced analyses to produce smart entities which are at the core of a networked creation of value.

8.3. Knowledge: Open innovation is marked by information sharing, and effective information management plays a significant role in the creation of goods and creativity for productive decision-making (Bouwman , et al., 2008; Aagaard, 2019). As well as building an understanding of an organization's prospects and risks concerning collaboration and networks, and their consequences for a specific company, creating

awareness of alternative modes of cooperation (e.g. creative clusters, industrial networks or joint-strategic) and relevant collaborators, identifying prospects and challenges and taking informed decisions (Schneider, 2018; Duarte, et al., 2020; Shafiq, et al., 2015) are critical in joint knowledge creation. Businesses should virtualize the processes (for minimizing physical iteration loops), increase data consistency (to organize actions) between participants, and use feedback from goods and machines in order to create more efficient supply chains and to maximize resource efficiency (Schneider, 2018). The smart factory is a knowledge-driven system; exchangeability of knowledge is the primary source of value for all business network and ecosystem participants. Joint designs, joint planning, joint-operations, joint problem solving and joint-decisions, and co-learning are enabled by knowledge exchange.

9. Financial Aspects

9.1. Revenue streams: The revenue streams are the cash inflows created by each consumer segment of a corporation. When clients are the heart of a corporate, their arteries are sales sources. The organization has to question itself what value does every customer segment actually want to pay for (Osterwalder , et al., 2011)? Thus, it contains the tools and sources from which the company generates revenue. The various ways in which a company gets revenue are performance's monetarization—for example, ads, selling of properties, subscription fees and rent (Charamba, 2017). Pricing and income sources, volumes and margins must be defined Adrodegari et al., (2016). Therefore, business can produce one or more revenue sources from each consumer segment (Osterwalder , et al., 2011).

9.2. Cost structure: The cost structure determines all the costs associated with the implementation of a business model (Osterwalder , et al., 2011). How different aspects of business models influence the cost structure must be determined and different costs associated with a business model are to be identified. Such costs include expenses incurred during value creation and distribution, the activation of customer interest, profits, compensation of employees (including trainers, marketers, and coordinators), maintaining resources, sustaining customers' relationship and service developing, etc. (Ngoufack, 2018; Solaimani, et al., 2017; Adrodegari, et al., 2016; Charamba, 2017). Thus, smart manufacturing enterprises incorporate operational (OP) aspects and information-communication (ICT) technologies to bring their clients into a fully

integrated manufacturing network to provide uniquely tailored goods in a scalable and cost-effective manner.

10. Continuous learning and Improvement:

Mandal (2008) stressed on the need for a systemic approach to information and knowledge-gathering, codification and dissemination, social capital development to allow individuals and societies to collaborate and concentrate on learning and training, and highlight the importance of using experience and skills in working practices. They also note that their analysis offers easy access to facts and enhance alliance effectiveness (Mandal, 2008). The connectivity, integrability, accessibility, and transparency, which allow internal and external interactions supported by destructive technologies, (such as augmented reality and simulation technologies) to exchange data and knowledge among business network's participants is the source of continues learning. These networks are considered as learning channels: as a knowledge-sharing channel for all participants, this capability consists of three-level of learning: organization's learning (exchanging of knowledge), system learning (machine learning), personal learning (business intelligence services) besides traditional learning channels. Simultaneously, the massive amount of heterogeneous data are sources of innovation and optimization, offers better visibility and insight into the firm's operations and assets (Waris, et al., 2018).

11. Performance and Risk management

11.1. Performance management: In order to remain competitive, organizations should create a productive working environment for the partners. This process includes the gathering of proper data and feedback from all partners on their assessment of the development of the partnership and joint-performance; thus links and the preservation of trust during the management stage are highly valuable (Mandal, 2008; Schaefer, et al., 2017). The smart factory is a scalable system that can auto-optimize performance over a more extensive network and can respond to different situations and learn from them. Each entity produces enormous amounts of data that expose problems with asset performance (via continuous analysis) that may require a corrective optimization (Burke, et al., 2017; Sjödin, et al., 2018). High coordination, connectivity, and sharing resources optimize the participated teams' performance (Daft, 2010).

11.2. Risk management: It is essential to share uncertainty and risks to all the concerned network participants. Therefore, businesses and consumers will define, assess, control and handle these uncertainties and risks in coordination with each other (Adrodegari, et al., 2016). A coordinated, integrated and economic resource usage to reduce the likelihood or effects of risk reduction and enhance tracking and regulating of it in the smart plant is feasible (Bin Nadir, et al., 2020). Consequently, risk detection, evaluation and prioritization and handling within a smart factory are feasible. In the risk management framework, smart factory qualities emanating from its capabilities that play an essential role. These are including but not limited to agility, lean, adaptability, sustainability, optimization, responsive, scalability, efficiency, connectivity, integrability, networked and smartness, in discovering and overcoming risks. This enables joint answers to such questions:

"Which risks could be identified? How will threats be found effectively? What knowledge is required to mitigate or eliminate risks? Do we have the required knowledge to handle the risks? Who is the risk parties? Which are the risk dimensions?"

4.2 The Unique Characteristics of Proposed Business Model

When utilized with the defined capability sets and the multi-perspective capabilities framework, the suggested business model:

- Takes into consideration a variety of partners.
- It complies with the developments in the organization theory, and literature in collaborative supply network. This supports the recent organizational ideas such as virtual enterprises, organizational fluidity and collaboration across blurring boundaries.
- It preserves the process orientation and customer-orientation.
- It considers all the smart factory capabilities identified in section 2.2.4 as the basis of network information sharing, transparency, integration, and collaboration.
- All these configured capabilities lead to joint-performance and joint-risk management among business network participants. Hence, all these capabilities serve for the development of network-level performance and risk management system. Hence, this is compatible with the recent collaborative supply chain performance and risk management literature.

- Multiple dimensions defined in Figures 4.3 & 4.4 form the basis for network-level value and knowledge creation as well as sharing. Hence, the framework and the business model suggested form the basis of the networked learning organizations.
- The dynamic configuration capabilities originating from smart factory leads to dynamic configuration of business network.
- Shop-floor smartness is extended to intelligent enterprises and networks.
- It values continuous learning and improvement, hence values innovation across the network.
- It does not lose the financial perspective. Hence, it is significant to highlight that this is totally compliant with the well-supported balanced scorecard perspective. All BSC perspectives are covered.

4.3 Proposed Multi- Perspective Framework for SMO

Smart manufacturing organizations will become more flexible, integrated, collaborative, lean and agile to survive and grow, via increasingly focuses on meeting a dynamic demand, enabling shareable resources, building dynamic capacities, higher utilization of resources and establishing collaborative production systems.

Drawn from studying of more than 180 publications, in the fields of IoT, BD, CPS, AM, CC, AR, robots, business model, BI, management systems, and architectures under SF, I4.0's scope. A large number of structures and models have been proposed, but none of them has offered a comprehensive view, and most of them consisted of a technological side, and ignore other sides or briefly discuss it. Smart manufacturing organizations is an integral, interactive and smart environment; accordingly, this section offers a multi-perspective capabilities framework (Figure 4.3 & 4.4) which corresponds and integrates with a proposed business model (Figures 4.1) for SMO. This multi-perspective framework, that developed by the author, encompasses five dimensions are present (Figure 4.1):

- System hierarchy perspective
- Stakeholder perspective
- Time perspective
- Capabilities perspective
- Macro-process perspective

The data-driven reconfigurable nature of smart factory has a multi-layered architecture consisting of six levels: the technological level, the design principles level the features level, the factory capability level, the enterprise capability level and networked capability level. The following level depends on the interaction of former levels; the data flow among the six levels form a closed and interacted loop. The multiple technologies, design principles and features (for which a detailed discussion and mapping has been provided in Chapter 2.2.4, Table 2.12) are interactive to produce and support capabilities at multiple levels (factory-level, organizational level and network level).

Figure 4.3: Multi-perspective capabilities framework for SMO

Figure 4.4: The interactions of multi-perspective capabilities framework (MPCF)

In this framework:

- **System hierarchy perspective:** takes into consideration system descriptions at all levels, starting from sensors, extending up-to the entire ecosystem, thus, this dimension corresponds with the IEC 62264 and IEC 61512 standards, but with extending to include the entire value network and their ecosystem, as well as, these levels in this hierarchy clarifies and organizes multiple classifications present in the literature, and enable planning, monitoring, integrating, automizing and control at any level (device/ station/work center/ factory/ enterprise/ /network. Many capabilities are configured and enabled in this dimension, just to name a few: instant data capture, optimize the real-time response, enhance product customization, enabling diagnostic ability, networking and individualizing of the business process, Situational alignment, data-driven economy, and dynamic integrated entities. etc.
- **Stakeholder perspective:** takes into consideration all the relevant stakeholders within the ecosystem. Stakeholders' fate are linked to each other's and the community's destiny. Thus, full partnerships with stakeholders reshape partners' strategies, capabilities and performance, and contribute in the configuration of the collaborative production system. Such partnerships involve inter-company connectivity, collaborative and integrated processes, responsive engineering processes, real-time and joint planning, decision making and joint actions.
- **Time perspective:** takes into consideration all the time horizons for planning implementing and control. Since real-time data capture is possible, execution level can be differentiated from the operational level in this classification. In this dimension, a set of capabilities and features are enabled, just to name a few: digitalizing most jobs and entities, dynamic coordination, stable implementation, real-time planning, dynamic planning (adaptable planning), dynamic-networked structure, real-time responsiveness, and self-diagnostic as a base of the maintenance planning, scheduling, implementing.
- **Capabilities perspective:** classification under this perspective comes from the detailed literature survey in previous Chapter 2. It covers autonomous, dynamic interaction, customizing, intelligence and competitive capabilities. These capabilities extend from shop-floor level to enterprise-level and then network-level capabilities. Thus, these capabilities extend from a smart shop-floor to smart networks.

- **Macro-process perspective:** multiple processes are taken into consideration (within-factory, within-enterprise, supplier-centric, customer-centric and collaborative network-level processes). Hence, technology-based smart capabilities become the base for multi-partner collaboration at multiple processes.

4.4 The Unique Characteristics of Proposed Multi- Perspective Framework

It is important to highlight that this representation given in Figures 4.3 & 4.4 are unique in:

- Clarifying smart system hierarchy on the way from sensors & devices to collaborative, smart ecosystems. This eliminates the confusion in terminology in the literature.
- Enabling multi-partner collaborative processes at multiple time dimensions and hierarchy levels. All time dimensions and processes are handled.
- Providing a unique classification of capabilities, and mapping with relevant technologies, design principles and features. The detailed mapping provided in Table 2.12 in section 2.2.4, when used with this Figure 4.4 provides a totally original contribution to literature.
- Considering all the stakeholders.
- Is a situation-driven integrative environment.
- Showing that heterogeneous entities (ideas, physical, process, cyber, human) can be integrated, interoperated and configured into a smart-collaborative manufacturing system.
- It complies with automation hierarchy and PLC management.

Consequently, the mapping in Figure 2.25, multi-dimensional framework in Figure 4.4 and the business model in Figure 4.1 forms a unique combination, and therefore contributes to smart collaboration literature.

CHAPTER 5:

SURVEY AND INDEX DEVELOPMENT

Based on the smart factory's requirements proposed in chapter 3, the smart capabilities business model & multi-perspective conceptual framework developed in Chapter 4 for SMO, and existing maturity models in the literature, this chapter develops an assessment survey and maturity index.

5.1. Survey Development

For the purpose of the research, an assessment survey is used as the method of data collection. The author has developed a new assessment survey to assess the smart factory requirements and to calculate a maturity index for transforming the smart factory's abstract requirements into specific and measurable items.

An assessment survey is prepared to investigate the current state of awareness and to identify how well smart factory requirements are met to assess the readiness and the maturity level of smart factory transformation in the Turkish industry to derive the road-map to smart factory adoption.

The author turned the proposed requirements in chapter 3, which are gathered based on comprehensive literature survey, into an easy-to-use requirements and assessment survey tool for determining SF maturity for manufacturing enterprises. It is worth mentioning that the developed requirements and the assessment survey are compatible with Smart-Capabilities Business Model (see section 4.1) and the multi-perspective framework for SMO (see section 4.3 Figure 4.4), which work together to facilitate industry 4.0 based smart factory establishment. The maturity model's assessment criteria are based on Industry 4.0 based smart factory's requirements given in Chapter 3 for (see Figure 3.2 for brief big-picture). Here it is important to highlight that most dimensions mentioned by Schumacher et al., 2016; De Carolis et al., 2017; Jung et al., 2016, and Akdil et al., 2017 (see table 21) are embedded in, and compatible with the requirements and sub-dimensions in proposed assessment survey.

The critical contribution of the developed model, assessment survey, and SFRMI is that they focus not only on technical aspects but also on organizational, managerial, human-related, and knowledge aspects such as strategy, capabilities, features, leadership, structure, business model, and people. Hence, the model and the survey tool form a multi-dimensional view of smart factory capabilities.

While developing the survey, maturity models in the literature are compared in the sense of digitization, smart factory, and industry 4.0. Several authors have examined existing maturity and readiness models for I4.0 and the smart factory. Each model has several unique dimensions, and the models are compared based on the number of dimensions and factors that they consider. As shown in Table 5.1, it is often unclear to which degree the factors used cover all organization faces. The scholars argue that it is hard to validate these models since lack of comprehensive perspective encompasses of all organizations' faces (technological, organizational, managerial, and human-related face).

An assessment survey given in Appendix (A) covering all these dimensions is developed to fill this gap. The following table shows a variety of maturity models in the literature and their coverage by the survey developed in this study.

Table 5.1: Existing maturity models

Maturity Model	Authors	Year	Dimensions	Coverage degree by SFRM survey
IMPULS—Industrie 4.0 Readiness	Lichtblau et al.	2015	Strategy and organization; Smart factory; Smart operations; Smart products; Data-driven services; Employees	Are 100% covered and included
Maturity model for assessing Industry 4.0 readiness and maturity of manufacturing enterprises	Schumacher et al	2016	Strategy; Leadership; Customers; Products; Operations; Culture; People; Governance; Technology	Are 90% covered and included
Smart Manufacturing System Readiness Assessment (SMSRA)	Jung et al.	2016	organizational, information technology, performance management, and information connectivity.	Are 100% covered and included
Industry 4.0/digital operations self-assessment	PWC	2016	Strategy & Organization; Smart Factory; Smart Operations; Smart Products; Data-driven Services; Employees	Are 100% covered and included
SIMMI 4.0	Leyh et al	2016	Vertical Integration, Horizontal Integration, Cross-sectional Technology Criteria)	Are 100% covered and included
Digital readiness Assessment Maturity	De Carolis et al	2017	Technology, Information connectivity, Process, Organization, and Personnel capability	Are 100% covered and included
Maturity and Readiness Model for Industry 4.0 Strategy	Akdil et al	2017	Smart products and services; Smart business processes; Strategy and Organization	Are 100% covered and included

The survey developed measures several different areas, e.g., structure characteristics, smart factory knowledge, capabilities, entities and process features, and hurdles over the smart factory transformation journey. An online version of the survey is created via the Google Form, as well as the hardcopy version in English and Turkish.

The assessment survey has 50 questions in total for all the related dimensions in compatibility with the requirements breakdown, and a few questions about the industry, strategies, size of the workforce, capabilities, and goals.

At the beginning of the survey, the author explained the purpose, and structure of the survey, provided instructional notes, and key terms of the survey to remove potential ambiguities. Afterwards, survey's questions are organized into six sections:

1. Section (A) is for collecting general information about the enterprise (employees' number, Business type. etc.).

2. Section (B) is for assessing the availability of knowledge.

3. Section (C) determines how well technological requirements are met for the smart factory (SF).

4. Section (D) is for determining how well managerial requirements are met for SF.

5. Section (E) is for determining how well organizational requirements are met for SF.

6. Section (F) is for determining how well human-related requirements are met for SF.

Researchers must be confident that the questions they put would allow the required data to be collected, so this survey consists of many types of questions:

A. Checklist-questions: include a list of choices, objects, and items, and the responder is asked to choose the suitable for the situation. To name a few:

Industry Type:

- | | | |
|---|--|---------------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Defense | <input type="checkbox"/> Food Processing | <input type="checkbox"/> Textile |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Aerospace | <input type="checkbox"/> Wood/furniture | <input type="checkbox"/> Agricultural |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Electronic | <input type="checkbox"/> Petrochemical | <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Automotive | <input type="checkbox"/> Construction | <input type="checkbox"/> Others |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Logistic and Transport | <input type="checkbox"/> IT | |

Please indicate the number of employees in your company.

- Up to 19 employees 250 to 499 employees
 20 to 99 employees 500 or 1000 employees
 100 to 249 employees 1001 or more employees

B. Multiple-choice questions offer many potential responses, and the individual is asked to choose the most appropriate. For example:

14- Which of following hurdles do you expect to face for switching to smart factory? (You can check more than one for each group)

Technological	Managerial	Organizational	Human
<input type="checkbox"/> Acquisition of Technologies	<input type="checkbox"/> Strategy development	<input type="checkbox"/> Reengineering organizational structure	<input type="checkbox"/> Qualified labor
<input type="checkbox"/> Installation of Technologies	<input type="checkbox"/> Vision & Mission development	<input type="checkbox"/> Business Process reengineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Collaborative interaction
<input type="checkbox"/> Utilization of Technologies	<input type="checkbox"/> Proper project manager skills	<input type="checkbox"/> Change management	<input type="checkbox"/> Innovative thinking
<input type="checkbox"/> Going live (implementation)	<input type="checkbox"/> Commitment and support	<input type="checkbox"/> Create collaborative culture	<input type="checkbox"/> Digital culture
<input type="checkbox"/> Maintenance	<input type="checkbox"/> Networked collaboration	<input type="checkbox"/> Info-integration from heterogeneous sources.	<input type="checkbox"/> Knowledge and experiences
<input type="checkbox"/> Upgrading	<input type="checkbox"/> Leadership style	<input type="checkbox"/> Cross-divisional transparency	<input type="checkbox"/> Data-related skills

C. Rating scale-questions include a list of things to be graded. For instance:

50- How do you evaluate the readiness of your workforce to use the following technologies?	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
IoT						
CPS						
CC						
BI						
AM						
CIM						
BD						
Robotics						
AR						
ERP						
Simulation						

15-How do you describe your enterprise structure regarding the following features? (Please check for each)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Lean						
Agility						
Integration						
Smartness						

16-How do you describe your enterprise culture regarding the support of the following features? (Please check for each)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Digitalization-orientation						
Knowledge-orientation						
Innovation orientation						
Quality-orientation						
Collaboration						
Continues Learning						
Participation						

An ordinal scale with varying rates of response was used in the survey. Depending on the question's nature, the assessment of the queries was done on a six-stage scale ("N / A" to "5") and based on a 5-point Likert scale ("strongly disagree" to "strongly agree"). Similarly, the proposed readiness model is used to calculate smart manufacturing enterprise readiness rates from 0 to 5.

D. Most questions are closed, and directed questions allow limited answers to elicit quantitative data. To simplify the survey and make it more analyzable, fully open questions were avoided.

A survey is usually designed to collect several different types of data, including facts, strategies, technologies, capabilities, and ideas. In this context, this assessment survey questions are designed to collect data about the following:

- General questions were designed to capture some data for the main description of considered manufacturing organizations in this study, such as (Enterprise Name, Industry type, address)
- Questions related to assess the existing level of related knowledge and all related technologies, e.g., “Please indicate knowledge level (how much you know) of your enterprise about these technologies.”
- Requirements-fulfillment questions: the maturity-related question will require the survey participants to rank readiness and maturity for each SF requirement's dimension from most significant (5) to more trivial (0), and for all related maturity items, e.g., “Which of the following technologies are already acquired at your organization but not utilized yet?”; “How well do you think the following design principles are met in your enterprise?”.
- Perspective and orientation identifying questions enable collecting a specific type of data that describe strategies, goals, opinions, practices, and plans to capture and understand a manufacturing enterprise's digitalizing efforts and development perspectives, e.g., “Have you formed a team of experts for Industry 4.0 in your enterprise?”; “Has your company started digitizing their management practices?”; “What is your organization's biggest digital transformation goal?”.

5.2. Validity and Reliability

Testing the validity and reliability of the assessment-survey scales used to measure the readiness and maturity level for Industry 4.0 based smart factory via five essential requirements (dimensions) is of high importance for the research study results.

Cronbach's alpha is employed to test scale reliability, and Pearson's correlation is used to test the validity.

5.2.1. Validity

Several literature surveys were conducted to conceptualize the study's core elements (industry 4.0; business model; smart factory). A huge part of conducted literature surveys relates to determining the main components, design principles, and features of the study's partitions (see chapter 2). Relying on 220 researchers' diverse opinions from various disciplines constitutes a core fundamental for building a reliable and measurable study.

In the third chapter, the study provided a primary reference for measuring maturity at various levels. The adoption of these requirements in building a model for measuring maturity contributes to building a coherent and integrated study, thus adding credibility and greater consistency between the study's various variables and dimensions (the model) with the requirements suggested by the study. Besides, the author developed a model and framework that allowed a standardized comparison between the individual cases leading to a high validity level.

To increase the consistency and coherence of study variables, a business model has been proposed for smart factories corresponding to proposed requirements. This study also provides a framework that contributes to creating an appropriate environment for establishing and managing smart factories. Ultimately, the maturity items used in this study integrate and correspond with all the above.

Pearson's correlation is a statistical method for determining the strength of a linear relationship between two variables (Leslie et al, 2006). It is widely used to assess the validity of the questionnaire (de Barros Ahrens, et al., 2020; Valim, et al., 2015). Construct validity of each dimension was assessed by determining its correlation with their sub-dimensions using Pearson's correlation coefficient. Construct validity refers to whether a scale or test measures the construct adequately. The following Tables 5.2 - 5.7 show Pearson correlation for the construct validity of requirements and subdimensions.

Table 5.2: Construct validity for knowledge maturity

	Knowledge maturity correlation
Does your enterprise have awareness and knowledge of the smart factory?	0.747**
Do you have studied or initialized any projects related to I4.0?	0.790**
Does your enterprise engage in any efforts to build desired awareness for digital transformation?	0.785**
Does your enterprise have proper awareness and knowledge of I4.0?	0.820**
Are the educational specializations of your employees related to the I4.0's technologies?	0.832**

Table 5.3: Construct validity for technological ML

Technological subdimension	Technological maturity correlation
Technologies	0.834**
Design principles	0.947**
Features	0.988**

Table 5.4: Construct validity for managerial ML

Managerial subdimension	Managerial maturity correlation
direction setting	0.801**
Leadership	0.954**
Managerial practices	0.885**

Table 5.5: Construct validity for organizational ML

Organizational subdimension	Organizational maturity correlation
Business Model	0.972**
Structure	0.926**
Culture-contents	0.976**

Table 5.6: Construct validity for human-related

	Human-related maturity correlation
Real-time capability	0.864**
Innovative-thinking	0.854**
Dynamic skills	0.817**
Interactive skills	0.881**
Data-related skills	0.852**

Table 5.7: Dimensional construct validity

Dimensions (requirements)	Total maturity correlation
Knowledge maturity	0.687**
technological maturity	0.985**
Managerial maturity	0.959**
Organizational maturity	0.955**
Human-related maturity	0.807**

As can be seen from the above tables, all dimensions and sub-dimensions are related, proved by the significant value of Pearson correlation.

5.2.2. Reliability

Internal consistency assesses how interrelated our assessment survey items are and tests the homogeneity and suitability of the survey elements (dimensions and questions) as a useful study tool. Internal consistency is measured using Cronbach's alpha to calculate how closely the study's questions represent each of the variables related to a group. Alpha ranges from 0 to 1, large Cronbach alpha showing a higher degree of interrelation between test items. Alpha values are healthy and acceptable between 0.70 and 0.95 (Nunnally, 1978; Sekaran, 2003; Karra, 2018).

Cronbach's Alpha test is used to assess the reliability of the independent dimensions' subdimension in the SPSS statistics software (de Barros Ahrens, et al., 2020; Valim, et al., 2015). Table 5.8 provides the results of the samples.

Table 5.8: Dimensional Cronbach's alpha value

<i>Dimensions</i>	<i>Sub-dimensions</i>	<i>Items</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>
Knowledge	1	13	0.791
Technological	3	9	0.816
Managerial	3	13	0.945
Organizational	3	9	0.981
Human related	1	4	0.889
Cross-dimensions	5	48	0.934

The results above table show that the sub-dimensions of requirements have high internal consistency. The overall value of the alpha coefficient for 236 items of the survey was (0.969), and this means that the reliability coefficient is high. Thus, the research has ensured the survey's items' validity and reliability to analyze the results and answer survey questions.

5.3. Smart Factory Requirements Maturity Index (SFRMI)

The degree of maturity remains unknown when architecture is given, which is a crucial question when determining maturity. This study aims to estimate the digital readiness of Turkish manufacturing enterprises via a scale of maturity levels. Based on the survey developed, this section proposes SFRMI. The author defined a total of 105 maturity items (see Table 5.9) that are unequally grouped into nine sub-dimensions within the main requirements dimensions which are prepared in compatibility with the requirements and the survey.

Table 5.9: Maturity model contents

Dimensions	Sub-dimensions	Maturity items
Knowledge		Awareness and understanding
Technological	Technologies	CPS; IoT; BD; CC; AM; CIM; ERP; BI; AR; Robotics; Simulation.
	Design-principles	Virtualization; Digitalization; Interoperability; Integrated system; Standardization; Flexibility; Service Orientation; Modularity; Safety and Security; Decentralization.
	Features	Self-controlled; Self-organization; Self-configuration; Self-coordination; Self-diagnostic; Self-decision; Self-compare; Self-optimization; Self-adapt; Self-predict; Self-aware.
		Connectivity; Integrability; Networked; Real-time Skills; Accessibility; Transparency; Traceability; Automation; Smooth data flow.
		Need-oriented; Small-lot order; Customization; Individualized product.
		Info-integration from heterogeneous sources; Intelligent visualization; Real-time data availability from heterogeneous sources; Intelligent analysis; Intelligent Learning; Intelligent sensing; Intelligent reconfiguration; Intelligent proactive behavior; Intelligent awareness; Intelligent predictability.
Agility; Lean; Adaptability; Sustainability; Optimization; Responsive; Scalability; Efficiency.		
Managerial	Direction setting	Clear vision & mission; Overall-strategy; SMART goals; Ongoing commitment and support.
	Leadership	Innovation-driven; Networked collaboration; Openness to change; Coaching style; Digital Skills; Tech-savvy.
	Managerial practice	Agility maximization; Lean maximization; Culture enhancement; Dynamic abilities; Motivation system; Participation; Innovation; Learning.
Organizational	Business Model	Comprehensive; Collaborative; Data-driven; Responsive; Dynamic; Networked;
	Structural	Lean; Agility; Integration; Smartness; Modularity;
	Culture-contents	Digitalization values; Knowledge orientation; Innovation orientation; Quality orientation; Collaboration; Learning; Initiatives & participation;
Human-related		Real-time capability; Innovative thinking; Dynamic skills; Interactivity; Data related skills;

In order to facilitate the analysis for the smart factory maturity model, manufacturing enterprises' maturity profiles are grouped under six clusters to summarize results better. These clusters and related lengths are shown in Table 5.10.

Table 5.10: Levels limit values

Maturity level	Range
Outsider (level 0)	0 – 0.83
Beginner (level 1),	0.84 – 1.66
Intermediate (level 2)	1.67 – 2.50
Experienced-learner (level 3)	2.51– 3.34
Expert (Level 4)	3.35– 4.18
First-mover-leader (Level 5)	4.19 – 5

Outsider consists of the enterprises that do not meet any of SF's requirements or never initialized any smart projects. **Beginner** are the enterprises that starts to embrace some technologies and initiate reengineering traditional functions, structures, and models. **Intermediate** level includes the enterprise that individually and separately (low level) meeting of some requirements. The **experienced-learner** level consists of the enterprises that meet many of the requirements at mid-level, acquire most of the technologies, build some of the design principles, and individually enable some features. **Expert** is a maturity level where the enterprise is ready to implement a smart factory, and most of the design principles and features are acquired and ready to use. **First-mover-leader** consists of the enterprises that all SF requirements are met and started to bear fruit; thus, a smart manufacturing environment is established, inspiring many businesses to start their smart initiative.

The range of each level is determined by (highest point in Likert scale (5) – the lowest point in Likert scale (0))/the number of the levels used (6), to determine the maximum and minimum length of a Likert type scale. Consequently, to determine the overall maturity level, limit values (range) (Akdil, et al., 2018; Wu , et al., 2017) for each level is given in Table 5.10, The Smart Factory Requirements Maturity Index (SFRMI) equation of considered enterprise will be:

$$SFRMI = \sum_{i=1}^n RM_i * W_i \dots\dots\dots(5.1)$$

where:

RM_i: maturity index for the (i) requirement,

i: set of main requirements, i: 1...n;

(i) ∈ {knowledge, technological, managerial, organizational, human related}; (n= 5)

W_i: the individual weight of requirements

Weights of the smart factory specifications as one of the two key components of the smart manufacturing maturity model have a strong effect on the evaluation maturity.

These weights are calculated to evaluate the maturity model of the smart factory's different requirements in practice. The unequal effect of each predefined criteria (SF's requirements) on the model's results requires utilizing the criteria' weights via expert preferences. Therefore, it is worth using the AHP approach developed by Saaty (1980) as a mechanism of criteria weighting. Generally, the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) seeks to measure the relative preferences of a given set of alternatives on a ratio scale, based on the decision-maker's opinion. It emphasizes the significance of the decision-intuitive maker's judgments and the accuracy of comparing alternatives in the decision-making process (Lin, Lee, & Wang, 2009).

The basic idea of this approach is to convert estimates of importance in proportion to a set of grades or weights based on the terms of the pairwise comparison, as it creates an integration of different quantitative and qualitative measures to be collected in one comprehensive degree reflecting the alternative order between a set of decision alternatives (Lin, Lee, & Wang, 2009). Therefore, surveyed experts were asked to judge a pair of SF's requirements to build a pairwise comparison matrix for requirements weights. Figure 5.1 presents smart factory requirements (knowledge, technological, managerial, organizational, and human-related) structure for which experts will estimate their weights.

Figure 5.1: Smart factory requirements

The following can be done manually or automatically by the AHP software kit:

1. Experts pairwise comparison matrix
2. Synthesizing the pairwise comparison matrix for SF's requirements
3. Calculate each requirement's weight, calculate the consistency ratio, and calculating λ_{\max} to calculate the consistency index (CI).

Table 5.11 offers the experts-views pairwise comparison matrix for SFs Requirements.

Table 5.11: Pair-wise comparison matrix for SF's requirements

	Knowledge	Technological	Managerial	Organizational	Human
Knowledge	1	0.25	0.4375	0.4375	1
Technological	4	1	2.625	2.5	4.375
Managerial	2.286	0.381	1	1.125	2.75
Organizational	2.286	0.4	0.889	1	2.75
Human	1	0.2286	0.3636	0.3634	1
SUM	10.57	2.260	5.315	5.426	11.875

Synthesizing the requirements pair-wise comparison matrix is performed by dividing each matrix element by its column total. For example, the value 0.094 in Table 5.12 is obtained by dividing 1 (from Table 5.11) by 10.606, the sum of the column items in Table 5.11 (1+4+2.375+2.341+0.88=10.57).

The weights in Table 5.12 can be obtained by finding the row averages. For example, the weight of knowledge concerning the rest of requirements in Table 5.12 is calculated via dividing the sum of the rows (0.094; 0.111; 0.082; 0.076; 0.091) by the number of requirements (columns), i.e., 5, in order to obtain the value 0.090. The weights for requirements, indicated in Table 5.12, are given below.

Table 5.12: Synthesized matrix for requirements

	Knowledge	Technological	Managerial	Organizational	Human	Requirements Weights
Knowledge	0.094	0.111	0.082	0.076	0.091	0.090
Technological	0.377	0.443	0.513	0.444	0.354	0.429
Managerial	0.224	0.169	0.195	0.244	0.232	0.202
Organizational	0.221	0.177	0.142	0.177	0.242	0.195
Human	0.084	0.101	0.068	0.059	0.081	0.083

$$\lambda_{\max} = 5.042 \quad CI = 0.0105, \quad RI = 1,12 \quad CR = 0: 0.0094 < 0.1 \text{ OK}$$

As CR's value is less than 0.1, the judgments are acceptable to determine a company's maturity index. Then we need to pre-calculate the maturity index of requirements, sub-dimensions, and items. The final weighted version of the SFRMI equation is:

$$W.SFRMI = \sum(\text{Knowledge} * 0.09) + (\text{Technological} * 0.429) + (\text{Managerial} * 0.202) + (\text{Organizational} * 0.195) + (\text{Human} * 0.083) \dots \dots \dots (5.2)$$

The reasons for using this requirements-based hierarchy structure are (1) providing a defined framework for maturity levels, (2) developing an index structure, SFRMI, support manufacturing enterprise for the implementation of concrete projects by defining the steps forward to achieve a transformation and goals, (3) identifying what

the sub-dimensions an enterprise has at each level, (4) providing clear diagnostic criteria, (5) providing integrated maturity items, either vertical or horizontal, as well as (6) the integrability and interoperability of requirements, and (7) providing a comprehensive maturity model.

In this way, the industry 4.0 based smart manufacturing requirements maturity level provides a generic model to the digital readiness maturity levels for several industry types.

5.3.1. Requirements Maturity Index

To identify the individual maturity index of SF-requirements for each company, six stages are used, and answers of the assessment survey are evaluated regarding these stages such as "Level 0: Outsider"; " Level 1: Beginner"; "Level 2: Intermediate"; "Level 3: Experienced-learner"; "Level 4: Expert" and "Level 5: First-mover-leader". The Maturity is examined under these levels for each requirement (associated field). Thus, each requirement in this maturity model is graded with related assessment survey questions by 0–5. Calculated scores of requirements are grouped under sub-dimensions in order to identify maturity levels individually and overall. Equations to calculate maturity levels are given in Eqs. 5.3 - 5.17. In the next step, the maturity Index (MI) of each requirement results from calculating the weighted average of all sub-dimension within its related requirement. This method's driving idea is to find the weighted average for each sub-dimension via sub-dimension equations to estimate the individual maturity index of requirements. All requirements' equations are calculated. After that, the individual equations of the requirement are applied to estimate manufacturing enterprises' maturity index.

5.3.1.1. Maturity index for technological requirements (MT)

To determine the maturity index of a company according to equation (5.2), the equation (Eq. 5.3) needs to be calculated based on the outputs of equations (5.4, 5.5, 5.6). The idea behind the 5.3 equation is to calculate the averages of the summation of the weighted average of all subdimensions maturity (technologies, design principles, and features).

$$RM_1 = MT = [MTT+ MTD + MTF]/ 3 \quad \dots\dots\dots (5.3)$$

where:

MT: The maturity of technological requirements.

MTT: Technologies Maturity level.

MTD: Design Principles Maturity level.

MTF: Features Maturity level.

The limit values for each level given in Table 5.10 and the maturity index for technological requirements (5.3 equation output) are used to find technological maturity. Besides, the technological maturity levels are explained in Table 5.13.

Table 5.13: Technological maturity level requirements

ML	Requirements
Level 0	Enterprise does not meet any of the requirements for Industry 4.0.
Level 1	Some of the requirements are at beginning level, some pilot initiatives started in functional departments, some individual acquisition of technology is started.
Level 2	Some of the requirements are met at low level, many pilot initiatives in functional departments. For instance, integration; virtualization; digitalization; and automation levels are at low or individual level. Also, individual acquisition of technology is started.
Level 3	Some of the requirements are met at mid-level, many innovative technologies are acquired and starting to interact for establishing many design principles such as integration; virtualization; digitalization; interoperability and automation levels are in mid-level but still in departmental level.
Level 4	Completed technological infrastructure. Most of design principles are created and desired features are funded. Establishment of many capabilities are complete. Company's business processes and technologies are at medium level in terms of integration, (data collecting/using/ sharing).
Level 5	An automated interactive environment of all smart entities is created, building competitive capabilities such as agility; lean; adaptability; sustainability; optimization; responsive; scalability; efficiency.

This aggregate formula is the core of measuring the smart factory maturity. It collects all key technologies, design principles and features that enable smart factories and express an overall technological maturity level. A set of equations are proposed below to calculate the weighted averages of subdimensions.

A. Technological Maturity of technologies (MTT)

Equations (5.3) have been calculated based on the maturity index of related items. As shown below, to estimate the technologies maturity index. Equation 5.4 is used to calculate items' maturity of technologies based on related questions.

$$MTT = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n MTT_i * WT_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n WT_i} \dots\dots\dots(5.4)$$

$$MTT_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m MTT_{ij}}{m} \dots\dots\dots(5.5)$$

where:

MTT_i= maturity items of technologies (smart factory proposed technologies).

WT_i= weight of ith item under technologies.

n= the number of related maturity items

m= the number of related questions

i= the index of items

j= the index of number of related questions

B. Design Principles Maturity level (MTd)

Equations (5.6) are developed to estimate the design principles maturity index.

$$MTD = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n MTD_i * WD_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n WD_i}$$

where:

MTD : design principles maturity level.

WD_i= weight of ith design principles.

n= the number of related maturity items

i= the index of items

C. Features Maturity level

The diverse scope of smart factory features imposes asking many questions to estimate features' readiness and identify the maturity of a set of features needed to increase digitalization and implement smart factories to compete in the digital environment more effectively. Equations (5.7) have been calculated based on the maturity index of related items, to estimate the features maturity index.

$$MTF = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n MTF_i * WF_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n WF_i}$$

Where:

MTF_i = features maturity items

WF_i = weight of ith Features.

n= the number of related maturity items

i= the index of items

5.3.1.2. Maturity index for managerial requirements

The idea behind the 5.8 equation is to calculate the averages of the summation of the weighted average of all subdimensions maturity level of managerial requirements. The limit values for each level given in Table 5.10 are used with the maturity index for managerial requirements (5.8 equation output) to determine the managerial maturity level. The managerial maturity level is explained in Table 5.14.

$$RM2= MM= [MMDS + MML+ MMP]/3 \dots\dots\dots(5.8)$$

where:

MMDS: maturity of direction setting items

MML: maturity of leadership

MMP: maturity of managerial practices.

Table 5.14: Managerial maturity level requirements

ML	Requirements
Level 0	Enterprise does not meet any of the requirements for Industry 4.0.
Level 1	Management has a clear vision and mission about industry 4.0; leadership has proper features and abilities for (SF) implementation, and management is considering implementing Industry 4.0 strategy with investments in a few areas.
Level 2	Proper leadership, clear strategies, SMART goals and leaders develop plans for Industry 4.0 and has made investments plan for next five years
Level 3	Clear strategies; identified goals, smart leadership, conducting some supporting practices; and applying some implementation goals.
Level 4	Providing a proper supporting and commitment along implementation journey, majority of the required managerial practices are applied.
Level 5	Fulfill all managerial requirements, a proper managerial environment is created for digital transformation and networked production system management.

Therefore, the Equations (5.8) has been calculated based on maturity index of related items, to estimate the related subdimensions maturity index.

A. Maturity index of direction setting items (MMDS)

Equations (5.9) have been calculated based on the maturity index of related items, as shown below, to estimate the direction-setting maturity index.

$$MMDS = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n MMDS_i * w_{di}}{\sum_{i=1}^n WDS_i} \dots\dots\dots(5.9)$$

where:

MMDS_i: maturity of direction setting items

WDS_i: weight of ith direction setting items.

n= the number of related maturity items

i= the index of items

B. Maturity index of leadership items (MML)

Equations (5.10) have been calculated based on the maturity index of related items, as shown below, to estimate the leadership maturity index.

$$MML = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n MML_i * W_{Li}}{\sum_{i=1}^n W_{Li}} \dots\dots\dots (5.10)$$

where:

MML_i: the maturity of leadership items

WL_i: weight of ith items for leadership.

n= the number of related maturity items

i= the index of items

C. Maturity index of managerial practices items (MM_p)

Equations (5.11) have been calculated based on the maturity index of related items. As it is shown below, to estimate the managerial practices maturity index.

$$MMP = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n MMP_i * WP_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n WP_i}$$

where:

MMP_i: maturity of managerial practices items

WP_i: weight of ith items for managerial practices.

n= the number of related maturity items

i= the index of items

5.3.1.3. Maturity index of Organizational Requirements (MO)

The idea behind the 5.12 equation is to calculate the averages of the summation of the subdimensions maturity of organizational requirements. To determine the organizational maturity level, the limit values for each level, as given in Table 5.10, are used with maturity index for organizational requirements (5.12 equation output), the organizational maturity level is explained in Table 5.15.

Table 5.15: Organizational maturity level requirements

ML	Requirements
Level 0	Enterprise does not meet any of the requirements for Industry 4.0.
Level 1	There are pilot initiatives to generate business models or transform the current one via creating desired features. Organizational structure is not suitable enough.
Level 2	Many of the features are enabled to enhance the current business model to be compatible with smart factory requirements, starting enrichment of culture contents, and reengineering the existing organizational structure.
Level 3	Many organizational structure features are established for initial Industry 4.0 projects and new business models are being generated; many useful contents are created in organizational culture for facilitating digital transformation.
Level 4	Organizational structure, culture contents, and business model are suitable for managing transformation across the company.
Level 5	A proper organizational environment is available for implementing, operating and managing the smart factory.

$$RM_3 = MO = [MOBM + MOS + MOCC] / 3 \quad \dots\dots\dots (5.12)$$

MOBM: maturity of business model items

MOS: maturity of structural

MOC: maturity of culture contents

The calculation of Equations (5.11) relies on the compound maturity index of related subdimensions, as is shown below.

A. Maturity index of Business Model items (MOBM)

The Business Model maturity level calculation utilizes the Equations (5.13) to find a weighted average of related maturity index items.

$$\text{MOBM} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \text{MOBM}_i * \text{WBM}_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n \text{WBM}_i} \dots\dots\dots (5.13)$$

where:

MOBM_i: maturity of business model items

WBM_i: weight of ith items for Business model.

n= the number of related maturity items

i= the index of items

B. Maturity of Structural items (MOS)

the calculation of structural maturity level utilizes the Equations (5.13) to find a weighted average of related maturity index items.

$$\text{MOS} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \text{MOS}_i * \text{WS}_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n \text{WS}_i} \dots\dots\dots (5.14)$$

where

MOS_i: maturity of structural items

WS_i: weight of ith items for structure.

n= the number of related maturity items

i= the index of items

C. Maturity of Culture contents items (MOc)

The calculation of culture maturity level utilizes the Equations (5.14) to find a weighted average of related maturity index items.

$$\text{MOC} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \text{MOC}_i * \text{WC}_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n \text{WC}_i} \dots\dots\dots (5.15)$$

where:

MOC_i: maturity of culture contents items

WC_i: weight of ith items for culture contents.

n= the number of related maturity items

i= the index of items

5.3.1.4. Maturity of Human-related Requirements (MHH)

The idea behind the 5.15 equation is to calculate the averages of the weighted averages summation of maturity index of human-related requirements items.

$$MHH = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n MHH_i * WH_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n WH_i} \dots\dots\dots (5.16)$$

where:

MHH_i: maturity of human-related items

WH_i: weight of ith items for human-related

n= the number of related maturity items

i= the index of items

The maturity index for human-related requirements (5.15 equation output) is used with the limit values for each level given in Table 5.10 to determine the human-related maturity level. The human-related maturity level is explained in Table 5.16.

Table 5.16: Human-related maturity level requirements

ML	Requirements
Level 0	Enterprise does not meet any of the requirements for Industry 4.0.
Level 1	There are pilot initiatives to generate the new workforce capabilities.
Level 2	Many of the capabilities are enabled to enhance the current employees' performance to compatible with smart factory requirements, such as innovative thinking, interactivity and data-related skills.
Level 3	Enabling dynamic skills, innovative thinking, interactivity and data-related skills.
Level 4	Enabling real-time capabilities, including instant decision making, and responsiveness.
Level 5	Proper workforce capabilities are ready for implementing, operating and managing the smart factory.

5.3.1.5. Maturity of knowledge requirements (MK)

The idea behind the 5.16 equation is to calculate the averages of the weighted averages of maturity index of knowledge requirements items.

$$MK = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n MK_i}{i} \dots\dots\dots (5.17)$$

where:

MK_i: weight of ith items for knowledge maturity

n= the number of related maturity items

i= the index of items

The proposed set of formulations aggregate the maturity scores from items to dimensions. Via calculating each dimension's scores, the overall maturity level is obtained and wrapped to one of the levels 0-6 (from outside to leader). This index structure developed in this section allows for:

- the calculation and analysis of an overall maturity value.

- the calculation and analysis maturity under different dimensions.
- allows for different weighting schemes to be incorporated into the model.
- allows for analyzing the sensitivity of the values with respect to changing weights.
- allows for pairwise comparison across companies and within sectors.

Hence, this chapter provided an assessment survey and provided an index development based on maturity measurement and analysis

CHAPTER 6:

FIELD APPLICATION

This chapter provides the field application of the survey and the maturity index developed in chapter 5 to demonstrate how the assessment survey tool and the index calculations could be used. The field application is performed in the automotive sector by multi-company case studies.

Case study refers to an individual, community, organization, or event's recorded history or observational investigation into a real-life phenomenon. In a case study, a particular organization's events can typically be represented as facing critical decisions or circumstances such as the launch of a new product, new technology, and management crises (Zikmund, et al., 2013). The approach allows the scope and essence of the phenomenon under investigation to be thoroughly examined and understood.

Thus, case studies were selected as the appropriate approach due to the uniqueness of the industry 4.0 based smart factory topic and comprehensive and multi-dimensional nature of the assessment survey developed.

6.1. Selection of The Case-Study Companies and Survey Approach

In this section, the considered manufacturing enterprises will be briefly presented.

Turkish industry survey participants were selected from manufacturing firms of different sectors. Considered organizations are selected from the automotive sector to show that the model is generic and not specific for a given sector.

Potential companies that can be representative of different sectors are contacted via a wide variety of channels, including the Chamber of Mechanical Engineers, Defense and Aerospace Industry Manufacturers Association (SASAD), Ankara Logistics Base, and OSTIM, as well as personal networks and company's websites.

This study's application progress is negatively affected by the still on-going COVID-19 pandemic, which everybody worldwide is well aware of. The author was subjected to partially operating educational and manufacturing organizations, staff absence due to infections and quarantines, curfews, and bans. The companies were reluctant to accept people into the organizations, and face-to-face meetings with participants became impossible under pandemic conditions. In line with the current desires of most surveyed organizations the author was forced to distribute the survey via on-line or e-

mail and expect the answer for the conducted companies. Therefore, the assessment survey was distributed online (link), email, or hardcopy, and it is left to companies' choice to fill in whichever way they are preferred. This was required to ensure no details were lost and only one response for each manufacturing organization.

The data collection is conducted during November to December 2020. Although all the companies in the defense sector were contacted via SaSaD, only one company from the Defense sector filled the survey. Also, there was an unanalysable (invalid) response due to data inconclusiveness, and four companies claimed they could not submit or evaluate since they are not using the smart concept or the topic is irrelevant to them. Furthermore, no response is received from the 38 companies contacted. As a result, 18 assessable and meaningful responses have been produced in total. This corresponded to a response rate of 30%. In the first three weeks, the most significant response could be produced.

Out of 18 responses, 8 of them are in the automotive sector. This representing the most meaningful group of responses. Also considering the high dominance and significance of the automotive sector for the Turkish economy, and the fact that it is the most relevant sector for industry 4.0 based smart factory, the analysis is built on 8 cases of the automotive sector. Dominance in the automotive sector is compatible with the results offered in the Turkish perspective section. Section 2.4.1 had already shown the Turkish industry sectors' significance and selecting automotive sector compatible with table 40 results depending on Turkstat data in 2020. Figure 2.37 reveals that motor vehicles and trailers sectors affect by 10%, these metrics interpret and prioritize the reasons for selecting this sector in this study.

The questionnaire was analyzed utilizing Microsoft Excel and SPSS instruments. In this study, company names could not be revealed due to the desire to remain anonymous since they operate in the automotive area.

Before accessing the companies, a pilot study has been carried out in three Turkish firms via an online and hardcopy assessment-survey. Respondents' answers were reviewed to see if all the questions needed were answered in a specified manner. It is also investigated whether the participants were part of the survey target group. Each survey takes around an hour.

Each company was evaluated individually for their maturity of each requirement group and graded from zero to five. Surveyed cases with the highest maturity were given five for the maturity scale, meaning they have wholly implemented smart concepts in the organization. The researcher assessed the maturity level after conducting a survey based on the individual-contribute weights assessed jointly by the academic experts for each maturity item.

The significant quantity (75%, six companies) of the surveyed manufacturing enterprises has more than 1001 employees, 12.5% (one company) of the conducted firms have less than 500, and 12.5% has less than 250, the distribution of eight companies concerning size is given in Figure 6.1.

Figure 6.1: Surveyed enterprises size

Distribution of the companies with respect to business type reveals that 62.5% depend on Business to Business (B2B) and 62.5% on Business to Customer (B2C), while only 25% are depended on Business to Government (B2G) type.

Figure 6.2: Business type

The companies' distribution concerning the degree of their products' technological level is given in Figure 6.3. It is shown that 50 % of the surveyed enterprise products had

high technology, and 50% of products are mid-tech. Thus, the surveyed companies still need to enhance their products' technological-level.

Figure 6.3: Technological level

According to the company replies in question, "where are you on the I4.0 implementation journey?", 25% of the participants claim that they are in the intermediate stage, 25% of the participants are in the beginner stage, 25% are in the experienced stage, 12.5% of the participants are outside this journey, and 12.5% are in expert level, as it is shown in Figure 6.4. Generally, 87.5% of surveyed companies need to re-engineer their vision, strategies, management practices, business models, and technologies compatible with smart factory requirements.

Figure 6.4: Maturity level assumed by the company

6.2. Calculation of The SF's Maturity Levels for 8 Case Companies

Smart factory maturity level calculation includes five main requirements equations. Each requirement area can be considered a self-contained module, and thus it is possible to add or remove one or more sub-dimensions if they are not meaningful in certain industrial situations or have no impact on the macro-structure foundation, functions

quality, and existed features. This section is devoted to the application of the scientific method to calculate the maturity indices for the case company data to determine their maturity level for the identified requirements, dimensions, and sets of maturity items within the smart factory context for obtaining a scientific and statistical background for a managerial road-map development for industry 4.0-based smart manufacturing enterprise.

During the indices' calculation, the author adopts using academic experts' ratings to determine each item's relative contribution and impact, which are used to calculate the weighted maturity score. The Analytic Hierarchy Process's objective is to assess and select the most appropriate weighting of smart factory core requirements and calculate the total maturity level in equation 5.1. Depending on experts' ratings of the relative weight of maturity items, the sub-dimensions contribution and requirements' contribution are also identified to validate the maturity item's practical meaningfulness.

The next Figure (6.5) shows the surveyed experts' characteristics, who have provided weights assessments.

Figure 6.5: Surveyed experts' description

6.2.1. Requirements Maturity Index (Dimensional Analysis)

To define maturity levels of SF-requirements for each company, an overall weighted maturity is calculated by aggregating across all maturity subdimensions via applying

equations 5.3 to 5.17 to provide a top-level indicator of maturity. A total maturity score has been identified to the companies depending on the aggregation.

6.2.1.1. Knowledge Maturity (MK)

The main objective of this dimension is to describe and explain the required knowledge level to embracing an industry 4.0 based smart factory. Based on the answers, the surveyed company's knowledge availability in terms of smart factory requirements has been classified into six groups, ranging from outside (level 0) to leader (level 5)—the result is shown in Figures 6.6 & 6.7.

Figure 6.6: Ranking of the companies for knowledge maturity

The scores found above for knowledge level show that 75% of the organizations have suitable knowledge to implement and operate smart factories, while 25% are still working to gain this knowledge. When comparing the calculated maturity scores (given in Figure 6.7) with the maturity limit values in Table 5.10, the following figure's maturity levels distribution is obtained.

Figure 6.7: Knowledge maturity level

Table 6.1 provides the knowledge maturity score in terms of company's size. The 100 to 249 employees' company was assessed in Level 4 (Expert) forming 33.3% of the expert companies. The "250 to 499 employees" company was located in the

intermediate level, forming 12.5% of the total sample and 50% of the intermediate level. The "1001 or more employees" companies have a diverse knowledge level and form 75% of the total sample (6 companies). 50% of them reached level 5 (3 company) that form 100% of leader level companies, 33.3% (2 company are in an expert level that consists of 66.7% of expert companies, and the rest 16.66% (1 company) are still in the intermediate level that consists 50% of intermediate companies.

Table 6.1: Knowledge maturity in term of company size

			Knowledge ML			Total
			Intermediate	Expert	Leader	
Size	100 to 249 employees	Count	0	1	0	1
		% within Knowledge ML	0.0%	33.3%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	12.5%
	250 to 499 employees	Count	1	0	0	1
		% within Knowledge ML	50.0%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	12.5%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
	1001 or more employees	Count	1	2	3	6
		% within Knowledge ML	50.0%	66.7%	100.0%	75.0%
		% of Total	12.5%	25.0%	37.5%	75.0%
Total	Count	2	3	3	8	
	% within Knowledge ML	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	% of Total	25.0%	37.5%	37.5%	100.0%	

The overall view shows that only 25% of the surveyed companies suffer from lack of knowledge; also, the knowledge maturity is statistically unrelated to companies' size as proved by the insignificant value of non-parametric Chi-square ($0.129 > 0.05$) (independent factors). The major size group is 1001 or more employees' companies (6 companies). Thus company 4 and 7 need to focus on investing in knowledge enhancement programs. When measuring the relationship between knowledge maturity and overall maturity through the Chi-square test, it was found that there is a significant statistical-relationship between knowledge and achieving overall maturity, proved by the significant value of the non-parametric Chi-square ($0.019 < 0.05$).

6.2.1.2. Technological requirements maturity level (MT)

To investigate which technological requirements are most mature for surveyed companies, each subdimensions maturity was assessed using equations 5.3 to 5.7 as shown below.

A) Technological maturity of technologies

In order to determine the technologies' maturity level, many questions were asked to estimate technologies' readiness in surveyed-cases. The results of implementing the equations 5.4 and 5.5 to the related responses presented in Figures 6.8 and 6.9.

Figure 6.8: Technologies maturity level radar chart

Some points that call for attention to the results listed in Figures 6.10 and 6.11 are the lack of technologies in 37.5% of the surveyed company, while the rest companies of the sample still have low mature levels. Only 25 % of the sample reached level 5 (leader). In Figure 6.9, the companies are plotted according to their readiness score for smart factory requirements.

Figure 6.9: Technologies-maturity's companies rank

Many technologies have recently appeared and evolved. Industry 4.0 based smart factory (I4.0-SF) has emerged as a new industrialization concept that exploits these new technologies to cope with smart environments. The current study showed that the surveyed companies suffer from a lack of used smart factory technologies, especially

in IoT and CPS, while ERP is the most mature technologies, proved by the mean of responses, as shown in Figure 6.10.

Figure 6.10: Used technologies

It can be seen from Figure 6.11 that the technologies maturity level of each surveyed case is low except for ERP. The technologies average is near to 3 points out of the maximum 5 points. Thus, a big difference in technologies maturity level is observed among the companies and technologies. The companies with the highest maturity level have not yet reached the sufficient maturity level of smart factory requirements; they have rather just partially implemented. As noted above, I4.0 is a collective term for technologies that will enable the manifestation of smart factories ' implementation capability. For instance, companies 3, 4, and 7 have the weakest technologies, except ERP, which is considered mature based on companies' responses, while company 8 has high mature level for all the technologies. BI technologies in 62.5% of surveyed companies need enhancement. Overall, CPS and IoT also need to be improved.

Besides that, investigating the maturity level of the different technologies in surveyed companies provides a comparative picture. Figure 6.11 clearly indicates that these technologies have different maturity levels in each surveyed company. For instance, companies 3, 4, and 7 have the weakest technologies. Hence, Figure 6.11 shows the development opportunity in the weakest technologies. providing a practical roadmap to satisfy technological requirements.

Figure 6. 11: Individual maturity level of smart factory's technologies

Table 6.2 shows that the lack of technologies maturity level is not specific to a particular company's size. For instance, 62.5% of the total sample companies (5 companies) are immature, and the remaining three companies, which form 37.5% of the total sample, have a mature level of technologies; all of them are in the expert level. In contrast, the

immature companies consist of two companies in experienced-learner level, two companies in the intermediate level and one company in the beginner level, 80% of immature companies are the companies with “1001 or more employees,” and the rest belong to companies with 250-499 employees, as it is shown in table38.

Table 6.2: Technologies maturity in term of company size

			Technologies ML				Total
			Beginner	Intermediate	Experienced-learner	Expert	
Size	100 to 249 employees	Count	0	0	0	1	1
		% within Technologies	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	33.3%	12.5%
		% of Total	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%	12.5%
	250 to 499 employees	Count	0	1	0	0	1
		% within Technologies	0.0%	50.0%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
	1001 or more employees	Count	1	1	2	2	6
		% within Technologies	100.0%	50.0%	100.0%	66.7%	75.0%
		% of Total	12.5%	12.5%	25.0%	25.0%	75.0%
Total		Count	1	2	2	3	8
		% within Technologies	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% of Total	12.5%	25.0%	25.0%	37.5%	100.0%

Using the non-parametric Chi-square test to measure the dependency between technologies maturity and overall maturity, test results showed a highly significant independence between the technologies and overall maturity level (The techniques showed no statistical relationship to the technological dimension that proved by the significant value of the non-parametric Chi-square ($0.149 > 0.05$), also technologies showed high independence of the company's size due to P-value is greater than 0.05 ($0.73 > 0.05$). Depending on the value of chi-square, several technologies maturity items showed a correlation and dependence with the overall maturity (such as IoT; CPS; CC; BD; Robotics; AM, Simulation), proved by the significant P values (less than 0.05), which ranged between (0.019-0.037) and chi-square values ranging between (10750-5.53). The rest of the technologies (BI; CIM; AR; ERP) showed high independence of the overall maturity level, with P-values ranging between ($0.69-0.18 > 0.05$).

Figure 6. 12:Business type distribution of technologies-maturity level

Figure 6.12 provides the detailed results for the technologies sub-dimensions in terms of business type are provided. 50% of a sample using B2B business, have an acceptable level of technologies maturity, while B2C company have the low maturity level and form 25% of the total sample. In hybrid business B2B; B2C; B2G combined, only 50% (2 companies) have an accepted maturity level while the rest (2 companies) have low technologies level.

To evaluate the surveyed companies' future efforts, a question was included to account for companies' direct and indirect efforts. Unfortunately, most companies suffer from weak preparation efforts. Only 25% of surveyed companies list the embracing of smart technologies as its priority, while the rest considered them as secondary priorities with a response average of ($M=2.82$, $\sigma=1.35$). In contrast, all companies did not have a project to add any smart technologies last year, which was proved by the response mean ($M=1.022$, $\sigma=0.988$) to the absence of SF technologies' acquisition strategies.

B) Design principles maturity level (MTd)

Several questions were included in the survey to evaluate design principles' readiness. The results from the 5.6 equation for 8 cases are shown in Figures 6.13 and 6.14. Figure 6.13 provides an overview of the companies' level for design principles. For 62.5% of case companies, the design principles maturity seems to be very high, and the rest suffers from a lack. Thus, the companies are categorized according to their readiness to smart factory requirements regarding design principles, as shown in the following figure.

Figure 6. 13:Design principles maturity level

Figure 6. 14:Design-principles ML companies ranks

Based on design principles' responses average, 70 % of design-principles have an acceptable mature level. In contrast, the rest of the design-principles like standardization, modularity, and decentralization have less than 3.3 average needs improving to be ready for the smart factory era, as is indicated in Figure 6.15.

Figure 6. 15:Design principles maturity level

Also, in Figure 6.16, detailed results for the design principles sub-dimensions in terms of business type are given. 100% of B2B companies have an accepted maturity of design principles, 50% of B2C companies have an accepted maturity level, while the rest of B2C companies still have low maturity. In combined business B2B; B2C; B2G, only 50% (2 companies) have an accepted maturity level while the remaining (2 companies) have low technologies level.

Figure 6. 16:Business type distribution of design principles-maturity level

A chi-square test of independence is used to investigate the possibility of a correlation between design-principles and overall maturity. The Chi-square test showed a highly significant relation ($p < .005$) between the design-principles and overall maturity and technological requirements, proved by the significant value of the non-parametric Chi-square ($0.021 < 0.05$). Design-principles showed high independence of the company's size due to P-value is greater than 0.05 ($0.317 > 0.05$). Depending on the value of chi-

square, several design principles maturity items showed a correlation and dependence with the overall maturity, such as (Virtualization; Integrated system; Standardization; Flexibility; Modularity; Decentralization), proved by the significant P values (less than 0.05), which ranged between (0.017-0.04) and chi-squared values ranging between (2.43-5.6). While the rest of the design principles (Digitalization; Interoperability; Service-Orientation; Safety and Security) showed high independence of the overall maturity level, due to P-value is greater than 0.05 and ranging between (0.06-0.119>0.05).

Table 6.3 mentions the distribution of design-principles maturity concerning the company's size, and some points mentioned in Table 6.3 call for attention. All companies with 100 to 249 employees (12.5% of the total sample) still in the experienced-learner level forming 50% of the total experienced-learner level. The company with “250 to 499 employees” assessed in level 4 (Expert) (12.5% of the total sample) forming 40% of total expert level. 66.6% of companies with “1001 or more employees” have the desired maturity level while the rest of “1001 or more employees” companies still in levels 2 and 3. 75% of the total sample are 1001 or more employees’ companies. Also, the most mature companies belong to companies with 1001 or more employees. The design-principles showed high independence of the company's size due to P-value is greater than 0.05 (0.505>0.05).

Table 6.3: Distribution of design principles maturity with respect to company size

			Design Principles				Total
			Beginner	Experienced-learner	Expert	Leader	
Size	100 to 249 employees	Count	0	1	0	0	1
		% within Design Principles	0.0%	50.0%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
	250 to 499 employees	Count	0	0	1	0	1
		% within Design Principles	0.0%	0.0%	50.0%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	12.5%
	1001 or more employees	Count	1	1	1	3	6
		% within Design Principles	100.0%	50.0%	50.0%	100.0%	75.0%
		% of Total	12.5%	12.5%	12.5%	37.5%	75.0%
Total		Count	1	2	2	3	8
		% within Design Principles	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% of Total	12.5%	25.0%	25.0%	37.5%	100.0%

C) Features maturity level

To calculate the maturity of the feature, equation 5.7 has been used to identify the maturity index of related features, as shown below, and Figures 6.17 and 6.18 present results from each case. 50% of companies do not have desired features. The rest of the companies have maturity levels draw near the lower limits of maturity, except company 8.

Figure 6. 17: Features maturity score

In Figure 6.17, an overview of the companies' features level is provided. For instance, 37.5% of the companies (C1, C5, and C6), the feature's maturity seems to be suitable but needs enhancement, and 50% suffers from a lack that needs strategic enhancement. Thus, the companies are categorized according to their readiness to smart factory requirements regarding features maturity.

Figure 6. 18: Ranking in terms of features-maturity

Since the industry 4.0 based smart factory concept is rather complicated, the author created a visual that integrates the key features with the smart factory's design principles and enabling technologies (see Figure 2.25). Regarding self-features (Autonomous capabilities), weakness is observed in the maturity level proved by each feature's response average, which indicates immature self-features, (see Figure 6.19). Thus, all companies need to focus on building and acquiring these types of features. The maturity of autonomous capabilities' features is given in Figure 6.19. Depending on the value of chi-square, most of the autonomous capabilities features showed a correlation and dependence with the overall maturity and technological requirements, proved by the significant P values (less than 0.05), which ranged between (0.019-0.037) and chi-squared values ranging between (2.58-5.53). Except for Self-controlled showed a kind of independence based on the non-significant P-value (0.108>0.05).

Figure 6. 19:Autonomous capabilities features-response averages

Dynamic Interaction Capability features are a little bit more mature than Autonomous Capability features. 50% of surveyed companies are immature, and the mature companies are still around the low level of maturity proved by the average of the responses shown in Figure 6.20. Unfortunately, no efforts are spent by surveyed companies to the future establishment of the dynamic interaction capability's features, proved by a low average of response (2.9) for question 21B in the assessment survey. Depending on the value of chi-square, most of the “Dynamic Interaction Capability features showed a correlation and dependence with the overall maturity and technological requirements, proved by the significant P values (less than 0.05), which ranged between (0.017-0.036) and chi-squared values ranging between (2.215-5.6). In

contrast, the “networked” and “traceability” showed a kind of independence based on the non-significant P-value (0.052; 0.137>0.05).

Figure 6. 20:Dynamic interaction capability features

Figure 6. 21: Customising capability

Customizing Capability includes all requirements to satisfy customers’ needs individually. Individualization demands that several configuration scenarios, different technologies, concepts, and features participate in its development. Figure 6.21 indicates that all the characteristics related to customizing capability possess a maturity level appropriate to the smart manufacturer's requirements. Most of the "Customizing capability features" exhibited independence from the overall maturity and technological

requirements based on their chi-square value, proved by the insignificant P-values (greater than 0.05), which ranged between (0.514-0.7).

Figure 6. 22: Intelligence capability features

Intelligence capabilities include intelligent predictability, info-integration from heterogeneous sources, intelligent visualization, real-time data availability from heterogeneous sources, and Intelligent learning, as shown in Figure 6.22. At first glance, there are observed weaknesses in intelligence capability' features and all surveyed companies lack smartness infrastructures, without future projects to establish these features proved by a weak response average ($M=3.08$, $\sigma= 1.52$). Depending on the value of chi-square, most of the Intelligence capabilities features showed a correlation and dependence with the overall maturity and technological requirements, proved by the significant P values (less than 0.05), which ranged between (0.015-0.037) and chi-squared values ranging between (3.431-5.89). In contrast, the “Intelligent awareness” showed a kind of independence based on the non-significant P-value ($0.063 > 0.05$).

Figure 6. 23:Competitive capability features

Regarding competitive capability features, only the lean capability is immature, and the rest have higher maturity level, as shown in Figure 6.23. Depending on the value of the chi-square, several of the competitive capability features displayed a correlation and dependency on the overall maturity and technological requirements like (Lean; Adaptability; Sustainability; Optimization; Efficiency), as shown by the significant P-values (less than 0.05) varying from (0.011-0.044) to the chi-square values ranging from (2.715-6.4). On the other hand, the "Agility; Responsive; Scalability" displayed a kind of independence dependent on the non-significant P-value ($0.063 > 0.05$).

The non-parametric Chi-square test showed a highly significant relation ($p < 0.05$) between the features and overall maturity level and technological requirements, proved by the significant value of the non-parametric Chi-square ($0.02 < 0.05$). While the features showed high independence of the company's size due to P-value is greater than 0.05 ($0.5 > 0.05$).

In Figure 6.24, the detailed results for the Features sub-dimensions are shown in terms of business type. 100% of B2B's company, which form 25% of a total sample, have an accepted level of maturity, while only 50% of B2C companies have an accepted maturity level, and 50% of B2C company still have low maturity, and both form 25% of the total sample. In combined business B2B; B2C; B2G, only 25% (1 company) have an accepted maturity level while the rest (3 companies) have low technologies level.

Figure 6. 24:Distribution of features ML with respect to business type

Table 6.4: Distribution of features ML with respect to company size

			Sub_Features_MLevel				Total
			Beginner	Intermediate	Expert	Leader	
Size	100 to 249 employees	Count	0	1	0	0	1
		% within Features	0.0%	50.0%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
	250 to 499 employees	Count	0	1	0	0	1
		% within Features	0.0%	50.0%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
	1001 or more employees	Count	2	0	3	1	6
		% within Features	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%	75.0%
		% of Total	25.0%	0.0%	37.5%	12.5%	75.0%
Total		Count	2	2	3	1	8
		% within Features	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% of Total	25.0%	25.0%	37.5%	12.5%	100.0%

Table 6.4 shows that all companies with 100 to 249 employees (12.5% of the total sample) are still at the intermediate level that forms 50% of the total intermediate level. The company with 250-499 employees has a low maturity level that forms 12.5% of the total sample (1 company), representing 50% of the intermediate level companies. The companies with 1001 or more employees form 75% of the total sample (6 companies), which consist, 16.6% of them reached level 5 (leader) that form 100% of total leader level, 50% of them reached level 4 (expert) that form 100% of a total expert level, 33.3% of "1001 or more employee" companies still in level 2 (beginner) that form 100% of a total beginner level.

Generally, the differentiated maturity of technological sub-dimensions (features, technologies, and design principles) refers to establishing and operating technological sub-dimensions separately, which means the surveyed companies do not have the

connected-integrated-interoperable environment that smart factory needs to operate effectively. When the sub-dimensions of each surveyed company's technological requirement are evaluated, only two companies have mature sub-dimensions (C1&C6), while C7 and C3 have an immature level of all sub-dimension of technological requirements. Design principles are notably more mature. Figure 6.25 provides a comparative picture for three subdimensions.

Figure 6. 25:Comparative plot of maturity levels for technological sub-dimensions

In the line and radar chart below (Figures 6.26&6.27), eight different companies' technological maturity values are presented. This diagram points out if there are significant differences among the surveyed sample regarding technological requirements readiness. Interestingly, 50% of the sample suffer from weak readiness and the vast difference among considered companies' maturity levels. For instance, companies 3 and 7 have the lowest score average (1.623 & 1.818), falling to the beginner and intermediate level. The non-parametric Chi-square test showed a highly significant relation ($p < 0.05$) between the technological requirements and overall maturity level, proved by the significant value of the non-parametric Chi-square ($0.021 < 0.05$). While the technological requirements showed high independence of the company's size due to P-value is greater than 0.05 ($0.5 > 0.05$).

Figure 6. 26:Technological maturity level

Figure 6. 27:Technological rank of companies

Table 6.5: Distribution of technological ML with respect to company size

			Technological ML					Total
			Beginner	Intermediate	Experienced-learner	Expert	Leader	
Size	100 to 249 employees	Count	0	0	1	0	0	1
		% within Technological	0.0%	0.0%	50.0%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
	250 to 499 employees	Count	0	0	1	0	0	1
		% within Technological	0.0%	0.0%	50.0%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
1001 or more employees	Count	1	1	0	3	1	6	
	% within Technological	100.0%	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%	75.0%	
	% of Total	12.5%	12.5%	0.0%	37.5%	12.5%	75.0%	
Total		Count	1	1	2	3	1	8
		% within Technological	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% of Total	12.5%	12.5%	25.0%	37.5%	12.5%	100.0%

The companies with 1001 or more employees form 75% of the total sample. 50% of them reached level 4 (expert), 16% of “1001 or more employees” companies reached level leader (5), 16.6% of them reached the intermediate level, and the rest of "1001 or more employee" companies still in level 1 (beginner), as mentioned in Table 6.5.

Also, in Figure 6-28, detailed results are offered for the technological dimensions in terms of business type. 100% of B2B’s company, which form 25% of a total sample, have an accepted level of technologies maturity, while only 50% of B2C companies have an accepted maturity level, and the rest 50% of B2C company still have low maturity and both form 25% of the total sample. In combined business B2B; B2C; B2G, only 25% (1 company) have an accepted maturity level while the rest (3 companies) have low technologies level, which form 50% of the total sample.

Figure 6.28: Business type distribution of technological ML

6.2.1.3. Maturity index for managerial requirements

Maturity assessment was done for each managerial sub-dimension to investigate the most mature surveyed cases. The evaluation approach used is based on equation 5.8 and all related equations shown below.

A. Maturity index of direction setting items (MMDS)

A set of questions was put to evaluate direction-setting maturity. The equations (5.9) have been calculated based on the maturity index of related items. Generally, 50% of the sample have a suitable direction-setting score for implementing and operating smart factories. The direction-setting maturity assessment results are given in Figures 6.29 and 6.30.

Figure 6.29: Direction setting maturity level

Figure 6.30: Ranking of the companies for direction setting ML

Looking at the maturity level distribution for each company, which is presented in Figure 6.31, the smart factory's direction-setting for company 7 and 4 need critical reengineering due to the apparent weakness for digital transformation management.

Research results indicate that 62.5% of the sample suffered from a weak digitalization vision and mission proved by the weak average and high Standard deviation, as shown in Figure 6.31. This continual ignoring leads to a gradual loss of competitiveness. Furthermore, 50% of the sample claimed that they have required strategies and plans to embrace digitalization, which proved by a weak average ($M=3.25$, $\sigma=1.67$). Unfortunately, only 37.5% of the sample have clear future objectives toward digitalization. Even though there is an intention to support digitization's projects proved

by a high average (3.5) compared to other dimensions, 50% of companies claim to provide a continuous desired commitment of smart factory transformation projects.

Figure 6.31: Direction setting items

Figure 6.32 analyses the direction-setting items concerning the managerial requirements. As we see from this table, managerial requirements related to clear vision & mission, overall-strategy, SMART goals, and ongoing commitment and support gained unequal attention and maturity. Thus, these differences indicate absence and uncoordination in their direction settings items. Case companies 4 and 7 suffer from the total absence of some items, while all direction setting items are immature for companies 2,3,7. In the same regard, companies 5,6, and 8 have an accepted maturity level of all direction-setting items.

The results show that many companies need to re-engineer their visions and missions to enable digital transformation, demystifying smart manufacturing concepts and benefits, and develop enabling strategies to identify digitalization's SMART goals. All direction-setting items need support and constant commitment by management to implement them.

These results are consistent with Figure 6.31 emphasizing the weakness of the integrated strategic preparation for the implementation of smart factories.

Figure 6. 32:Direction setting's items for each company

Detailed results for the direction-setting maturity level in terms of companies' business type are also given in Figure 6.33. All B2B's company, which form 25% (2C) of a total sample, have an accepted level of direction setting maturity, while only 50% of B2C companies have an accepted maturity level, and the remaining 50% of B2C companies still have low maturity and both form 25% of the total sample. B2B; B2C; B2G combined, only 12.5% (one company) has an accepted maturity level while the remaining (3 companies) have low technologies level, forming 50% of the sample.

Figure 6. 33:Business type distribution of direction-setting ML

The Chi-square test exhibits a significant relation($p < 0.05$) between the direction-setting and overall maturity level proved by the significant value of the non-parametric Chi-

square ($0.021 < 0.05$). While the direction-setting showed high independence of the company's size due to P-value is greater than 0.05 ($0.31 > 0.05$). Furthermore, direction-setting items showed statical relation with overall maturity, proved by P-values (less than 0.05) varying from (0.018-0.027).

In Table 6.6, the companies' direction-setting maturity levels are shown according to size. Among the “100 to 249 employees” companies, 12.5% of the surveyed company, 100% of companies within this size were at experienced-learner level, and cover 100% of experienced-learner level companies. The lonely company with 250-499 employees (12.5% of the sample) is still at beginner level forming 50% of the total beginner level. Regarding the companies with 1001 or more employees (75% of the sample), 50% of them reached the leader level forming 100% of leader level. 16.6% of them reached expert level forming 100% of expert level companies. The rest of companies (33.4% of "1001 or more employees" companies) are at immature level, 16.6% of "1001 or more employees companies reached an intermediate level (3) forming 100% of a total intermediate level, 16.6% of "1001 or more employee" companies are still in beginner level that forms 50% of a total beginner level.

Table 6.6: Size distribution of direction setting ML

			Direction setting ML					Total
			Beginner	Intermediate	Experienced-learner	Expert	Leader	
Size	100 to 249 employees	Count	0	0	1	0	0	1
		% within direction setting	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
	250 to 499 employees	Count	1	0	0	0	0	1
		% within direction setting	50.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	12.5%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
	1001 or more employees	Count	1	1	0	1	3	6
		% within direction setting	50.0%	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%	75.0%
		% of Total	12.5%	12.5%	0.0%	12.5%	37.5%	75.0%
Total	Count	2	1	1	1	3	8	
	% within direction setting	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	% of Total	25.0%	12.5%	12.5%	12.5%	37.5%	100.0%	

B. Maturity index of leadership items (MML)

Another point to consider is how does evaluate leadership readiness of the managerial requirements and digital transformation. The maturity scores are calculated based on a 5.10 formula. Equations (5.10) have been calculated based on the maturity index of

leadership-related items, and the results from the case data are shown in Figures 6.34 and 6.35. Generally, 62.5% of the sample have suitable leadership features for implementing and operating smart factories.

Figure 6. 34:Leadership maturity level

Analyzing the eight responses, it becomes clear that the companies had different leadership characteristics for satisfying smart manufacturing requirements in digitalization and Industry 4.0. Moreover, companies 7,2, and 3 have the weakest leadership characteristics towards smart factory requirements, while the rest companies have high mature leadership with suitable characteristics for smart factories implementation and operation.

Figure 6.35: Ranking of the companies for leadership

The maturity level distribution for each company is given in Figure 6.36. The smart factory's leadership sub-requirements have accepted levels for 62.5 % of the sample. The leadership features in other companies, such as companies 2 and 7, are immature, while company 3 is still partly immature. Within each mature company, there is the same maturity level for each leadership characteristic, which means they have the same impact in the smart factory embracing journey.

Figure 6.36: Leadership items maturity level

The average maturity level for each leadership item is low; however, the innovation-driven characteristic has an acceptable level with ($M=3.625$, $\sigma=1.506$), but it still needs further enhancement and development. Open to networked interaction's characteristic is considered at the heart of smart management but within the sample, this characteristic still immature, proved by sample response average ($M=3.25$, $\sigma=1.58$). Thus, we need to improve networked cooperation and connectivity capabilities. Having a coaching-style leader adds positive energy to learning and training efforts and provides moral support for employees. This characteristic is mature within surveyed companies based on sample response average ($M=3.375$, $\sigma=1.302$), although this maturity level is at a low accepted-level. The "Open to change" characteristic is significant for remove hurdles, especially for change, development, and innovation management, which have

mature levels in our surveyed sample. Having digital skills and being tech-savvy considered integrative capabilities with smart factory design principles. Even so, it still immature in our surveyed companies, proved by a low sample response average (M=3.25, σ =1.39).

Table 6.7: Size distribution of leadership ML

			Leadership ML				Total
			Beginner	Intermediate	Expert	Leader	
Size	100 to 249 employees	Count	0	1	0	0	1
		% within Leadership	0.0%	50.0%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
	250 to 499 employees	Count	0	0	1	0	1
		% within Leadership	0.0%	0.0%	33.3%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	12.5%
	1001 or more employees	Count	1	1	2	2	6
		% within Leadership	100.0%	50.0%	66.7%	100.0%	75.0%
		% of Total	12.5%	12.5%	25.0%	25.0%	75.0%
Total	Count	1	2	3	2	8	
	% within Leadership	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	% of Total	12.5%	25.0%	37.5%	25.0%	100.0%	

Some points mentioned in Table 6.7 call for attention by looking at the maturity level distribution for each company size. Regarding the beginner level, which forms 12.5% of the total sample, 100% of these level companies are "1001 or more employees" size. Regarding the intermediate level that forms 25% of the sample, 50% of intermediate companies are within "100 to 249 employees" size, and the rest 50% are within "1001 or more employees" size. In terms of the expert level, which forms 37.5% of the total sample (3 companies), 33.3% of these level companies within "250 to 499 employees" size, and the rest are "1001 or more employees" companies. Regarding leader-level companies, which form 25% of the sample (2 companies), 100% of these level companies are within "1001 or more employees" size.

The Chi-square test showed a highly significant relation ($p < 0.05$) between the leadership and overall maturity and managerial requirements proved by the significant P-value of the non-parametric Chi-square (0.029 ; $0.024 < 0.05$). In the same regard, the maturity items of leadership revealed statical relations with overall maturity, proved by significant P-values (less than 0.05) varying from (0.026-0.046) to the chi-square values ranging from (3.99-5). While the leadership characteristics showed high independence of the company's size due to P-value is greater than 0.05 ($0.402 > 0.05$).

In Figure 6.37, the leadership is more mature in B2B's company, which form 25% (2C) of a total sample, while only 50% of B2C companies have an accepted maturity level, and the rest company still have low maturity and both form 25% of the total sample. In combined business B2B; B2C; B2G, only 50% (2 companies) have an accepted maturity level while the rest (2 companies) have a low leadership maturity level.

Figure 6.37: Business type distribution of leadership ML

C. Maturity index of managerial practices items (MM_p)

The other managerial requirements phase is managerial practices, a set of questions was put to identify the maturity level of managerial practices needed to implement and develop smart factories. Equations (5.11) have been calculated based on the maturity index of related items. The results from the case companies are shown in Figures 6.38 and 6.39. Generally, 62.5% of the sample have reasonable managerial practices for implementing and operating smart factories. Regarding immature companies, companies 2, 3, and 7 suffer from smart factories' managerial practices absence, but C3 and C2 are the weaker ones.

Figure 6. 38: Managerial practices maturity level

Figure 6. 39: Ranking of the companies for managerial practices

At first glance, based on the mean of managerial practices items, it becomes clear that all elements are in a state of maturity, except culture enhancement. Generally, it is considered a healthy indicator of the validity of the management practices for digitalization transformation, as is shown in Figure 6.40.

Figure 6.40: Managerial practices items' ML

The big question at this point is how a manufacturer makes its digital transformation when it comes to managerial practices. The answer would be through a comprehensive and integrated managerial roadmap that carefully identifies the most required managerial practices to establish smart factories' managerial infrastructure. It is notable in Figure 6.41 that companies have different maturity levels, meaning that the smart factory managerial practices for each company is idiosyncratic. Regarding managerial practices items maturity level, the surveyed companies have an acceptable level of management practices to improve the organization's agility, except for company 3, which suffers from weak agility practices. The existence of lean practices constitutes the necessary infrastructure for smart manufacturing companies. Paying attention to these practices is observed in 62.5% of surveyed companies, while companies 3, 2, and 7 still need more attention. 62.5% of surveyed companies depending on culture enhancement practices. However, 37.5% of companies still ignore cultural preparation practices. Companies 2 and 3 have immature managerial practices regarding the rest of managerial practices, thus considered the weakest.

Figure 6. 41: Detailed comparison of managerial practices maturity items

Non-parametric Chi-square showed a highly significant relation ($p < 0.05$) between (managerial practices and overall maturity and (managerial practices and managerial requirements) proved by the significant P-value ($0.029; 0.024 < 0.05$) respectively. Simultaneously, several of the managerial practice's items showed independence from the overall maturity and managerial requirements, as shown by the significant P values (greater than 0.05) varying from (0.061-0.098) and chi-square values in the range (2.734-4.34). On the other hand, "Lean; Culture enrichment; Dynamic capabilities"

displayed a kind of dependency proved by the significant P-value (0.044; 0.046; 0.037 < 0.05) respectively. In contrast, the managerial practices demonstrated independence from the company's size according to P-value, which was greater than 0.05 (0.402>0.05).

Table 6.8: Size distribution of managerial practices

			Managerial Practices ML				Total
			Intermediate	Experienced-learner	Expert	Leader	
Size	100 to 249 employees	Count	1	0	0	0	1
		% within managerial Practices	50.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	12.5%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
	250 to 499 employees	Count	0	0	1	0	1
		% within managerial Practices	0.0%	0.0%	50.0%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	12.5%
	1001 or more employees	Count	1	1	1	3	6
		% within managerial Practices	50.0%	100.0%	50.0%	100.0%	75.0%
		% of Total	12.5%	12.5%	12.5%	37.5%	75.0%
Total	Count	2	1	2	3	8	
	% within managerial Practices	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	% of Total	25.0%	12.5%	25.0%	37.5%	100.0%	

Evaluation of managerial practices maturity for each company is shown in Table 6.8 with respect to company's size. Regarding companies with 100 to 249 employees (12.5% of the total sample), 100% of these companies are still at the intermediate level, forming 50% of the total intermediate level. 100% of the companies with 250-499 employees (12.5% of the sample) are still at the expert level, forming 50% of the total expert level. The companies with 1001 or more employees form 75% of the total sample (6 companies).50% of them reached level 5 (leader) that form 100% of a total leader level, 16.66% of them reached an expert level (4) that form 50% of expert-level companies, 16.66% of them reached an intermediate level (3) that form 50% of a total intermediate level, and 16.66% of "1001 or more employee" companies are still in the experienced-learner level that forms 100% of a total experienced-learner level.

Furthermore, Figure 6.42 shows comprehensive findings for managerial practices (sub-dimensions) maturity level in terms of business type. 100% of B2B's companies, which form 25 % (6C) of a total sample, have an accepted maturity level of managerial practices, whereas only 50% of B2C companies have an accepted maturity level, and the rest of B2C company still have low maturity and both form 25% of the total sample. Just 50% of combined company B2B-B2C-B2G have a mature managerial practice, while the remainder (2 companies) have low technology maturity.

Figure 6.42: Distribution of managerial practices ML with respect to business

Figure 6.43: Comparative plot for managerial maturity level: direction setting, leadership, and practice

It is worthwhile to present the comparison among managerial sub-dimensions. In Figure 6.43 it can be seen that there is a difference in the maturity in fields of direction-setting, leadership, and managerial practices for each surveyed case. Therefore, 37.5% of the sample have the lowest maturity level in all sub-dimensions, such as companies 2, 3, and 7. In the same regard, the absence of harmony among managerial sub-dimensions in all surveyed-cases (variation in the level of sub-dimensions maturity for each

company) may be considered a negative indicator for surveyed companies. A comparative picture is given in Figure 6.44.

Figure 6. 44:Managerial maturity level

How manufacturing companies respond to business challenges largely depends on their managerial infrastructure, including strategic orientation, leadership characteristics, and managerial practices. The Figure 6.45 shows the surveyed companies' differentiated maturity levels based on the assessment-survey findings. The managerial readiness in 37.5% of surveyed companies is immature and needs to be re-engineered and reoriented toward satisfying smart factory requirements. Thus, companies 2, 3, and 7 are far from matching managerial requirements. However, some indicators are positive, and they are still insufficient for embracing smart factories.

In contrast, 62.5% of surveyed companies have a suitable managerial environment for smart factory implementation and operation. Similarly, companies 2, 3, and 7 still at the intermediate level (3), while company 4 has a mature level but still has a low score of maturity. All these companies need to work hard to enhance managerial infrastructure, as shown in Figure 6.45.

Figure 6.45: Ranking of the companies for managerial maturity

Table 6.9 calls for attention via looking at the managerial maturity level distribution for each company size, the smart factory's managerial requirements are fulfilled by 62.5% of the surveyed companies. Regarding companies with 100 to 249 employees (12.5% of the total sample), 100% of these companies still of the intermediate level that forms 33.3% of the total intermediate level.

Table 6.9: Size distribution of managerial requirements

			Managerial ML			Total
			Intermediate	Expert	Leader	
Size	100 to 249 employees	Count	1	0	0	1
		% within Managerial requirement	33.3%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	12.5%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
	250 to 499 employees	Count	0	1	0	1
		% within Managerial requirement	0.0%	33.3%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	12.5%
	1001 or more employees	Count	2	2	2	6
		% within Managerial requirement	66.7%	66.7%	100.0%	75.0%
		% of Total	25.0%	25.0%	25.0%	75.0%
Total	Count	3	3	2	8	
	% within Managerial requirement	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	% of Total	37.5%	37.5%	25.0%	100.0%	

The companies with 250-499 employees are at the expert level that forms 12.5% of the total expert level company. While the companies with 1001 or more employees form 75% of the total sample (6 companies), 33.3% of them reached level 5 (leader) that form 100 % of a total leader level, 33.3% of them reached level expert (4), that form 66.7% of a total expert level, and the rest 33.3% of them are still at the intermediate level, that form 66.7% of a total the intermediate level.

Non-parametric Chi-square showed a highly significant relation ($p < 0.05$) between managerial requirements and overall maturity level proved by the significant P-value ($0.021 < 0.05$). Simultaneously, the managerial requirements demonstrated independence from the company's size according to P-value, which was greater than 0.05 ($0.505 > 0.05$).

Regarding the company's business type shown in Figure 6.46. All companies of B2B company have an accepted level of managerial maturity, while only 50% of B2C companies have an accepted maturity level, and the rest of B2C company still have low maturity. In combined business B2B; B2C; B2G, only 50% (2 companies) have an accepted maturity level while the rest (4 companies) have a low managerial-maturity level.

Figure 6.46: Business type-based managerial ML

6.2.1.4. Maturity index of organizational requirements (MO)

The approach applied to determine the maturity level of organizational requirements as shown below is based on (5.12) equations and all relevant sub-equations.

1. Maturity index of business model items (MOB)

The business model's maturity index for each company is calculated based on equation (5.13). A weighted average of business model items is used to find a business model maturity score. A set of questions was put to evaluate the company's business model's readiness to identify each organizational maturity item's maturity level for implementing and developing smart factories. The results from the cases are shown in

Figures 6.47 and 6.48. In general, 62.5% of the case companies have suitable business models for implementing and operating smart factories. Companies 2, 3, and 7 still suffer from immature levels, and their business models are unsuitable for smart factories.

Figure 6.47: Business model maturity level

Figure 6.48: Ranking of the companies for business model ML

The overall business model evaluation for each company's maturity level and their comparison group's results will be presented in the next table. Regarding companies with 100 to 249 employees (12.5% of the total sample), 100% of these companies are still at the experienced-learner level, forming 100% of the total experienced-learner level. Regarding the companies with 250-499 employees that form 12.5% of the sample, 100% of these companies are still at the expert level that forms 50% of the total expert level. The companies with 1001 or more employees form 75% of the total sample (6 companies), and 50% of them reached level 5 (leader), 100% of a total leader

level, 16.6% of them reached level expert (4) that form 50% of expert-level companies, 33.3% of them reached an intermediate level (3) that form 100% of a total intermediate level, as it is shown in Table 6.10. According to P-value, the business model demonstrated independence from the company size, which was greater than 0.05 ($0.615 > 0.05$).

Table 6.10: Distribution of BM maturity level with respect to company size

			Business Model ML				Total
			Intermediate	Experienced -learner	Expert	Leader	
Size	100 to 249 employees	Count	0	1	0	0	1
		% within Business Model	0.0%	100.0%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
	250 to 499 employees	Count	0	0	1	0	1
		% within Business Model	0.0%	0.0%	50.0%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	12.5%
	1001 or more employees	Count	2	0	1	3	6
		% within Business Model	100.0%	0.0%	50.0%	100.0%	75.0%
		% of Total	25.0%	0.0%	12.5%	37.5%	75.0%
Total		Count	2	1	2	3	8
		% within Business Model	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% of Total	25.0%	12.5%	25.0%	37.5%	100.0%

Furthermore, in Figure 6.49, 100% of B2B companies have proper characteristics in their business model paved by their accepted maturity level, whereas only 50% of B2C companies have an accepted maturity level, and the rest of B2C company still has low maturity. Just 50% of combined company B2B-B2C-B2G have a mature managerial practice, while the remainder (2 companies) have low technology maturity.

Figure 6.49: Business type distribution of business model ML

As illustrated in Figure 6.50, several characteristics can be utilized to support and enable the smart manufacturing enterprise business model to match smart factory requirements and smart environments. In the same regard, immaturity and weakness

continue for companies 2, 3, and 7. Therefore, their business models are the weakest among surveyed companies and are not suitable for adopting the smart factory and facing smart business environment challenges. Collaborative and networked features are the weakest in immature companies. Thus, it is a particular concern and needs attention.

Figure 6.50: Business model items ML

It is useful to say that the proposed business model's characteristics generally receive the attention of a majority surveyed manufacturing enterprise, which indicates the importance and role of these characteristics in preparing the basic requirements for building smart organizations, proved by the ranges of response average (3.38 - 3.88) and standard deviations (0.835 - 1.768). The non-parametric chi-squared test shows the relation nature among business model and overall maturity. Consequently, the business model showed a correlation and dependence with the overall maturity and

organizational requirements, proved by the significant P values (0.029; $0.024 < 0.05$), respectively. Similarly, most of the business model maturity items showed a correlation and dependence with the overall maturity, proved by the significant P values (less than 0.05), which ranged between (0.017-0.02) and chi-squared values ranging between (3.452-5.048), like comprehensive, collaborative, data-driven, and networked. Except for responsiveness and dynamism showed a kind of independence based on the non-significant P-value (0.06 ; $0.063 > 0.05$), respectively.

2. Maturity of Structural items (MOs)

To identify the individual maturity index of structure maturity level for each company, Equation (5.13) is used to find a weighted average of structure-related maturity index items. A set of questions was put to evaluate the company's structure's readiness to identify each organizational maturity item's maturity level for implementing and developing smart factories. The results from the cases are shown in Figures 6.51 and 6.52. Generally, 75% of the sample have a suitable structure for implementing and operating smart factories. Although the rest of the sample still insufficient for smart factory operation, such as companies 7 and 3, which is still immature, as shown in Figure 6.52. Each surveyed manufacturing enterprise follows a particular structure. Therefore, they need tailored restructuring processes.

Figure 6.51: Structure maturity level

Based on the chi-square value, which shows a weak relationship (insignificant) between the sub-dimension (structure) and overall maturity proved by the chi-square value (3.45) and the significance of P-value 0.058 (greater than 0.05).

Figure 6.52: Ranking in terms of structure-maturity

The structure evaluation for each company's size is presented in Table 6.11. In respect of “100 to 249 employees” companies, 100% of these companies reach the expert level that forms 25% of the total expert level. Regarding the companies with 250-499 employees that form 12.5% of the sample, 100% of these companies are still at the expert level that forms 25% of the total expert level. The companies with 1001 or more employees form 75% of the total sample (6 companies), and 33.3% of them reached level 5 (leader) that form 100% of a total leader level, 33.3% of them reached level expert (4) that form 50% of the expert-level companies, and 16.6% of them reached an experienced-learner level (3) that form 100% of a total experienced-learner level, while 16.6% of them reached an intermediate level (3) that form 100% of a total intermediate level, as shown in Table 6.11.

Table 6.11: Distribution of structure ML with respect to company size

			Structur_ML				Total
			Intermediate	Experienced-learner	Expert	Leader	
Size	100 to 249 employees	Count	0	0	1	0	1
		% within Structur_ML	0.0%	0.0%	25.0%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	12.5%
	250 to 499 employees	Count	0	0	1	0	1
		% within Structur_ML	0.0%	0.0%	25.0%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	12.5%
	1001 or more employees	Count	1	1	2	2	6
		% within Structur_ML	100.0%	100.0%	50.0%	100.0%	75.0%
		% of Total	12.5%	12.5%	25.0%	25.0%	75.0%
Total	Count	1	1	4	2	8	
	% within Structur_ML	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	% of Total	12.5%	12.5%	50.0%	25.0%	100.0%	

Furthermore, Figure 6.53 offers comprehensive findings for structure (sub-dimensions) maturity level in terms of business type. 100% of B2B companies, which form 25%

percent of the total sample, have a mature structure for smart factory operation, whereas only 50% of B2C companies have an accepted maturity level, and the rest of B2C companies still have low maturity. Just 75% of combined company B2B-B2C-B2G have a proper structure, while the remainder (1 company) have an unsuitable structure.

Figure 6.53: Business type distribution of structure ML

The changes accompanying smart factory implementation and many requirements affect every corner of the manufacturing enterprises and the supply chain, including the organizational side, especially their org-structure. Based on the organizational requirements outlined in Chapter 3, a set of characteristics and trends are supposed to exist in the organizational structures of organizations that seek to become smart. It is worthy to note that companies 1, 4, 5, and 8 have a fully mature organizational structure, which means their structure contents are ready to embrace smart factories. While company 3 is still totally immature, and the rest of the companies are partly mature, “agility” is mature in most of the remaining companies except company 6. The “integration” is mature in the most partly-mature companies except company 7. The smartness characteristic is less mature than the rest of the characteristics. Companies 7 and 2 suffered from smartness absence in their structure. Therefore, partly mature companies need to re-engineer their structure individually to satisfy smart factory requirements.

Figure 6. 54:Structure items maturity

The non-parametric chi-squared formula shows the relation nature among structure items and organizational and overall maturity. The P-value of "lean" and "smartness" is 0.02 and 0.021 (less than 0.050) that refers to a significant association with SF's organizational requirements. Also, they have a relation with overall maturity, proved by P-values (0.036; 0.037). In contrast, the other structural features (agility, integration) are independent of the organizational requirements proved by a P-value (greater than 0.05) and overall maturity proved by P-value (0.278; 0.063). However, in general, the organizational structure showed a significant relationship with the SF's organizational requirements proved by a P-value of 0.024, which is less than 0.05.

3. Maturity of culture contents items (MOC)

Equation (5.15) is utilized to find a weighted average of culture-contents maturity items to identify the individual maturity index of culture-contents for each company. Question 43 was put to evaluate the company's readiness to identify each organizational maturity item's score for implementing and developing smart factories. The results from these cases are shown in Figures 6.55 and 6.56. Generally, 62.5% of the sample have a suitable culture for implementing and operating smart factories.

Figure 6. 55:Culture-contents ML

Figure 6.56: Ranking of the companies for culture-contents maturity

Therefore, there is an imperative need to enhance organizational culture contents, especially for companies 2, 3, and 7, and better prepare themselves for smart factory operation style and requirements.

The rapid development in smart factories' technological, managerial facilities can create challenges, such as analysis and usage of big data, dynamic skills, real-time capabilities, and robot-human co-work, which is a complex interaction. Hence, it is useful to reinforce the implications of the organizational culture for companies seeking to be smart, which is the most essential in building capabilities and skills, overcoming obstacles, and implementing strategies. In this context, the author suggests a group of fields such as digitalization, collaboration, knowledge, learning..., all of which are required to build a suitable culture for smart factories.

Figure 6.57: Culture content items' ML

Regarding surveyed-cases, 50% of the surveyed companies suffer from an apparent weakness in their organizational culture contents in terms of digitalization values, knowledge orientation, and innovation orientation, which are critical smart factory pillars, such as companies 2, 3, 4, and 7. In the same regard, 25% of the sample suffered from a lack of quality orientation, collaboration, learning, initiatives, and participation. Still, companies 2 and 3 suffer from totally immature culture and partly for company 7. However, all culture's contents are mature in 50% of the sample, depending on the weighted response score of these characteristics. 62.5% of the surveyed companies have sought to enhance their quality and learning culture. Within 75% of the surveyed companies, collaboration and participation are entrenched contents in their culture, whereas knowledge, innovation, and digitalization are mature in 50% of the sample's companies.

The nonparametric chi-square test revealed a significant relationship between culture content and organizational requirements proved by the p-value (00.02) is less than the critical point of 0.05. The test also showed a highly significant relation ($p < 0.05$) between culture contents and overall maturity level proved by the significant P-value

(0.025<0.05). Regarding overall maturity, the test results showed a significant relationship between most culture content items and overall maturity verified by P-values range from (0.008-0.042), which are less than 0.05, except for collaboration, which showed independence from overall maturity according to P-value (0.063>0.05). Simultaneously, the culture contents demonstrated independence from the company's size according to P-value, which was greater than 0.05 (0.479>0.05).

Table 6.12: Culture-contents ML with respect to company size

			Culture contents ML				Total
			Intermediate	Experienced -learner	Expert	Leader	
Size	100 to 249 employees	Count	0	1	0	0	1
		% within Culture content	0.0%	50.0%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
	250 to 499 employees	Count	0	0	1	0	1
		% within Culture content	0.0%	0.0%	50.0%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	12.5%
	1001 or more employees	Count	1	1	1	3	6
		% within Culture content	100.0%	50.0%	50.0%	100.0%	75.0%
		% of Total	12.5%	12.5%	12.5%	37.5%	75.0%
Total		Count	1	2	2	3	8
		% within Culture content	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% of Total	12.5%	25.0%	25.0%	37.5%	100.0%

Regarding companies with 100 to 249 employees (12.5% of the total sample), 100% of 100-249 companies are at the experienced-learner level that forms 50% of the total experienced-learner level. Regarding the companies with 250-499 employees that form 12.5% of the sample, 100% of these companies still in the expert level that forms 50% of the total expert level. The companies with 1001 or more employees form 75% of the total sample (6 companies), which consist of 50% of them reached level 5 (leader) that form 100% of a total leader level, 16.66% of them reached level expert (4) that form 50% of expert-level companies, and 16.66% of them reached an experienced-learner level (3) that form 50% of a total experienced-learner level, while 16.66% of them still at intermediate level (3) that form 100% of a total intermediate level, as it is shown in Table 6.12.

Findings for culture-contents (sub-dimensions) maturity level in terms of business type can be seen in Figure 6.58. 100% of B2B companies, which form 25% of the total sample, have mature culture, whereas only 50% of B2C companies have an accepted maturity level, and the rest of the company of B2C companies still have low maturity. Just 33.33 % of combined company B2B-B2C-B2G have a mature managerial practice, while the remainder (2 companies) have low technology maturity.

Figure 6.58: Business type distribution of culture-contents ML

Generally, the organizational Maturity level (ML) is evaluated based on its related sub-dimensions (business model; structure, culture contents). It is worthwhile to show the comparison among organizational sub-dimensions; when the diagrams in Figure 6.59 are compared, it can be seen that there is a difference in the maturity in fields of the business model; structure, and culture contents for each case company. However, notably, the structure appears mature in 75% of the sample. Also, 62.5% of the sample have a mature culture and business model. Figure 6.59 provides a comparative picture.

Figure 6.59: Comparative plot of organizational maturity level items

The technological and managerial infrastructure imposed by smart factories might affect in redefining organizational requirements. All three sub-dimensions of organizational requirements are applied in the 5.12 equation to calculate the average maturity level. When it comes to organizational maturity level, 37.5% are in

leader level, 25% are in expert level, while 37.5% of the sample suffer from low organizational maturity, see Figure 6.60.

Figure 6.60: Organizational maturity level

Figure 6. 61:Ranking of the companies for organizational maturity

Looking at the maturity level distribution for each company given in Figure 6.61, 62.5% of the sample companies have the desired level of organizational readiness for the smart factory, while the rest companies suffer from a lack of maturity.

Regarding companies with 100 to 249 employees (12.5% of the total sample), 100% of 100-249 companies are at the experienced-learner level that forms 50% of the total experienced-learner level. Regarding the companies with 250-499 employees that form 12.5% of the sample, 100% of these companies are still in the expert level that forms 50% of the total expert level. The companies with 1001 or more employees form 75% of the total sample (6 companies), which consist of 50% of them reached level 5 (leader) that form 100% of a total leader level, 16.66% of them reached level expert (4) that

form 50% of expert-level companies, and 16.66% of them reached an experienced-learner level (3) that form 50% of a total experienced-learner level, while 16.66% of them still at intermediate level (3) that form 100% of a total intermediate level, as it is shown in Table 6.13.

Table 6.13: Size distribution of organizational ML

			Organizational_M_level				Total
			Intermediate	Experienced-learner	Expert	Leader	
Size	100 to 249 employees	Count	0	1	0	0	1
		% within organizational	0.0%	50.0%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
	250 to 499 employees	Count	0	0	1	0	1
		% within organizational	0.0%	0.0%	50.0%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	12.5%
	1001 or more employees	Count	1	1	1	3	6
		% within organizational	100.0%	50.0%	50.0%	100.0%	75.0%
		% of Total	12.5%	12.5%	12.5%	37.5%	75.0%
Total		Count	1	2	2	3	8
		% within organizational	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% of Total	12.5%	25.0%	25.0%	37.5%	100.0%

In this case, the non-parametric chi-square showed a highly significant relation ($p < 0.05$) between organizational requirements and the overall maturity level proved by the significant P-value ($0.043 < 0.05$). Simultaneously, the organizational requirements demonstrated independence from the company's size according to P-value, which was greater than 0.05 ($0.739 > 0.05$). The smart factory readiness requirements and organizational requirements are related.

Furthermore, in Figure 6-62, we attempt to see comprehensive findings for Organizational maturity level in terms of business type. 100% of B2B's companies, which form 25% (2C) of a total sample, have an agreed level of managerial practices maturity, whereas only 50% of B2C companies have an accepted maturity level, and the rest of B2C company still have low maturity and both form 25% of the total sample. 50% of combined company B2B-B2C-B2G have a mature managerial practice, while the remainder (2 companies) have low technology maturity.

Figure 6.62: Business type distribution of organizational ML

6.2.1.5. Maturity of human-related requirements (MHh)

The evaluation approach that is used is based on the (5.16) equation. Weighted maturity for the entire human-related dimension is calculated. The total maturity score has been defined to find trends and patterns of the most advanced manufacturing enterprises.

Figure 6.63: Human-related maturity level

Figure 6.64: Ranking of the companies for human-related maturity

The results from these cases are shown in Figures 6.63 and 6.64. Generally, 88.5% of the sample have suitable human-related requirements for implementing and operating smart factories.

Figure 6.65: Human-related items ML

Except for company 2, which suffers from complete weakness in their workforce abilities, company 3 is partly immature for real-time capability, dynamic skills, and interactivity. The total immaturity of company 2 makes them unable to satisfy smart factory requirements. To build like these capabilities, they need long-time programs and strategies.

Non-parametric Chi-square showed a weak relation ($P > 0.05$) between human-related requirements and overall maturity level proved by the insignificant P-value ($0.0591 < 0.05$). Simultaneously, the human-related requirements demonstrated independence from the company's size according to P-value, which was greater than 0.05 ($0.505 > 0.05$).

Table 6.14: Size distribution of human-related

			Human_M_level2			Total
			Intermediate	Expert	Leader	
Size	100 to 249 employees	Count	1	0	0	1
		% within Human ML	100.0%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	12.5%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
	250 to 499 employees	Count	0	1	0	1
		% within Human ML	0.0%	33.3%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	12.5%
	1001 or more employees	Count	0	2	4	6
		% within Human ML	0.0%	66.7%	100.0%	75.0%
		% of Total	0.0%	25.0%	50.0%	75.0%
Total		Count	1	3	4	8
		% within Human ML	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% of Total	12.5%	37.5%	50.0%	100.0%

Table 6.14 indicates the overall human-related evaluation for each company's size. Regarding companies with 100 to 249 employees (12.5% of the total sample), 100% of these companies are still in the intermediate level that forms 100% of the total intermediate level. Regarding the companies with 250-499 employees that form 12.5% of the sample, 100% of these companies are still at the expert level that forms 33.3% of the total expert level. The companies with 1001 or more employees form 75% of the total sample (6 companies), which consist of 66.6% of them reached level 5 (leader) that form 100% of a total leader level, 33.3% of them reached level expert (4) that form 66.6% of expert-level companies, as it is shown in Table 6.14.

Figure 6.66 shows human-related (sub-dimensions) maturity level in terms of business type. 100% of B2B companies have a mature workforce, and 100% of B2C companies have an accepted maturity level. Just 75% of combined company B2B-B2C-B2G have mature human-related requirements, while the remainder (1companies) have low maturity.

Figure 6.66: Business type distribution of human-related ML

6.2.2 Smart Factory Requirements Maturity Index (SFRMI)

Following Equations 5.1 and 5.2 of the maturity models, the overall maturity reports are created for each manufacturing enterprise with a detailed analysis such as comparing all participants' maturity ratings to reveal their smart factory readiness. Thereby, the higher scores indicate an increased alignment of participants with the smart factory requirements. The overall and consolidated maturity level is determined by applying 5.3 to 5.17 equations, which individually calculate and analyze all dimensions and subdimensions maturity of the SF's requirements. For each maturity level (SFRMI), 50 questions are asked about the requirement, getting each requirements' scores, applying weights, and applying related equations. The 5.1

equation's idea is to calculate total maturity via summation of weighted maturity for each weighted-requirement (knowledge, technological, managerial, organizational, and human-related). The applied weights are shown in Table 6.15, adapted from experts' proposed weights via the AHP method (see section 5-3).

Table 6.15: Requirement weights

Knowledge	Technological	Managerial	Organizational	Human-related
0.090	0.429	0.202	0.195	0.083

Based on the AHP results of surveyed experts

Table 6.16 shows the current maturity level of the surveyed companies for every defined requirement. After applying these weights and calculating the total maturity, the weakest requirements are identified to be developed further to achieve a more mature stage. By weighting each requirement, multiply each requirement by the relative weight obtained by the AHP method (see Table 6.15), the weighted requirements' maturity level (overall requirements maturity) is calculated and shown in Table 6.17.

Table 6.16: Requirement's maturity level

Surveyed companies	Requirements				
	Knowledge	Technological	Managerial	Organizational	Human related
Company 1	4.2	3.794	4.108	4.766	4.396
Company 2	3.4	2.763*	2.303*	3.182*	2.201*
Company 3	3.4	1.623*	2.162*	1.809*	3.403
Company 4	1.8*	2.577*	3.423	3.829	4.000
Company 5	4.2	3.871	4.173	4.061	4.000
Company 6	4.6	4.071	4.452	4.411	4.604
Company 7	2*	1.818*	2.101*	2.645*	4.200
Company 8	4	4.471	4.884	5.000	4.60

*The lowest accepted maturity level is 3.34(The expert level initiation point)

Under the weights assumed in the maturity level calculation (5.2 equation), the above big-picture is obtained, and undoubtedly sensitivity with different weighting schemes can be obtained. Based on managerial preferences, different weights can be utilized to see the impact of proposed weights.

The actual levels in Table 6.17 provide evidence for infrastructure and assets suitability for the requirements of smart factories. The calculated overall maturity levels in Tables 6.16 and 6.17 for each organization indicates the readiness of these organizations to adopt and operate the smart factory, also showing the ability and readiness of 50% of

surveyed companies to meet the requirements of the smart factory. These companies have mature levels for each requirement.

Table 6.17: Weighted maturity level

Surveyed companies	Weighted Requirements					W. Total Maturity	Maturity level
	Knowledge	Technological	Managerial	Organizational	Human related		
weights	0.090	0.429	0.202	0.195	0.083		
Company 1	0.378	1.593	0.830	0.929	0.365	4.096	EXPERT**
Company 2	0.306	1.160	0.465	0.621	0.183	2.735	Experience-learner
Company 3	0.306	0.681	0.437	0.353	0.282	2.059	Intermediate
Company 4	0.162	1.082	0.691	0.747	0.332	3.014	Experience-learner
Company 5	0.378	1.625	0.843	0.792	0.332	3.971	EXPERT
Company 6	0.414	1.709	0.899	0.860	0.382	4.266	Leader
Company 7	0.18	0.763	0.424	0.516	0.349	2.232	Intermediate
Company 8	0.36	1.877	0.987	0.975	0.382	4.581	Leader

** Calculated based on Table 5.10.

However, 50% of surveyed companies suffer from immaturity and inability to meet entirely or partially proposed SF's requirements. 50% of these companies are located at the intermediate level. Thus, they must re-engineer their operations, assets, and strategies according to the smart factories' requirements. For example, companies 3 and 7 suffer from immature requirements, except that they have mature human-related requirements, and company 3 has practical knowledge. While the rest of immature companies still in experience-learner level are considered at the edge of maturity, such as companies 2 and 4, which suffer from partly mature, they need more focus on weakest and immature requirements. The distribution of the companies concerning their maturity level given in Figure 6.67

Figure 6.67: Distribution of the companies in terms of maturity levels

In Table 6.18, 100% of companies with 100 to 249 employees (12.5% of the total sample), still at the experienced-learner level that forms 50% of the total experienced-learner level. Regarding the companies with 250-499 employees that form 12.5% of the sample, 100% of these companies still at the experienced-learner level that form 50% of the total experienced-learner level. The companies with 1001 or more employees form 75% of the total sample (6 companies), which consist of 33.3% of them reached level 5 (leader) that form 100% of a total leader level, 33.3% of them reached level expert (4) that form 100% of expert-level companies, while 33.3% of them still at intermediate level (3) that form 100% of a total intermediate level, as it is shown in Table 6.18.

Table 6.18: Size distribution of total maturity level

			TOTAL_MLevel				Total
			Intermediate	Experienced-learner	Expert	Leader	
Size	100 to 249 employees	Count	0	1	0	0	1
		% within TOTAL_ML	0.0%	50.0%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
	250 to 499 employees	Count	0	1	0	0	1
		% within TOTAL_ML	0.0%	50.0%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
		% of Total	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%
	1001 or more employees	Count	2	0	2	2	6
		% within TOTAL_ML	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%	75.0%
		% of Total	25.0%	0.0%	25.0%	25.0%	75.0%
Total		Count	2	2	2	2	8
		% within TOTAL_ML	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% of Total	25.0%	25.0%	25.0%	25.0%	100.0%

The survey responses presented in the previous section is be analyzed and summarized in Figure 6.68. Therefore, this figure compares the eight companies' maturity in five dimensions. Partially mature manufacturing enterprises do not exhibit the same degree of immaturity. Therefore, it may require special programs and strategies to overcome these individual weaknesses and move toward smart factories ' applications and operations. For instance, company 2 needs integrated enhancing program and re-engineering strategies for technological, managerial, organizational, and human-related requirements. While company 4 needs to focus on technological requirements and building proper knowledge.

Figure 6.68: Dimensional and total maturity levels

In Figure 6-69, findings for total maturity level in terms of business type are given. 100% of B2B companies have an agreed level of total maturity, whereas only 50% of B2C companies have an accepted maturity level, and the rest of the B2C companies still have low maturity. Just 25% of combined company B2B-B2C-B2G have a proper maturity, while the remainder (3 companies) have low organizational maturity.

Figure 6- 69:Business type distribution of total maturity level

The SFRMI model assumes that some of the SFRMI items influence others during the assessment process. The chi-squared test is used to analyze an association between the proposed requirements and overall maturity. The P-values range between (0.021-0.043), which is less than the critical point of 0.05 for most requirements. Thus, the total maturity and the knowledge, technological, managerial, organizational, and human-related requirements are related.

The case study conducted in this chapter provided a field application for the maturity level index developed. This section provided a detailed insight into measuring the readiness level for smart factory implementation. Theoretically relevant information and the systematic assessment of the maturity level within the Turkish companies are transparently given.

Calculation of the indices based on the data obtained from the case companies has shown that:

- Breakdown provided in the proposed model and the survey allows for the evaluation and comparison of maturity in terms of multiple dimensions.

- It is clear that all maturity models' requirements are easy to estimate, and their estimate models are easily applicable; thereby, we could generalize for other sectors.
- The index set provided is easy to use since it includes summation-based weighted roll-ups of different indices.
- Index set allows for the inclusion and the use of flexible weighting sets; based on managerial judgment and insight.
- The model and the index set suggested allow for a single company and multi-company evaluations within and across sectors. These evaluations lead to visual, easy-to-understand, and comparative radar charts.

6.3. Further Findings

Under section 6.2, calculations of the maturity levels based on the index set are provided. The survey provides further findings regarding digital transformation hurdles, needed initiatives toward the smart factory, and case company organizational features.

6.3.1 Digital transformation hurdles

“Which of following hurdles do you expect to face for switching to smart factory?”

All surveyed companies believe that identifying hurdles is essential, and it will most likely become even more critical due to increased uncertainty, smartness, interconnectivity, interoperability, and integration among business environment entities. Several hurdles and challenges emerge during digital transformation and smart factories' operation. It is first essential to identify the opportunities and risks associated with challenges. There are some challenges associated with the technological, managerial, organizational, and human-related fields. The following table (Table 6.19) shows the hurdles of adopting and implementing a smart factory in Turkey identified by the multi-case study.

Table 6.19: Smart factories hurdles

	Percentage	Hurdles	Company 1	Company 2	Company 3	Company 4	Company 5	Company 6	Company 7	Company 8	Items percentage	Companies percentage
Technological	24.73%	Acquisition of Technologies				✓	✓	✓	✓		4.30%	50.00%
		Installation of Technologies				✓		✓	✓		3.23%	37.50%
		Utilization of Technologies		✓		✓			✓		3.23%	37.50%
		Going live (implementation)	✓	✓		✓			✓		4.30%	50.00%
		Maintenance		✓	✓	✓			✓		4.30%	50.00%
		Upgrading	✓		✓	✓			✓	✓	5.38%	62.50%
Managerial	21.51%	Strategy development	✓		✓	✓		✓	✓		5.38%	62.50%
		Vision & Mission development			✓	✓		✓	✓		4.30%	50.00%
		Proper project manager skills		✓	✓	✓			✓		4.30%	50.00%
		Commitment and support		✓	✓	✓					3.23%	37.50%
		Networked collaboration				✓	✓				2.15%	25.00%
		Leadership style		✓		✓					2.15%	25.00%
Organizational	24.73%	Reengineering organizational structure		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			5.38%	62.50%
		Business Process reengineering		✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	6.45%	75.00%
		Change management				✓			✓	✓	3.23%	37.50%
		Create collaborative culture		✓		✓			✓		3.23%	37.50%
		Info-integration from heterogeneous sources	✓	✓	✓	✓					4.30%	50.00%
		Cross-divisional transparency				✓				✓	2.15%	25.00%
Human-related	29.03%	Qualified labor	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		7.53%	87.50%
		Collaborative interaction		✓		✓					2.15%	25.00%
		Innovative thinking		✓	✓	✓			✓		4.30%	50.00%
		Digital culture	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	7.53%	87.50%
		Knowledge and experiences		✓		✓				✓	3.23%	37.50%
		Data-related skills			✓	✓			✓	✓	4.30%	50.00%

Smart manufacturing enterprises are capable of coping up with various hurdles faced by the existing industries. However, some hurdles still exist during smart factory implementation, mentioned by manufacturers' responses.

Results show that human-related matters are the most problematic. Human problems constitute 29% of the total problems that manufacturing enterprises are exposed to. 87.5% of companies suffer from the scarcity of qualified-labor and the difficulty of building a digital culture, which was confirmed by the answers of 100% of the surveyed companies with a response average ($M=4.5$, $\sigma=0.535$). 50% of case-companies suffer from the absence or weak of innovative thinking and data-related skills.

Simultaneously, building practical knowledge and experience is considered a hurdle for 37.5% of companies.

Technological hurdles formed 24% of the total hurdles that the surveyed companies are exposed to. 62.5% of companies considered upgrading entities one of the most important concerns that preoccupy Turkish manufacturing companies. 50% of samples suffer from the difficulty acquiring smart technologies, going live (implementation), and maintenance, and consider them as core hurdles.

In organizational hurdles, which form 24% of total hurdles, business process reengineering is considered one of the possible obstacles for 75% of surveyed companies. Reengineering processes could be hurdles for 62% of the sample. Also, the utilization of heterogeneous information is still hard for 50% of surveyed companies.

Finally, the manufacturing enterprises are exposed to managerial obstacles, which form 20% of the total hurdles. For instance, Strategy development represents one of the difficulties faced by 62.5% of the companies. 50% of these companies believe having an appropriate vision and mission solves many hardships.

100% of the companies surveyed emphasized the role of knowledge in ignoring or adopting the smart factory, and indicated that the lack of knowledge drives organizations to ignore and refuse to enter the 4th industrial era. Thus, knowledge could be one of the hurdles proved by a response average ($M=4.25$, $\sigma=0.463$). Lack of standards leads to avoiding the smart factory's adoption, which was confirmed by the answers of 75% of the surveyed companies with a response average ($M=3.75$, $\sigma=0.886$).

This section provided an overview of the obstacles to Turkish automotive manufacturing companies seeking digital transformation via the completely fulfilling of smart factory requirements mentioned in Chapter Three and adopting the proposed business model that contributes to preparing traditional organizations to enter the digital business (4th industrial era).

6.3.2 Needed Initiatives Towards Smart-Factory Preparation

"What are the real initiatives towards digital transformation?"

Many indicators obtained from the surveyed companies' responses provide information about the organization's digital transformation efforts.

The empirical results indicate that 75% of the surveyed companies do not evaluate their digital maturity, thereby not having a clear and applicable vision proved by a response average ($M=3.13$, $\sigma=0.99$).

Regarding the digital transformation team, 37.5% of the sample confirms that it has embarked on building a digital transformation team. Team establishing is an important starting point for a digital transformation program, but the sample shows inadequate preparation for the smart factory, which is proved by a response average ($M=2.5$, $\sigma=1.69$).

Only 12.5% of the sample seek a networked collaboration to help them for digital transformation. This indicator is disappointing because smart factories mainly depend on permanent cooperation between partners. The lack of network collaboration was proved by a response average ($M=2.38$, $\sigma=1.3$).

On the other hand, 50% of the sample started digitizing their management practices, proved by a response average ($M=3.13$, $\sigma=1.5$). Also, 50% of the sample depends on data-driven decisions that align with ERP and BI outputs, with a response average ($M=3.63$, $\sigma=1.32$).

6.3.3 Cases' Organizational Features

Regarding organizational structure, the empirical findings show that 62.5% of the surveyed companies have flat -structure, high responsiveness, adaptiveness proved by a response average ($M=3.38$, $\sigma=1.302$). They can make a fast decision which is proved by a response average ($M=3.88$, $\sigma=0.835$).

Regarding data-exchangeability of structure, 62.5% of the surveyed enterprise structure ensure data-transparency and facilitate a smooth exchanging of data, which are the backbone of smart factories, confirmed by a response average of question 45 ($M=3.63$, $\sigma=1.5$). Data-transparency results were consistent with Question 44, which indicates that 50% of the sample uses information technology to perform their functions and operations effectively.

The smart factory business model's collaborative and integrative nature relies on high data exchangeability, with different usages of gathered data. 62.5% of the sample claimed to digitize their business model. The sample showed apparent differences in the methods and objectives of data and knowledge sharing. For example, 75% of the sample agreed to use data for decision making, 62.5% of the sample indicate using data

to achieve integration, 62.5% of the sample prefer using data for managing processes, assessing performance, driving behavior, and optimizing.

Emerging technologies and methods will radically change the nature of jobs and the types of skills needed. The following approaches are used in the surveyed enterprise to enhance the expertise and skills: 37.5% of the sample depends on workshops and training programs. Learning programs are the favorite choice for 75% of the sample. 50% of the sample rely on self-learning efforts, while the virtual and augmented-reality approaches are used less by 12.5% of the sample. It is evident from the above that the traditional methods prevail in most of the surveyed organizations. Thus, surveyed companies need to use an innovative way to enhance employees' skills and experiences. When the enterprise pursues to build the following innovative capabilities in the next five years, 62.5% of the sample aims to build real-time capabilities, dynamic-skills, and interactive skills, while 75% pursue build innovative-thinking and data-related skills. The pursuit of capacity development is considered a positive indication of the surveyed companies' digital transformation intentions.

6.3.4 Research Questions Revisited

6.3.4.1 A roadmap to the future

“Does industry 4.0 has a roadmap to the future?”

To capture the current impression of smart manufacturing concepts and to answer the research question "Does industry 4.0 has a roadmap to the future?" it is interesting to investigate the expected impact of smart manufacturing concepts in the future success of SMO. In line with the empirical results that indicate the 100% of the surveyed sample stated that industry 4.0 based smart factory influences future performance as to future's roadmap, 50 % evaluate the practical relevance as "agree" and 50% as "Strongly agree" with the mean ($M=4.5$, $\sigma=0.535$) 4.5 and Std. Deviation 0.535. The 87.5 % of companies that give data analyzing and building knowledge high priority due to their significant impact on Turkish manufacturing companies' future performance, proved by the response average ($M=4.63$, $\sigma=0.744$).

6.3.4.2 The manufacturing enterprises' reasons for embracing the industry 4.0

“What are manufacturing enterprises' reasons for embracing the industry 4.0 and transforming into smart manufacturing enterprises?”

Participants were asked to address the question, "what is the organization's greatest digital transformation target." It was found that there is excellent consensus in identifying the digital transformation's key goals, 75% of surveyed automotive companies seen that transformation to smart factory as opportunities to enhance their productivity. 62.5% of the sample considered digital transformation as a way of increasing the profit and market share. Moreover, 75% agreed that digital-transformation optimizes efficiency and effectiveness, and the same proportion considered them as competitive advantage sources. In general, these tendencies encourage speeding smart factory implementation due of the expected benefits are known, as seen in the figure below:

Figure 6.70: Digital transformation's key goals

6.3.4.3 Turkish manufacturing enterprises effort toward I.40

“Do Turkish manufacturing enterprises (TME) embrace any tendency toward industry 4.0 implementation?”

The surveyed companies appear weak in their preparation of smart factories' transformation strategies and plans. 62.5% of surveyed companies suffer from weak vision regarding digital transformation, which proved by response average ($M=3.25$, $\sigma=1.581$). At the same time, 50% do not have the required strategies and plans. This weak preparation of the smart factory interprets an immature level, which is proved by response average ($M=3.25$, $\sigma=1.67$).

6.3.4.4 Turkish manufacturing enterprises' awareness and knowledge

“Does Turkish manufacturing enterprises TMEs have proper awareness and knowledge to apply industry 4.0?”

To identify the current knowledge suitability, the sample was asked many questions about their knowledge. The surveyed companies' responses show that 62.5% of the sample possesses the required knowledge for an industry 4.0 based smart factory. The empirical results showed that the response average was ($M=3.88$, $\sigma=0.835$). This corresponds to the knowledge maturity level of the surveyed companies.

6.3.4.5 Current digitalization, smartness, and automation level

“What is the current level of digitalization, smartness, and automation among surveyed manufacturing companies.”

Empirical results interpret the current features of machines, processes, and products in terms of digitalization, smartness, and automation. Regarding machines, 25% of the surveyed companies have smart machines with a response average ($M=2.25$, $\sigma=1.488$); this is a modest percentage that does not align with digital transformation expectations. 50% of the sample have digitalized machines with a response average ($M=3.25$, $\sigma=1.28$), while only 37.5% of the sample have automated machines with a response average ($M=2.88$, $\sigma=1.45$). Thus, the current mechanical infrastructure is unsuitable for smart factory infrastructure in the automotive sector.

Regarding the process, 25% of the sample have smart processes with a response average ($M=2.63$, $\sigma=1.59$). This modest percentage does not suit the aspirations of digital transformation. 62.5 of the companies do not have digitized processes, with a response average ($M=2.75$, $\sigma=1.38$). While only 12.5% of the surveyed companies automated processes with a response average ($M=1.87$, $\sigma=1.55$).

Regarding the products, 25% of the sample have smart products with a response average ($M=2.25$, $\sigma=1.67$). 75% of the companies do not have digitized products, with a response average ($M=2.63$, $\sigma=1.6$). Simultaneously, 37.5% of the surveyed companies have an automated product with a response average ($M=3.12$, $\sigma=1.45$). These modest percentages do not align with digital transformation requirements.

CHAPTER 7:

CASE-BASED DISCUSSION AND ROADMAP DEVELOPMENT

Based on the field application performed in Chapter 6, this chapter offers case-based discussion to provide specific suggestions and guidelines for the surveyed companies to overcome the immaturities identified and then develops a generic roadmap for the SF implementations.

7.1. Case-based discussion

7.1.1. Case Company-1

7.1.1.1 Knowledge requirement

The results show that Case-1 has a suitable awareness and knowledge of the industry 4.0 based smart factory and related technologies, as proven by their knowledge maturity. In contrast, the educational specializations of employees are still unrelated to the I4.0's technologies, and the precise knowledge for BI, AM, and CIM are weak. Therefore, the case company needs to attract specialties related to the I4.0 based smart factories and focus on deep knowledge building of advanced and new technologies. Moreover, the adoption of continuous programs and educational means are required to improve the level of knowledge and its sustainability.

7.1.1.2 Technological requirements

Among the companies surveyed, case 1 has the lowest acceptable level of technological requirements. Case-1's machines still suffer from weak smartness, digitalization and, automation. Consequently, Case 1 needs to improve its technological content.

The technology maturity assessment results of case-1 show the lowest levels of technology maturity. This company suffers from partial maturity and weaknesses under technologies, such as immature technologies of BI and CPS. Case 1 suffers from inadequate preparation for these innovative technologies. Therefore, it still considers them one of the possible hurdles for the smart factories' implementation. To eliminate the immaturity and technical weakness, case 1 should work on developing acquisition strategies, digitalizing most entities and processes, enabling smooth flow of real-time data, enabling self-diagnostic as a base of the maintenance strategies, depending on data-driven strategy, data-driven value stream, establishing integrated and automated processes, enhancing CIM contents (smart, flexible, CNC machine), and enabling real-time and continuous monitoring.

Case 1 has the highest level of maturity among the surveyed organizations for design principles. They are considered fundamental pieces of the smart factory for easy and systematic implementation and innovative value creation.

Case 1 suffers from a low maturity level of smart factory features and partly mature items of features. Therefore, it needs to focus on building the immature features and enabling self-capabilities and intelligent capabilities which suffer weakness, such as self-configuration, intelligent sensing, traceability, and advanced analysis. The interdependent configuration of each capability requires building the holistic strategies to SF capabilities via establishing a completed technological infrastructure and desired features to build an integrated, connected, interactive, and intelligent system.

7.1.1.3 Managerial requirements

Case 1 still suffers from weak and unclear smart factory vision and mission, and the absence of future targets, which reflect on their performance. The company openly considers strategy development as one of the main hurdles to be faced. Thus, improving the skills of managers and workers, attracting relevant competencies, using ICT to improve upstream and downstream managerial relations, and building cooperation networks to lead the digital transformation could help case-1 to handle the unsatisfied requirements under this heading and to provide a proper direction for manufacturing enterprise.

Case 1 showed high maturity in terms of leadership, characterized by being innovation-driven, open to networked interaction, open to change, having digital skills, being tech-savvy, and adopting a coaching-style leadership approach. All these characteristics form suitable leadership for managing digital transformation and operating smart factories. Thus, case-1 should urge its leaders to adopt smart factories and build appropriate visions and strategies for digital transformation.

Case 1 has mature managerial practices, which provides them a strength in their smart factory implementation. Case 1 should work on building a vertical and horizontal integration with the smart factory's environment.

7.1.1.4 Organizational requirements

Case 1 has a high maturity level in terms of business model requirements, and this shows a certain level of readiness for a smart factory. Most of the features have a proper maturity but still need continuous enhancing capabilities and enabling vertical and

horizontal integration. Case 1 considered the integration of heterogeneous information as one of the expected hurdles it could face. Thus, it needs to digitize business processes and functions, embrace BI technologies, and establish Enterprise Asset Management systems(EAMs).

The results showed that case 1 has a mature organizational structure, which means their structure is ready to embrace a smart factory, but still needs to improve structure's functional fitness via changing jobs-content to facilitate instant sharing of data to offer better visibility and insight into the firm's operations and assets.

Case1 has a mature culture and mature culture content items. In spite of this, it considers the digital culture as one of the expected hurdles it could face. Thus, building a digital culture, creating a culture of continuous improvement, enhancing intellectual skills, and building a security culture still worth further attention.

7.1.1.5 Human-related requirements

Case 1 has a mature workforce regarding capabilities, skills, and qualifications. Despite this, case 1 considered qualified labor as one of the expected hurdles could face.

7.1.2. Case Company-2

7.1.2.1. Knowledge requirement

Case 2 demonstrated mature knowledge and suitability for implementing the smart factory transformation. In other words, the company has accepted knowledge and knowledge-building programs. Nevertheless, it still has the lowest acceptable level of knowledge. However, the study that was conducted showed a lack of appropriate knowledge regarding BI techniques and CPS. The company's answers confirmed its continuing concern about the existing knowledge and needed experience, considering them as one of the most significant obstacles that it may face during the transition towards smart factories. Therefore, case-2 needs to conduct specialized courses, hire external experts, encourage self-learning, and provide online-learning services to enrich knowledge contents.

7.1.2.2. Technological requirements

The results indicate that case 2 suffers from immature technological requirements, So it needs to reformulate strategies and reengineer its technological contents and build required capabilities via acquiring new and innovative technologies, configure design principles, and building desired features.

Proposed smart factory's technologies in case 2 suffer from being partly mature. For instance, CPS, IoT, CC, and BI technology have an immature level, and their machines, processes, and products lack smartness, digitization, and automation. On the other hand, case 2 refers to "utilization of technologies", "production," and "maintenance" as significant hurdles. Therefore, case 2 needs strategies to acquire these technologies to enhance entities' capabilities and instill desired features to ensure their end-to-end, vertical and horizontal integration. It is recommended that the proposed roadmap in the next section be followed for case 2

Case 2's design principles have an immature level, and they are not eligible for the smart factory implementation, especially for virtualization, digitalization, interoperability, standardization, modularity, and decentralization. Case 2 needs to focus on building these design principles across entities and processes. Hence, innovative strategies, new technologies, new partners, new outsourcing, reengineering existing production systems, and reorganization are needed to bridge this shortcoming.

Case 2 suffers from immaturity and lack of readiness for the smart factory. The assessment reveals that most of the characteristics associated with smart factories are not available. Hence, case 2 is not qualified for smart factory adoption. It needs comprehensive reengineering, innovative strategies, and new technologies to build smart and dynamic capabilities for all entities to build these properties. Each feature needs specific requirements to configure. E.g., to enable self-diagnostic capability needs AI algorithms, sensors, actuators, deep and machine learning, embedded-micro-computers. Besides that, all required hard-components and software that ensure interconnectivity, interoperability, and integrability. Therefore, the integrative and joint-establishment of features is shown in the proposed SF Capabilities mapping in Table 2.12.

7.1.2.3. Managerial requirements

Case 2 also demonstrates that their managerial requirements are immature. Maturation of managerial infrastructure needs real focus on reengineering managerial contents, starting from putting-direction to competitive capabilities building, including enabling networked collaboration, getting cloud-based services, and providing BI services.

The results showed a weakness in the strategic content of case 2. To satisfy setting-direction requirements, case 2 should build a clear vision & mission to define a digital

transformation's overall-strategy and set the transformation's SMART goals to establish smart factories. Thus, case-2 can use the networked-collaborative partners, learning tools, training programs, external experts, and attracting new blood to overtake these hurdles. Company 2 should ensure that the top management provides ongoing commitment and support for the digital transformation journey.

Case 2's leadership has an immature level of readiness and unsatisfied requirements in terms of leadership. To tackle immaturity, innovation-driven, open to change, open to networked interaction is required to embed in leadership. Having a coaching-style leadership approach will encourage participation and innovation. Enhancing leadership's digital skills and technical awareness facilitate embracing and managing SF. All of the above should work together toward satisfying SF requirements.

Case 2's managerial practices have an immature level, and they show weak readiness and unsatisfied SF managerial requirements. Case 2 should rely on agility and lean maximizing practices, embrace culture enhancement practices, engage in practices to build dynamic abilities, embrace practices to support and increase participation, innovation, and learning. Many of the SF capabilities and related features depend on managerial support to complete their realization.

7.1.2.4. Organizational requirements

Case 2 results have shown weak and immature organizational requirements. Thus case 2 is faced several challenges, e.g., reengineering organizational structure, business process reengineering, create a collaborative culture, and info-integration from heterogeneous sources during the adoption of SF.

Case 2 suffers from an immature business model and not ready for the smart factory's operations and interactions. Case 2 should develop its business model by making the business model more comprehensive (including most monetizing and value creation entities), increasing collaborative value creation (focus on joint-performance) and data-driven value creation, increasing real-time responsiveness, enhancing dynamism, and networked performance. All of the above should work together towards tackling the immaturity and weakness of the business model to satisfy SF requirements.

Case 2 has a mature structure while lean and integration items suffer from weak readiness, which leads to unsuitability for smart factories. Case 2 should reengineer its

structure by making the structure leaner and more agile, increasing its integration level, and increasing its smart interrelations.

Unfortunately, Case 2 culture-contents are immature and weak for smart factory transformation. Company should reengineer and enrich its culture via identifying and anchoring the digitalization values, encouraging knowledge orientation, anchoring the innovation orientation, making quality-orientation a lifestyle for all partners, encouraging collaboration spirit, supporting learning effort, and increasing effective initiatives and participation. Hence, the company needs to put significant effort related with cultural content.

7.1.2.5 Human-related requirements

Case 2 human-related abilities are immature and weak to operate and manage smart factories. It still suffers from workforce unreadiness for SF technologies. Thus, it needs to enhance and create innovative and smart capabilities within human assets, such as real-time capability, innovative thinking, dynamic skills, interactivity, and data-related skills via diverse training and learning programs.

7.1.3. Case Company-3

7.1.3.1. Knowledge requirement

Even though it has knowledge improvement programs, Case 3 has the lowest acceptable level of knowledge among the companies surveyed. The results confirmed the weakness of the knowledge component about Industry 0.4 and its technologies. Therefore, company needs intensive programs to improve the knowledge content, and it should focus on learning practices via the cognitive-qualifications orientation, communities of practice, learning programs, increasing IT skills, enriching learning instruments, and technology-based training.

7.1.3.2. Technological requirements

Case 3 results indicate immaturity and a weak readiness to satisfy technological SF requirements. Thus, the company needs to focus on comprehensive reengineering strategies to enrich its technological contents.

The results showed that Case 3 lacked mature technologies and has weak readiness for SF. Most enabling technologies except ERP are immature and need to be developed, and future technology acquisition plans are still absent. Also, company 3 considers technology maintenance and upgrading as a big hurdle. Therefore it needs to eliminate

the immaturity and technical weakness. Developing technologies reengineering strategies, acquisition strategies, embracing new technologies and capabilities, digitalizing most entities and processes, enabling smooth flow of real-time data, enabling self-diagnostic as a base of the maintenance strategies, enabling cloud-based software application, depending on data-driven strategy, data-driven value stream, establishing integrated and automated processes, enhancing CIM contents (smart, flexible, CNC machine), enabling real-time and continuous monitoring, and ensuring their end-to-end, vertical and horizontal integration, are required.

Case 3 suffers from weak and immature design principles, and it is not ready for smart factory implementation and operation in this regard. Thus, it needs to focus on strategies to build design principles, and these strategies extend to technologies, features, and capabilities-building strategies. In other words, case 3 should adopt interdependent-configuration of features, design principles, and technologies.

Results indicate absence and immature SF features for case 3. Hence this dimension is again unsuitable for smart factory implementation and operation. Thus, case-company needs to embrace comprehensive reengineering strategies, including design principles building, technologies acquisition, and capabilities building.

7.1.3.3. Managerial requirements

The managerial requirements are immature, and managerial contents are still unsuitable for the implementation and operation of the smart factory.

Direction setting capability is immature in Case 3, and it points out that developing a good vision and mission and developing required strategies are the key hurdles that could face. This explains why the weak maturity levels of other requirements are observed. To overcome weaknesses and immaturity under this heading, case 3 need to have a clear digital transformation's vision and mission. Many options are available for case 3, like co-development team (partners), third-parties consultants, and enhanced leaders' capabilities (training, learning), attracting innovative leaders and experts. Developing achievable and innovative strategies to set SMART goals for digitalization and provide a full ongoing commitment and support are needed.

The Leadership in Case 3 is weak and immature, which manifests itself in ignoring the digital transformation. For overcoming these weaknesses and immaturity, case 3 needs to enhance leadership characteristics and capabilities, such as innovation-driven

capabilities, open to networked interaction, having a coaching-style leadership approach, openness to change, having digital skills, and being tech-savvy. Effective learning programs and benefitting from joint-leadership with partners can have a significant impact to improve this dimension.

Case 3 has immature and insufficient managerial practices to embrace smart factories. Thus, it needs to focus on culture enhancement, agility & lean maximization, building dynamic abilities, developing motivation systems, adopting practices that support innovation, increasing participation, and encouraging learning. In general, everything mentioned needs the collaborative efforts of all parts of the organization, e.g., flexible resource allocation, standardized ways of working, digitizing processes and functions, seamless collaboration, team-oriented approach, increased information transparency, joint-performance, encouraging initiatives, and proactively identifying opportunities.

7.1.3.4. Organizational requirements

The organizational side of Case 3 is still immature and unsuitable for smart factories' operation. Reengineering organizational structure, business process reengineering, and info-integration from heterogeneous sources are the biggest hurdles in digital transformation for case 3.

Case 3 has an immature business model, showing the weakness and unsuitability of the business model for adopting and operating a smart factory. This results in ignoring digital transformation. Thus, Case 3 should develop its business model by making the business model more comprehensive (including most monetizing and value creation entities), increasing collaborative value creation (joint-performance), data-driven value creation, increasing real-time responsiveness, customer-centric, enhancing dynamism, and networked performance.

Case 3 has an immature structure. Thus, company should reengineer its structure by making the structure more lean and agile, increasing its integration level, and increasing its smart interrelations. To improve structure's functional fitness, changing jobs-content, shifting to flat structure, facilitating instant sharing of data offers better visibility and insight into the firm's operations and assets, expanding the scope of action, digitalizing business processes and functions, data-driven processes, and enabling BI tools are required.

Case 3 culture-contents are immature and weak to handle smart factories. Thus, company needs to reengineer and enrich their culture via identifying and anchoring the digitalization values, encouraging knowledge orientation, anchoring the innovation orientation, making quality-orientation a lifestyle for all partners, encouraging collaboration spirit, supporting learning effort, and increasing effective initiatives and participation.

7.1.3.5. Human-related requirements

Case 3 human-related abilities are immature and weak to operate and manage smart factories. Thus, it needs to enhance and create innovative and smart capabilities within human assets, such as real-time capability (analyzing, responding), innovative thinking, dynamic skills, interaction abilities, and data-related skills via diverse learning and training programs, attracting qualified workers, enhance innovative thinking, boost human-machine interface, and enriching digital culture.

7.1.4. Case Company-4

7.1.4.1. Knowledge requirement

Case 4 suffers from immature knowledge content, unacceptable knowledge level, and lack of awareness regarding smart factory technologies. To tackle the immaturity of knowledge requirements, integrated, long-term, and comprehensive strategies and programs are needed (such as cognitive-qualifications orientation, enabling cooperation networks of all participants, encouraging communities of practice, learning programs, increasing IT skills, enriching learning instruments, and technology-based training.

7.1.4.2. Technological requirements.

The technological requirement of Case 4 is still immature and unsuitable for smart factories' operation. The proposed roadmap could be a practical choice for case 4 due to the comprehensive weakness which suffered.

Case 4 has immature technologies and has weak readiness to meet SF requirements. Most enabling technologies are immature and need to be developed, and their future technologies-acquisition plans are still modest. Company 4 also considers technology acquisition, maintenance, and technology upgrading as the biggest hurdles to face. Therefore, case 4 needs to reengineer its technological strategies, focus on embracing new technologies, build related-knowledge and know-how, develop strategies towards

building capabilities and enable entity's features, to integrate all entities and processes in networked production systems.

Design principles in Case 4 are partly mature. The immature design principles are unsuitable for smart factory implementation and operation. Thus, it needs to focus on strategies to build immature design principles (e.g., standardization, modularity, decentralization), and these strategies interrelate to technologies, features, and capabilities-building strategies. For instance, many technologies and features are collaborated to build decentralization (but not limited to self-aware, self-decision, self-organized and CPS, IoT, BD, CC, ERP, and BI). The features in case 4 are partly mature.

The absence and immaturity of several features create unsuitability for smart factory implementation and operation. Several SF capabilities are immature in case 4, such as intelligent, self-, and dynamic capabilities, while competitive capabilities are partly mature. Thus company 4 needs to focus on immature features building via embracing comprehensive reengineering strategies, including design principles building, technologies acquisition, and capabilities building.

7.1.4.3. Managerial requirements

The managerial requirements are partly mature in case 4, and managerial contents are still unsuitable for the implementation and operation of the smart factory.

The setting-direction capabilities are immature for Case 4. It is what causes the other criteria to be so immature. Case 4 still considers vision, mission, strategy development, and management's commitment as possible hurdles for their smart factory transformation journey. To overcome these weaknesses, case 4 needs to have a clear digital transformation's vision and mission to establish an achievable overall-strategy to set SMART goals for digitalization and provide a full ongoing commitment and support. To enhance strategic abilities, sight, and knowledge, case 4 needs special courses, learning programs, a collaborative advisory board with partners, third-party assisting, and leaders training. The proposed roadmap provides a set of tools to estimate the current state of companies, which facilitate setting SMART goals.

Case 4 has a mature leadership dimension and the characteristics under this heading form suitable leadership understanding for managing digital transformation. Nonetheless, company still considers leadership skills one of the possible hurdles for

smart factory transformation. Case 4 could urge their leader to think and planning integratively to draw their organization's digital transformation organization.

Case 4 has mature managerial practices, which is a strength for their smart factory implementation.

7.1.4.4 Organizational requirements

The organizational requirements in case 4 has a mature level and suitable for digital transformation.

The business model in Case 4 has a mature level of readiness for a smart factory implementation. Nevertheless, case 4 considers the business process reengineering, info-integration from heterogeneous sources, and cross-divisional transparency as expected hurdles for their digital transformation. To overcome these hurdles, case 4 should shift to data-driven value, digitalize business process, utilize joint-creation of value, enhance business model responsivity, enable adaptability, and increase SF technologies-centric.

Case 4 is mature for the structural dimension, which means their structure is ready to embrace a smart factory. Nevertheless, case 4 still considers the reengineering organizational structure and cross-divisional transparency as expected hurdles for digital transformation. Case 4 should enable cloud-based services, servitization of functions, digitize processes and functions, increase integrability, establish cloud-based collaboration, renew jobs content, allows cross-organizational networked integration, and increase the accessibility of knowledge.

Case 4 considers the digital culture, change management, and creating a collaborative culture as expected hurdles it could face. Despite this, they have a mature culture and mature culture content items. Thus, building a digital, collaborative, and continuous improvement culture, enhancing intellectual skills, increasing participation, and building a security culture.

7.1.4.5. Human-related requirements

Case 4 has a mature workforce regarding capabilities and skills. Despite this, case 4 suffers from an unprepared workforce for SF technologies and weak knowledge regarding technologies. Also, case 4 considered qualified labor, collaborative interaction, innovative thinking, digital culture, knowledge and experiences, and data-related skills as key expected hurdles for their digital transformation journey. To

eliminate this weakness, the company needs to reshape capabilities, skills, culture values, thinking style, and knowledge of the workforce via long-term learning and training programs, encourage self-learning, providing BI services, and increase knowledge accessibility.

7.1.5. Case Company-5

7.1.5.1. Knowledge requirement

The results show that Case 5 has a suitable awareness and knowledge of the industry 4.0 based smart factory. It has an acceptable knowledge level for each technology. Moreover, the adoption of continuous programs is required to improve the level of knowledge and its sustainability. Therefore, it needs to focus on building deep knowledge of advanced and new technologies.

7.1.5.2. Technological requirements

Case 5 has a mature level for technological requirements but still at a weak level. Thus, their technological contents still need continuous improvement.

In general, case 5 has partly mature technologies. Indeed, CPS and IoT technologies in case 5 are immature, but the company is still insufficient. Also, it still suffers from a weak technologies acquisition strategy. Thus C-5 needs to reengineer its technological strategies, focus on embracing new technologies, build knowledge, develop strategies towards building capabilities and enabling entity's features, link all entities, develop their maturity, and integrate all entities, processes, and humans in networked production systems.

The results show that case 5 has mature design principles, but case 5 processes are still manual and non-smart, and their products are traditional. Thus, it needs to execute its design principles within smart factory environments and in an integrative and manner.

The results show that case 5 has mature features, and it is ready for a smart factory. Although its operations do not suit the smart factory environment and mechanism, its products also do not reflect the characteristics of smart products. For this, case 5 is required to direct and operate its properties of integrative action to building the smart factory.

7.1.5.3. Managerial requirements

Case 5 has mature and sufficient in terms of managerial requirements for a smart factory but still consider networked collaboration as a big hurdle to could face.

Case 5 is mature in setting direction, which is sufficient for managing a digital transformation. Case 5 should set a set of integration strategies to enable SF capabilities and determine digital transformation managing strategy.

Case 5 has a mature leadership, and their leadership features are sufficient for managing a digital transformation.

Case 5 has mature managerial practices, which are sufficient for operating a digital transformation. To eliminate the hurdles, case 5 should focus on building networked collaboration with partners.

7.1.5.4. Organizational requirements

Case 5 is mature in meeting the organizational requirements, and they are sufficient for a smart factory implementation in terms of organizational dimension. The company is mature in terms of business model, structure, and cultural contents, but still considers reengineering organizational structure and business process reengineering as the biggest hurdles it could face. Therefore, case 5 should enable servitization of functions, digitize processes and functions, increase integrability, establish cloud-based collaboration, renew jobs content, and allows cross-organizational networked integration.

7.1.5.5. Human-related requirements

Case 5 has a mature workforce regarding capabilities, skills, and qualifications. Despite this, case 5 considered qualified labor and digital culture as key expected hurdles to face during digital transformation. To overcome these hurdles, the company needs to reshape workforce capabilities, skills, culture values, enhance thinking style, and knowledge of the workforce via long-term learning and training programs, encourage self-learning, provide BI services, and increase knowledge accessibility

7.1.6. Case Company-6

7.1.6.1. Knowledge requirement

Case 6 has turned out to be the most mature company among the 8 companies analyzed. It satisfies SF-knowledge requirements and has suitable awareness for most SF's technologies, except for AR, AM, CRP technologies. To handle the lack of awareness regarding some smart factory technologies, the company needs specific strategies, related learning courses, and training efforts towards these strategies.

7.1.6.2. **Technological requirements**

The technological requirements are mature in case 6 and suitable for the smart factory.

Most of the technologies are mature in case 6, except AR technology. Case 6 deemed all technologies as their future priority. Still, company considered technologies-acquisition and technologies-installation as key expected hurdles along the digital transformation journey and still depend on manual and non-smart processes. Case 6 needs to focus on immature technologies, technologies-acquisition strategies and to establish an interactive and integrative production environment via enabling process capabilities (automated, smart, real-time responsiveness, lean process) and establishing integrated systems (vertical, horizontal, and end-to-end)

Case 6 has mature design principles. Nevertheless, case 6 processes are still manual and non-smart. Thus, it needs to run its design principles in an integrative and manner within whole smart factory environments.

Generally, case 6 has mature features but has some immature features, such as self-controlled, self-organization, self-configuration, real-time data availability from heterogeneous sources, proactive behavior, awareness, and intelligent predictability. Besides that, it has manual and non-smart processes. Thus, case 6 should focus on improving these specific immature features, embracing the holistic building strategies for SF capabilities, and developing mechanisms to implement these strategies.

7.1.6.3. **Managerial requirements**

Case 6 is mature and sufficient to meet managerial requirements for a smart factory.

Case 6 has a mature setting-direction, which is sufficient for managing a digital transformation but still considers strategy development, vision & mission development as important hurdles to face. Thus, it is possible to rely on the partners' expertise, external consultants, or specialized courses and learning programs and attract new leaders. Hence, the leadership in case 6 (despite its maturity) needs to improve abilities, building related-knowledge for managing and applying the digital transformation. All of the above is not achieved without appropriate managerial practices. The managerial practices are mature and sufficient for operating a digital transformation. As a result, management practices should collaborate to facilitate smart factory features and enable competitive capabilities.

7.1.6.4. Organizational requirements:

Case 6 has mature organizational requirements, and they are sufficient for a smart factory implementation in terms of business model, structure and culture. Reengineering organizational structure, handling change management, creating a collaborative culture are considered as possible hurdles that could face case 6 at transformation journey. Company can focus on digitalizing business processes and functions, enhancing responsiveness, servitization of functions, increasing integrability, renewing job content, and allowing cross-organizational networked integration to overcome these hurdles.

7.1.6.5. Human-related requirements

Case 6 has a mature workforce regarding capabilities, skills, and qualifications. Despite this, the company still considers qualified labor, innovative thinking, digital culture, and digital and data skills as key expected hurdles for their digital transformation journey. Therefore, building a digital and collaborative culture, anchoring a continuous improvement culture, enhancing intellectual skills, increasing the accessibility of knowledge, increasing participation, and building a security culture are required.

7.1.7. Case Company-7

7.1.7.1 Knowledge requirement

Case 7 suffers from immaturity regarding the awareness and knowledge for the I4.0 based smart factory and lack of awareness regarding most smart factory technologies except ERP. Company still considers knowledge as one of the most significant obstacles that it may face during the transition towards smart factories. To tackle the immaturity of knowledge requirements, integrated, long-term, and comprehensive strategies and programs are needed, such as enabling cooperation networks of all participants, encouraging communities of practice, learning programs, increasing IT skills, enrich learn-instruments, attracting related educational specializations, and technology-based training.

7.1.7.2. Technological requirements

The technological requirements are still immature in case 7 and unsuitable for smart factories' operation. It needs to reengineer its technological contents and build required capabilities to vanquish the hurdles it could face, like the acquisition of technologies, installation of technologies, utilization of technologies, going live (implementation), maintenance, and upgrading.

Case 7 is immature regarding the technologies and has a weak level of readiness to meet SF requirements. Most enabling technologies are immature and need to develop except ERP, and their future technologies-acquisition plans are still absent. The company considers technology installation, utilization, maintenance, and upgrade as big hurdles. To handle these obstacles, Case7 needs to reengineer and reform its strategies to acquire and implement SF technologies, enable entities' capabilities, instill desired features and develop current technologies to ensure their end-to-end, vertical, and horizontal integration. It is preferred that the proposed roadmap be followed.

Design principles in Case 7 are partly mature, making the company unsuitable for smart factory implementation and operation, especially for virtualization, standardization, decentralization, modularity, and service-orientation. Thus, it needs to focus on building these immature design principles across entities and processes and how can achieve entities-integration. These strategies interrelate to technologies, features, and capabilities-building strategies.

In general, the features in case 7 are immature. The absence and immaturity of most features create unsuitability for smart factory implementation and operation. Thus, C-7 needs to focus on comprehensive reengineering, innovative strategies, and new technologies to build SF capabilities for all entities and processes. Specific technologies collaborate to build each SF feature, and the capabilities mapping in Table 2.12 can help for features configuration.

7.1.7.3. Managerial requirements

The managerial requirements are immature in case 7, and managerial contents are still unsuitable for the implementation and operation of the smart factory.

The direction setting is immature, leading to weak maturity levels of other requirements. Meanwhile, case 7 considers vision, mission, strategy development, and management's commitment as possible hurdles at the smart factory transformation journey. To overcome these weaknesses and immaturity, company needs to have a clear digital transformation's vision & mission to establish an achievable overall-strategy for setting SMART goals for digitalization and provide a full ongoing commitment and support.

The Leadership in Case 7 is weak and immature, which shows the ignoring of digital transformation. To overcome these weaknesses and immaturity, case-7 need to enhance

leadership characteristics and capabilities, such as innovation-driven capabilities, openness to networked interaction, having a coaching-style leadership approach, open to change, having digital skills, and being tech-savvy. To establish these capabilities and features, case 7 need to conduct specialized courses, enable learning tools, encourage self-learning, attract innovative leadership, increase knowledge accessibility, and benefit from joint-leadership with partners.

Case 7 has partly mature managerial practices. The immature managerial practices, e.g., culture enhancement, lean, and dynamic abilities, make case 7 unsuitable for embracing smart factories. Thus, company 7 needs to focus on developing immature managerial practices via collaborative efforts, integrative performance, clear strategies, identified and SMART goals, digitize processes and functions, increased information transparency, encourage joint-performance culture, encouraging initiatives, and install digital culture via training learning programs.

7.1.7.4. **Organizational requirements**

Case 7 suffers from immature organizational requirements and still considers business process reengineering and change management as critical hurdles that could be faced. Hence, its organizational contents are unsuitable for managing and operating smart factories.

Case 7 has an immature business model. Thus, C-7 should develop its business model by making the business model more comprehensive (including most monetizing and value creation entities), increasing collaborative value creation, data-driven value creation, digitalize business process, increasing real-time responsivity, enhancing dynamism, increase SF technologies-centric, and networked performance.

Company 7 has an immature structure except for agility. Thus, case 7 should reengineer its structure by making the structure more lean and agile, enabling cloud-based services, increasing its integration level, establishing cloud-based collaboration, digitizing processes and functions, and increasing its smart interrelations.

Culture-contents are immature and weak to manage smart factories. Thus, Company needs to reengineer and enrich their culture via anchoring the digitalization values, enhancing intellectual skills, anchoring collaborative values, encouraging knowledge orientation, anchoring the innovation orientation, making quality-orientation and

continuous improvement a lifestyle for all partners, supporting learning effort, and increasing effective initiatives and participation.

7.1.7.5. Human-related requirements

Case 7 has a mature workforce regarding capabilities, skills, and qualifications. Despite this, case 7 considered qualified labor and required knowledge and experiences as expected hurdles that could be faced. To eliminate this weakness, the company needs to reshape and enhance workforce capabilities by improving thinking style, enhancing knowledge, providing effective learning and training programs, encouraging self-learning, encouraging practice communities, and increasing knowledge accessibility.

7.1.8. Case Company-8

7.1.8.1 Knowledge requirement

The case company has a suitable awareness and knowledge of the I4.0 based smart factory and seeks to build desired awareness for digital transformation via the adoption of continuous improvement programs. Regarding SF's technologies, it has an acceptable knowledge level for each technology. Based on the evolutionary nature of a smart factory, several strategies are suggested to keep knowledge at a suitable level, such as encouraging communities of practice, specialized courses, increasing IT skills, enrich learn-instruments, and new technology-based training.

7.1.8.2. Technological requirements

The technological requirements are rate as mature in case 8 and suitable for the smart factory but still considers technology upgrading as a big obstacle to face. Company 8 processes are manual and non-digital. They have traditional machines, while their products are classic and unsmart.

All technologies are rate as mature in case 8. However, it deemed all technologies as secondary priorities, besides insufficient processes and machines. Therefore, case 8 needs to focus on establishing an interactive and integrative production environment through enabling process capabilities (automotive, smart, real-time responsiveness, lean process), establishing integrated systems (vertical-horizontal, end-to-end), providing smart products.

Case 8 has mature design principles without full implementation, as evidenced by insufficient processes and machines. So, case 8 needs strategies to generalize utilization of design principles across all entities and processes.

There is a weakness of the processes and machines in case 8. Despite the maturity of the SF's features, case 8 needs to enable entities and processes features and build SF capabilities that reflect on the whole organization.

7.1.8.3 Managerial requirements

Case 8 is mature and sufficient managerial requirements for a smart factory. Setting direction, leadership, and Managerial practices dimensions are mature, which are sufficient for operating a digital transformation.

7.1.8.4. Organizational requirements

Case 8 is mature in meeting the organizational requirements, and they are sufficient for a smart factory implementation in terms of organizational dimension. The company is mature in terms of business model, structure, and cultural contents.

7.1.8.5. Human-related requirements

Case 8 has a mature workforce regarding capabilities, skills, and qualifications. Despite this, case 8 considered qualified labor, digital culture, and data skills as key expected hurdles at the digital transformation journey.

7.2 Suggesting the Roadmap for Smart Factory Implementation.

As has been clearly put forward since the beginning of the study, implementing a smart factory will radically change a manufacturing enterprise's current and traditional capabilities, and it will necessitate new methods, operational models, organizational changes, management practices, and comprehensive business models covering all smart entities, advanced operations, innovative technology, and human resources.

Based on the previous chapters and sections, this section suggests a generic and systematic transformation roadmap towards smart factories by offering a step-by-step approach to fulfill the smart factory requirements.

The roadmap implies preference is given to the areas that will profit significantly from digitalization and create core infrastructures to establish smart capabilities. These strategies are needed to establish stable foundations of technological, managerial, organizational, and human-related requirements which will allow the transition to "smart factory." The three-level maturity analysis (items; dimensions, enterprise) pave the way for the development and implementation of a practical roadmap that describes the phases of the process of transition to smart factory. The proposed roadmap is given in the following figure:

Figure 7. 1: Smart manufacturing enterprise roadmap

In this figure, main steps are further divided into sub-steps, which are recommended to be run sequentially to ensure a systematic approach for the digital transformation of the manufacturing enterprises and building the related capabilities.

The roadmap represents an integrative systematic implementation approach, which means the departments and managements of the manufacturing enterprise can define targets (desired status) based on main strategies and intended capabilities.

Within the proposed roadmap, the maturity model and the maturity index logic developed in this study serve for both the determination of the actual state and the targets for each action field. Proposed framework, business model, set of requirements and index to measure maturity work together to assess the as-is situation in terms of the determined dimensions and requirements, and direct and help the enterprise's strategy preparation. This is not a simple feat, and needs long-term dedication to ensure a smooth shift from traditional to smart systems. The roadmap can be applied to the entire manufacturing enterprise or at the supply chain level.

The roadmap given in Figure 7.1 contains the following steps:

1. Initiating transformation project team:

A digital transformation team of multidisciplinary specialists- (professionals, internal and external experts, board members and senior managers) are required. Initial knowledge building and assessments of the expected project benefits are needed.

- Building initial-knowledge: the purpose of the initial workshop and startup meeting is to give an impetus to the manufacturing enterprise. It will provide an initial awareness and motivation by introducing the necessary smart factory principles, features, technologies, and related innovations. In order to highlight the importance of this issue, a gradually increasing set of industry 4.0 based smart factory use cases can be introduced in this context to exemplify the realistic implementation of I4.0 based smart factory technologies.
- Assessing expected benefits: The workshop helps the enterprise understand how I4.0 solutions are effectively applied to make the issue more feasible and tangible. The team should identify and quantify the expected benefits and prove the viability of an industry 4.0 based smart factory for manufacturing enterprise to justify the initial investments

needed. This is vital to ensure the top management support needed throughout the transformation project.

2. Evaluation:

At this step, a comprehensive evaluation and analysis of the current status and existing competencies is conducted to provide a comprehensive picture that includes technical and non-technical aspects. After performing a general SWOT analysis, a detailed evaluation is performed based on the requirements, framework and the maturity measurement index developed in this study. Thus, it is possible to define the following steps:

- **SWOT:** The business environment analysis is performed via SWOT analysis to put forward a profile of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats.
- **Maturity measurement:** Using the logic developed in this study, current situation is determined and maturity levels are assessed to see the readiness and how well requirements are met in the five main dimensions:
 - **Knowledge availability:** assessing knowledge quality, availability, suitability, sufficiency, and shareability.
 - **Technological dimension:** gauging the suitability of current technologies, the availability of design principles, and which of the required features are possessed.
 - **Managerial dimension:** Evaluating the suitability of current strategies, leadership abilities and used managerial practices for the digital transformation.
 - **Organizational requirements:** assessing the alignment of their business model, structure, and culture contents for smart manufacturing system.
 - **Human-related requirements:** gauging the suitability of the current workforce capability, skills, qualification, for smart manufacturing system.

The proposed maturity model and related index set can be used as a systemic approach for any organization due to the comprehensive and applicable character.

- **Benchmarking:** The study's proposed dimensions (knowledge availability, technological, managerial, organizational, and human-related), all related subdimensions) and proposed capabilities can be used as tools for benchmarking. The

systematic proposed can identify the best practices and can be a comparison base to enable further improvement.

3. Identifying gaps:

The accuracy of strategies and the roadmap carried out in the subsequent stages depends on the rigor of the evaluation stage and gaps identification. Step 2 already revealed the existing situation in multiple dimensions and provided a benchmarking. At this stage, the target states are defined and gaps are determined for dimensions and subdimensions. This reveals a complete picture of any deficiencies and gaps for the smart enterprise journey.

4. Direction setting:

The requirements analysis at stage 2 and gap identification at stage 3 are critical for strategy development and direction-setting. The industry 4.0 based smart factory requirements chosen in this paper provide the underlying framework for manufacturing enterprises' digitalizing strategies. This means that the digitalization team discusses the smart factory strategies, smart capabilities to be improved or developed, and which future target states are to be achieved to fulfill the industry 4.0 based smart factory transition. The assessments and gaps for the respective dimensions (knowledge availability, technological, managerial, organizational, human-related) help determine the target states. Hence, according to real evaluation and analysis of the current status, this step enables the project team to develop:

- A clear vision and mission: Smart factory implementation is facilitated by building the desired knowledge, clear vision, and comprehension of smart factory contents (concept, technology, implementation, mechanisms).
- Strategies: The journey of the SMO begins with acquiring complete awareness and specific views based on the pre-known objectives and the evaluation of real technical maturity.
- Project planning: Based on the identified strategies, a detailed project plan is to be developed towards smart factory implementations. Undoubtedly project plans should manage scope, schedule, cost, quality and budget required for the entire project.

SMART goals: At this stage, SMART goals should be set. Here the main concerns are: Are your targets specific? Can you measure progress towards that objective? Is the target achievable (applicable)? How relevant is your digitalization goal?

5. Bridging the gap:

Based on the previous steps, this step involves all the efforts to bridge the knowledge gap and to reengineer technological, managerial, organizational and human-related dimensions to eliminate weaknesses and immaturities. Bridging the knowledge gap can be handled through workshops, various training programs, self-learning, and various course (short- mid- and long-term).

Depending on the weaknesses and maturities observed, degree of reengineering efforts changes to obtain the desired capabilities. Evidently, these efforts should be handled in multiple dimensions. Radical innovations may be required in the business models applied. Radical change may be needed in the technological dimension, requiring clear acquisition strategies, transition strategies and training. Undoubtedly, managerial practices are to be reengineered to ensure the alignment between the technological requirements and managerial requirements. Hence, aligning managerial practices with SF requirements are needed.

In the cultural and human dimension, digital transformation demands a set of reinforced values, ideals, and ethics. This study highlighted the vitality of culture contents for configuring a smart factory. Hence, workers should develop cognitive skills which are preferred over muscular skills, leading to new digital skills exceeding beyond conventional capabilities. Thus, ongoing and innovative learning and training programs are required.

6. Capabilities building:

Based on the five steps defined, 5 set of smart capabilities (autonomous capability, dynamic interaction, customizing capability, intelligence capability and competitive capability) are developed. Enabling technologies and a set of design principles are used to create the desired features that configure each capability. Interaction among the capabilities contributes to building other capabilities as well. In other words, many of the traits overlap and interact to form traits and abilities at the same level or at higher levels. For instance, self-diagnostic contributes to self-decision configuration and self-diagnostic build in sensing, analysis features. That means the intelligent-capabilities

participate in self-abilities configuration. This interaction is summarized in Figure 7.2 below.

Figure 7. 2:Capabilities interactions

The impact of realized smart factory capabilities extends to all entities, operations and processes. Entities' acquired characteristics are reflected in the processes involving these entities. Therefore, enabling the macro-processes capabilities in the smart factory are intertwined and integrated with enabling capability of entities. These capabilities are extended to all the following major processes:

- Within-factory processes
- Enterprise-centric processes
- Supplier-centric processes (SRM)
- Customer-centric processes (CRM)
- Collaborative network-level processes

7. Going smart:

In this step, organizations start reaping the benefits of digital transformation and embodying competitive capabilities, like agility, lean, adaptability, sustainability, optimization, responsive, scalability, and efficiency. Smart networked production systems, networked and joint value creation, and valuable and smart products are enabled to face the business environment challenges.

The roadmap developed undoubtedly requires the following continuous responsibilities:

- Ongoing commitment and support: to ensure a successful long-term shifting from traditional to the smart factory, on-going managerial support, multi-year budgets and financial commitments are needed to complete the required projects.
- Managing the digital transformation: systematic application of project management systematic is needed to handle planning, leading, implementing, monitoring, and maintaining for all desired actions to ensure an integrative path of implementation.
- Continuous knowledge buildup: a learning culture should be created in the organization to lead to continuous buildup of knowledge regarding the smartness.
- Continuous improvement: an environment of continuous improvement must be established in these systems to ensure that smart capabilities are continuously improved and a kaizen culture is created in the company.
- On-going education and training: This is vital for all the managerial levels and it should be on-going to enable continuous learning and improvement at all the steps.
- On-going organizational change management: Efforts towards managing the organizational and cultural aspects should be on-going and applied systematically and continuously to get successful results.

CHAPTER 8:

CONCLUSION AND FURTHER RESEARCH SUGGESTIONS

This study has focused on the SF capabilities building and requirements. The study developed a business model, a generic framework, and maturity measurement index system and provided a managerial roadmap for an industry 4.0 based smart manufacturing enterprise. Field application is performed via 8 case studies in the automotive sector.

This chapter concludes by highlighting the contributions, practical implications of the study and suggesting further research.

8.1. Contributions of the Study

The study contributes to the literature in the following aspects:

1. **Providing a conceptualization:** The study compared various industry 4.0, smart factory, and business model definitions and put forward the similarities and differences in extant literature. Philosophy, importance, components, architecture, existing models and frameworks, existing technologies, benefits, and challenges are also comprehensively discussed. Hence, the study is a contribution toward a sound conceptualization of the research area.
2. **Providing a smart capability mapping:** The study provided a comprehensive review to identify and classify the technologies, design principles, features, and capabilities regarding the smart factory, and a mapping among them. This mapping presents how different characteristics, design principles, and enabling technologies can be clustered and interrelated to create smart factory capabilities.

The configurative and composite nature of industry 4.0 imposes that a wide variety and range of heterogeneous technological components which interact and integrate are utilized simultaneously to establish the desired smart system capabilities. Multiple technologies, design principles, and features interact to produce and support capabilities at multiple levels (factory-level, organizational level, and network-level). Based on extant literature, this study put forward a comprehensive classification of major technologies, identifying and proposing a set of cooperative and interactive technologies (such as CPS, BD, IoT, CC, AM, Robotics, CIM, ERP, Simulation, and

AR, together with business intelligence and related technologies). Most of these enabling technologies work in clusters, as embedded technologies, or as supporting technologies to major technologies for realizing the desired features. Industry 4.0's configuration requires smart interaction and integration among heterogeneous entities, similar to the lego-style interaction, to result in high reconfigurability, flexibility, and interoperability, although standardization is still under development. Therefore, mapping among technologies, design principles, features, and capabilities is one of the major contributions of the study.

3. Identifying smart factories requirements: Based on a comprehensive literature review, smart factory requirements are identified under five main headings, namely: knowledge availability, managerial, organizational, technological, and human-related, to build an integrated vision of the essential requirements to setup smart factories and enable the digital transformation. Using these main headings, a house of requirements is developed to give an integrated picture. This clarifies and clusters the requirements and provides a compact summary representation of these requirements, which is a unique representation.

4. Developing smart capabilities business model: Based on the business canvas logic and multi-perspective capabilities and requirements, this study offered a smart-capabilities business model as a comprehensive picture of the business aspects to satisfy the business challenges.

The smart factories require unique capabilities and sophisticated requirements, and involve handling and integration of complex technological aspects. Shifting to intelligent business models while considering sustainability and keeping all business operations profitable are essential in line with smart factory technological requirements. The proposed model manifests itself at the process, organizational, and network levels. It is compatible with the system hierarchy of the multi-perspective framework proposed; complies with the previously mentioned smart factory requirements and considers all the smart factory capabilities identified as the basis of network information sharing, transparency, integration, and collaboration. The comprehensive nature of the proposed model ensures compatibility with smart factory requirements and answers the challenges of the smart and dynamic business environment.

All the configured capabilities lead to joint-performance, joint-monetization, and joint risk management among business network participants. Hence, all these capabilities serve to develop network-level performance and risk management systems, and ultimately, the model is compatible with the recent collaborative supply chain performance and risk management literature.

The model developed complies with the developments in the organization theory and collaborative supply network literature. This supports the recent organizational ideas such as virtual enterprises, organizational fluidity, and collaboration across blurring boundaries. Thus, BM developed is a comprehensive representation of intended interactions among heterogeneous entities aiming to develop approaches towards goals. They provide a primary value proposition for consumers, provide a beneficial structure of cost-risk, and consider key resources and relationships to be formed.

5. Developing a multi-perspective framework for SMO: A generic framework is developed corresponding to and integrating with a proposed business model, conforming to the smart factory requirements and the dynamic and smart business environment requirements. The proposed framework encompasses five dimensions of "System hierarchy perspective," "Stakeholder perspective," "Time perspective," "Capabilities perspective," "Macro-process perspective."

The data-driven reconfigurable nature of a smart factory has a multi-layered architecture consisting of six levels: technological level, design principles level, features level, factory capability level, enterprise capability level, and networked capability level. The subsequent level depends on the interaction of former levels, and the data flow among the six levels form a closed and interacted loop. The proposed framework clarifies smart system hierarchy on the way from sensors & devices to collaborative smart ecosystems. This eliminates the confusion in terminology in the literature. It enables multi-partner collaborative processes at multiple time dimensions and hierarchy levels. All time dimensions and processes are handled. Also, it complies with the automation hierarchy and PLC management.

Thus, a multi-perspective framework proposed in this study is a situation-driven integrative environment and it handles heterogeneous entities (ideas, physical, process, cyber, human) as integrated, interoperated, and configurable objects into a smart-

collaborative manufacturing system. As such, it is one of the major contributions of the study.

6. Smart factory requirements maturity index development: The study developed a new assessment survey to determine smart factory requirements and a maturity index to translate the smart factory's abstract requirements into specific and measurable items. The assessment survey developed is compatible with the breakdown of capabilities, requirements, technological components, and features identified. SFRMI focuses on technical aspects and organizational, managerial, human-related, and knowledge aspects such as strategy, capabilities, features, leadership, structure, business model, and people.

In compatibility with the survey tool, a set of maturity measurement indices and a flexible scoring system are suggested for quantifying the maturity in multiple dimensions and to obtain an overall measurement. Maturity level calculation includes five main requirements equations. Each requirement area can be considered a self-contained module, and can be scored. Thus, it is possible to add or remove one or more sub-dimensions in certain industrial situations or when it is desired to measure specific dimensions only for the planned digital transformation. The scoring system also allows for different weighting schemes to be applied.

Hence, the model, survey tool, and index system developed to form a multidimensional, comprehensive, and unique view of smart factory capabilities. This can be used as a self-assessment method for investigating the maturity of the factories, and it is applicable to any sector. Hence, a generic approach is contributed to the literature.

7. Roadmap development: After conducting the field study, a generic and practical roadmap is offered to manufacturing enterprises to guide companies towards smart factory implementations. The study's systematic sequence resulted in an integrated and comprehensive roadmap.

Due to its multidimensional and comprehensive nature of the study, all of the above are contributions to literature. Thus, the study offered an in-depth academic overview as a theoretical contribution, and a practical systematic for the enterprises seeking to adopt the smart factory.

8.2. Practical Implications:

Field study performed for 8 case companies has shown the applicability and practicality of the survey tool and the scoring system to investigate the readiness and maturity levels of the enterprises.

This study provided an integrated systematic method for estimating the readiness and maturity for industry 4.0 based smart factory, starting with comprehensive criteria (SF requirements), data collection method (survey), measurement method, and finally targeted levels. Maturity score calculations in multiple dimensions are enabled for digital transformation. Thus, the integrated systematic offered in this study can be used by the enterprises as a self-assessment tool to determine their existing situation. After determining the current readiness, the roadmap developed can guide the enterprises towards their smart implementation journey.

The thesis has identified the different motivations, expected hurdles, and smartness orientation levels of the smart factory adoption for Turkish automotive companies. It has been found that the knowledge buildup regarding smart factories and industry 4.0 has acceptably existed in the automotive sector. Industry 4.0 based smart factory concept is being widely recognized as a tool for productivity improvement, effectiveness and efficiency enhancement and hence, continues competitive advantage.

Turkish manufacturers operating in the automotive sector have a low degree of technological maturity, suggesting that they need further efforts toward SF implementation. Simultaneously, the actual level of managerial and organizational infrastructures of the respondent companies has been assessed through a maturity level and proved that managerial and organizational contents in surveyed companies are suitable for smart factories.

The study showed that surveyed Turkish automotive companies have individual maturity of many requirements towards smart factory. Still, it does not mean that they have all smart factory characteristics and capabilities. Since smart factories require integrated installations of many capabilities, they have to focus on the gaps identified to continue their journey towards smart integration.

The workplace changes that occur as a result of the digital transition have a significant effect on the company's workers, who must adapt to these changes and learn new skills.

Companies that are undergoing digital transformations must ensure that their employees are adequately trained to deal with the changes.

The different hurdles that Turkish companies may face in their journey toward a smart factory have also been discussed based on their identification being how owning qualified labor, building a digital culture, business process reengineering, reengineering organizational structure, digitalization strategy development, acquisition of technologies, and continuous upgrading of technologies. Because of these hurdles, recommendations were made by the author consisting mainly in embracing smart capabilities business model, developing overall transformation strategy based on universal smart factory requirements, and multi-perspective framework for SMO.

Thus, the integrative structure developed enabled the author to provide specific suggestions to individual surveyed companies from practical perspective, and facilitated an overall picture of multiple companies within a sector.

8.3. Further Research Suggestions

The system developed in this study allowed for enterprise-based evaluations and cross-enterprise comparisons within a sector. If applied systematically in multiple sectors, the approached offered can be used for cross-sector comparisons and benchmarking. Hence, the systematic suggested in this study can be applied to other types of businesses, industries, or countries. Thus, feedback from comparative results of multiple applications of the proposed model across many countries, sectors, and organizations will be valuable further research avenues. The authors hope that the systematic suggested here can lead to various specific projects and implementations in different sectors.

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Appendix A: SFRMI Survey

Industry-4.0 based smart manufacturing requirements maturity level survey

Aims of the survey

This questionnaire is prepared to investigate the current state of awareness and identify how well smart factory requirements are met to assess the readiness and the maturity level of smart factory transformation in Turkish industry to derive the roadmap to smart factory adoption. It will be conducted within the scope of the PhD Thesis "*A managerial roadmap development for industry 4.0-based smart manufacturing enterprise: a cross-sector study in Turkey*" in Business Administration Department, THK University. The survey questions are organized in 6 sections:

Section (A) is for collecting general information about the enterprise.

Section (B) is for assessing availability of knowledge.

Section (C) is for determining how well technological requirements are met for smart factory (SF).

Section (D) is for determining how well managerial requirements are met for SF.

Section (E) is for determining how well organizational requirements are met for SF.

Section (F) is for determining how well human-related requirements are met for SF.

To cope with and face today's environmental challenges, the industrial organization should be, flexible, lean, agile, adaptable, responsive, integrative, profitable, and proactive behavior to be able to survive, grow, and realize a sustainable competitive advantage. Therefore, the manufacturing organization should ride the change wave towards smart Factory for competitiveness and survival.

Industry 4.0 (I4.0) The term Industry 4.0 comprises a variety of technologies to enable the development of a digital and automated manufacturing environment as well as the digitization of the value chain via embedding a computational and networking capabilities.

Smart Factory (SF) is a set of physical and cyber entities working and interacting smartly to ensure configuring an integrated and networked production system which is characterized by dynamic configuration, self-optimization, self-diagnosis, self-adaption, self-control, and self-learning, human-centered manufacturing, customer-focused manufacturing and collaborative abilities.

Business Model (BM) is a comprehensive tool describing the interactions' logic (organizational relationships) among key entities (including humans, physical, and cyber) to configure a conceptual view of monetization mechanism (value creation network), features, capabilities, and potential scenarios.

Note*: Please find a glossary of terms attached at the end of the survey for further key terms used.

List of abbreviations		Explanation
Internet of Things	IoT	All enabling technologies to facilitate the communicability of physical objects and their interactivities to Cyberspace.
Cyber Physical System	CPS	An integrating environment for physical and virtual entities which ensure real representation of physical objects in cyberspace, deploying high level of interconnectivity, interoperability, and knowledgeability.
Cloud Computing	CC	Enabling technology of on-demand sharing and remote-usage of distributed and heterogeneous IT resources.
Business Intelligence	BI	Processes, methods, software and services to transform data into actionable insights that inform and support an organization's strategic and tactical business decisions.
Additive Manufacturing	AM	The transformative set of technologies to build 3D objects by depositing layers to gradually embody the product's from its CAD file through 3D printers.
Computer Integrated Manufacturing	CIM	Manufacturing approach of using computers to control entire production process.
Big Data	BD	Extracting, managing and finding the valuable and realistic meaning hidden behind data of huge volume, variety and velocity to reconfigure systems to smart systems.
Augmented reality	AR	A technology that superimposes a computer-generated image on a user's view of the real world, thus providing a composite view.
Enterprise resource planning	ERP	Integrated set of business applications to manage and integrate all business processes and resources within the organization.
Robots		Smart; interactive; reconfigurable; and adaptable entity to work as part of a collaborative manufacturing environment.
Simulation		An approximate imitation of the operations of a process or system in a computerized environment; representing its operation over time.

Note** Please take in your account the following description of **levels** for answering the survey questions.

NO/ Not applicable (N/A)	1	2	3	4	5
0	Low..... High				
Outsider	Beginner	Intermediate	Experienced	Expert	First-mover/ leader

Outsider	Enterprise does not meet any of the requirements for SF.
Beginner	Enterprise is starting to embrace some technologies and to initiate reengineering traditional functions, structures and models.
Intermediate	Individual, separate and low-level meeting of some requirements in the enterprise.
Experienced	Many of the requirements are met at mid-level, most of the technologies are acquired, some of the design principles are built, and individually enabling of some features in the enterprise.
Expert	A maturity level where the company is ready to implement a smart factory. Most of the design principles and features are acquired and ready to use.
First-mover/ leader	All requirements are met and started to bear fruit in the enterprise. Thus, a smart manufacturing environment is established which inspire can many other businesses to start their smart initiative.

A) General information

Enterprise Name:

Industry

Type:

- Defense
- Aerospace
- Electronic
- Automotive
- Logistic and Transport
- Food Processing
- Wood/furniture
- Petrochemical
- Construction
- IT
- Textile
- Agricultural
- Packaging
- Others

Address:

Department Name of the interviewee:

Position title:

E-mail:

Please indicate the number of employees in your company.

- Up to 19 employees
- 20 to 99 employees
- 100 to 249 employees
- 250 to 499 employees
- 500 or 1000 employees
- 1001 or more employees

Main Business:

- B2B (Business to Business)
- B2C (Business to Customer)
- B2G (Business to Government)

Technological level of the product provided	Low-tech	Mid-tech	Hi-tech

B) Knowledge availability

In this section, please indicate the level of information (how much you know about) and cognitive readiness of your company to implement the smart factory and Industry-4.0 technologies according to the list of the following questions.

	NO	Yes				
		1	2	3	4	5
1- Does your enterprise have awareness and knowledge of smart factory?						
2- Do you have studied or initialized any projects related with I4.0?						
3- Does your enterprise engage in any efforts to build desired awareness for digital transformation?						
4- Does your enterprise have proper awareness and knowledge of I4.0?						
5- Are the educational specializations of your employees related to the I4.0's technologies?						

	No idea	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
6- Industry 4.0 and smart manufacturing concepts will be the key for future success.						
7- Lack of knowledge about I4.0 & SF will lead to ignoring the digital transformation.						
8- Lack of standards will lead to postponing the embracement of I4.0 and SF						
9- Lack of qualified employees cause ignoring the I4.0 and SF concepts.						
10- Our business success relies on data, knowledge, and analytics						

11- Please indicate knowledge level (how much you know) of your enterprise about these technologies (Please check for each technology).	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
IoT						
CPS						
CC						
BI						
AM						
CIM						
BD						
Robotics						
AR						
ERP						
Simulation						

12- How will the digitalization of your enterprise serve their customers better?	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Need-oriented						
Small-lot order						
Customization						
Individualized product						

13. To which degree your enterprise processes; products; and machines are smart, digitalized and automated?	Smart					Digitalized					Automated							
	N/A	1	2	3	4	5	N/A	1	2	3	4	5	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Processes																		
Product																		
Machines																		

14- Which of following hurdles do you expect to face for switching to smart factory? (You can check more than one for each group)

Technological	Managerial	Organizational	Human
<input type="checkbox"/> Acquisition of Technologies	<input type="checkbox"/> Strategy development	<input type="checkbox"/> Reengineering organizational structure	<input type="checkbox"/> Qualified labor
<input type="checkbox"/> Installation of Technologies	<input type="checkbox"/> Vision & Mission development	<input type="checkbox"/> Business Process reengineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Collaborative interaction
<input type="checkbox"/> Utilization of Technologies	<input type="checkbox"/> Proper project manager skills	<input type="checkbox"/> Change management	<input type="checkbox"/> Innovative thinking
<input type="checkbox"/> Going live (implementation)	<input type="checkbox"/> Commitment and support	<input type="checkbox"/> Create collaborative culture	<input type="checkbox"/> Digital culture
<input type="checkbox"/> Maintenance	<input type="checkbox"/> Networked collaboration	<input type="checkbox"/> Info-integration from heterogeneous sources.	<input type="checkbox"/> Knowledge and experiences
<input type="checkbox"/> Upgrading	<input type="checkbox"/> Leadership style	<input type="checkbox"/> Cross-divisional transparency	<input type="checkbox"/> Data-related skills

C) Technological requirements

Please indicate the level of technological readiness (maturity level) of your company to implement SF according to the list of the following questions.

15- Which of the following technologies are in your planned acquisition priority? (Please check for each technology. 5: highest priority).	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
IoT						
CPS						
CC						
BI						
AM						
CIM						
BD						
Robotics						
AR						
ERP						
Simulation						
16- Which of the following technologies are already acquired at your organization but not utilized yet? (Please check for each technology)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
IoT						
CPS						
CC						
BI						
AM						
CIM						
BD						
Robotics						
AR						
ERP						
Simulation						
17- Which of the following technologies are already used at your organization (Please check for each technology)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
IoT						
CPS						
CC						
BI						
AM						
CIM						
BD						
Robotics						
AR						
ERP						
Simulation						

18- How well do you think the following design principles are met in your enterprise? (Please check for each principle)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Virtualization						
Digitalization						
Interoperability						
Integrated system						
Standardization						
Flexibility						
Service Orientation						
Modularity						
Safety and Security						
Decentralization						

19- To which degree your enterprise processes and equipment are characterized by following features? (Please check for each feature)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Self-controlled						
Self-organization						
Self-configuration						
Self-coordination						
Self-diagnostic						
Self-decision						
Self-compare						
Self-optimization						
Self-adapt						
Self-predict						
Self-aware						

20- Which of the following features are currently ready, or to be achieved in 3-5 years in your enterprise? (Please check for each feature)	Readiness					Next 3-5 years						
	N/A	1	2	3	4	5	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Connectivity												
Integrability												
Networked												
Real-time skills												
Accessibility												
Transparency												
Traceability												
Automation												
Smooth data flow												

21- Which of the following intelligence capability(ies) do you have for enhancing business operations? Or which do you plan to establish? (Please check for every capability) (N/A=0: Yes, to some extent = 3; Yes, completely = 5)	Existed					Next 3-5 years						
	N/A	1	2	3	4	5	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Intelligent predictability												
Info-integration from heterogeneous sources												
Intelligent visualization												
Real-time data availability from heterogeneous sources												
Intelligent analysis												
Intelligent learning												
Intelligent sensing												
Intelligent reconfiguration												
Intelligent proactive behavior												
Intelligent awareness												

22- In which capability(ies), do you think, your enterprise needs to invest? (Please check for every capability)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Competitive Capability						
Intelligence Capability						
Customizing Capability						
Dynamic Interaction						
Autonomous Capability						

23- How do you evaluate your enterprise competitive capability regarding the following characteristics? (Please check for every capability)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Agility						
Lean						
Adaptability						
Sustainability						
Optimization						
Responsive						
Scalability						
Efficiency						

D) Managerial requirements

Please indicate the level of managerial readiness (maturity level) of your company to implement SF according to the list of the following questions.

	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
24- Does your enterprise have plan, or strategy, to implement Digital Transformation?						
25- Does your enterprise have a clear vision & mission regarding the digital transformation (smart factory establishment)?						
26- Does your management provide the desired commitment and support for digital transformation projects?						
27- Does your enterprise have clear targets for the next five years regarding transformation to the smart factory?						
28- Do you have an evaluation of your own digital maturity?						
29- Are you looking for networked collaboration to help you switching to smart factory?						
30- Have you formed a team of experts for Industry 4.0 in your enterprise?						
31- Has your company started digitizing their management practices?						
32- To which degree your employees' behavior and decisions are integrated with ERP and BI software?						

	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
33- How would you evaluate your enterprise goals regarding SF transformation? (Please check for each characteristic)	N/A					
Specific (simple, sensible, significant).						
Measurable (meaningful, motivating).						
Achievable (agreed, attainable).						
Relevant (reasonable, realistic and resourced, results-based).						
Time-bound						
34- What's your organization 's biggest digital transformation goal? (Please check for each characteristic)	N/A					
Productivity						
Profits						
Market share						
Competitive advantage						
Effectiveness and efficiency						
35- How would you evaluate your enterprise managers when it comes to the following characteristics? (Please check for each characteristic)	N/A					
Innovation-driven						
Open to networked interaction						

	Having a coaching-style leadership approach						
	Open to change						
	Having digital skills						
	BeingTech-savvy						
36-	How would you evaluate your enterprise practices when it comes to support the following objectives? (Please check for each characteristic)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
	Agility						
	Lean						
	Culture enrichment						
	Dynamic capabilities						
	Motivation						
	Participation						
	Innovation						
	Learning						

E) Organizational requirements

Please indicate the level of organizational readiness (maturity level) of your company to implement SF according to the list of the following questions.

37- How do you describe your enterprise regarding the following features? (Please check for each feature)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Flat structure						
Responsiveness						
Adaptiveness						
Fast decision-making						
38- How do you describe your enterprise business model regarding the following features? (Please check for each feature)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Comprehensive						
Collaborative						
Data-driven						
Responsive						
Dynamic						
Networked						
39- To what degree does your business model enable data-sharing for:	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Decision making						
Integration						
Managing processes						
Assessing performance						
Optimizing						
Driving behavior						
40- How can you describe your business model regarding the following? (Please check for each)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Sustainability						
Interaction						
Integration						
Collaboration						
Responsiveness						
Connectivity						
Dynamism						
41- How do you describe your enterprise structure regarding the following features? (Please check for each)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Lean						
Agility						
Integration						
Smartness						

42- How do you describe your enterprise culture regarding the support of the following features? (Please check for each)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Digitalization-orientation						
Knowledge-orientation						
Innovation orientation						
Quality-orientation						
Collaboration						
Continues Learning						
Participation						
	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
43- Does your enterprise reengineer traditional functions to ensure IT and operations are working together effectively?						
44- Does your enterprise structure ensure data-transparency and facilitate a smooth exchanging of data?						
45- Does your enterprise digitalize the business model used?						

F) Human-related requirements

This section concentrates on the role and abilities related with the human resources. Please indicate the level of human resource readiness (maturity) level of your company to implement SF according to the list of the following questions.

46- What is the degree of importance to the following skills and competencies in your company towards a smart factory? (Please check for each)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Real-time capability						
Innovative-thinking						
Dynamic skills						
Interactive skills						
Data-related skills						
47- Emerging technologies and methods will radically change the nature of jobs and the types of skills needed. To what degree are the following used in your enterprise to enhance the expertise and skill inventory?	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Workshops						
Training programs						
Learning programs						
Self-learning						
Virtual Reality						
Augmented Reality						
48- To what extent does your enterprise pursue to build the following innovative capabilities in the next 5 years?	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Real-time Capability						
Innovative-thinking						
Dynamic-Skills						
Interactive skills						
Data-related skills						
49- How do you evaluate the readiness of your workforce to use the following technologies?	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
IoT						
CPS						
CC						
BI						
AM						
CIM						
BD						
Robotics						
AR						
ERP						
Simulation						

Glossary of Terms

Term	Description
Accessibility	The practice of making data usable by as many entities as possible.
Adaptability	Ability to quickly respond to changes, trends, innovation, and shifts in industry and economy. .
Agility	Ability of a company to adapt to market changes, and responding rapidly and flexibly to customer demands.
Automation	Performing with minimal human intervention.
Autonomous Capability	A wide range of features could lie under this capability to enable autonomous interaction, triggering actions, reacting, create services, and awareness...etc, for all entities.
Competitive Capability	The ability of the system to cope with challenges and changes in the business environment regardless of dynamism and complexity of challenges.
Connectivity	The ability to connect to or communicate with other entities.
Customized products	Tailored design and producing product according to customers need and preferences.
Customizing Capability	Ability to produce and offer products according to customer requirements. U
Decentralization	The ability of autonomous decision-making (self or local), and managing their own behaviour for each entity.
Digitalization	Digital form of the physical objects and processes that can be processed by a computer.
Dynamic Interaction	Ensuring the operation of the entire system in an integrated and coordinated manner. They allow smooth exchanging of data among entities (physical, cyber, process, and human), ensure interoperability and collaboration among distributed objects.
Dynamic-Skills	Ability to continuously adopt and develop skills.
Flexibility	Ability to respond to changeable-demand and product variety.
Info-integration from heterogeneous sources	All entities and partners considered as data generators in the smart factory context. It refers to integration across sources of different character.
Integrability	The ability to establish an integrative framework to create a harmonic and cooperative environment of heterogeneous entities including technologies, human and systems.
Integrated system	u A system in which subsystems and components are unified to realize goals.
Intelligence Capability	Source of smartness for all entities and enterprises. This capability starts in acquiring data to produce knowledge, and it enables knowledge dissemination to enable predictions.
Intelligent analysis	Any form of analysis that will lead to smart decisions
Intelligent awareness	Ability to create knowledge based on heterogeneous data sources.
Intelligent learning	Ability to learn from heterogeneous sources of data, information, and knowledge.
Intelligent predictability	The degree to which a correct prediction or forecast of a system's state and performance can be conducted either qualitatively or quantitatively based on heterogeneous integrated data.
Intelligent proactive behavior	Data-driven behavior that is preventive for future problems.
Intelligent reconfiguration	The arrangement of parts or entities of a system in a different form or combination to realize different goals.
Intelligent sensing	A huge set of networked and distributed sensors for smart, real-time, , integrated, and comprehensive sensing.
Intelligent visualization	Any technique for creating digital images, diagrams, animations, so on to be shared among entities.
Interoperability	Creating a cooperative and integrative interaction and behaviour of various entities

Lean	Maximizing customer value by using fewer resources operating in an optimized and effective manner, and minimizing waste.
Modularity	The degree of reconfigurability of systems from structured, well-defined pieced to compose different systems, operations, functions and products.
Networked	Entities are connected together so that they can share information, and engage in joint-decision making, resource sharing and co-performance.
Optimization	Making the best or most effective use of a situation or resource, such as maximizing value or minimizing cost.
Real-time Capability	The ability to perform real-time data and analysis to support decision making processes.
Real-time responsiveness	The ability of immediate response to problems, demand, needs, developments, challenges and risks.
Responsive	The ability of reacting quickly and effectively for customer-centric results. .
Safety and Security	The condition of being free from digital and physical harm or risk.
Scalability	Ability of a system to handle increased or expanded or scope.
Self-adapt	The machine's ability to exhibit contextual behavior.
Self-aware	The ability to be context-sensitive and to be able to learn, and create knowledge continuously.
Self-compare	The machine's ability to make a comparison with other entities within the same production network.
Self-configuration	A process by which machines automatically adapt their own configuration of components without human direct intervention.
Self-controlled	The machines' or systems' ability to control their behavior.
Self-coordination	A process by which machines automatically coordinate and re-coordinate with the operational environment entities without direct human intervention.
Self-decision	The machine's ability to make a choice or decide by itself.
Self-diagnostic	The process by which machines automatically recognize, or identify the symptoms or unhealthy signs and conditions from the machines or systems.
Self-optimization	The machine's ability to make optimization and finding the best solution.
Self-organization	The machine's or systems's ability to auto-connect and network with other entities.
Self-predict	The machine's ability to make realistic predictions with sensitivity to situational indicators, symptoms, signs and conditions.
Service Orientation	Making everything (software, platform, infrastructure) accessible in terms of service via a service provider.
SF knowledge	Overall knowledge of All SF- related concepts, philosophy, mechanism, benefits and challenges
Smart products	High-tech products that have capabilities such as connectivity, monitoring and error-diagnostics.
Standardization	Using fully accepted interacting and performing methods and rules by most parties.
Sustainability	Ability of a company to sustain its operations in multiple dimensions such as financial, economic, social and environmental.
Traceability	Ability to verify the history, location, or transactions of an item by means of documented and recorded identification.
Transparency	Operating in such a way that it is easy for others entities and partners to see generated data and information.
Virtualization	Creating a paired digital version of physical entities and processes.

Endüstri 4.0 tabanlı akıllı üretim gereksinimleri olgunluk seviyesi anketi

Anketin amaçları

Bu anket mevcut farkındalık durumunu araştırmak ve akıllı fabrika (SF) adaptasyonuna giden yol haritasını çıkarmak üzere Türk endüstrisindeki akıllı fabrika dönüşümünün olgunluk düzeyinin ve hazır olup olmadığını değerlendirmek için akıllı fabrika gereksinimlerinin ne kadar iyi karşılandığını araştırmak için hazırlanmıştır. Bu anket, THK Üniversitesi İşletme Bölümü'nde “Endüstri 4.0 tabanlı akıllı üretim işletmesi için bir yönetsel yol haritasının geliştirilmesi: Türkiye’de sektörler arası çalışma” Doktora tezi kapsamında yürütülecektir. Anket soruları 6 bölüm halinde düzenlenmiştir:

- 1- Bölüm (A), işletme hakkında genel bilgi toplamak içindir.
- 2- Bölüm (B), bilginin varlığını değerlendirmek içindir.
- 3- Bölüm (C), akıllı fabrika (SF) ile ilgili teknolojik gereksinimlerin ne kadar iyi karşılandığını belirlemek içindir.
- 4- Bölüm (D), akıllı fabrika (SF) ile ilgili yönetsel gereksinimlerinin ne kadar iyi karşılandığını belirlemek içindir.
- 5- Bölüm (E), akıllı fabrika (SF) ile ilgili organizasyonel gereksinimlerin ne kadar iyi karşılandığını belirlemek içindir.
- 6- Bölüm (F), SF için insanla ilgili gereksinimlerin ne kadar iyi karşılandığını belirlemek içindir.

Endüstriyel organizasyon; günümüzün çevresel zorluklarıyla başa çıkmak, bu zorluklar ile yüzleşebilmek ve bu zorluklar karşısında hayatta kalabilmek, büyüyebilmek ve sürdürülebilir bir rekabet avantajı elde edebilmek için esnek, yalın, çevik, uyarlanabilir, cevap veren, bütünleştirici, karlı ve proaktif davranışlar sergilemelidir.

Bu nedenle, üretim organizasyonu, rekabet gücü ve hayatta kalmak için akıllı fabrikaya olan değişim dalgasını doğru yönetmelidir.

Endüstri 4.0 (I4.0): Endüstri 4.0 terimi, dijital ve otomatasyona dayalı bir üretim ortamının geliştirilmesinin yanı sıra, hesaplama ve ağ oluşturma yeteneklerinin yerleştirilerek değer zincirinin dijitalleştirilmesini sağlayan çok çeşitli teknolojileri içerir.

Akıllı fabrika (SF): dinamik konfigürasyon, kendi kendine optimizasyon, kendi kendine teşhis, kendi kendine uyarlama, kendi kendini kontrol etme ve kendi kendine öğrenme, insan merkezli üretim, müşteri odaklı üretim ve işbirliğine dayalı yetenekler ile karakterize edilen entegre ve ağa bağlı bir üretim sistemini yapılandırmayı sağlamak için akıllıca çalışan ve etkileşimde bulunan bir dizi fiziksel ve siber varlıktır.

İş Modeli (BM); para kazanma mekanizmasının (değer yaratma ağı), özelliklerin, yetkinliklerin ve potansiyel senaryoların kavramsal bir görünümünü yapılandırmak için temel varlıklar (insanları, fiziksel ve siber dâhil) arasındaki etkileşim mantığını (organizasyonel ilişkileri) açıklayan kapsamlı bir araçtır.

Kısaltmaların listesi		Açıklama
Nesnelerin İnterneti	IoT	Fiziksel nesnelerin iletişimini ve onların siber uzayda etkileşimlerini iletişimini sağlamaya imkân veren tüm teknolojiler.
Siber Fiziksel Sistem	CPS	Fiziksel ve sanal varlıklar için siber uzayda fiziksel nesnelerin gerçek temsilini sağlayan; yüksek düzeyde karşılıklı bağlantı, birlikte çalışabilirlik ve bilgi paylaşımını kullanan için entegre bir ortamdır.
Bulut bilişim	CC	Dağıtılmış ve heterojen BT kaynaklarının uzaktan kullanımını ve isteğe bağlı paylaşımını sağlayan teknolojidir.
İş zekâsı	BI	Bir kuruluşun stratejik ve taktiksel iş kararlarına bilgi sağlayan ve destekleyen, aynı zamanda verileri eyleme geçirilebilir görüşlere dönüştürmek için kullanılan süreçler, yöntemler, yazılım ve hizmetlerdir.
Katmanlı üretim	AM	Bir ürünün CAD dosyasından 3D yazıcılar aracılığıyla üretimini kademeli olarak gerçekleştirmesi için katmanları yerleştirme yardımıyla 3D nesnelere oluşturmakta kullanılan dönüştürücü teknolojiler setidir.
Bilgisayarla Tümlşik Üretim	CIM	Tüm üretim sürecini kontrol etmek için bilgisayar kullanan üretim yaklaşımı.
Büyük Veri	BD	Sistemleri akıllı sistemler şeklinde yeniden yapılandırmak için devasa hacimli, çeşitlilikte ve hızdaki verilerin ardında gizli olan değerli ve gerçekçi anlamı çıkarmak, yönetmek ve bulmak.
Artırılmış Gerçeklik	AR	Bir kullanıcının gerçek dünya görüşünün üzerine bilgisayar tarafından oluşturulan bir görüntüyü yerleştiren ve böylece birleşik bir görüntü sağlayan bir teknolojidir.
Kurumsal Kaynak Planlaması	ERP	Bir organizasyon içindeki tüm iş süreçlerini ve kaynakları yönetmek ve entegre etmek için kullanılan bütünlük (entegre) iş uygulamaları setidir.
Robotlar		Akıllı, etkileşimli, yeniden yapılandırılabilir ve işbirliğine dayalı bir üretim ortamının parçası olarak çalışmak için uyarlanabilir varlık.
Simülasyon		Bir sistem ya da süreç işleyişinin bilgisayarlı bir ortamında ve zaman içerisindeki çalışmasını temsil eden yaklaşık bir taklidi dir.

Not *:Anketin sonunda yer alan terimler sözlüğünde ihtiyacınız olabilecek diğer önemli anahtar terimlerin açıklamalarını bulabilirsiniz.

Not **: Lütfen anket sorularını yanıtlamak için aşağıdaki düzey tanımlarını dikkate alınız.

HAYIR / Uyulanamaz/Mevcut değil (N / A)	1	2	3	4	5
0	Düşük Yüksek				
Konuya yabancı	Yeni başlayan	Orta düzey	Deneyimli	Uzman	İlk hareket eden / Lider

Konuya yabancı	İşletme, Akıllı fabrika (SF) için hiçbir gereksinimi karşılamaz.
Yeni başlayan	İşletme, bazı teknolojileri ve geleneksel işlevlerin, yapıların ve modellerin yeniden yapılandırılmasını benimsemeye başlamaktadır.
Orta düzey	İşletmede bazı gereksinimlerin birbirinden ayrı ve düşük düzeyde olarak karşılanması.
Deneyimli	İşletmede gereksinimlerin çoğu orta düzeyde karşılanır, teknolojilerin çoğu edinilmiş/elde edilmiştir. Bazı tasarım ilkeleri oluşturulmuş ve bazı özelliklerin ayrı ayrı etkinleştirilmesi sağlanmıştır.
Uzman	İşletmenin akıllı bir fabrika uygulamaya hazır olduğu bir olgunluk seviyesi. Tasarım ilkelerinin ve özelliklerinin çoğu edinilmiş ve kullanıma hazırdır.
İlk hareket eden / Lider	İşletmede tüm gereksinimler karşılanmaya ve fayda vermeye başlamıştır. Böylece, diğer birçok işletmeye akıllı girişimlerini başlatmaları için ilham veren akıllı bir üretim ortamı oluşturulmuştur.

A. Genel Bilgiler

Kuruluş Adı :

Sektör Tipi :

- | | | |
|--|---|-----------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Savunma | <input type="checkbox"/> Gıda işleme | <input type="checkbox"/> Tekstil |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Havacılık | <input type="checkbox"/> Ağaç / Mobilya | <input type="checkbox"/> Tarımsal |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Elektronik | <input type="checkbox"/> Petrokimya | <input type="checkbox"/> Diğer |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Otomotiv | <input type="checkbox"/> İnşaat | <input type="checkbox"/> Ambalaj |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Lojistik ve Taşımacılık | <input type="checkbox"/> BT | |

Adres:

Görüşülen kişinin Bölüm Adı:

Görev Ünvanı:

E-posta:

Lütfen şirketinizin çalışan sayısını belirtin.

- | | |
|--|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> 19 çalışana kadar | <input type="checkbox"/> 250 - 499 çalışan |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 20 ile 99 çalışan | <input type="checkbox"/> 500 veya 1000 çalışan |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 100 ile 249 çalışan | <input type="checkbox"/> 1001 veya daha fazla çalışan |

Ana iş:

- B2B (İşletmeden İşletmeye)
- B2C (İşletmeden Müşteriye)
- B2G (İşletmeden Devlete)

Sağlanan ürünün teknolojik seviyesi	Düşük Teknoloji	Orta Teknoloji	Yüksek Teknoloji

B. Bilgi varlığı

Bu bölümde, lütfen aşağıdaki soru listesine göre şirketinizin akıllı fabrika ve Endüstri-4.0 teknolojilerini uygulamaya yönelik bilgi düzeyini (ne kadar bildiğiniz) ve bilişsel olarak hazır olup olmadığını belirtin.

	Hayır	Evet				
		1	2	3	4	5
1) İşletmenizin akıllı fabrika ile ilgili farkındalığı ve bilgisi var mı?						
2) I 4.0 ile ilgili çalıştınız mı veya herhangi bir projeyi başlattınız mı?						
3) İşletmeniz dijital dönüşüm için istenen farkındalığı oluşturmak için herhangi bir çaba gösteriyor mu?						
4) İşletmeniz I4.0 konusunda yeterli farkındalığa ve bilgiye sahip mi?						
5) Çalışanlarınızın eğitim uzmanlıkları I4.0 teknolojileriyle ilgili mi?						

	Fikrim yok	Kesinlikle katılmıyorum	Katılmıyorum	Nötr	Katılıyorum	Kesinlikle katılıyorum
6) Endüstri 4.0 ve akıllı üretim kavramları, gelecekteki başarının anahtarı olacaktır.						
7) I4.0 ve SF hakkında bilgi eksikliği, dijital dönüşümü görmezden gelmeye sebep olacaktır.						
8) Standartların olmaması, I4.0 ve akıllı fabrika (SF) nın benimsenmesinin ertelenmesine sebep olacaktır.						
9) Nitelikli çalışan eksikliği, I4.0 ve SF kavramlarının göz ardı edilmesine neden olur.						
10) İş başarımız veri, bilgi ve analitiğe dayanır.						

11) Lütfen işletmenizin bu teknolojilerle ilgili bilgi düzeyini (ne kadar bildiğinizi) belirtin (Lütfen her bir teknoloji için işaretleyin).	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Nesnelerin İnterneti (IoT)						
CPS						
Bulut bilişim (CC)						
İş zekâsı (BI)						
Katmanlı üretim (AM)						
Bilgisayarla Tümlleşik Üretim (CIM)						
Büyük Veri (BD)						
Robot						
Artırılmış Gerçeklik (AR)						
Kurumsal Kaynak Planlaması (ERP)						
Simülasyon						
12) İşletmenizin dijitalleşmesi müşterilerinize nasıl daha iyi hizmet edecek?	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
İhtiyaç odaklı						
Küçük-lot sipariş						
Özelleştirme						

13- Kurumsal süreçleriniz, ürünleriniz ve makineleriniz ne ölçüde akıllı, dijital ve otomatik?	Akıllı					Dijitalleştirilm iş					Otomatik							
	N/A	1	2	3	4	5	N/A	1	2	3	4	5	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Süreçler																		
Ürün																		
Makineler																		

14- Akıllı fabrikaya geçerken aşağıdaki engellerden hangisiyle karşılaşmayı bekliyorsunuz? (Her grup için birden fazla işaretleyebilirsiniz)

Teknolojik	Yönetimsel	Örgütsel	İnsan
<input type="checkbox"/> Teknolojinin Edinilmesi	<input type="checkbox"/> Strateji Geliştirme	<input type="checkbox"/> Organizasyon yapısının yeniden yapılandırılması	<input type="checkbox"/> Nitelikli işgücü
<input type="checkbox"/> Teknolojilerin kurulumu	<input type="checkbox"/> Vizyon ve misyon geliştirme	<input type="checkbox"/> İş süreçlerinin yeniden yapılanması	<input type="checkbox"/> İşbirlikçi etkileşim
<input type="checkbox"/> Teknolojilerin Kullanımı	<input type="checkbox"/> Uygun proje yöneticisi becerileri	<input type="checkbox"/> Değişiklik yönetimi	<input type="checkbox"/> Yenilikçi düşünce
<input type="checkbox"/> Canlıya geçiş (uygulama)	<input type="checkbox"/> Bağlılık (taahhüt) ve destek	<input type="checkbox"/> İşbirliği kültürü oluşturulması	<input type="checkbox"/> Dijital kültür
<input type="checkbox"/> Bakım	<input type="checkbox"/> Ağ üzerinde işbirliği	<input type="checkbox"/> Heterojen/ farklı kaynaklardan bilgi entegrasyonu	<input type="checkbox"/> Bilgi ve deneyimler
<input type="checkbox"/> İyileştirme/geliştirme	<input type="checkbox"/> Liderlik tarzı	<input type="checkbox"/> Bölümler arası şeffaflık	<input type="checkbox"/> Verilerle ilgili beceriler

	Konuya yabancı	Yeni başlayan	Orta	Tecrübeli	Uzman	Lider
15- I4.0 uygulama yolculuğunun neresindedesiniz?						

C. Teknolojik gereksinimler

Lütfen aşağıdaki soru listesine göre şirketinizin akıllı fabrika (SF) uygulamaya yönelik teknolojik hazırlık (olgunluk) düzeyini belirtin.

16- 16- Aşağıdaki teknolojilerden hangisi sizin planlanlı edinme/satınalma önceliğinizde yer alıyor? (Lütfen her teknoloji için işaretleyin. 5: en yüksek öncelik).	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Nesnelerin İnterneti (IoT)						
Siber Fiziksel Sistem (CPS)						
Bulut bilişim (CC)						
İş zekâsı (BI)						
Katmanlı üretim (AM)						
Bilgisayarla Tümüleşik Üretim (CIM)						
Büyük Veri (BD)						
Robotlar						
Artırılmış Gerçeklik (AR)						
Kurumsal Kaynak Planlaması (ERP)						
Simülasyon						
17- Aşağıdaki teknolojilerden hangisi kuruluşunuzda hâlihazırda elde edinilmiş olup henüz kullanılmamıştır? (Lütfen her teknoloji için işaretleyin)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Nesnelerin İnterneti (IoT)						
Siber Fiziksel Sistem (CPS)						
Bulut bilişim (CC)						
İş zekâsı (BI)						
Katmanlı üretim (AM)						
Bilgisayarla Tümüleşik Üretim (CIM)						
Büyük Veri (BD)						
Robotlar						
Artırılmış Gerçeklik (AR)						
Kurumsal Kaynak Planlaması (ERP)						
Simülasyon						

18- Kuruluşunuzda aşağıdaki teknolojilerden hangileri hâlihazırda kullanılmaktadır? (Lütfen her teknoloji için işaretleyin)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Nesnelerin İnterneti (IoT)						
Siber Fiziksel Sistem (CPS)						
Bulut bilişim (CC)						
İş zekâsı (BI)						
Katmanlı üretim (AM)						
Bilgisayarla Tümüleşik Üretim (CIM)						
Büyük Veri (BD)						
Robotlar						
Artırılmış Gerçeklik (AR)						
Kurumsal Kaynak Planlaması (ERP)						
Simülasyon						
19- İşletmenizde aşağıdaki tasarım ilkelerinin ne kadar karşılandığını düşünüyorsunuz? (Lütfen her prensip için işaretleyin)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Sanallaştırma						
Dijitalleştirme						
Birlikte çalışabilirlik						
Entegre sistem						
Standardizasyon						
Esneklik						
Servis Odaklılık						
Modülerlik						
Emniyet ve güvenlik						
Yerinden yönetim (sorumluluğun dağıtılması)						
20- Kurumsal süreçleriniz ve ekipmanlarınız hangi ölçüde aşağıdaki özelliklerle karakterize edilir? (Lütfen her özelliği kontrol edin)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Kendinden kontrollü						
Kendi kendine organizasyon						
Kendi kendine yapılandırma						
Kendinden koordinasyon						
Kendi kendine teşhis						
Kendi kendine karar						
Kendi kendine karşılaştırma						
Kendi kendine optimizasyon						
Kendi kendine uyum						
Kendi kendine tahmin						
Öz farkındalık						

21- Aşağıdaki özelliklerden hangisi şu anda hazır veya işletmenizde 3-5 yıl içinde elde edilecek? (Lütfen her özellik için işaretleyin)	Hazır						Önümüzdeki 3-5 yıl					
	N/A	1	2	3	4	5	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Bağlanabilirlik												
Entegre edilebilirlik												
Ağ bağlantılı												
Gerçek zamanlı beceriler												
Ulaşılabilirlik												
Şeffaflık												
İzlenebilirlik												
Otomasyon												
Sorunsuz veri akışı												
22- İş operasyonlarını geliştirmek için aşağıdaki yetenek(ler) den hangilerine sahipsiniz? Veya hangisini kurmayı planlıyorsunuz? (Lütfen her yetenek için işaretleyin) (N / A = 0: Evet, bir dereceye kadar = 3; Evet, tamamen = 5)	Mevcut						Önümüzdeki 3-5 yıl					
	N/A	1	2	3	4	5	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Akıllı öngörülebilirlik												
Farklı kaynaklardan bilgi entegrasyonu												
Akıllı görselleştirme												
Heterojen/ Farklı kaynaklardan gerçek zamanlı veri kullanılabilirliği												
Akıllı analiz												
Akıllı öğrenme												
Akıllı algılama												
Akıllı yeniden yapılandırma												
Akıllı proaktif davranış												
Akıllı farkındalık												

23- İşletmenizin hangi yetkinlik (ler) e yatırım yapması gerektiğini düşünüyor musunuz? (Lütfen her yetenek için işaretleyin)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Rekabet Yetkinliği						
İş zekâsı Yetkinliği						
Özelleştirme Yetkinliği						
Dinamik Etkileşim Yetkinliği						
Otonom Yetkinliği						
24- Kurumsal rekabet gücünüzü aşağıdaki özelliklere göre nasıl değerlendiriyorsunuz? (Lütfen her yetenek için işaretleyin)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Çeviklik						
Yalınlık						
Uyum yeteneği						
Sürdürülebilirlik						
Optimizasyon						
Cevap verebilirlik						
Ölçeklenebilirlik						
Verimlilik						

D. Yönetimsel gereksinimleri

Lütfen aşağıdaki soruların listesine göre, şirketinizin akıllı fabrika (SF) uygulamaya yönelik yönetimsel hazırlık (olgunluk) seviyesini belirtin.

	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
25- İşletmenizin Dijital Dönüşümü uygulamak için bir planı veya stratejisi var mı?						
26- İşletmenizin dijital dönüşüme (akıllı fabrika kurulumuna) ilişkin net bir vizyonu ve misyonu var mı?						
27- Yönetiminiz dijital dönüşüm projeleri için istenen bağlılığı/taahhüdü ve desteği sağlıyor mu?						
28- İşletmenizin önümüzdeki beş yıl için akıllı fabrikaya dönüşümle ilgili net hedefleri var mı?						
29- Kendi dijital olgunluğunuza ilişkin bir değerlendirmeniz var mı?						
30- Akıllı fabrikaya geçmenize yardımcı olacak ağ bağlantılı işbirliği arıyor musunuz?						
31- İşletmenizde Endüstri 4.0 için uzmanlardan oluşan bir ekip oluşturduunuz mu?						
32- Şirketiniz, yönetim uygulamalarını digitalleştirmeye başladı mı?						
33- Çalışanlarınızın davranışları ve kararları Kurumsal Kaynak Planlaması (ERP) ve iş zekâsı (BI) yazılımları ile ne derece bütünleşmiş?						

34- Akıllı fabrika (SF) dönüşümü ile ilgili kurumsal hedeflerinizi nasıl değerlendirirsiniz? (Lütfen her özellik için işaretleyin)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Spesifik (basit, mantıklı, anlamlı).						
Ölçülebilir (anlamlı, motive edici).						
Ulaşılabilir (kararlaştırılmış, ulaşılabilir).						
İlgili (makul, gerçekçi ve kaynakları sağlanmış, sonuçlara dayalı).						
Zamana bağlı						
35- Kuruluşunuzun en büyük dijital dönüşüm hedefi nedir? (Lütfen her özellik için kontrol edin)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Üretkenlik						
Karlılık						
Pazar payı						
Rekabet avantajı						
Etkililik ve verimlilik						
36- Aşağıdaki özellikler söz konusu olduğunda işletme yöneticilerinizi nasıl değerlendirirsiniz? (Lütfen her özellik için işaretleyin)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Yenilikçilik odaklı						
Ağ bağlantılı etkileşime açık						
Koçluk tarzı liderlik yaklaşımına sahip						
Değişime açık						
Dijital becerileri olan						
Teknolojiyi takip eden						
37- Aşağıdaki hedefleri desteklemek söz konusu olduğunda kurumsal uygulamalarınızı nasıl değerlendirirsiniz? (Lütfen her bir özellik için işaretleyin)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Çeviklik						
Yalınlık						
Kültürel zenginleştirme						
Dinamik yetkinlikler						
Motivasyon						
Katılım						
Yenilikçilik						
Öğrenme						

E. Organizasyonel gereksinimler

Lütfen aşağıdaki soru listesine göre, şirketinizin Akıllı Fabrika (SF) uygulamaya yönelik organizasyonel hazırlık (olgunluk) belirtin.

38- İşletmenizi aşağıdaki özelliklerle ilgili olarak nasıl tanımlıyorsunuz? (Lütfen her özellik için işaretleyin)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Düz organizasyon yapısı						
Cevap verebilirlik						
Uyarlanabilirlik						
Hızlı karar alma						
39- Kurumsal iş modelinizi aşağıdaki özelliklere göre nasıl tanımlıyorsunuz? (Lütfen her özellik için işaretleyin)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Kapsamlı						
İşbirlikçi						
Veriye dayalı						
Cevap verebilen						
Dinamik						
Ağ bağlantılı						
40- İş modeliniz aşağıdakiler için veri paylaşımını ne derece etkinleştiriyor? (Lütfen her biri için işaretleyin)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Karar verme						
Entegrasyon/ Bütünleşme						
Süreç yönetimi						
Performans değerlendirilmesi						
Optimizasyon						
Davranışı yönetme						
41- Aşağıdakilerle ilgili iş modelinizi nasıl tanımlayabilirsiniz? (Lütfen her biri için işaretleyin)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Sürdürülebilirlik						
Etkileşim						
Entegrasyon						
İşbirliği						
Cevap verebilirlik						
Bağlanabilirlik						
Dinamizm						

42- Aşağıdaki özelliklerle ilgili olarak kurumsal yapınızı nasıl tanımlıyorsunuz? (Lütfen her biri için işaretleyin)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
	Yalnlık					
	Çeviklik					
	Entegrasyon					
	Akıllılık					
43- Aşağıdaki özelliklerin desteğiyle ilgili kurumsal kültürünüzü nasıl tanımlıyorsunuz? (Lütfen her biri için işaretleyin)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
	Dijitalleşme odaklılık					
	Bilgi odaklılık					
	Yenilik odaklılık					
	Kalite odaklılık					
	İşbirliği					
	Devamlı öğrenme					
	Katılım					
	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
44- İşletmeniz, BT ve operasyonların etkin bir şekilde birlikte çalışmasını sağlamak için geleneksel işlevleri yeniden yapılandırıyor mu?						
45- Kurumsal yapınız veri şeffaflığı sağlıyor ve sorunsuz veri alışverişini kolaylaştırıyor mu?						
46- İşletmeniz kullanılan iş modelini dijitalleştiriyor mu?						

F. İnsanla ilgili gereksinimler

Bu bölüm, insan kaynağının rolü ve ilgili yeteneklere odaklanmaktadır. Lütfen aşağıdaki soru listesine göre, şirketinizin akıllı fabrika (SF) ile ilgili insan kaynağı konusunda hazır olma (olgunluk) belirtin.

47- Akıllı bir fabrika için şirketinizde aşağıdaki beceri ve yeterliliklerin önemi nedir? (Lütfen her biri için işaretleyin)	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
	Gerçek zamanlı yetenek					
	Yenilikçi düşünce					
	Dinamik beceriler					
	Etkileşimli beceriler					
	Verilerle ilgili beceriler					

48- Gelişen teknoloji ve yöntemler, işlerin doğasını ve ihtiyaç duyulan beceri türlerini kökten değiştirecektir. Kuruluşunuz uzmanlık ve beceri envanterini geliştirmek için aşağıdakilerden hangilerini ne ölçüde kullanıyor?	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Atölyeler						
Eğitim programları						
Öğrenme programları						
Kendi kendine öğrenme						
Sanal gerçeklik						
Arttırılmış gerçeklik						
49- İşletmeniz önümüzdeki 5 yıl içinde aşağıdaki yenilikçi yetenekleri ne ölçüde geliştirmeye çalışıyor?	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Gerçek zamanlı yetenek						
Yenilikçi düşünce						
Dinamik beceriler						
Etkileşim becerileri						
Verilerle ilgili beceriler						

50- İş gücünüzün aşağıdaki teknolojileri kullanmaya hazır olma durumunu nasıl değerlendiriyorsunuz?	N/A	1	2	3	4	5
Nesnelerin İnterneti (IoT)						
Siber Fiziksel Sistem (CPS)						
Bulut bilişim (CC)						
İş zekâsı (BI)						
Katmanlı üretim (AM)						
Bilgisayarla Tümlleşik Üretim (CIM)						
Büyük Veri (BD)						
Robotlar						
Arttırılmış Gerçeklik (AR)						
Kurumsal Kaynak Planlaması (ERP)						
Simülasyon						

Appendix C: ETHICAL BOARD PERMISSION LETTER

T.C.
TÜRK HAVA KURUMU ÜNİVERSİTESİ
Etik Kurulu

Sayı : 63878715-050.01-E.6282
Konu : 2 Numaralı Etik Kurulu Kararı

10/11/2020

REKTÖRLÜK MAKAMINA
(Sosyal Bilimleri Enstitüsü)

Üniversitemiz 06.11.2020 tarih ve 02 Numaralı Etik Kurulu Kararı ve bahse konu karara ait ekler Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Müdürlüğü'ne iletmek üzere bilgilerinize sunulmuştur.

Gereğinin yapılması hususunu bilgilerinize arz ederim.

e-imzalıdır

Prof.Dr. İbrahim Halil GÜZELBEY
Etik Kurulu Başkanı

Ek:
1- 06.11.2020 Numaralı Etik Kurul Kararı
2- SF Maturity Survery Turkish Version
3- SF Maturity Survery English Version

10/11/2020 Kalite Uzmanı : H.KILIÇ
10/11/2020 Genel Sekreter V. : A. KOÇYİĞİT

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Elektronik Ağ: <http://www.thk.edu.tr/>

KARAR NO	02	GÜNDEM
KARAR TARİHİ	06.11.2020	1) Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Müdürlüğü tarafından 23.10.2020 tarih ve E. 5954 sayılı yazının görüşülmesi.
Toplantı Tarihi:	06.11.2020	
Başkan:	Prof. Dr. İbrahim Halil GÜZELBEY	
Üyeler:	Prof. Dr. Hasan ERBAY, Prof. Dr. İbrahim Halil GÜZELBEY, Prof. Dr. Dursun BİNGÖL, Prof. Dr. Nevsan ŞENGLİ, Dr. Öğr. Üyesi Hicran KASA, Doç. Dr. Yaşar KÖSE, Dr. Öğr. Üyesi Doç. Dr. Suat DENGİZ, Dr. Öğr. Üyesi Durmuş Sinan KÖRPE, Dr. Öğr. Üyesi Şafak KURT	
TÜRK HAVA KURUMU ÜNİVERSİTE ETİK KURUL KARARI		
KARAR 1: Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Müdürlüğü tarafından gönderilen 23.10.2020 tarih ve E.5954 sayılı yazı gereğince; Enstitümüz İşletme (İngilizce) Doktora programı 1403922004 numaralı öğrencisi Atheer Haso Ashak GAJO Tez çalışması kapsamında "Ceva Lojistik Ankara, Netlog Lojistik Ankara, Ekol Lojistik Ankara, Akkoç Lojistik Ankara, Ankara Lojistik Üssü, Savunma ve Havacılar Sanayi İmalatçılar Derneği "(SasaD)" şirketlerinde Anket uygulaması yapmasında ve Anket formlarının ilgili şirketlere Üniversitemiz aracılığıyla ile yollanmasında etik açıdan bir sakınca olmadığına,		

The bottom of the page features several handwritten signatures and initials in blue ink. From left to right, there is a large signature, a smaller signature, a signature with a checkmark, a signature with a checkmark, a signature, and a signature with the number '7' above it and '0.5' below it.